

CIRAN

D5.2 Guidelines for public engagement and dialogue

Results and insights from public engagement activities

Funded by the
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Executive summary

This report presents the methodologies developed within the framework of Task 5.3 of the CIRAN project, *“Engagement and Dialogue for Knowledge Co-Creation”*, aimed at engaging and co-creating knowledge with citizens. This task primarily involved the organisation of focus groups and public dialogues across six established communities in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Italy, Portugal, France, and Ireland.

The methodologies outline each step necessary for the successful organisation of both activities, along with all related materials. For the public dialogues, a role-play exercise developed under WP3 was embedded and tested in one community.

The report also presents the results of these activities, which will inform Work Package 6 and contribute to the development of policy recommendations.

The focus group activities aimed to assess participants' general knowledge and interest in the topic of mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas. Public dialogues, instead, had both educational and deliberative purposes, with the ultimate goal of participants providing recommendations on specific scenarios.

In total, 12 citizen engagement activities took place across the six aforementioned countries, involving 173 participants. The participant demographics showed a gender distribution of 57% male and 43% female. The groups included representatives of public and private bodies, local NGOs, and civil society organisations. Notably, 14% of participants did not represent any organisation.

All focus groups (conducted in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Italy, Portugal, France, and Ireland), revealed deep concern for environmental sustainability, strong public mistrust of mining actors, and a widespread call for education, transparency, and genuine public involvement. Across all countries, citizens favoured circular economy approaches over extraction and supported mining only under strict, ethical, and transparent governance frameworks.

The focus group conducted in Lens, France, was characterised by a high level of participant expertise, which led to more nuanced and specific discussions. These emphasised the need for a strategic approach to sustainable resource management, as well as a clear commitment from both public and private actors to sustainable transitions, innovation, and ethical consumption. The importance of education and mediation, along with transparency and informed consent, was also highlighted as essential to addressing low awareness and public distrust.

Public dialogues took place in Portugal, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Italy, and Ireland, and revealed strong commonalities in citizens' views on the future of critical raw materials. Five key cross-cutting themes emerged: a broad demand for transitioning to circular economies and more sustainable lifestyles; a firm prioritisation of environmental protection, particularly in opposition to mining in protected areas; conditional acceptance of mining only under strict ethical, environmental, and oversight standards; widespread mistrust in institutions and corporate influence; and strong support for education, innovation, and inclusive public engagement.

Despite national differences in emphasis, these shared themes reflect a consistent public vision for a more ethical, transparent, and ecologically responsible approach to critical raw material governance in Europe.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Strategic context and legal framework

Europe is the best region in the world in terms of democracy, social standards, and way of living. This statute is possible thanks to the economic, industrial, social, and environmental policies driven by the EU and its foreign partners. However, the new geopolitical context and the challenges posed by the climate change and the necessary energy transition, demands that Europe redefines some of its fundamental politics. One of those is the recently published EU “Raw Materials Act”.

This Act aims to respond to the fact that EU is exposed to severe actual and potential supply risks for certain Critical Raw Materials (later in the document indicated as “CRMs”) and the only way to avoid that is for Europe to gradually reduce that dependency is to look for alternatives in its own territories and secure the extraction of CRMs from local EU resources.

However, this brings specific environmental challenges, because some of these CRMs may occur in part or even entirely in environmentally protected areas, and biodiversity conservation is a high priority for us all. Hence, CIRAN is trying to find a way to reconcile these two objectives and needs.

To find a viable solution and to design a realistic strategy, it is vital to develop a co-creation process among all the relevant stakeholders: policymakers, local citizens, conservation organizations, and mining companies.

1.2 Purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable

This document outlines the methodologies developed within the framework of Task 5.3 “Engagement and dialogue for knowledge co-creation”, which primarily involved the organization of focus groups and public dialogues across the six established communities in Czech Republic, Slovakia, Italy, Portugal, France and Ireland.

It also presents the results of these activities, which will inform Work Package 6 (WP6) and contribute to the development of policy recommendations.

The document is structured into several chapters. Two chapters are dedicated to the methodologies used for organizing and conducting the focus groups and public dialogues. The two methodologies were elaborated as two different documents. Another chapter provides an overview of the public engagement activities carried out in the five communities. Additionally, six chapters focus individually on each of the six communities, with a distinction made between the results of the focus groups and the public dialogues in each case. The full reports of the activities conducted are embedded as annexes in the document.

The document concludes with a final chapter summarizing the key findings.

The purpose of this document is to provide a comprehensive description of the process followed by WP5 leaders and collaborators in organizing the focus groups and public dialogues across the different sites. This process could serve as a replicable model for other communities. Furthermore, the document demonstrates the effectiveness of the developed methodologies by presenting an analysis of the results of these activities.

1.3 Relation to other work packages and tasks

As already mentioned above, the results of the activities conducted under Task 5.3 will directly inform WP6 and in particular Task 6.2 “Policy recommendations for permitting, model social contract and ESG to achieve

a social-environmental-economic equilibrium” and related D6.2 “Triple Bottom Line policy recommendation for permitting, social model contract and ESG reporting” (Figure 1).

The development of the methodologies for conducting citizen engagement activities was influenced by the work carried out within Task 5.1 “Understanding the narratives in public debate” and D5.1 “Narratives for public deliberation processes”. Moreover, the preliminary work done under T5.2 “Coordination of civil society meetings” mainly related to the stakeholders mapping and engagement and the elaboration of clear communication messages was essential to prepare the ground for an effective implementation of the focus groups and the public dialogues.

The collaboration with WP3 and Task 3.3 “Nexus between policy decisions and drivers of change” it also important to be mentioned, since one of the public dialogues conducted embedded the role-play and the “What if” cases developed within Task 3.3 and included in D3.3 “Nexus of policy decision and drivers of change”.

Figure 1 – Relation with other tasks and deliverables.

2 Methodology for public engagement – Focus group

2.1 Purpose of the methodology

This document was drafted in the framework of the Horizon Europe funded project " Critical RAw materials extraction enviroNmentally protected areas" (CIRAN project ID 101091483). The project aims to reconcile two, sometimes conflicting, societal objectives and needs: protecting environmentally sensitive areas and increasing the socio-economic resilience in the EU.

The document, resulting from the activity carried out within Task 5.3, presents CIRAN's methodology for conducting focus groups, and it is part of Work Package 5 of the project, which focuses on "Inclusion and knowledge co-creation".

This guide is intended for anyone involved in the planning and execution of Focus Groups and its associated activities, including facilitators of the focus groups, members of the partner organisation and other collaborators. The rationale behind this Methodology arises from the necessity to standardise the implementation across all locations to ensure the consistency and quality of data collected.

Upon reading this guide, the facilitators, project partners and other collaborators should be able to:

- Understand the project's methodology for conducting a focus group.
- Understand how to choose participants for the Focus Group.
- Feel well equipped to deliver the Focus Group.

2.2 Introduction to CIRAN Focus Group

Activities in WP5 of CIRAN "*Inclusion and knowledge co-creation*" are focused on designing, testing and validating governance models through the participation of citizen groups from five different EU communities in co-creation processes (through focus groups and public consultations) aiming to define/improve standards for mining activities in environmentally protected areas.

The questions prepared for the focus groups aimed to provide responses allowing to reach the goal to understand different perspectives of local citizens on minerals extraction in environmentally protected areas.

The six local focus groups were organised in:

1. Portugal – Idanha-a-Nova,
2. Ireland – Dublin,
3. Italy – Baiso,
4. Slovakia – Banska Bystrica,
5. Czechia – Veselí nad Moravou,
6. Frances – Lens.

2.3 Methodology of CIRAN Focus Group

What is a Focus Group?

A focus group is a qualitative research technique that entails a small gathering from six to twelve individuals who engage in discussions of a particular subject or matter¹. The key components include a trained moderator who guides discussions with carefully selected participants. Based on the specific purpose of the research the selection might be done considering key aspects such as the demographic characteristics as in the participants' age, gender, education etc; but also their expertise on the domain and topic chosen; and their potential background homogeneity and heterogeneity depending on the research goal. Homogeneity and heterogeneity of participants must be carefully considered and evaluated, indeed, if a group is too heterogeneous, the differences between participants can make a considerable impact on their contributions. On the other side, if a group is homogenous regarding specific characteristics, diverse opinions and experiences may not be revealed. As highlighted by Gibbs ([Gibbs, 1997](#)), participants need to feel comfortable with each other, since meeting with others whom they think of as possessing similar characteristics also in terms of position of power, is more appealing than meeting with those who are perceived to be different². Sessions held in controlled environments that last 1 to 2 hours maximum to maintain participant engagement and focus. Questions are open-ended, with the aim of stimulating an informal discussion and sampling people's views in more detail than is possible through a survey.

The primary objective of a focus group is to acquire in-depth insights into participants' viewpoints, attitudes, convictions, and actions regarding the subject under study. When conducted effectively, a focus group establishes a welcoming atmosphere that enables participants to comfortably respond to questions in their own words, thereby enhancing the depth of their answers and uncovering a wealth of detailed information and opinions³.

Focus group technique in CIRAN project

Focus groups are valuable for investigating complex societal issues that require in-depth understanding, such as assessing participants' perspectives on a specific subject⁴. The topics of CIRAN, namely protecting environmentally sensitive areas and increasing socio-economic resilience in the EU are indeed very complex. Hence, the technique of focus groups can very well help to understand different perspectives of local citizens from different communities on mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas.

¹ Swartling Å. G., (2007). Focus groups, in *Advanced Tools for Sustainability Assessment*, European Commission.

² Gibbs, A. (1997). Focus groups. *Social research update*, 19(8), 1-8.

³ Onwuegbuzie et al. (2009). A Qualitative Framework for Collecting and Analyzing Data in Focus Group Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940690900800301>

O.Nyumba et al. (2018). The use of focus group discussion methodology: insights from two decades of application in conservation, *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12860>

<https://www.simplypsychology.org/what-is-a-focus-group.html>

<https://www.urban.org/research/data-methods/data-collection/focus-groups>

⁴ <https://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/assessment/assessing-community-needs-and-resources/conduct-focus-groups/main>

The focus group technique is appropriate when it is necessary to better understand preferences, behaviours and beliefs of the target audiences. This corresponds very well with the objective set for CIRAN Focus groups: To understand different perspectives of local citizens on minerals extraction in environmentally protected areas.

2.4 Participants in CIRAN's Focus Groups

As already mentioned, an important step when organising any focus group is identifying the participants that should be involved with a view on its objective, since there is potentially a wide range of actors who may be included.

Size of the group

The group should be sufficiently sizable to foster meaningful discussions while avoiding it to be too numerous, which could lead to some participants feeling excluded. Depending on different topics and approaches, focus groups typically have a minimum of five and a maximum of around twelve participants.

In case of CIRAN focus group, the number of participants depended on the specific context of the local community, but the ideal number of participants range between 6 and 12 people.

Composition of the group

The choice of focus group participants should always be aligned with the research goals and the particular themes or questions that are to be investigated. It is important to involve individuals with interest, experience related to the topic under examination, or being representative of relevant stakeholder groups. In the end, the key to a successful focus group hinges on the selection of participants who can offer valuable insights and viewpoints pertaining to the research objectives, irrespective of whether they hold similar or diverse perspectives.

In case of CIRAN focus groups, participants slightly differed in each community because the selection process considered the local context of the community. However, the following selection criteria were considered when composing the group.

Selection criteria:

- **Local residents:** Participants should primarily be individuals residing within the local community or living in close proximity to the protected area. This ensures that they have a direct connection to the area in question.
- **Knowledge of the topic:** Participants do not need to have prior familiarity with the specific topics of mineral extraction or nature conservation. However, they should have a genuine interest in sharing their opinions and insights on these subjects.
- **Age:** Participants should be 18 years old or older, although consideration may be given to involving individuals as young as 15. The goal is to include a diverse range of age groups to capture different perspectives.
- **Diversity:** It is important to have a diverse group of participants representing various segments of the community. This diversity may include individuals from different backgrounds, such as farmers, beneficiaries of tourism, environmental protection advocates, school teachers, religious leaders, community influencers, and at least one representative from the local municipality. Special effort should be made to involve vulnerable groups within the community.

- **Experience with participatory processes:** While prior experience in civic engagement is not mandatory, participants with a history of active civic involvement are welcome to join. Their experience and perspectives can contribute to a richer discussion.
- **Limited prior relationships:** Ideally, participants should not know each other well to prevent pre-existing group dynamics from influencing the discussion. This helps ensure that the conversation remains unbiased and unfiltered, allowing for more genuine responses.

These criteria aim to create a diverse and inclusive focus group that represents the local community's various perspectives and allows for an open and unbiased exchange of opinions on the topics of mineral extraction and nature conservation.

Diversity of participants

Diversity in stakeholder representation within a focus group is crucial for a comprehensive and well-rounded exploration of the research topic. By including individuals from various segments of the community, different perspectives and insights can be gathered, leading to a more holistic understanding of the subject matter.

Here are the various groups of stakeholders that should be considered to be invited to a focus group:

- **Policy-makers:** Policy-makers, such as representatives from public bodies and local authorities, should be included in the focus group. Their involvement is essential as they play a key role in decision-making processes and can provide insights into the regulatory aspects related to the research topic.
- **Private sector:** Representatives from the private sector, particularly those from industries relevant to the research, should be included. Their input can shed light on the economic implications and challenges related to the topic, such as tourism and energy.
- **Environmental advocates:** To emphasise environmental considerations, representatives focused on biodiversity and ecological aspects should be invited. Their insights can contribute to nature-centric perspectives within the discussions.
- **Civil Society (NGOs, Associations):** To ensure a holistic and community-centred approach, it is important to involve civil society representatives, including members of non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and community associations. They can advocate for local interests and provide grassroots perspectives.
- **Vulnerable groups:** Special attention should be given to involving representatives of vulnerable groups within the community. Their unique experiences and concerns need to be heard and considered in the decision-making process. Generally speaking, vulnerability can affect: i) Access to resources (access to tangible and intangible goods, public and private goods); ii) Governance (representation, or lack thereof, of vulnerable groups in decision-making bodies); iii) Culture; iv) Knowledge (knowledge transmission, social memory, traditional ecological knowledge, deep time knowledge, and knowledge co-production); v) Employment; vi) Health, vii) Education. Specific vulnerable groups relevant for the local context will be identified in cooperation with each community.
- **Media:** Local media can be engaged as participants. They possess in-depth knowledge of the region and can play a critical role in disseminating information and project results to the wider community.
- **Academia/Research Centres:** Engagement with academic and research institutions is vital to bring a scientific and data-driven perspective to the discussions. These stakeholders can contribute valuable research-based insights and expertise.
- **General public:** This group represents citizens who may not have specialized knowledge or affiliations with specific organizations but have a stake in the issues being discussed. Including the general public

in the focus group can provide diverse perspectives and ensure that the outcomes of the discussion resonate with a broader audience.

The diverse stakeholder groups listed above should be represented in the focus group. This blend of varied participants facilitates a holistic understanding of community needs, fosters diverse insights, and promotes more effective decision-making in addressing environmental challenges related to the topic at stake.

By adhering to these criteria and involving diverse stakeholder groups, the focus group can create a well-rounded platform for discussion. This approach ensures that a wide range of perspectives is considered, leading to more informed and inclusive recommendations for the CIRAN project across European regions.

Ensuring the diversity of participants

In a focus group, individuals interested in participating, sharing their opinions, and engaging in discussion on a given topic can take part in it voluntarily. No financial or other forms of remuneration are provided to participants. Depending on the local context, stakeholder groups interested in attending a focus group may vary widely, and some groups may be more prominent or better represented than others.

For example, if the topic concerns mining in protected natural areas, it may attract greater interest from environmental advocates within the local community than from the private sector. As a result, the former group may be more strongly represented in the focus group.

To ensure broad stakeholder representation, the goal is to include as many groups as possible.

If some invited representatives do not confirm participation, other members from the same groups should be invited. This helps make an extra effort to achieve balanced and diverse participation in the focus group.

Context of communities

The composition of stakeholder groups in each community is expected to vary, and the willingness of their representatives to participate in a focus group on the given topic may differ accordingly. It is not realistic to expect identical group compositions across all focus groups, as participation will depend on the local context.

To ensure that the results of each focus group are well grounded in the specific context of the community, a description of that context will be included in the corresponding report. This will cover aspects such as geography and location, population characteristics, infrastructure, economy, government and governance, community engagement and participation, and relevant history or heritage.

Identification and recruiting of participants

Focus group participants can be recruited through various methods which are presented in the following paragraph to illustrate the variety of possible approaches to identification of participants. Some of the most commonly used approaches include:

- **Nomination:** In this method, key individuals suggest other individuals they believe would be suitable participants. Nominees should be interested in the topic of discussion and they should be able to talk about it. They should be known for their ability to express their opinions respectfully, and be willing to dedicate approximately 2 hours of their time.
- **Random Selection:** When participants are selected from a large but well-defined group (e.g., an entire town) with many interested individuals, names can be randomly drawn from a pool until the desired number of qualified participants is reached.
- **Members of the same Group:** Sometimes, it's advantageous to invite participants from an existing group that already shares common interests or characteristics.
- **Same Role/Job Title:** Depending on the topic, the selection pool might be defined by a specific position, title, or condition (e.g., teachers, community social workers, owners of businesses in town).

- Volunteers: When the selection criteria are broad, participants can be recruited through the distribution of flyers and newspaper advertisements.

After reviewing different methods for identifying and recruiting focus group participants, and considering that a local partner has already been appointed in each community, the best selection approach for CIRAN was considered to be “Nomination.”

In this case, the key identified stakeholders were recommended by the local partner from the community involved in the project (see explanation in the chapter “Roles in focus group” below) and this person helped to identify individuals suitable for CIRAN focus group.

The whole process of selection of participants was carried out in two steps:

- 1) Using the Nomination technique, one key stakeholder in the community, that cooperates on the implementation on CIRAN activities, identified participants for the local focus groups. This was based on the selection criteria and diverse stakeholders outlined and he/she created the list of suggested participants.
- 2) A responsible person from the CIRAN consortium made a final selection of participants based on the suggestions provided by the key person in the community, carefully considering all the selection criteria and diverse groups of stakeholders. In case the group was not sufficiently diverse or big enough, the key stakeholder in the community was asked to provide further suggestions for potential participants.

A valuable tool for selecting participants for focus groups in the CIRAN project is a "Stakeholder Selection Table" (see [Annex 1](#)). This MS Excel table served as a systematic approach to identify and choose participants. Here is how it works:

- Stakeholder Identification: Begin by listing all the stakeholders identified in the Stakeholder Selection Table.
- Diversity Criteria: Apply the criteria for diversity mentioned earlier, considering factors such as locality, age, expertise, and vulnerability. Indicate how well each stakeholder meets these criteria.
- Mapping the Selection: Use of a visual representation, such as color-coding or a rating system, to map the selection of participants. This can be done directly within the stakeholder selection table or in a separate document. The process will finally identify potential participants and also back-up participants.

By employing this Stakeholder Selection Table, the CIRAN staff used the same approach to identify participants of focus groups in each community, which ensured that the selection process aligned closely with the project's goals and that the perspectives of various stakeholders are thoughtfully integrated into the research process.

Inviting participants to Focus groups

An invitation was extended to chosen participants by the responsible person from the CIRAN consortium. The following two-phase invitation process was implemented:

Phase 1: Initial Invitation (Approximately one month before the event)

In the first phase, potential participants are invited to join the CIRAN focus group. This invitation is conveyed through a clear and accessible email or letter, emphasising the project's objectives and the importance of

their involvement. This email also includes essential event details, such as the date, time, and location of the focus group meeting. The communication is designed to be easily understood by a diverse range of individuals, regardless of their background or prior knowledge of the project. Recipients are encouraged to express their interest and availability.

In case participants decline the invitation, other candidates within the reserve list of back-up participants are invited. An alternative solution could be used if more people decline the invitation; the originally invited participants are asked to recommend other potential candidates (See [Annex 2: Initial invitation letter](#)).

Phase 2: Reminder (2-5 Days Prior to the Event)

In the second phase, a reminder is sent to those who have expressed interest in participating. This reminder confirms essential event details. Its purpose is to ensure that participants are well-informed and have adequate notice of the upcoming event. It serves as a prompt for participants to reconfirm their commitment and attendance. Contact information are provided for any inquiries or clarifications. This proactive reminder contributes to a high level of participation and engagement in the CIRAN project's focus groups (See still [Annex 2](#)).

Together, these two phases of invitation and reminder aim to engage stakeholders effectively and encourage their active participation in the project's activities.

2.5 Roles in Focus Groups

A successful implementation of a focus group is the result of the interactions of a variety of people having specific roles.

1. Participants in the focus group:

- **Role:** Focus group participants are vital community stakeholders directly involved in discussions. Their profile is outlined in the previous chapter of this document.
- **Responsibilities:** Chosen for their relevance to the topic or deep understanding of the community, participants represent community ideas and experiences. They actively contribute to discussions, sharing insights and feedback.

2. Responsible Person from the CIRAN Consortium:

- **Role:** The responsible person, a member of the CIRAN consortium, is in charge of community communication and serves as the primary point of contact with the community.
- **Responsibilities:** This individual speaks the local language fluently, initiates and maintains communication with the community, and establishes trust. They act as a bridge between the project and the community, ensuring that community perspectives are accurately represented.

3. Key Stakeholder from the Community/local partner of the CIRAN project:

- **Role:** A key stakeholder from the community or local partner is a person or organisation with a significant role or position within the local context who is willing to actively support the CIRAN project implementation. This could be the mayor, a municipal representative, a local NGO representative, or another community leader or a local organisation (for example local NGO).

- Responsibilities: Key stakeholders facilitate project activities within the community, advocating for its goals and connecting community needs with project objectives, proposes participants for the focus group.

4. Facilitator:

- Role: Facilitators guide and moderate focus group discussions.
- Responsibilities: Fluent in the local language, experienced facilitators lead discussions, ensuring conduction and productivity. They possess a strong grasp of qualitative research methods and interpersonal skills. Facilitators steer discussions using a discussion guide, manage conversation flow, and ensure all participants contribute effectively.

5. Assistant Facilitator/Note Taker:

- Role: Assistant facilitators or note-takers support facilitators and document focus group proceedings.
- Responsibilities: Proficient in the local language, they assist in facilitating discussions and record key points, insights, and observations. Their notes are essential for data analysis and project outcomes.

In the CIRAN project, these roles collaborate to execute focus groups effectively. The responsible person establishes trust and communication, key stakeholders advocate for the project, participants provide community insights, and facilitators and assistant moderators ensure productive discussions are conducted and documented for analysis.

Find more details about the role of facilitator and assistant facilitator in the session [“Notes and instructions for the facilitator using the guide” – section 2.8.](#)

2.6 On-site preparation of Focus Groups

In preparation for a focus group within the framework of the CIRAN project, several key elements need to be organised on-site to ensure a conducive environment and smooth facilitation.

Setting up the Focus Group

- **Location:** Select a comfortable, well-lit conference room that provides a quiet and private setting. Ensure there are enough chairs for participants and some tables for refreshments on the side.
- **Seating Arrangement:** Arrange seating so that all participants are in a circle or another format where everyone can see each other, sitting at the same level. Avoid having the facilitator and notetaker standing while participants are sitting on chairs etc.

Figure 2 – Schematic view of the seating arrangement of Focus Group participants.

- **Refreshments:** Ensure that refreshments, at least drinks, are available for participants.
- **Time Management:** Start the session 15 minutes prior to the actual discussion time to allow for paperwork, snacks, and settling in.

Materials and equipment

- **Consent forms:** Print the prepared consent form that ensures that participants are fully informed about the purpose, procedures, and potential risks of their involvement in the discussion, and to obtain their voluntary permission to participate and record their contributions. These forms also protect the ethical rights and privacy of participants and serve as a legal record of their informed consent, helping to establish transparency and trust in the research process. See Annex 4 – Participant Information Sheet Focus Group, and [Annex 4 – Consent form Focus Group](#).
- **Facilitator checklist:** You can also print out a document that serves as a checklist of all the materials and tasks that should be prepared before the focus group begins. See [Annex 5 – Checklist for facilitator](#).
- **Note-taking template:** Print the prepared template that will be used by the assistant facilitator to capture key points, themes, and quotes. See [Annex 6 – Note-Taking template](#).
- **List of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs):** Print one for each participant and member of the team of the focus group. See [Annex 7 – List of Critical Raw Materials \(CRMs\)](#).
- **Pictures of objects of everyday use that contain CRMs :** Have them ready to present on the screen or projector (they are already available in the presentation [here](#)). Or you can print them on A4 format to show to participants. These are examples of some of the items that CRMs are used for, and this is not an exhaustive list. See Annex 8 – Pictures of objects of everyday use that contain CRMs.
- **Movie about CRMs:** Download short animated video and prepare a device where you can play the movie to participants during the focus group. The video is available [here](#).
- **Presentation on CRMs:** The presentation contains slides on which there is a list of CRM, as well as pictures of daily necessities containing these raw materials. At the end, he/she also gives an example of one of the CRMs (elements of rare metals) and this particular example can be used to explain the

"criticality" of these raw materials if needed. See [here](#). The presentation can be integrated with visuals and/or information emphasizing environmental conservation and sustainable resource management aspects.

- **Recording equipment:** Set up equipment for audio or video recording of the meetings to capture valuable discussions (seek permission first).
- **Data projector, screen, speakers and computer:** This equipment (or large TV screen) will be necessary to show the film (and presentation).
- **Roll-up banner:** Banner with the name and logo of CIRAN and indication of EU support to the project (available [here](#)).
- **Name signs:** Provide name signs with participant first name and number for identification.
- **Additional materials (optional):** For example informative leaflet about the CIRAN project, pads and pencils for each participant, flip chart paper, and markers for the facilitator.

Overall, meticulous on-site preparation is essential to create an environment that fosters productive discussions and allows for the smooth operation of the focus group within the CIRAN project framework. The facilitator and assistant facilitator should be on site early to make sure everything is set-up and tested in order to avoid wasting people's time with last-minute corrective actions.

2.7 Agenda and guidance for the facilitator

Time	Activity
20 minutes	Welcoming Introductory presentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presenting CIRAN ● Explaining the purpose of the focus group
60-80 minutes	Core discussion around 4 main questions
10-20 minutes	Conclusion

As visible from the agenda the focus group is structured in three main parts:

- An introductory part
- A core discussion
- A conclusive part

Here below detailed guidance for the facilitator(s) is provided divided into the three focus group's phases.

Phase 1: Introduction (20 min)

[Begin by standing or sitting at the front of the room, ensuring that all participants can see and hear you clearly]

- Welcome participants, introduce the CIRAN team, and explain that the focus group aims to gather community perspectives on mineral extraction in protected areas.
- Briefly outline the project's context and explain the research, specifying the recognized importance of hearing European citizens' opinion around the project topics. Also, emphasize that there are no active or planned mining projects in the community, this is a research exercise to inform future public discussions.
- Explain the follow up activities and the use of collected data: data collected from the focus group will serve as a basis for preparation of a public dialogue, a second activity that will follow up in a couple of months, where the set of topics covered during the focus group will be discussed and evaluated by a broader group of local citizens. Following that, the data collected from both focus group and public dialogues are analysed and a final report is created. All opinions expressed during these events are treated anonymously.
- Explain the format of the focus group.
- Explain the ground rules:
 - There are no right or wrong answers; your experiences and opinions are highly valued.
 - What is discussed within this room remains confidential. We aim to create a safe space for discussing sensitive issues.
 - The records will be anonymised with respect to who said what.
 - Your active participation is essential, but it's perfectly fine if you choose not to respond to certain questions. Your preferences will be respected.
 - Basic Communication Rules:
 - Everyone has the right to speak, and only one person speaks at a time.
 - Avoid side conversations with neighbours.
 - Each participant will have an opportunity to share views; no one person should dominate the discussion.
 - We address each other on a first-name basis *[if local context and practice allows it]*.
 - While you may not necessarily agree with others, please listen respectfully when others share their views.
- Inform participants that the session will be recorded for research purposes.
- Ask for any questions, collect consent forms, and have participants introduce themselves before starting the main discussion.

Phase 2: Core discussion (60-80 min)

- Go over the questions one by one, ensuring all participants have an opportunity to speak. In case participants do not talk a lot about the given question, use the follow-up questions listed below the main question. Prompt quieter individuals for their opinions and gently manage overly dominant speakers. Use probing questions like "Can you talk about that more?" or "Help me understand what you mean" to encourage participants to provide deeper insights. Do not rigidly adhere to a predetermined list of questions. Allow the discussion to flow naturally and be prepared to ask follow-up questions when interesting points emerge.
- After the last question, allow participants to simply finish the discussions streams that have started. Participants are given space to express what they did not have time to say during the course, but in such a way that they no longer start new discussions.

Topic 1: CRMs

- **Q1: How familiar are you with the concept of CRMs? Have you ever heard about them? What do you consider to be CRMs?**
 - *[Show to participants pictures of objects of everyday use that contain CRMs]*
 - What materials do you think that these objects are made from?
 - *[Handout to participants the list of CRMs]*
 - This is the complete current list of CRMs; do you know what these materials are used for?
 - *[To make sure that participants understand basics of the topic discussed at the focus group, show them the short movie about CRMs and share with them the cards explaining their use. Only after that, continue with next questions.]*
 - Do you know why these materials are considered critical?
 - Where do you think Europe gets the materials from?
 - Are you aware that many important mineral raw materials are imported and often from a single country (e.g. China)?
 - If these countries refuse to export their minerals, where do you think we can obtain them from?
- **Q2: What are your thoughts on potential outcomes if Europe did refrain from producing its own CRMs in the next 20 years? Conversely, what if Europe initiates production instead?**
 - Do you think Europe could avoid using these materials?
 - Do you believe that it's feasible for Europe to persist in not producing the big majority of its supply of these materials?
 - What would be the consequences Europe would be facing when not having access to these raw materials?
- **Q3: What are your reflections on the dilemma between the need for environmental protection and the need to ensure socio-economic resilience?**
 - What do you think would be the options for the policymakers to face the potential dilemma between safeguarding the environment and ensuring socio-economic resilience?

Topic 2: Mining in environmentally protected areas

- **Q4: What do you know about the relationship between mining and communities nearby?**
 - Having these relationships in mind, do you have any example of mining in mind? Can you share any experiences related to the mining or exploration of minerals?
 - What do you believe are the potential negative impacts of mineral extraction on the environment and local communities?
 - What do you believe are the potential positives that mineral extraction can bring to the local community?
 - Can you envision a situation where the adoption of innovative and more environmentally friendly mining technologies (such as underground mining with minimal environmental disruptions) could transform mining operations into beneficial force for local communities?
- **Q5: Would you be willing to accept a mining activity in a protected area in your region if it meant that it would help with the security of supply?**
 - What would your decision about this depend on?
 - How would you feel about shifting the responsibility onto others and transferring the mining to other communities or countries?

Topic 3: Politics, policies and public perspective

- **Q6: Do you think public opinion accurately reflects challenges and positives aspects of mining of CRMs?**
 - Do you believe that individuals who are not directly affected by mining operations would be willing to forgo the socio-economic comforts that they are accustomed to, such as phones, computers, surgical lasers, streetlamps etc., considering the potential harmful impacts associated with the production of CRMs?
- **Q7: Are you aware of any European, national, and local policies relevant to CRMs?**
 - Who do you believe holds the greatest sway over public perceptions regarding mining of CRMs?
 - Which institution do you think should bear the responsibility for decision-making regarding the mining of CRMs: local, national, or European entities?
- **Q8: Do you feel that people are included enough in decision making when it comes to deciding about exploration or mining of CRMs?**
 - Have you participated in any decision making in your region? Can you think of any specific case when you participated?
 - How do you think local communities should be involved in the process of deciding about exploration or mining of CRMs?
 - Do you think European, national, and local policies take sufficiently into account the needs of communities when deciding about exploration or mining of CRMs in the communities?
 - Do you think the current rules take enough into consideration the wellbeing of both the communities and the environment?

Phase 3: Conclusion (10-20 min)

- Thank participants for the participation and contribution.
- Ask for any additional questions/thoughts/comments on the activity and the topic.
- Explain the next steps and follow ups.
- Ask to summarize the most important point or issue they identified from the discussion.

2.8 Notes and instructions for facilitators using the guide

In the following instructions, we will outline the key responsibilities of a focus group facilitator based on the guidelines provided. These instructions will help you to moderate discussions effectively, manage group dynamics, and handle challenging situations to ensure a productive and respectful exchange of ideas among participants.

These instructions are particularly useful for less experienced facilitators, providing valuable guidance on moderating focus group discussions. Experienced facilitators may find these guidelines to be familiar, but they serve as a helpful reminder of best practices in ensuring productive and respectful dialogues.

2.8.1 About the role of the facilitator

In the context of the CIRAN project, the role of the facilitator in the focus group is pivotal in ensuring productive and meaningful discussions. Here is an in-depth description of the facilitator's role and ideal expected competences⁵:

- Experienced leadership: The facilitator, chosen for CIRAN focus groups is an experienced professional who plays a central role in guiding and maintaining the direction of the discussion. He/she brings a wealth of expertise to the table.
- Qualitative research skills: The facilitator possesses a strong grasp of qualitative research methods. This expertise allows he/she to effectively elicit and capture qualitative insights from focus group participants.
- Strong interpersonal skills: Interpersonal skills are a hallmark of a facilitator. He/she must exhibit strong interpersonal abilities to create a comfortable and open atmosphere in which participants feel encouraged to express their thoughts and ideas.

⁵ A variety of sources have been consulted:

[Crew, T. \(2009\), A guide to running focus groups, Gwynedd Council.](https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/training/evaluation-learning-portal/focus-groups_en)

https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/training/evaluation-learning-portal/focus-groups_en

<https://stansgigs.com/focus-group-roles-and-responsibilities/> <https://larricklawfirm.com/the-five-faces-of-a-focus-group-moderator/>

<https://archive.unu.edu/unupress/food2/UIN03E/UIN03E06.HTM>

- Language proficiency: The facilitator is fluent in the community's language, enabling seamless communication and understanding between all participants. This linguistic capability is critical for effective facilitation.
- Steering discussions: The facilitator's primary responsibility is to steer the discussion in alignment with the project's goals. He/she do so by posing questions from the discussion guide that are designed to generate valuable insights. These questions prompt participants to share their opinions and experiences.
- Promoting active participation: Actively promoting and encouraging participation is a key role of the facilitator. He/she ensures that all participants have an equal opportunity to contribute and that dominant voices do not overshadow others. This approach fosters a balanced and inclusive discussion.
- Maximising idea generation: The facilitator's ultimate goal is to maximise the generation of diverse ideas and opinions within the given time frame. He/she creates an environment where participants feel empowered to share their perspectives, irrespective of their background or experience.
- Listening skills: The ideal facilitator possesses excellent listening skills, demonstrating sensitivity and empathy towards participants. He/she can listen attentively while simultaneously processing and responding to the discussion dynamics.
- Objectivity and authority: The facilitator maintains objectivity, keeping personal views and ego out of the facilitation process. He/she are someones the group can relate to, while also being viewed as an authority figure, ensuring that discussions remain focused and respectful.
- Managing challenging dynamics: The facilitator is skilled in managing challenging group dynamics. He/she are prepared to address situations where certain participants may dominate the discussion, ensuring that everyone has an opportunity to contribute.
- Equal participation: To promote inclusivity, the facilitator ensures that people talk for an appropriate duration, giving more individuals a chance to share their thoughts. This approach ensures a balance between speaking time and the number of participants engaged.
- Covering of all questions: Ensure that all prepared questions are adequately covered within the allocated time.
- Engaging all participants: Make an effort to get every participant to talk and provide detailed explanations of their answers. Encourage all participants to speak. If someone is not actively contributing, invite their opinion. If one person is dominating the conversation, ask for input from others to balance the discussion.
- Probing for details: Ask follow-up questions and probe for more details when participants bring up interesting points. This helps to uncover deeper insights. Use probing techniques such as:
 - "Can you talk about that more?"
 - "Help me understand what you mean."
 - "Can you give an example?"
- Staying neutral: Maintain a position of neutrality and avoid showing agreement or disagreement with participants' comments through non-verbal cues such as nodding or raising eyebrows.
- Facilitating open conversation: Keep in mind that a focus group is an open conversation, not a survey. Encourage participants to share their thoughts openly and authentically.
- Managing group dynamics: Pay attention to the group dynamics. Ensure that everyone has the opportunity to express themselves and that no single participant dominates the discussion.
- Respect and sensitivity: Approach sensitive topics with respect and sensitivity. If a topic appears to make participants uncomfortable, be prepared to move on tactfully.

In summary, the facilitators in the CIRAN project's focus groups are seasoned professionals, responsible for steering discussions, encouraging active participation, and maximising idea generation. They possess a unique combination of qualitative research expertise, interpersonal skills, and cultural sensitivity, all the while ensuring that the discussions remain objective, respectful, and inclusive.

2.8.2 About the role of the assistant facilitator/note taker

The role of the assistant facilitator, often referred to as the "note taker" in the CIRAN project's focus groups, is instrumental in ensuring that the discussion runs smoothly and that valuable insights are recorded effectively. Here is a comprehensive description of the assistant facilitator's role:

- **Note-taking and recording:** Throughout the focus group discussion, the assistant facilitator takes detailed notes. These notes include various types of information, such as notable quotes, key points, themes for each question, follow-up questions, big ideas, hints, and thoughts relevant to the discussion. The assistant facilitator is responsible for operating recording equipment, ensuring that all discussions are captured accurately for later analysis. In addition to note-taking, the assistant facilitator observes non-verbal cues, including body language, physical excitement, eye contact, or other clues that indicate participants' levels of agreement, support, or interest, and note them in the specific section of the note-taking template (see Annex).
- **Non-participation in discussion:** The assistant facilitators do not actively participate in the discussion. Instead, they take on an observer role, focusing on recording and facilitating the logistics of the session. The assistant facilitators only participate verbally when invited to do so by the primary facilitator. This ensures that the primary facilitator maintains control over the discussion.
- **Debrief with moderator/facilitator:** The assistant facilitator engages in a debriefing session with the primary facilitator/moderator, discussing their observations, insights, and any factors that may aid in the analysis of the focus group data.
- **Feedback on analysis and reports:** The assistant facilitator's insights and recorded observations are valuable contributions to the analysis process. They offer perspectives and contextual information that can enhance the understanding of the focus group data.

In essence, the assistant facilitators play a multifaceted role in CIRAN focus groups. They provide vital logistics support, capture and document critical insights, and contribute to the overall success of the focus group discussions by ensuring that valuable information is recorded, which is essential for analysis and reporting in the CIRAN project.

2.8.3 Shared responsibilities of the facilitator and assistant facilitator

Both, the facilitator and assistant facilitator in a focus group share common tasks related to participant engagement, hospitality, and administrative preparation. Here are the common tasks they are expected to perform together:

- **Logistics support:** Before the focus group begins, the facilitator and the assistant facilitator arrange the room to create a comfortable and conducive environment for the discussion. They also assist with setting up and managing equipment, ensuring that any necessary tools are functioning properly.
- **Refreshments and hospitality:** Both moderators ensure that participants have access to food and refreshments, if provided. They may help distribute or arrange refreshments as needed, ensuring participants are comfortable.

- Name signs: They help participants receive their name signs. Signs should show the participant's name (first, family, or full name according to local customs), which makes it easier for everyone to address each other.
- Pre-group paperwork: Both the moderator and assistant moderator guide participants through any pre-group paperwork or forms (e.g. consent forms) that need to be completed before the focus group starts. They provide assistance and answer any questions participants may have regarding the paperwork.

By jointly performing these tasks, the moderator and assistant moderator ensure that participants feel welcomed, comfortable, and well-prepared for the focus group discussion. This attention to participant engagement and hospitality contributes to a positive and conducive environment for productive discussions.

2.8.4 Handling challenging participants

- Self-Appointed Experts: Redirect the conversation by saying, "Thank you for your input. What do others think?"
- The Dominator: Encourage others to share their thoughts by saying, "Let's hear from some other participants."
- The Rambler: Politely interrupt or redirect their focus, for example, by looking at your watch or gently interrupting when they pause.
- The Shy Participant: Make an effort to involve them by making eye contact, calling on them directly, or smiling to create a welcoming atmosphere.
- The Quiet Speaker: Ask them to repeat their response more loudly so that everyone can hear and engage with their input.

Adapt and apply these instructions to your specific focus group context as needed. Remember, the goal is to foster a productive and open discussion where all participants have the opportunity to share their perspectives and insights.

2.8.5 Further notes, limitations

- Be Prepared for Resistance: It's important to be prepared for participants who may not be willing to understand or listen as the topics of the discussion could be very sensitive. Maintain a patient and open demeanour throughout the discussion.
- Monitor Sentiments: While it is not necessary to directly ask about strong sentiments for or against CIRAN and its objectives, be vigilant for reactions that indicate such sentiments. This information can be crucial for refining communication strategies.
- Addressing Concerns: If participants express concerns or feel threatened by mining in their community, reassure them that you understand their worries. Make it clear that your objective is to gather their opinions and that you are not the problem.
- Consulting Those Without Direct Problems: Recognise that consulting with people who may not have a direct problem with the issue at hand can be challenging. Consider framing questions to engage them effectively and gather their valuable input.
- Limitations of focus groups: Be aware of the limitations of focus groups – the findings may not represent the views of the entire population.

2.9 Research conclusion and data analysis

This chapter delves into the details of analysing the data collected in CIRAN focus groups, suggesting several steps that will be taken after each public dialogue.

Data preparation and transcription

Gather all data collected during the focus group activity, including notes in the PowerPoint presentation, transcripts, notes, recordings, and any additional comments sent by email. Organise the data in a systematic manner, ensuring that it is easily accessible and well-documented. Consider anonymizing sensitive data to protect the privacy of participants, if necessary, while maintaining the integrity of the analysis.

If opted for recording the group work activity the recorded material should be transcribed verbatim using the automatic function of MS Office Word or any other similar program. The translation of the transcript into English can be done using an AI tool. It is important to check for nuances lost during translation.

Data analysis

With the gathered and transcribed data in hand, the next step is the analysis. Here are the key components of the analysis phase.

Identify Key Themes and Patterns

Review the data to identify all recommendations and comments that emerged during the public dialogue activity. Look for commonalities, differences, and areas of consensus or contention among participants' viewpoints.

Use qualitative analysis techniques such as thematic coding or content analysis to categorize and organise the data based on identified themes.

Evaluate Stakeholder Perspectives

While ensuring anonymity, assess the diversity of perspectives represented among participants, including those of different stakeholder groups. Analyse the extent to which various stakeholders' viewpoints align or diverge on key issues and recommendations.

Report and Presentation

Prepare a clear and concise report summarizing the findings of the data analysis, including key themes, patterns, and recommendations as well as quotes of participants.

Verification

The facilitator and the assistant facilitator undertake the analysis. However, to enhance the validity of the findings, the report is shared with other researchers – members of the CIRAN research team who were engaged in the development of the methodology of the focus group. Their insights and feedback will help ensure the accuracy and credibility of the conclusions.

After receiving feedback and making necessary revisions, the report is finalised.

For template of reporting the results of the focus group are available [here](#).

Comparative analysis

After concluding focus groups in all communities, it is essential to compare findings across different focus groups, if applicable, it can provide a broader perspective. It helps identify commonalities, disparities, and unique insights from various groups. Members of the CIRAN research team working on the methodology and participating on focus groups, and also facilitators and assistant facilitators will meet to exchange experiences and support the development of the report.

3 Methodology for public engagement – Public Dialogue

3.1 Purpose of this methodology

This document was drafted in the framework of the Horizon Europe funded project "Critical Raw materials extraction environmentally protected areas" (CIRAN project ID 101091483). The project aims to reconcile two, sometimes conflicting, societal objectives and needs: protecting environmentally sensitive areas and increasing the socio-economic resilience in the EU.

The document, resulting from the activity carried out within Task 5.3, presents CIRAN's methodology for conducting public dialogues, and it is part of Work Package 5 of the project, which focuses on "Inclusion and knowledge co-creation".

This guide is intended for anyone involved in the planning and execution of public dialogues and its associated activities. The rationale behind this Methodology arises from the necessity to standardise the implementation across all locations to ensure the consistency and quality of data collected.

Upon reading this guide, the facilitators, project partners and other collaborators should be able to:

- Understand the project's methodology for conducting a public dialogue,
- Understand how to choose participants for the public dialogue,
- Feel well equipped to deliver the public dialogue.

3.2 Introduction to CIRAN public dialogue

Activities in Work Package 5 of CIRAN, "Inclusion and Knowledge Co-creation," focus on designing, testing, and validating governance models through the participation of citizen groups from five different EU communities. These communities engage in co-creation processes, including focus groups and public dialogues, with the aim of defining and improving standards for mining activities in environmentally protected areas.

The methodology developed for public dialogues seeks to achieve the following goals:

- Raise awareness about mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas,
- Deliver recommendations from ordinary citizens and collect their preferences and priorities regarding potential future scenarios.

Expected Outcome

Each public dialogue is anticipated to produce a set of consensual and negotiated recommendations that reflect the preferences and priorities of ordinary citizens.

While the ideal result would be achieving consensus among all participating stakeholders, this may prove too challenging given the complexity of the topic and the diverse range of perspectives involved. Considering the

primarily research-oriented nature of our activities, our priority is to ensure that everyone has the opportunity to share their thoughts and contribute to the decision-making process.

Even if consensus is not reached, the goal is to gather a wide range of recommendations and understand the participants' priorities. These findings will be included in the final outputs of Work Package 5 (WP5).

Six local public dialogues were organised in five communities:

1. Portugal – Idanha-a-Nova,
2. Italy – Baiso,
3. Slovakia – Banska Bystrica,
4. Czechia – Veselí nad Moravou,
5. Ireland – Dublin.

Public dialogues followed and built on the previous activities conducted in each community: the focus groups. The goal of the focus groups was to explore and understand the diverse perspectives of local citizens on mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas.

The insights and understanding gathered through the focus groups serve as a foundation for the public dialogues, which aim to further support the research conducted as part of the project.

3.3 Methodology for CIRAN public dialogue

What is a public dialogue?

There is no commonly agreed definition or concept of “public dialogue”, but defining it here, based on various resources, a public dialogue serves as a tool promoting evidence-informed policy-making. It brings together stakeholders with diverse perspectives and expertise to discuss pressing public issues⁶. As defined in the Sciencewise Guiding Principles, public dialogue is “*a process during which members of the public interact with scientists, stakeholders and policy makers to deliberate on issues relevant to future policy decisions*”⁷.

Successful public dialogues are characterized by:

- Having clear objectives and defined outcomes, ensuring participants understand the purpose and expected results from the outset,
- Being grounded in evidence-based information, participants receive information and materials that are based on best available research to establish a common understanding and starting point for discussions,

⁶ Mitchell, P., Reinap, M., Moat, K. *et al.* An ethical analysis of policy dialogues. *Health Res Policy Sys* 21, 13 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-023-00962-2>

⁷ https://sciencewise.org.uk/about-dialogue/what-is-public-dialogue/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

- Encouraging deliberation, supporting reflective consideration and collaborative discussion rather than debate,
- Involving stakeholders who are directly affected by the issue and this ensures meaningful contributions from all involved,
- Being action-oriented, aiming to generate motivation and shared commitments towards implementing effective public solutions, even if formal decision-making authority lies beyond the dialogue itself,
- Being supported by a facilitator,
- And beyond the meeting room, following-up with activities such as monitoring and evaluation, ensuring real-world impact of the dialogue.

All activities engaging the public in the context of the CIRAN project meet the above defined criteria of public dialogue. The objectives and outcomes are clearly defined and described in the previous chapter, as well as further in the methodology of the activity. Participants receive evidence-based information in the first Informative phase of the activity, while the second Deliberative phase engages participants into a collaborative discussion. Throughout this whole event, they are supported by an experienced facilitator. Participants who are invited to the event are locals who are or could be potentially affected by mining activities within their community. The event is also action-oriented because the outcome from the discussion will be acknowledged in the policy recommendation that the CIRAN project will produce as an output within WP6. As the planned events are dealing with “what if” scenarios, the monitoring of real-world impact on local communities will not be implemented.

3.4 Participants of public dialogue

A wide range of actors may participate in a public dialogue. Ideally, representatives from all diverse interest groups within the community should be present. However, the event invitation remains open to anyone interested in participating.

Size of the group

The ideal size for a group participating in the CIRAN public dialogue is set between 15 and 50 participants. Of course, there is a significant difference between having a smaller group of 15–30 people and a larger group of 30–50 participants; each has its own advantages and disadvantages. Ultimately, the final number of participants will depend on the local context and the possibilities within each community involved.

A larger group of 30–50 participants offers advantages like a wider range of perspectives, increased public awareness, and stronger community representation, but can be challenging to manage and may be difficult to recruit for less familiar topics.

In contrast, a smaller group of 15–30 participants is easier to organise, encourages more active and meaningful participation, and is more practical when resources are limited. Smaller groups also allow for more focused and inclusive discussions, giving each participant more opportunity to contribute. However, they may lack the diversity and broader influence of larger gatherings.

Ultimately, selecting the appropriate group size requires balancing these trade-offs and considering the specific goals, resources, and context of the community.

Composition of the group

The composition and stakeholder diversity for the public dialogue largely mirror those established for the focus group. Like the focus group, the public dialogue includes a diverse mix of local residents and key stakeholder groups, such as policy-makers, private sector representatives, environmental advocates, civil society, vulnerable groups, media, academia, and the general public. While tailored to each community's specific context, the selection criteria and goals for broad, balanced representation remain consistent across both activities. Therefore, this section builds on the participant selection approach already described for the focus group.

Identification and inviting of participants

In ensuring broad representation and robust engagement in the public dialogues of the CIRAN project, two distinct approaches to inviting and identifying participants will be employed. These methods are designed to balance the need for a minimum number of participants and the representation of diverse groups while remaining open to all interested individuals. It is suggested to give a catchy title to the event to be then shared in the communication materials, for example "Building a Sustainable Europe: The Role of CRMs". Also, in communications it is very important to highlight that the purpose of the event is not only to raise the awareness on the topic but also to hear citizens/stakeholders opinions on it, which will then flow into a project deliverable and integrated into the project's policy briefs.

Individual Invitations

One way for participant identification involves leveraging the expertise and networks of key stakeholders within each community. These stakeholders will be entrusted with nominating suitable participants based on established selection criteria. These nominees should demonstrate a genuine interest in the topic, possess the ability to articulate their opinions respectfully, and commit to the required time investment.

Some of these possible participants have already been recommended to participate in the previous activity – focus group, so they will be invited also to the public dialogue, but also new people will be identified and contacted. A list of identified stakeholders will be created (see [Annex 1– Stakeholder selection table](#)).

Once identified, these nominees receive an invitation letter, outlining the project's objectives and the importance of their involvement. The communication emphasizes the significance of their participation and include essential event details such as the date, time, and location of the focus group meeting. Recipients will be encouraged to express their interest and availability. They are also encouraged to share the invitation with their friends, family, colleagues etc.

(See [Annex 10: Invitation email](#))

Invitations to the General Public:

In parallel, efforts are made to invite the broader public through various channels to ensure inclusivity and diversity of perspectives. These methods include:

- Utilization of social media platforms of the municipality, of the CIRAN project as well as other organizations involved in the activity (see [Annex 11 Example of social media post](#)),
- Posting the events and related invitations on the websites of the municipality/organizations involved in the CIRAN project,
- Posting fliers and poster on public places – municipality building and other public facilities, schools, libraries, restaurants and shops, local boards etc. (see Annex 12: Invitation poster),

- Advertisement in local newspapers, both in print and online formats,
- Coordination of interviews or articles with local radio stations or newspapers to raise awareness and generate interest,
- Another option could be to pay an advertisement in local media.

Invitations sent to the general public should look attractive and the topic should be clear and interesting, also containing essential details such as the purpose of the assembly, the meeting schedule, logistical information, and contact details for registration.

Registration Process:

To ensure adequate preparation, all participants, regardless of invitation method, will be required to fill out a registration form. This form will collect necessary information such as email addresses for sending reminders and determining the final headcount. Registration beforehand will enable the project team to gauge participation levels and make necessary arrangements.

In the registration form, the participants will only be asked for their name, gender (giving the following options: male, female, non-binary, prefer not to say) and e-mail address where they will receive more information about the upcoming meeting a couple days in advance. They will also be able to agree with further materials to be sent to them about the CIRAN project and activities via newsletter and other means. In this form, there will also be a pdf document linked with more information about the event especially for those people, who only saw the invitation poster or social media post that don't contain as many information as the invitation email sent to selected individuals.

See Annex 13 "Registration form" for specific questions and link to the English template of the registration form. The registration form will be shared with the invited participants, and the link to it (via QR code) will also be shared on the Invitation poster. [Here](#) an editable pdf version is also available.

However, recognizing that not all individuals may have access to online registration, the project will allow on-site registration for those who did not register prior to the event. This ensures inclusivity and provides an opportunity for wider community participation.

In conclusion, the combined use of individual invitations and outreach to the general public aims to engage stakeholders effectively and encourage their active participation in the project's activities. Through careful planning and inclusive communication strategies, the CIRAN project seeks to create a dynamic and diverse dialogue platform for addressing critical issues in the community.

3.5 Roles in a public dialogue

In addition to the actual participants of public dialogues, during their implementation within the CIRAN project, various other people will play crucial roles in ensuring effective planning, communication, engagement, and the facilitation of productive discussions.

1. Participants in the public dialogue

- Role: public dialogue participants are vital community stakeholders directly involved in discussions. Their profile is outlined in the previous chapter of this document.

- Responsibilities: Participants represent community ideas and experiences, and they actively contribute to discussions, sharing insights and feedback.

2. Responsible Person from the CIRAN Consortium

- Role: The responsible person, a member of the CIRAN consortium, is in charge of community communication and serves as the primary point of contact with the community.
- Responsibilities: This individual speaks the local language fluently, initiates and maintains communication with the community, and establishes trust. They act as a bridge between the project and the community, ensuring that community perspectives are accurately represented.

3. Key Stakeholder from the Community/Cooperation organisation

- Role: A key stakeholder from the community is a person with a significant role or position within the local context who is willing to actively support the CIRAN project implementation. This could be the mayor, a municipal representative, a local NGO representative, or another community leader. It could also be a whole organisation supporting implementation of CIRAN activities in the community.
- Responsibilities: They facilitate project activities within the community, advocating for its goals and connecting community needs with project objectives, proposes participants for the focus group.

4. Facilitator

- Role: Facilitators guide and moderate public dialogue.
- Responsibilities: Fluent in the local language, experienced facilitators lead discussions, ensuring direction and productivity. They possess a strong grasp of qualitative research methods and interpersonal skills. Facilitators steer discussions using a discussion guide, manage conversation flow, and ensure all participants contribute effectively.
- “It may also be desirable to involve an external facilitator for the actual national public dialogue event”

5. Assistant Facilitator/Note Taker

- Role: Assistant moderators or note-takers support facilitator and document public dialogue proceedings.
- Responsibilities: Proficient in the local language, they assist in facilitating discussions and record key points, insights, and observations. **Their notes are essential for data analysis and preparing the report of the event. It is important that within the group activity they also write down any relevant citations made by participants.** As far as how many assistants/facilitators/note takers to involve, it depends on the number of participants, in order to ensure one of them is present in each group (see information on the group work below).

6. CIRAN Ethics committee

- Role: Members of CIRAN Ethics committee will be provided methodological and communication materials beforehand, and will also be put in CC of relevant communication with local community, to oversee the processes.

- Responsibilities: They scrutinise CIRAN's activities to ensure that these conform to the Ethics Principles endorsed by the Consortium, they also deal with complaints or grievances from external stakeholders (in case any occur).

In the CIRAN project, these roles collaborate to execute public dialogues effectively. The responsible person establishes trust and communication, key stakeholders advocate for the project, participants provide community insights, and facilitators and assistant moderators ensure productive discussions are conducted and documented for analysis.

3.6 Duration and agenda of the public dialogue

The public dialogue should last 2 hours and 15 minutes and the agenda suggested is the following.

Time	Activity
35 minutes	Welcoming and Menti survey Introductory presentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presenting CIRAN ● What are CRMs and why are they critical ● Different scenario for EU
70 minutes	Group work on discussion and deliberation
10 minutes	Break
20 minutes	Plenary session, vote and closing

Each section of the agenda will be detailed in the next sections.

3.7 On-site preparation of public dialogue

In preparation for a public dialogue within the framework of the CIRAN project, different key elements need to be organised on-site to ensure a suitable environment and smooth facilitation.

Setting up the activity

- Location: Choose a conference room that is spacious enough to comfortably accommodate all participants and easily accessible. Ensure there are sufficient chairs for everyone, along with tables for refreshments set up on the side. Additionally, confirm that the venue is fully equipped to accommodate participants with physical disabilities.
- Seating Arrangement: The conference room should have a big screen for the introductory part aimed at introducing/presenting the project and showing the video, well as allow people working in groups for the deliberation phase (see later). See pictures below:

- Refreshments: Ensure that refreshments – at least drinks and biscuits, are available on tables for participants.
- Time Management: Make sure to have enough time to register participants as well as allow them to sit down before starting the session.

Materials and equipment

All the materials need to be translated in local languages.

- Signature lists and participant information sheet: Print the prepared signature lists where participants write their name and signature, and also select groups that they belong to (Municipality, Local business owners, Environmental Advocates, NGOs, Media, Academia, Citizens). They will also be invited to add their emails. By signing this list, they also confirm that they are fully informed about the purpose and procedures of the activity ([Annex 14 Participant Information Sheet](#)), and that they are granting their voluntary permission to participate as well as record their contributions in case you opt for it (see [Annex 15 Signature list](#)). Recording it is not mandatory but can be considered useful especially for the group work activity in order to support the reporting activity, therefore it is up to the facilitator(s) and/or those writing the final report to decide if to record the sessions or not.
- Guidelines of CIRAN public dialogue activity for the facilitator: Print the prepared guide for the facilitator containing an overview of the key information to be obtained, specific questions, additional questions, and guidelines on managing the discussion (see [Annex 16 Guidelines of CIRAN Policy dialogue activity](#)).
- Video about CRMs: Prepare the movie and a device where you can play the video to participants (video accessible [here](#)). The video is embedded into the Introductory presentation. Since it is in English you can add automatic translations into local languages.
- Introductory presentation: Have the prepared presentation ready to share with participants information about main topics of the project as well as about the main results of the previous focus group (see here [the Introductory presentation](#)).

- Blank powerpoint presentation: Prepare the blank presentation with CIRAN graphic background where you will write the notes from the discussion in groups, as well as the statements/recommendations emerged.
- Mentimeter poll: prepare a short Mentimeter poll to share with participants at the beginning (see [Annex 17 Menti questions](#))
- Other supporting materials: Print materials required for the public dialogue, for example INTRAW scenarios, the CIRAN information brochure or any other visual materials necessary for the discussion.
- Recording Equipment: Set up equipment for audio or video recording of the meetings to capture valuable discussions (seek permission first) that could support the reporting process (not mandatory).
- Microphone if considered needed.
- Name badges for facilitator, assistant facilitator and CIRAN staff.
- Roll-up banner with the name and logo of CIRAN and indication of EU support to the project (roll up available [here](#)).
- Remember to take a few pictures for reporting purposes.

Overall, meticulous on-site preparation is essential to create an environment that fosters productive discussions and allows for the smooth operation of the public dialogue within the CIRAN project framework. The facilitator and assistant facilitator should be on site early to make sure everything is set-up and tested in order to avoid wasting people's time with last-minute corrective actions.

3.8 Introductory and informative part

The first part of the activity will be dedicated to an introduction to the day during which the agenda will be presented as well as the topic introduced which the support of the following materials:

- the presentation available [here](#)
- the Video about CRMs, accessible [here](#) (and embedded in the presentation).

The presentation also includes a session in which the results of the previous focus groups conducted in the different communities are shown. If not available yet please also add the results of the focus group conducted in your country.

From 5 to 10 minutes should be left for participants to intervene and comment especially on the results of previous activities before moving to the next session of the activity.

3.9 Key activities: the discussion in groups and the voting session

Discussion/deliberation in groups

The main goals of the deliberation phase are:

- To stimulate meaningful discussions among participants on the proposed topics and questions,
- To confirm and comment on the results of the focus group, integrating relevant findings as deemed appropriate by the facilitator,
- Identify 3-5 key statements on which the whole group agrees that will be used during the final voting session.

Rules for the debate

During this session, participants will be divided in groups composed of 6-10 people each. The number of groups will depend on the number of participants. Groups should be gender-balanced and when possible, include representatives of different stakeholders (ideally each group could have representatives of public bodies, private companies, environmental groups, media, NGOs, and normal citizens). The groups will discuss the questions presented below. Everyone is encouraged to share their thoughts, feelings, and recommendations, considering the information shared and drawing from their personal experiences.

- **Duration:** The group discussion will last for 70 minutes.
- **Group size:** each group should be composed of 6-10 people in order to foster the discussion. Therefore the number of groups depends on the number of participants.
- **Participation:** Everyone is encouraged to share their comments, ideas, or recommendations. To allow equal participation, each person should limit their speaking time to 2–3 minutes per topic or question. (The moderator will remind participants if they exceed their allotted time.)
- **Follow-Up:** If time permits, a second round of discussion may be conducted for the same question. Additionally, participants can share further comments by email after the session.
- **Aim:** The discussion aims to collect participants' comments and recommendations. A note-taker will document the discussion and work with the group to identify 3–5 statements to propose for voting during the plenary session.
- **Time-management:** the facilitator/note taker will take care of time and ensure each question does not take more than 15 minutes. 10 final minutes will be used for identifying 3-5 key statements.

Ground rules for the discussion

1. **Respect all opinions:** There are no right or wrong answers—every opinion and recommendation is highly valued.
2. **Equal opportunity to speak:** Everyone has the right to share their views, and only one person speaks at a time.
3. **Avoid distractions:** Refrain from side conversations.
4. **Balance participation:** Everyone should have an opportunity to contribute; no single participant should dominate the discussion.
5. **Respectful listening:** Listen attentively and respectfully to others when they speak.
6. **Anonymity and confidentiality:** The discussion will be recorded for analysis and reporting purposes, but all comments will be anonymized, and GDPR compliance will be ensured.

Discussion/questions

As mentioned, each group will engage in a **70-minute discussion**, guided by the suggested following questions (also shown on slides), 15 minutes per question:

1. What should the European Union prioritize to ensure a sustainable supply of CRMs?
2. What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of CRMs? Do you think any changes are needed? If so, which ones?
3. Should the extraction of CRMs be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?
4. What do you envision for the future of CRMs that are currently being extracted?

Questions can be adapted by the facilitator(s). Also, in case of groups of 8 people or more, 15 minutes might not be sufficient. In this case, the facilitator(s) can opt for discussing 3 out of 4 questions. In particular, the first 3 questions can be discussed.

Main output

In the last 10 minutes each group will work toward identifying 3-5 key statements that reflect shared agreements, which will be presented during the plenary session for voting. Facilitator(s)/note taker(s) can consider creating sub-groups of 2-3 people in each group and ask each sub-group to identify 1 statement to share during the plenary session. The facilitator(s)/note taker(s) will then collect the statements emerging from the discussion.

Examples of kind of statements that could emerge from the discussion are the followings:

- "Support for research, scientific innovation, and the exploration of alternatives is essential".
- "Diversifying the production of CRMs, both within the EU and outside of it, along with increasing recycling efforts, is essential"
- "It is crucial to educate society in order to encourage a shift in consumer behaviour".

Facilitator(s)/note taker(s) role

As participants share their comments and recommendations, the facilitator(s)/note taker(s) will:

- Take detailed notes of the discussion, also reporting **any relevant quote**,
- Help the group to agree on 3-5 key statements for the voting phase reporting them in a blank presentation. As mentioned above for this specific phase they can also consider splitting the groups in sub-groups of 2-3 people each.

Before the plenary session, the facilitator and note takers will finalize the statements to ensure clarity and alignment with group discussions.

Plenary and voting session

Objective of the decision-finding phase

The goal of this phase is to develop consensual and negotiated recommendations or statements that will be incorporated into CIRAN's policy recommendations.

Voting process

The facilitator will present each statement, and participants will be asked to vote. There are two possible voting methods:

1. **By show of hands;** participants will indicate their level of agreement with each statement (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree).
2. **Via a digital form;** to simplify and speed up the process, the statements can be included in a Google Form. Participants can access the form using a QR code shared during the session and vote.

Based on the voting results, the most relevant and widely supported statements will be identified.

Conclusions

Before concluding, the facilitator will:

- Share the project's contact information and email address in case participants wish to provide additional input after the session.
- Explain the next steps; the CIRAN team will carefully analyse the information gathered during this discussion and compare it with the results from similar dialogues conducted in other European countries. This analysis will contribute to a final report summarizing the findings and recommendations.
- Thank all participants for their valuable contributions to the discussion and remind them that participants who provided an email address will receive:
 - ❖ A summary of the statements and recommendations resulting from the activity,
 - ❖ Updates on upcoming news and results from the CIRAN project as a whole.

3.10 The role-play

As part of the work led by La Palma Research Centre in CIRAN under WP3 and in particular resulting in D3.3 "Nexus of policy decision and drivers of change" (Lopes et al., 2024), an innovative and interactive gaming framework for public use was developed based on the CIRAN 2035 Scenarios.

Figure 3 – CIRAN 2035 scenarios.

These consist of four possible futures for the Critical Raw Materials’ context in Europe in the timeframe of the next 10 years, with the view not to impose but rather to encourage diverse discussions around whether certain trends and drivers are more or less likely to occur in different parts of Europe in the upcoming future (Figure 3). This approach highly seeks to foster multistakeholder dialogue by proposing a set of potential frameworks in a short-term vision, thus facilitating the process of imaginary futures’ thinking across the general public (Lopes et al., 2024). A core objective of the work conducted under this WP was to produce specific outcomes suitable for interoperability across other project tasks, namely, WP5. For this reason, the “What If” framework based on gaming techniques was developed with the aim to test it across WP5 activities throughout 2025, especially targeting their use during Public Dialogues in the selected communities.

In particular, the Public Dialogue which took place in Baiso (Italy), successfully integrated the role-play methodology developed within WP3 and included in D3.3 “Nexus of policy decision and drivers of change”. The role-play game is oriented to foster interaction amongst local participants (players) towards decision-making, seeking to better understand the narratives around and possible futures for CRM extraction in that specific context. It is worth noting that the original methodology was slightly adapted to better fit into the public dialogue framework, allowing for a smooth and enjoyable experience for participants and organisers alike. Therefore, the main difference with the original version of the game is that participants were presented a specific scenario to focus on while at the same time each of them representing a specific character. For this, a set of cards with diverse character role were shared and each player was asked to take one of them and read them silently without disclosing with the other players which stakeholder they were to represent in the discussion.

In other words, each participant would put themselves in the shoes of a different stakeholder and, thus, defend their position, as outlined in their respective character card, throughout the discussion dedicated time. They are thus challenged to engage in the discussion from a perspective that would not necessarily be aligned with their own thoughts on the topics discussed. This is made on purpose to further challenge local perspectives and foster a conversation that encompassed multiple and not necessarily aligned points of view,

thus, preventing the risk that all or most participants from a specific local background in the conversation would have consensus from the beginning. All in all, this very much fosters the development of out-of-the-box thinking and contributed to developing interpersonal intelligence abilities such as empathy and mutual understanding.

Based on the outlined approach, the facilitator decides on which scenario to ask groups to focus on. Depending on the group size, it is encouraged to use multiple scenarios to allow more diverse results of the discussions.

Also, following the methodology sets in D3.3, it is suggested to develop the role-play game materials in the primary language of the community where they are used. This would ensure that all participants are able to express their opinions and contribute to the discussion on equal terms.

The four scenarios are described in [Annex 18](#), while the characters cards are available in [Annex 19](#).

Ideally, having 8 different characters, groups should be composed of 8 people, however, in case of smaller groups facilitators can decide removing some of the characters. In case of bigger groups, facilitators can duplicate some of the characters' descriptions, in this case a few participants would play the same roles.

Each participant picks up a card and reads it silently without disclosing to others which character they represent. The facilitator in each group explains once more the scenario they need to focus on and discuss on the "what if" case study question related to the specific scenario adopted. The templates with the "What if" case study questions are available in [Annex 20](#).

The discussion over the "what if" question lasts around 30 minutes, plus 5 additional minutes to identify a final decision at the group level which needs to be in dedicated cards. After that players within each group reveal each other's role, trying first to guess what everyone was presenting (this is not necessary if participants already disclosed it during the discussion).

At the end of the game, the players become participants again, and leaving their role aside, they engage in a discussion over two of the questions mentioned in the previous version of the exercise in particular, they focus on the following questions:

- What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of CRMs? Do you think any changes are needed? If so, which ones?
- Should the extraction of CRMs be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?

As indicated in the previous version of the group work (which did not embed the role-play), in the last 20 minutes each group works toward identifying 3-5 key statements that reflect shared agreements, which are later presented during the plenary session for voting. Facilitator(s)/note taker(s) can consider creating sub-groups of 2-3 people in each group and ask each sub-group to identify 1 statement to share during the plenary session. The facilitator(s)/note taker(s) then collect the statements emerging from the discussion.

Plenary and voting session

Objective of the decision-finding phase

The goal of this phase is to develop consensual and negotiated recommendations or statements that will be incorporated into CIRAN's policy recommendations. In case the second version of the group work is adopted, the objective of this phase is also to briefly present the results of the "what if" questions as well as the results of the discussion around the two additional questions posed in the last 20 minutes of the workshop.

Results of the "what if" questions

A representative for each group briefly recaps with the help of the facilitator

- the scenario they worked on (in case different scenarios are used)
- the results of the discussion around the what if question (in case the role-play is adopted)
- the results of the discussion around the questions (2 or 4).

Voting process

The facilitator presents each statement emerging from the discussion over the 4 questions (or 2 in case the second version of the group exercise is adopted), and participants are asked to vote. There are two possible voting methods:

1. **By show of hands**; participants indicate their level of agreement with each statement (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree).
2. **Via a digital form**; to simplify and speed up the process, the statements can be included in a Google Form/Mentimeter. Participants can access the form using a QR code shared during the session and vote.

Based on the voting results, the most relevant and widely supported statements are identified.

Conclusions

Before concluding, the facilitator:

- Shares the project's contact information and email address in case participants wish to provide additional input after the session.
- Explains the next steps; the CIRAN team carefully analyses the information gathered during this discussion and compares it with the results from similar dialogues conducted in other European countries. This analysis contributes to a final report summarizing the findings and recommendations.
- Shares an ex-post questionnaire - see details in the next session on "Follow-up activities" (based on the timing the facilitator can decide if to ask participants to answer it before leaving or to send it by email in the next few days)
- Thanks all participants for their valuable contributions to the discussion and remind them that participants who provided an email address will receive:
 - A summary of the statements and recommendations resulting from the activity,
 - the ex-post survey (if not shared during the session),
 - Updates on upcoming news and results from the CIRAN project as a whole.

3.11 Follow-up activities

Following up on the CIRAN public dialogue activity could involve various strategies to engage participants further and disseminate the outcomes of the discussion as well as to evaluate the event. The two aspects below should be addressed in an engagement plan.

Email for Evaluating the event as well as providing additional comments/recommendations

A dedicated email should be sent to all participants and stakeholders who provided their email in the signature list, by the next couple of days from the event, thanking them for their participation and contributions, and asking them to kindly fill an anonymous evaluation questionnaire that will also allow them to provide additional comments or recommendations if they wish, emphasizing that their input is crucial for shaping future actions and policies. Any additional comments received by participants by email are checked and included in the analysis.

A questionnaire using google form can be prepared making sure to include the following points/questions:

- How do you self identify? (options: male/female/non-binary/prefer not to say)
- Affiliation of stakeholder represented (options: public body / private sector / Environmental Advocates / Civil Society (NGOs, Associations / Vulnerable Groups) / Media / Academia & research / other / none of the above I am a normal citizen)
- Are you satisfied with the public dialogue? (options: yes/no/partly)
- Did you get the information you expected? (options: yes/no/partly)
- Did you feel you could contribute to the group work session? (options: yes/no/partly)
- What do you think could be improved? (open question)
- Would you like to share any thoughts/comments related to the dialogue and its topic? (open question)
- Would you like to know more about the topic of CRMs and be updated about the results of the project? If yes please leave your email here (open question).

In case participants do not answer in a few days, a reminder should be sent.

The results of the questionnaire are collected and reported in the activity's report.

CIRAN social media, website, newsletter

To extend the impact of the public dialogue activity, highlights from the event are shared on social media and the website of the CIRAN project. An article summarizing the key topics discussed, major recommendations made by participants, and any notable insights gained is created and published. An overview of the public dialogue activity is presented also in the upcoming newsletter.

3.12 Notes and instructions for the facilitator of a public dialogue

Please rely on what already shared in the [section 2.8](#), about the roles of the facilitator and the assistant facilitator/note taker and related shared responsibilities. Here possible challenges that might emerge during a CIRAN public dialogue are highlighted.

Possible challenges of CIRAN public dialogue

- What if somebody does not agree with the recording: there is more than one facilitator or assistant on site, so it is possible that the participants talk to one of them separately, in a different room. It is possible to offer to the participant to share the comments via email.

- Prepared for resistance: It's important to be prepared for participants who may not be willing to understand or listen as the topics of the discussion could be very sensitive. Maintain a patient and open demeanour throughout the discussion.
- Monitor sentiments: While it is not necessary to directly ask about strong sentiments for or against CIRAN and its objectives, be vigilant for reactions that indicate such sentiments. This information can be crucial for refining communication strategies.
- Addressing concerns: If participants express concerns or feel threatened by mining in their community, reassure them that you understand their worries. Make it clear that your objective is to gather their opinions and that you are not the problem.
- Consulting those without direct problems: recognise that consulting with people who may not have a direct problem with the issue at hand can be challenging. Consider framing questions to engage them effectively and gather their valuable input.

3.13 Research conclusion and data analysis

This chapter delves into the details of analysing the data collected in CIRAN public dialogues, suggesting several steps that will be taken after each public dialogue.

Data preparation and transcription

Gather all data collected during the public dialogue activity, including notes in the PowerPoint presentation, transcripts, notes, recordings, and any additional comments sent by email. Organise the data in a systematic manner, ensuring that it is easily accessible and well-documented. Consider anonymizing sensitive data to protect the privacy of participants, if necessary, while maintaining the integrity of the analysis.

If opted for recording the group work activity the recorded material should be transcribed verbatim using the automatic function of MS Office Word or any other similar program. The translation of the transcript into English can be done using an AI tool. It will be important to check for nuances lost during translation.

Data analysis

With the gathered and transcribed data in hand, the next step is the analysis. Here are the key components of the analysis phase.

Identify key themes and patterns

Review the data to identify all recommendations and comments that emerged during the public dialogue activity. Look for commonalities, differences, and areas of consensus or contention among participants' viewpoints.

Use qualitative analysis techniques such as thematic coding or content analysis to categorize and organise the data based on identified themes.

Evaluate stakeholder perspectives

While ensuring anonymity, assess the diversity of perspectives represented among participants, including those of different stakeholder groups. Analyse the extent to which various stakeholders' viewpoints align or diverge on key issues and recommendations.

Report and presentation

Prepare a clear and concise report summarizing the findings of the data analysis, including key themes, patterns, and recommendations as well as **quotes of participants**.

Verification

The facilitator and the assistant facilitator undertake the analysis. However, to enhance the validity of the findings, the report is shared with other researchers – members of the CIRAN research team who were engaged in the development of the methodology of the focus group. Their insights and feedback will help ensure the accuracy and credibility of the conclusions.

Finalisation

After receiving feedback and making necessary revisions, the report is finalised.

The template for the report is available at this [link](#).

Comparative analysis

After concluding public dialogue in all communities, it is essential to compare findings across different countries to get a broader perspective. It helps identify commonalities, disparities, and unique insights from various groups. Members of the CIRAN research team working on the methodology and participating in public dialogues, and also facilitators and assistant facilitators will meet to exchange experiences and support the development of the report.

4 Overview of public engagement activities in the six communities

4.1 Overall results of public engagement activities

Overall, 12 public engagement activities – 6 focus groups and 6 public dialogues - have been conducted within the CIRAN project. The activities took place in 6 different communities:

- In the Municipality of Baiso in Italy, with 1 focus group and 1 public dialogue.
- In the community of Veselí nad Moravou in the Czech Republic, with 1 focus group and 1 public dialogue.
- In the Mid East Region in Ireland, with 1 focus group and 1 public dialogue.
- In Rimavská Sobota in Slovakia, with 1 focus group and 1 public dialogue.
- In Idanha-a-Nova in Portugal, with 1 focus group and 2 public dialogues.
- In Lens in France, with one focus group.

The 12 public engagement activities involved overall 173 participants, with the majority of them being male (99 out of 173, representing the 57%).

Figure 4 – Gender representation in all public engagement activities.

4.2 Involvement of local stakeholders in public engagement activities

People taking part in the activities represented a wide range of stakeholders, with the higher percentage being students (47 out of 173, representing 27%) followed by representatives of public authorities (36 out of 173, representing the 20.8%) and citizens not representing any specific stakeholder (25 out of 173, representing 14,4%).

Students were particularly present in one of the public dialogues organised, the one in Idanha-a-Nova which took place in a school.

Figure 5 – Type of stakeholders represented in all activities.

Local partners and facilitators made significant efforts to recruit the necessary number and diversity of participants. In some cases, this proved quite challenging—particularly in Italy, Ireland, and Portugal. In Portugal, for example, the difficulty in recruitment led to the organization of a second public dialogue session, held in a school setting.

LPRC, as T7.1 “*Communication and outreach*” leader, supported the promotion of the events by developing tailored dissemination materials, including custom posters and other communication tools. They also produced ex-post videos, such as the one created for the focus group in Baiso (Italy), available at: <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/64LmSpz27-A>.

4.3 Main discourses and key statements identified

This section provides an analysis of the overall results of the activities conducted across the different communities. Focus groups and public dialogues have been conducted using the methodologies presented in chapters 2 and 3, although in some cases with some adaptations. Detailed results for each community are presented in Chapter 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. Additionally, reports on the individual activities are included in the annexes.

4.3.1 Main discourses and key takeaways from the focus group activities

The focus group activities conducted in Italy, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Ireland and Portugal revealed a deep concern for environmental sustainability, strong public mistrust of mining actors, and a widespread call for education, transparency, and genuine public involvement. Across countries, citizens favoured circular economy approaches over extractions, and supported mining only under strict, ethical, and transparent governance frameworks.

Recurring cross-country themes can be synthesized as follows:

1. Limited public awareness but strong demand for education and inclusion

- Portugal, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Italy, Ireland: Many participants lacked a clear understanding of what CRMs are, their importance, and their role in everyday life.
- The term “critical” was questioned, and there was surprise at how widespread CRM use is.
- Need for action: Strong demand for education campaigns, especially early in the decision-making process, to build informed public opinion.

2. Mistrust toward mining & governance structures

- Portugal, Italy, Ireland, Slovakia: Widespread distrust of mining companies and public authorities.
- Concerns included corruption, weak enforcement, lack of transparency, and a history of broken promises or harmful impacts.

3. Environmental protection and preference for sustainable alternatives

- All countries: most of the participants emphasised the need to prevent environmental degradation.
- Portugal, Ireland, Italy: Mining is seen as harmful to biodiversity, landscapes, and long-term ecological balance.
- Participants favoured reuse, recycling, and circular economy models over new extraction.

4. Socio-economic trade-offs and strategic autonomy

- Italy, Czech Republic, Ireland: Recognition of the need to balance environmental concerns with economic development and EU autonomy.
- Conditional support for mining where strong regulation, public benefits, and community engagement are present.
- Italy, Ireland, Czech Republic: Acknowledged EU’s dependency on CRM imports (especially from China)

5. Decision-making, participation and democracy

- All countries: Strong consensus on the need for early, genuine, and inclusive public participation.
- Ireland and Italy: Consultations were often viewed as tokenistic, with pre-made decisions.
- Participants called for stronger local governance and a step-by-step participatory process.

With regard to the focus group conducted in Lens, France, the participants’ high level of expertise led to a set of slightly distinct considerations, which can be summarized as follows:

1. Sustainable resource management is a strategic issue requiring eco-friendly practices, state responsibility for post-mining, and fair benefit sharing.
2. Public and private actors must commit to sustainable transitions, innovation, and ethical consumption, ensuring intergenerational justice.

3. Public mistrust due to past impacts and poor knowledge calls for early citizen engagement through education and mediation.
4. Transparency, citizen education, and informed consent are key to building trust and legitimizing mining projects.
5. Strengthening scientific culture and communication from an early age is essential to foster responsibility and acknowledge mining regions' heritage.

4.3.2 Main discourses and key takeaways from the public dialogue activities

The public dialogues across Portugal, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Italy, and Ireland revealed strong commonalities in citizens' views on the future of CRMs. Five key cross-cutting themes emerged: a broad demand for transitioning to circular economies and more sustainable lifestyles; firm prioritization of environmental protection, especially in opposition to mining in protected areas; conditional acceptance of mining only under strict ethical, environmental, and oversight standards; widespread mistrust in institutions and corporate influence; and strong support for education, innovation, and inclusive public engagement. Despite national differences in emphasis, these shared themes reflect a consistent public vision for a more ethical, transparent, and ecologically responsible approach to CRM governance in Europe confirming the results of the previously conducted focus groups.

1. Transition to circular economy and sustainable lifestyles

- Strong cross-country support for moving away from linear extractive models towards **reuse, recycling, reduction of consumption, and development of sustainable alternatives** to CRMs. This theme reflects a foundational public desire to **minimize dependency on raw materials** through **technological innovation, lifestyle change, and economic restructuring**.
- All countries: all participants resulted supporting recycling, reuse and the extension of product lifespans
- Italy, Slovakia, Czech Republic: participants called for consumer education and behavioral change.

2. Environmental protection as a non-negotiable baseline

- Environmental protection consistently emerged as a dominant public priority, with particular concern over the risk of mining in protected areas, biodiversity loss, water contamination and long-term ecological damage.
- All five countries strongly advocated limiting or outright banning mining in protected areas, **unless under exceptional, heavily regulated conditions**.
- There was broad agreement that irreversible environmental or health damage must be avoided at all costs.

3. Conditional acceptance of mining based on ethics and oversight

- While there was widespread scepticism toward mining, in general participants did not fully reject it. **Conditional acceptance** depended on factors such as **transparency, ethical conduct, strict environmental criteria, and democratic oversight**.
- **Ethical standards and codes of conduct** for companies (especially those operating abroad) were broadly supported in each
- Emphasis on **modern, low-impact extraction techniques** and **mandatory environmental restoration**.

- General preference for **public or EU-based entities** over private multinationals to lead projects.

4. Distrust in institutions and corporate influence

- A widespread **lack of trust in national and EU-level institutions**, alongside corporate scepticism, shaped the dialogues. This mistrust often translated into rejection of mining proposals, especially where participants felt excluded, manipulated, or insufficiently informed.
- Portugal, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Ireland: participants reported public trust deficits.
- Concerns about lobbying, corporate capture of EU policy, and biased consultation processes were frequently raised.
- Transparent, participatory decision-making was seen as essential for rebuilding trust.

5. Public engagement, education and innovation as enablers of change

- There was a strong call for **investment in public education, community participation, and innovative approaches** to facilitate informed, future-oriented decisions. Participants wanted **transparency, inclusion, and respect for local values and knowledge**.
- All countries highlighted the **importance of education and awareness-raising**, particularly around sustainability and mining impacts.
- Participants emphasised the need for **local and community involvement** in decision-making.
- Many dialogues pointed to **future-facing solutions**: alternative materials, AI, or even space mining.

4.3.2.1 Results of the deliberation sessions

As outlined in the methodology, the public dialogues also included a deliberation session during which participants, divided into groups, identified commonly agreed-upon statements and then voted in plenary on their level of agreement with each statement.

Below are the statements that received the highest levels of agreement (with more than half of participants agreeing or strongly agreeing) or disagreement (with more than half disagreeing or strongly disagreeing), reported by country/community.

Portugal – Idanha-a-Nova	
The circular economy and paradigm shift in economic growth are the most viable alternatives for reducing Europe’s dependence on CRMs	High agreement
Reducing the use of CRMs is bound to have a negative economic impact in Portugal (economic crisis, unemployment, etc.).	High disagreement
Most CRMs are considered “critical” essentially because of the strength of economic lobbies.	High agreement
It is impossible to find a balance between responding to current needs for CRMs and mining in protected areas.	High disagreement
If it was possible to mine underground without affecting the surface of protected areas, I would be in favour of this type of exploitation.	High disagreement

Slovakia – Rimavská Sobota	
The EU should prioritize mining sites where there is no risk of irreversible environmental and health damage, or choose more sensitive mining methods, even at higher cost.	High agreement
Strategies and monitoring mechanisms for mining should be carried out professionally and impartially, with emphasis on reducing consumption, increasing recycling, and raising consumer awareness. Implementation within the EU should be conducted by EU-based or domestic entities.	High agreement
Mining in protected areas should not be allowed, unless it is the only source, in which case stricter conditions must apply to minimize environmental and health impacts.	High agreement
Technologies and mining methods should be modernized, mining strictly regulated and monitored, and investment made in innovation while reassessing past mining practices.	High agreement
An ethical code should apply to companies mining or importing CRMs and the EU should support fair trade in supplier countries, ensuring compliance with environmental and social limits.	High agreement
A “spaceship economy” approach should be adopted—minimizing waste of CRMs so they remain available for essential needs, while supporting the search for alternatives.	High agreement
Extraction should not take place in protected areas due to past negative experiences (e.g., Nižná Slaná, Predajná) and lack of trust in Slovak institutions.	High agreement
The future lies in innovation, such as space programs and research into alternative materials, along with public awareness campaigns.	High agreement

Czech Republic – Buchlovice	
It is always necessary to compare the results of mining and describe its impact.	High agreement
There needs to be financial support for research and science and search for alternatives.	High agreement
Diversification of production of CRMs (EU, non-EU) and recycling is necessary.	High agreement
It is necessary to educate society to change consumer behaviour.	High agreement
It is necessary to insist on the responsibility of global corporations, producers, and politicians.	High agreement
It is important to build strategic partnerships while maintaining moral standards.	High agreement
If possible, mining in protected areas should be avoided.	High agreement
Environmental damage should be compensated (but mining can also create new habitats).	High agreement
Mining should be avoided if it means endangering water resources.	High agreement
Extraction needs can change over time.	High agreement

Italy – Baiso	
Invest in the recovery and reuse of existing materials and promote products that are more durable, repairable, and upgradable.	High agreement
Foster cultural and economic changes that counter obsolescence and support long-term sustainability.	High agreement
Extraction in protected areas can be considered only if: The resource is genuinely present in significant and strategic quantities and the area does not represent an irreplaceable ecosystem.	High agreement
Do not abandon extraction in Europe but promote a culture of sustainable resource use through education, information, and ethical marketing at all levels of society.	High agreement
Decisions are based on multidisciplinary expertise, impact assessments, and integrated approaches.	High agreement
In some cases, it is possible to design models with dual positive impacts, combining economic development with environmental protection.	High agreement
Include binding ethical regulations for European companies operating abroad.	High agreement
Link extraction activities to conscious planning of future needs.	High agreement
Evaluate on a case-by-case basis the possibility of extraction in protected areas, starting with those that are less sensitive and considering more delicate areas only as a second option, using clear and shared criteria.	High agreement
Allow extraction only with low-impact techniques, ensuring mandatory environmental restoration, territorial compensation, and landscape integration plans.	High agreement

Ireland – Mid-East Region	
Developing an independent and secure supply via diversification, reduction and reuse should be an EU priority.	High agreement
Knowledge and education are critical in facilitating public acceptance of mining projects.	High agreement
Streamlining the planning process, stable geopolitical relationships and substitution of materials are important for a sustainable supply.	High agreement
Providing for joined up thinking and partnership creating in projects with public, private and local communities is essential.	High agreement
More efforts should be made to give successful examples of mining in protected areas.	High agreement

5 Public engagement activities in Portugal: the community of Idanha-a-Nova

5.1 Overview of the local context and stakeholders involved in the activities

In Portugal, the citizen engagement activities took place in the Idanha-a-Nova village, a Portuguese village in the district of Castelo Branco, part of the province of Beira Baixa, with around 2.100 inhabitants. Idanha is rich in natural heritage, creativity, and innovation. The economy of the municipality of Idanha-a-Nova revolves around agriculture, animal husbandry, forestry, tourism, local government, and agribusiness. The area also hosts an UNESCO Geopark, the Montes-Ilha de Monsanto.

The activities were organised with the support of the Municipality of Idanha-a-Nova.

Overall, 3 citizen engagement activities have been organised at Idanha-a-Nova: 1 focus group and 2 public dialogues. 59 people have been involved in the 3 activities. The graph below shows the gender composition and stakeholder categories taking part in the activities.

Figure 6 – Gender of participants in activities at Idanha-a-Nova.

As visible from the graph above, the rate of male and female participants is quite similar.

Figure 7 – Types of stakeholders in activities at Idanha-a-Nova.

As visible from the graph above, the most represented category is the one of students, since the participants of the second public dialogue were mainly students (38 out of 41).

5.2 Implementation of the focus group and key findings

The focus group at Idanha-a-Nova took place on 21st November 2023 from 2:30 to 4:30 pm at the Municipal library of Idanha-a-Nova. The mayor of the village was contacted to present the project, propose the activity and ask for support especially with reference to the identification of participants to be involved.

The implementation of the focus group followed the methodology detailed in chapter 2.

The overall report is available in [Annex 21](#).

Eight people participated in the event, six self-identifying as female and two as male. The composition of the group was quite varied with representatives of environmental activism, a local entrepreneur, an academic, a teacher, two representatives of NGOs and a geologist. The majority of participants showed to have clear interests on environmentally protected issues, either through personal or professional activities.

5.2.1 Focus group's key findings

During the focus group's introductory part, some participants showed scepticism on the fact that no projects for the extraction of mineral resources were planned in Idanha-a-Nova and three of them clearly stated they were there to have an active role against any mining project that may be planned for Idanha-a-Nova.

The main arguments emerged during the focus group's core discussion can be summarised as follows:

- Participants generally **lacked awareness and understanding of critical raw materials (CRMs)**. Some of them contested the world "critical" wondering what and whom such materials might be critical to. Also, they did not know any examples of mining activities.

- There was a notable concern for environmental protection, overshadowing potential economic benefits of mineral extraction. **Scepticism** towards mining projects was prevalent, driven by doubts about their long-term benefits and impacts on local ecosystems.
- Everybody agreed that there should be **alternatives** to importing or mining minerals. Three participants focused their discussion on the idea that the economic system needs to start a degrowth process to avoid further need for mining, and that everyone needs to start changing their behaviour in terms of consumption, while the rest of them highlighted alternatives such as investing in technology, reusing and recycling.
- In terms of impacts of mining activities, although some participants could not see any positive impacts, others had a more integrated view, mentioning **positive social economic impacts**.
- All the group agreed that in general the public is on the side of environmental protection.
- The group strongly expressed the need for **more transparent and inclusive decision-making processes**. Some participants suggested that the involvement of a local community should be done through several steps: by starting to explore the degree of knowledge of the locals, then by educating them on the topic and then explaining the project.
- A general sense of mistrust was felt in the group regarding the involvement of public agencies and private companies in the evaluation of environmentally sensitive projects like mining.

5.3 Implementation of the public dialogues and key findings

Two public dialogues took place in Idanha-a-Nova took. One took place on the 14th of May 2024 at the Cultural Forum of Ihanha from 6 till 8 pm, while the other on the 13th of November 2024 at the School's auditorium from 3 to 5 pm. The involvement of the mayor of the village was again very important for the identification of participants to involve. The implementation of the focus group followed the methodology detailed in chapter 2 with slightly differences related to the fact that the core discussion went around the following 5 scenarios (instead of the four questions indicated in the methodology):

- 1) Obtaining CRMs by trade, keeping current dependency on non-EU suppliers (current model). Yes, but?
- 2) Obtaining CRMs by trade through building strategic partnerships outside of Europe, thus diversify sources (trusted partners outside of Europe) Yes, but?
- 3) Obtaining CRMs through EU domestic sourcing initiatives, thus localise and diversify sources (secure resources in the EU) Yes, but?
- 4) Shift towards a circular economy and resource efficiency (reducing waste, promoting recycling, and maximising resource efficiency throughout the product life cycle – still hidden potential) Yes, but?
- 5) Drastic change in values and consumption behaviour of European society (reduce consumerism) Yes, but?

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 22](#).

7 people participated in the first event, three self-identifying as female and four as male, only one participant represented an NGO, while the others were normal citizens. The second public dialogue involved 41 people, with the majority being students (above 18 years old) and three teachers. 18 were females and 23 males.

Figure 8 – First public dialogue in Idanha-a-Nova.

Figure 9 – Second public dialogue in Idanha-a-Nova.

5.3.1 Public dialogues' key findings

Five main topics/issues emerged during the **first public dialogue** with relevant findings:

1. **Technology and innovation as alternatives:** Participants broadly supported the use of technological and scientific innovation to reduce dependence on mining and CRMs. This included investing in alternative energies like hydrogen, exploring new energy storage materials, and trusting scientific research to develop sustainable solutions.
2. **Changing lifestyles and societal values:** A smaller but vocal group advocated for a fundamental shift in lifestyle and societal values—moving away from materialism, embracing minimalism, and redefining quality of life. They emphasised recycling and reducing consumption as essential strategies.
3. **Environmental priority above all:** The environment was consistently cited as the top priority, with a shared sense of urgency for transformative change. Participants expressed skepticism about the mining industry's environmental impact and stressed the need for a global, long-term perspective.
4. **Distrust in European politicians and corporate influence:** There was a widespread distrust of European politicians and institutions, especially regarding their ties to corporate and lobbying interests. Participants called for greater transparency, independence in policy-making, and investment in alternative solutions free from corporate control.
5. **Unanimous rejection of mining in protected areas:** The group was unanimously opposed to any mining in protected areas, viewing it as contradictory to their conservation purpose. They demanded strict preservation of these zones, regardless of economic or strategic interests.

During the deliberation phase, the voting confirmed what emerged in the discussion phase regarding an overall reluctance to endorse mining, even with potential environmental safeguards. There is a complex and often mistrustful stance among participants towards CRMs and mining in general, and also towards the questions asked. While there is consensus on the potential benefits of a circular economy and technological alternatives, participants exhibit significant scepticism regarding the reduction of CRMs impacting economic growth and the possibility of environmentally responsible mining. Some responses revealed distrust towards the motives behind the questions, with participants sometimes interpreting them as leading or "rigged" to elicit specific answers.

The picture below shows the results of the voting phase in the first public dialogue.

Voting phase questions - Likert Scale - Public Discussion Idanha-a-Nova - CIRAN							
Date: May 14th 2024							
Author: Rodrigo Castro (main facilitator)							
	QUESTIONS	ANSWERS					Refused to respond
		1 - Strongly Disagree	2 - Disagree	3 - Neutral	4 - Agree	5 - Strongly Agree	
1	It is credible to find alternatives and technological innovations in the short term (1-5 years) that can avoid Europe's current dependence on critical raw materials.	1	1	3		3	
2	The circular economy and a paradigm shift in economic growth are the most viable alternatives for reducing Europe's dependence on critical raw materials				3	5	
3	Reducing the use of critical raw materials is bound to have a negative economic impact in Portugal (economic crisis, unemployment, etc.)	4	3	1			
4	Most critical raw materials are considered "critical" essentially because of the strength of economic lobbies		1	1	3	3	
5	I would be willing to reduce my economic income to avoid mining European/Portuguese soil						8
6	I'm not against mining per se, I'm especially against mining in protected areas						8
7	It is possible to find a balance between responding to current needs for critical raw materials and mining in protected areas	4	4				
8	Mining almost always involves highly destructive impacts in ecological terms			3		3	1
9	If there are no alternatives, I prefer to continue importing raw materials from abroad rather than exploiting European soil			1			7
10	If it were possible to mine underground without affecting the surface of protected areas, I would be in favour of this type of exploitation	6		2			

Figure 10 – Results of the voting session.

The **second public dialogue** in Idanha-a-Nova brought a fresh perspective due to its distinct participants profiles. The absence of environmental NGOs allowed attendees to voice their personal and independent viewpoints. Notable themes and conclusions from this session include:

- **Conditional acceptance of mining in protected areas:** Participants emphasised that any mining project in Idanha, a protected region, must align with a significant societal purpose. When faced with the question of approving a CRM mine, attendees unanimously opposed projects aimed at meeting excess consumption but cautiously supported those justified by collective benefits, such as renewable energy or critical infrastructure.
- **Pragmatism over idealism:** While earlier sessions highlighted fatalistic and activist-driven opposition to mining, this group displayed a more pragmatic approach. They sought a balanced perspective, recognizing the tension between ecological conservation and societal needs.
- **Reinforcing regional identity:** Participants strongly identified with their region's status as a protected area and viewed it as both a privilege and a responsibility. Discussions reflected a commitment to stewardship while remaining open to meaningful, transformative projects.

5.4 Key takeaways

Overall, three main takeaways can be identified from the results of the activities conducted in Idanha-a-Nova:

1. **Lack of knowledge and misinformation:** Many participants lacked a clear understanding of mining and critical raw materials (CRMs), showing confusion despite the educational materials provided. The complexity of the topic and difficulty distinguishing between types of mining contributed to widespread misconceptions.
2. **Distrust toward mining and related entities:** There was deep scepticism about mining operations, policymakers, corporations, and even the public consultation process itself. Participants questioned the transparency and motives of all involved, including CIRAN and its affiliated organizations.
3. **Strong influence of environmental activists:** Activists had a strong impact on participants, largely because of their persuasive focus on environmental protection. Their influence was amplified by the public's limited knowledge and existing distrust of mining-related actors, making their "greed vs green" narrative especially compelling.

6 Public engagement activities in Slovakia: the community of Rimavská Sobota

6.1 Overview of the local context

The citizen engagement activities took place in the Rimavská Sobota district town located in the Banskobystrický region of southern Slovakia which is home to around 80,000 inhabitants. The area has a long history of industrial and agricultural activity, with mining, metalworking, and forestry playing key roles in its economic development. However, in recent decades, the region has faced economic decline, high unemployment rates, and depopulation, making it one of the most economically disadvantaged areas in Slovakia.

Overall, 2 citizen engagement activities were organised in this region namely one focus group and one public dialogue with 25 people overall being involved in these two activities.

The graph below shows the gender composition and stakeholder categories taking part in the activities.

Figure 11 – Gender of participants in activities at Rimavská Sobota.

As visible from the graph above, the rate of male and female participants is quite similar with a percentage of male participants being slightly higher.

When it comes to the kind of stakeholders, the following graph illustrates the different profiles of participants with most of them being citizens that don't necessarily represent any defined type of stakeholders; the majority of them embodying the general public and residents with 10 participants from this category. The second most represented category among participants was academics and researchers, with a total of five individuals. This was followed by environmental activists/advocates and NGO representatives, each represented by two participants.

Figure 12 – Types of stakeholders in activities at Rimavská Sobota.

6.2 Implementation of the focus group and key findings

The focus group at Rimavská Sobota took place on the 11th of December 2024 at the community centre CITADELA, a relatively new local venue for alternative culture, used for civic discussions, cultural events, and public meetings.

The focus group was organised by Centrum komunitného organizovania (CKO) in collaboration with Rimavská kaviareň (RK). CKO is a well-established non-governmental organization active in community engagement, public participation, and environmental advocacy in the city of Banská Bystrica (having active community called Green Banská Bystrica) while RK is a informal but very active community player in the region.

The implementation of the focus group followed the methodology detailed in chapter 2.

The overall report is available in [Annex 23](#).

Ten people participated in this event, which included seven males and three females. The composition of the group was quite varied with participants embodying local entrepreneurs and environmental activists along with some other participants representing the general public and residents which were considered as a majority in this case. Most of them expressed a strong interest in gaining new insights into environmental issues and sustainability, attending the discussion out of curiosity and a desire to contribute to local decision-making.

6.2.1 Focus group key findings

Four main themes and concerns were highlighted during the discussion, these latter mostly concentrated on consumption and sustainability, resource extraction and its consequences, mining in protected areas, and public and political attitudes.

Therefore, the main arguments emerged during the focus group's core discussion can be summarized as follows:

- Participants questioned the necessity of current consumption levels and suggested that reduced demand in Europe could influence countries like China to scale back mining.
- Concerns were raised about the energy and clean water needed for recycling, with calls for stricter regulations on waste imports to ensure accountability.
- The issue of resource extraction sparked strong views, with one participant calling raw materials as "tools of war" and warning that lobbying could corrupt public policy.
- Many doubted that major powers like China and India would reduce mining voluntarily, citing the unsustainable nature of a growth-driven global economy.
- While some saw possible exceptions based on the materials involved, there was broad agreement that mining companies should fund land restoration upfront, amid concerns about corruption and poor environmental enforcement in Slovakia.
- Participants emphasised the need to link future extraction to research, innovation, and environmental education, noting low public awareness of CRMs and a tendency to oppose local mining while supporting it abroad.
- Political populism and misinformation were seen as major barriers to informed public debate on sustainability in Slovakia.

Figure 13 – Picture from the focus group in Rimavská Sobota.

6.3 Implementation of the public dialogue and key findings

When it comes to the public dialogues, this latter took place on the 9th of April 2025 in Rimavská Sobota. The event was organised by Centrum komunitného organizovania and Rimavská kaviareň at the Cultural centre CITADELA. It brought together fifteen participants representing various sectors namely academics and researchers, representatives of NGOs, one participant from the public authority, one media person and the majority being from the general public. Participants were both women and men, almost reaching a gender balance (7 women and 8 men).

The implementation of the public dialogues followed the methodology detailed in Chapter 3.

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 24](#).

The participants engaged in two structured groups deliberating on four key questions:

- What should the European Union prioritize to ensure a sustainable supply of CRMs?
- What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of CRMs? Do you think any changes are needed?
- Should the extraction of CRMs be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?
- What do you envision for the future of CRMs that are currently being extracted?

Figure 14 – Picture from the public dialogue in Rimavská Sobota.

Figure 15 – Picture from the public dialogue in Rimavská Sobota.

6.3.1 Public dialogue’s key findings

Four main discussion points emerged from the groups:

- Both discussion groups emphasised that any extraction of critical raw materials (CRMs) must be approached with caution, respect for environmental values, and attention to long-term societal impacts. Also, participants emphasised the need to avoid extraction in places where irreversible environmental damage could occur, including risks to human health and biodiversity. A code of ethics for companies extracting and importing CRMs should be adopted.
- Participants supported increasing the reuse of materials and ensuring that extraction and monitoring strategies are driven by expert, non-political processes, as well as the introduction of a code of ethics for companies.
- A group strongly opposed mining in protected areas unless it was the only possible source. While scepticism and mistrust toward Slovak authorities was a significant reason for the other group for rejecting mining near protected areas, highlighting governance as a central concern.
- Participants advocated for the modernization of mining methods, as well as a long-term planning based on consumption projections, renewed interest in space mining, and improved public education.

The dialogue concluded with the deliberation phase focused on the following eight statements that summarize the main outcomes of the discussions:

1. The EU should prioritize mining sites where there is no risk of irreversible environmental and health damage, or choose more sensitive mining methods, even at higher cost.
2. Strategies and monitoring mechanisms for mining should be carried out professionally and impartially, with emphasis on reducing consumption, increasing recycling, and raising consumer awareness. Implementation within the EU should be conducted by EU-based or domestic entities.
3. Mining in protected areas should not be allowed, unless it is the only source, in which case stricter conditions must apply to minimize environmental and health impacts.
4. Technologies and mining methods should be modernized, mining strictly regulated and monitored, and investment made in innovation while reassessing past mining practices.
5. An ethical code should apply to companies mining or importing CRMs, and the EU should support fair trade in supplier countries, ensuring compliance with environmental and social limits.
6. A “spaceship economy” approach should be adopted—minimizing waste of CRMs so they remain available for essential needs, while supporting the search for alternatives.
7. Extraction should not take place in protected areas due to past negative experiences (e.g., Nižná Slaná, Predajná) and lack of trust in Slovak institutions.
8. The future lies in innovation, such as space programs and research into alternative materials, along with public awareness campaigns.

Several major topics were unanimously agreed upon throughout this phase, including promoting ecologically safe mining, modernizing mining technology, the importance of ethical sourcing and fair trade, and long-term investments in innovation and public awareness. These findings demonstrate a shared commitment to sustainable, responsible, and forward-thinking approaches to raw material extraction.

All members (15 votes for, 0 against) agreed that mining should only occur where there is no risk of irreversible environmental or health damage, even if it results in higher costs. There was also unanimous agreement on adopting ethical standards for companies involved in mining or importing CRMs, and on pursuing a “spaceship economy” model that minimizes waste and secures essential resources.

Most members (14 for, 1 against) backed the need for professional and impartial mining strategies, implemented by domestic or EU-based entities, with a focus on reducing consumption, increasing recycling, and raising awareness. However, opinions diverged on mining in protected areas. One proposal, allowing it only when no alternative exists, passed narrowly (9 for, 5 against, 1 abstention), while another proposal calling for a complete ban due to past negative experiences and low institutional trust received broader support (13 for, 1 against, 1 abstention). Finally, there was unanimous agreement on supporting future-oriented innovations, such as space exploration and alternative materials, alongside public education campaigns.

6.4 Key takeaways

Overall, these three main takeaways can be identified from the results of the activities conducted at Rimavská Sobota:

1. Participants across both the focus group and public dialogue strongly emphasised the need to avoid irreversible environmental damage.
2. Ethical standards for companies involved in mining or importing CRMs should be adopted.
3. A lack of trust in Slovak institutions, fuelled by past environmental damage and corruption, led many to oppose mining in protected areas.
4. Both sessions highlighted the need for investment in research, environmental education, and innovation (including alternative materials and space technologies) as essential strategies for a sustainable future.

7 Public engagement activities in Czech Republic: the community of Buchlovice

7.1 Overview of the local context

Two citizen engagement activities were organised in the Czech Republic. They took place in two key locations.

The focus group was held in "Panský dvůr", in Veselí nad Moravou, a gateway to the White Carpathians Protected Landscape Area (PLA) and UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. The town was chosen for its strategic location and the presence of the Czech partner organisation, the Education and Information Centre Bílé Karpaty (VIS BK), as well as the regional office of the White Carpathians PLA Administration. In 2024, the White Carpathians House of Nature also opened there, serving as a modern visitor centre for the White Carpathians Protected Landscape Area.

The public dialogue was later held at Hotel Buchlov during the 2024 Carpathian Convention Stakeholders Meeting.

The White Carpathians are located in the eastern part of the Czech Republic, on the border with Slovakia; and were designed in 1980 as a Protected Area which covers approximately 715 km² with the main objects of protection being species-rich meadows and orchards.

Overall, 43 participants were involved in the two activities conducted, the graph below shows their gender composition.

Figure 16 – Gender of participants in activities at the Czech Republic.

As visible from the graph above, the rate of male and female participants is quite similar with a percentage of male participants being slightly higher.

When it comes to the types of stakeholders involved, the graph below illustrates the diverse profiles of participants. The largest group consists of individuals from public authorities, with approximately 20 participants, most of whom represent state administrations and public institutions. The second most prominent group includes representatives of NGOs and CSOs, accounting for around 13 participants.

Figure 17 – Types of stakeholders in activities at the Czech Republic.

7.2 Implementation of the focus group and key findings

The focus group in Veselí nad Moravou, took place on the 20th of June 2024 at Panský dvůr. This public building hosts several key institutions, including the municipal gallery, a business incubator, the tourist information centre, and the offices of various NGOs, among them the Education and Information Centre Bílé Karpaty (VIS BK), which served as the official organiser of the focus group meeting. The implementation of the focus group followed the methodology detailed in chapter 2.

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 25](#).

Seven people took part in the event, including three men and four women. The group had a diverse composition, with most participants representing NGOs and public authorities, alongside one researcher and one environmental activist. Most of them already had some personal experience with active citizenship, and almost half of them had some international relations and connections in the field they were engaged in.

Figure 18 – Picture from the focus group in Veselí nad Moravou.

7.2.1 Focus group key findings

Three main themes of discussion were highlighted during the focus group, each focusing on different aspects of the critical raw materials (CRMs) debate:

1. Familiarity with the concept of CRMs

In general, participants admitted that they were not very familiar with the concept of CRWs. They were surprised by the wide number of products embedding these materials. Someone commented *“It’s the kind of raw material that we desperately need”*. Participants were also aware of some geo-political realities and the fact that most deposits are in third countries and that Europe is dependent on imports. They mentioned the need for good international relations with resource-rich countries, the need to get rid of a certain "colonial" perspective and for reciprocal and mutually beneficial relations. Also, they acknowledged that there is an urgent need for strong state and EU states control in the area of raw materials. Regarding the dilemma between the need of environmental protection and socio-economic resilience some radical statements emerged such as *“There is just one Earth. It’s not that Europe is separate from the rest of the world. And the only solution, I think, is maybe some kind of complete blackout. I really think so. Until people learn not to be greedy.”*

2. Mining in environmentally protected areas

Participants reflected on both past and present mining activities, recalling the communist regime’s disregard for communities and the environment. A recent case in Ostrožská Nová Ves and Uherský Ostroh was mentioned, where plans to expand sand and gravel extraction have sparked protests over fears of groundwater depletion. One participant noted they were *“quite lucky”* that no major deposits exist in the White Carpathians, with former quarries now left to regenerate naturally rather than undergoing *“costly recultivations”*. When asked about accepting mining in protected areas for supply security, most leaned towards prevention and smarter alternatives. *“Does it make sense to mine phosphorus? No,”* one said, citing the high levels already present in Czech soil and the possibility of releasing it through better agricultural practices. Participants emphasised the need for a circular economy and expressed a clear

preference for reopening already degraded sites over disturbing untouched ones. The ongoing Bučník quarry discussions were seen as a telling example of how extraction could be negotiated while respecting local ecological dynamics.

3. Politics, policies, and public perspectives

Participants recognized the environmental risks of mining, noting that some materials create more waste than others. Public understanding was seen as limited, with one noting that *“a huge amount of waste... cannot be put back into the landscape.”* Knowledge of CRMs policies was low. While broader EU strategies like the Green Deal were mentioned, participants criticized poor communication and bureaucratic complexity, saying this leads to public confusion and backlash. They agreed locals should be involved in decisions, as they best understand regional impacts. Citing Dambořice, one said extraction brought compensation through infrastructure and cultural investment. Participants stressed the need for transparent negotiations, fair compensation, and strong local leadership to ensure long-term community benefits.

Therefore, the main arguments that emerged from the core discussions of the focus group can be summarized as follows:

- Priority should be given to alternatives to opening new quarries, such as recycling or more sustainable sourcing methods.
- Re-opening previously closed quarries was seen as a more acceptable option, provided it is thoroughly assessed and justified.
- In the case of re-opening quarries, there is a strong need for oversight and control by both state authorities and local communities to ensure transparency and accountability.
- The role of private business should be limited in the management of strategic raw materials to avoid misuse and loss of public control over these vital resources.
- The concept of strategic raw materials should be made accessible and understandable to the general public.
- There is a clear need for improved communication and public engagement on this issue, ensuring people are well-informed and meaningfully involved in related decisions.

7.3 Implementation of the public dialogue and key findings

When it comes to the public dialogue, this latter took place on the 14th of November 2024 at 6:30 p.m. at Hotel Buchlov (Buchlovice, Czech Republic) conference hall. The event was organised by the Bílé Karpaty Education and Information Centre, o.p.s. (hereinafter referred by the Czech name VIS BK), a non-profit organisation that has long been involved in the interpretation of the natural, historical and cultural heritage of Bílé Karpaty.

The event brought together 36 participants from a range of sectors, with a balanced mix of 16 women and 20 men. Most participants represented state administration and public institutions, accounting for approximately 18 individuals. The next most prominent group included representatives of NGOs and civil society organizations, with around 10 participants involved.

The implementation of the public dialogues followed the methodology detailed in Chapter 3

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 26](#).

The participants engaged in four structured groups deliberating on four key questions:

1. What should be the European Union's approach to ensuring a sustainable supply of CRMs?
2. Does anything need to change within the EU to ensure a sustainable supply of CRMs?
3. Should we allow the possible extraction of CRMs also in protected areas? If so, under what conditions? If not, what are the main reasons?
4. How do you see the future of the CRMs currently being extracted?

Figure 19 – Picture from the public dialogue in the Hotel Buchlov conference hall.

7.3.1 Public dialogues' key findings

The main discussion points emerged from the four groups were the following:

- Participants recognized the necessity of mining CRMs, while also acknowledging its potential negative impacts on nature, the landscape, and local communities.
- There was a shared understanding that, although CRMs are likely indispensable, sustainable extraction must be prioritized through increased support for scientific research and innovation, awareness raising and improved public information, active search for sustainable alternatives, greater emphasis on recycling, and the promotion of high-quality, repairable products with longer lifespans
- Regarding mining in protected areas, all groups agreed that it may be acceptable under strict conditions. These include the use of environmentally friendly technologies, full respect for the natural and cultural value of the area, and thorough case-by-case assessments before any activity begins.

The dialogue concluded with the deliberation phase focused on the following twelve statements that summarize the main outcomes of the discussions:

1. It is always necessary to compare specific conclusions to find out the impact of mining.
2. It doesn't matter whether the extraction of CRMs takes place in the EU or outside the EU.

3. There needs to be support for research and science and search for alternatives.
4. Diversification of production of CRMs (EU, non-EU) and recycling is necessary.
5. It is necessary to educate society to change consumer behaviour.
6. It is necessary to insist on the responsibility of global corporations, producers, and politicians.
7. It is important to build strategic partnerships while maintaining moral standards.
8. If possible, mining in protected areas should be avoided.
9. Environmental damage should be compensated (but mining can also create new habitats).
10. Advanced (environmentally friendly) technologies should be used in mining.
11. Mining should be avoided if it means endangering water resources.
12. Abstraction needs can change over time.

When voting on these statements arising from the discussions, the participants demonstrated near-unanimous agreement on several key issues. There was strong consensus on the necessity of comparing specific conclusions to fully understand the impact of mining, with 34 participants in favour and only one abstention.

The importance of supporting research and science, alongside the search for viable alternatives, was affirmed unanimously. Most participants also agreed on the need for diversification of CRMs production, both within and outside the EU, and emphasised the role of recycling, with only two abstentions on this point. Educating society to foster more responsible consumer behaviour was broadly supported, as was the call for holding global corporations, producers, and politicians accountable for their role in the supply chain. Participants also stressed the value of building strategic partnerships, provided that moral and ethical standards are maintained.

While the majority agreed that mining in protected areas should be avoided, when possible, they acknowledged that in some cases, if done under strict environmental safeguards, it may be acceptable. Opinions were more divided on the use of advanced, environmentally friendly technologies in mining, reflecting a degree of scepticism or uncertainty regarding feasibility or implementation. Nonetheless, there was near-unanimous agreement that mining should not proceed if it endangers water resources, and that any environmental damage caused should be compensated, recognizing also that, in some instances, mining could contribute to the creation of new habitats. Finally, the group acknowledged that societal needs and perspectives on resource abstraction may evolve over time, and that policies should be flexible enough to adapt to these changes.

7.4 Key takeaways

Overall, these main takeaways can be identified from the results of the activities conducted in the Czech Republic:

1. CRMs are essential but must be extracted without harming the environment or local communities.
2. Alternatives like recycling, innovation, and circular economy solutions should be prioritized over new mining.
3. Transparency, ethical governance, and inclusive decision-making are crucial to building public trust.
4. Strategic resources should remain under strong state control, limiting corporate influence.
5. Mining in protected areas should only occur under exceptional, strictly regulated conditions.

8 Public engagement activities in Italy: the community of Baiso

8.1 Overview of the local context and stakeholders involved in the activities

Two citizen engagement activities were organised in Italy. Both of them took place in the Municipality of Baiso, a small municipality of approximately 3,200 inhabitants located in the province of Reggio Emilia, in the Emilia-Romagna region of northern Italy. It was chosen due to its location in the Apennines, a region known for its rich natural heritage and proximity to several environmentally protected zones.

Overall, the focus group and public dialogue brought together a total of 20 participants. The male participation was more prominent, with 13 men and 7 women taking part in the discussions.

The graph below shows the gender composition taking part in the activities.

Figure 20 – Gender of participants in activities at Baiso.

When it comes to the types of stakeholders, the following graph illustrates the different profiles of participants with the largest group consisting of individuals from public authorities, with approximately 7 participants, most of whom were municipality representatives and collaborative councillors. The second most prominent group included citizens not representing any stakeholders accounting for around 4 participants.

Figure 21 – Types of stakeholders involved in activities at Baiso.

8.2 Implementation of the focus group and key findings

The focus group in Baiso was held on the 26th of July 2024 from 10:00 to 12:00. The focus group was organised through collaboration with the local municipality and with a local organization - environmental education and sustainability centre (CEAS).

The implementation of the focus group followed the methodology detailed in chapter 2.

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 27](#).

A total of 9 participants took part in the event, with a balanced mix of ages and a slight predominance of men, including 6 men and 3 women. The group was diverse, with equal representation from NGOs/CSOs and public authorities -three participants each- alongside one teacher, one researcher, and one citizen.

Figure 22 – Picture from the focus group in Baiso in Italy.

8.2.1 Focus group key findings

Three main themes of discussion were highlighted during the focus group, each focusing on different aspects of the critical raw materials (CRMs) debate:

1. **Familiarity with the concept of CRMs:** Participants showed a clear awareness of the importance of critical raw materials (CRMs) in modern life, particularly their role in technology, economic development, and Europe's geopolitical positioning. While many admitted to not being deeply familiar with the term, they were surprised to learn how embedded these materials are in everyday products. A shared concern was Europe's heavy dependence on imports, especially from China, highlighting the strategic vulnerability this creates. Many stressed the urgency of raising public awareness and investing in sustainable extraction technologies. There was strong support for domestic production to ensure autonomy and resilience, though participants were also mindful of the environmental and social costs. As one noted, *"If we do not [invest in extraction], we risk losing our economic and technological independence"*, while others emphasised the importance of balancing production with sustainability, calling for repair, reuse, and circular economy models. The dilemma between socio-economic resilience and environmental protection sparked nuanced reflections; participants acknowledged mining's economic benefits but urged sustainable practices, advanced technologies, and stronger regulations. A notable suggestion was the need for EU subsidies to support start-ups focused on repair and modularity, revealing a broader desire for systemic change alongside technical solutions. Overall, the discussion revealed a strong call for strategic autonomy, environmental responsibility, and a shift in mindset toward long-term sustainability.

- 2. Mining in environmentally protected areas:** Participants expressed a clear understanding of the complex relationship between mining and local communities, recognizing both the economic benefits and the environmental costs. Many cited local examples, such as clay quarrying to highlight how mining once stimulated economic booms and job creation but later left behind deep scars on the landscape and ecosystems. Some participants also described how their regions prospered during mining operations but are now grappling with abandoned, damaged lands. There was a shared view that long-term planning and sustainable practices are essential. Participants stressed that communities must not only be informed but actively involved in decision-making. As one participant strongly emphasised: *“it is crucial to monitor environmental impacts and take corrective measures when necessary”*. Several pointed to the psychological and ecological value of ecosystems, arguing that natural areas, though not always economically profitable, deserve protection for their intrinsic worth and human well-being. One participant notably stated that *“ecosystems are CRMs”* and that policies must guarantee compensation and protection when environmental degradation occurs. Ultimately, participants called for a middle ground where economic development does not come at the expense of the environment or the health and autonomy of local populations.
- 3. Politics, policies, and public perspectives:** Participants expressed strong ethical and environmental concerns about mining in protected areas. While acknowledging the need for CRMs, many emphasised that preserving biodiversity should always come first, and that extraction in such zones should only be considered as an absolute last resort and *“only if there are no viable alternatives and if there are solid guarantees of environmental sustainability”*. They also stressed on the fact that any potential mining must be strictly regulated, transparent, and include early and meaningful involvement of local communities.

The discussion also revealed a lack of trust in the current political systems managing raw material policies. Several participants expressed concern that public voices are often left out of key decisions. As one noted, *“Often, decisions are made by experts and politicians without real dialogue with local communities”*. Others stressed that local voices, especially youth, are too often ignored *“Young people are not involved enough. There is a lack of battle against disinformation, decision-making processes are driven by very large and powerful structures that influence democracy”*. Disinformation and poor-quality information were also flagged as issues, with calls for better civic education and media literacy to support genuine democratic engagement.

There was also a strong sense that the public is not well-informed about CRMs and related policies, which was linked to a broader call for more transparent communication and participatory mechanisms that involve communities from the beginning, not only after decisions have been taken.

In summary, participants recognized the importance of securing CRMs, but emphasised that the process must be transparent, inclusive, and environmentally just, with strong opposition to mining in protected areas and a clear demand for genuine public involvement.

Therefore, the main arguments that emerged from the core discussions of the focus group can be summarized as follows:

- Participants emphasised that any future mining must be accompanied by real and tangible environmental compensation measures, including ecosystem restoration and the establishment of protected areas.
- There is a deep mistrust toward extractive industries due to the long-term environmental damage caused by previous mining activities, such as water contamination and landscape degradation.
- Rather than relying solely on resource extraction, the community advocates for investment in alternative economic sectors like sustainable tourism, organic agriculture, and technological innovation.
- Participants highlighted the need for stronger environmental education and more opportunities for youth to engage in decision-making processes related to development and sustainability.
- A recurring concern was the lack of transparency and limited community involvement in past decisions. The group called for open, inclusive, and continuous consultation processes to rebuild trust.

8.3 Implementation of the public dialogue and key findings

The public dialogue took place on the 29th of March 2025, in Baiso, at the Centro Funzionale, located on Toschi Street, 53. The event was co-organised by ALDA, with session facilitation by Futour. The Emilia Romagna Region, as a CIRAN project partner, contributed the initial informative segment, together with Generator, also a CIRAN partner.

The event brought together 11 participants from a range of sectors, with a balanced mix of 4 women and 7 men. Most participants represented public authorities (4 participants), followed by citizens not representing any stakeholder (3 participants).

The implementation of the public dialogue followed the methodology detailed in [section 3.10](#) and therefore embedded the role-play “What if..?” gaming methodology elaborated by LPRC in T3.3. Following the principles established in D3.3 (Lopes et al., 2024), the role-play game materials were developed in Italian to ensure the principle of equal opportunities to participation was ensured, and thus, all discussion participants would be able to express their opinions and contribute to the discussion on equal terms in their first language. Outputs of the discussion were then provided in English by the local facilitators (Futour) and ALDA.

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 28](#).

After an introductory part, two groups were formed (5 and 6 participants each), each of them engaged with one of the following future-oriented scenarios:

- the *Innovazione Insulare* (“Insular Innovation”) scenario.
- the *Stato Stazionario* (“Steady State”) scenario.

The composition of both groups was balanced in terms of gender and represented a diversity of profiles. Within each group, participants received a fictional character card representing a stakeholder with a specific point of view on the issue (e.g., a local farmer, environmental activist, government official, mining company representative, etc.). They were asked to role-play in a discussion, framed around a concrete “What if..?” scenario set of questions, putting forward their character’s interests and decisions in response to a fictional proposal to extract CRM in a protected area. This method allowed participants to step into different perspectives and explore the tensions and dilemmas that arise in real-world decision-making, fostering out-of-the box thinking and the discussion around future imaginaries – for more details refer to [Section 3.10](#).

During the roleplay, the groups addressed the following question:

“What would your character think or decide about the proposed CRM extraction project in this scenario?”

Each group explored the interests and values of their fictional characters, considering trade-offs between economic development and environmental protection, and reflecting on the broader social and political implications of CRM extraction with a specific focus on how that fictional future would unfold and the potential consequences for their local community and broader regional and national context.

For the first group, five different stakeholders were part of the discussion:

- Two of them were supportive of local extraction, with a rational view of progress, but provided that this were performed according to environmentally respectful parameters; they represented the local electronics store worker and the local government official characters respectively.
- Two were opposed to extraction, one strongly warning of environmental damage (the tourism operator), and one adopting a pragmatic stance, open to models that combine conservation with limited economic use (the environmental expert).
- One remained uncertain (i.e., the local farmer), conditionally supportive, favouring a controlled extraction aligned with local activities.

For the second group, six different stakeholders participated:

- One stakeholder supported local extraction if it complied with environmental standards (the electronics store worker), while another - the mining company representative - was fully in favor of extraction and territorial investment.
- The tourism operator, in contrast, was opposed, believing that a pristine environment would benefit tourism and strongly supported environmental protection. The local government official took a pragmatic and realistic stance.
- The local farmer on the hand was against the opening of new mines, while the environmental activist supported alternative extraction methods and warned about the overuse of Earth's resources.

The outcomes of the role-play discussion in Baiso are summarised in the following table.

<p>1. Sustainable CRM Supply</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote a cultural shift towards responsible consumption through education, awareness campaigns, and ethical marketing. Emphasize repairability, durability, and reuse of products. • Invest in recycling and recovery systems (e.g., RAEE, incinerator residues) to reduce dependence on new extractions. • Support European self-sufficiency by encouraging local, ethically regulated extraction, rather than relying on imports from regions with lower environmental and labor standards. • Establish international ethical regulations and traceability mechanisms for CRMs, inspired by models such as the Kimberley Process⁸ for diamonds. • Align extraction activities with actual needs, connecting mining efforts to long-term strategic planning rather than short-term market speculation.
<p>2. Extraction in Protected Areas</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply a case-by-case assessment, considering both the ecological value of the area and the strategic importance of the resource. • Clarify and differentiate the concept of protected areas, recognizing that not all hold the same level of ecological significance. • Permit extraction only when low-impact techniques (e.g., underground mining) are used, ensuring environmental restoration and compensation to local communities. • Explore dual-use models, integrating mining with territorial regeneration (e.g., transforming former quarries into green public spaces). • Guarantee multidisciplinary expertise in decision-making processes, involving ecologists, geologists, urban planners, and local residents.

⁸ <https://www.kimberleyprocess.com/>

3. Sustainable CRM Supply

- Promote a cultural shift towards responsible consumption through education, awareness campaigns, and ethical marketing. Emphasize repairability, durability, and reuse of products.
- Invest in recycling and recovery systems (e.g., RAEE, incinerator residues) to reduce dependence on new extractions.
- Support European self-sufficiency by encouraging local, ethically regulated extraction, rather than relying on imports from regions with lower environmental and labor standards.
- Establish international ethical regulations and traceability mechanisms for CRMs, inspired by models such as the Kimberley Process for diamonds⁹.
- Align extraction activities with actual needs, connecting mining efforts to long-term strategic planning rather than short-term market speculation.

4. Extraction in Protected Areas

- Apply a case-by-case assessment, considering both the ecological value of the area and the strategic importance of the resource.
- Clarify and differentiate the concept of protected areas, recognizing that not all hold the same level of ecological significance.
- Permit extraction only when low-impact techniques (e.g., underground mining) are used, ensuring environmental restoration and compensation to local communities.
- Explore dual-use models, integrating mining with territorial regeneration (e.g., transforming former quarries into green public spaces).
- Guarantee multidisciplinary expertise in decision-making processes, involving ecologists, geologists, urban planners, and residents.

After the role-play simulation, participants moved into an open reflection phase, stepping out of character to collaboratively address the following guiding questions:

1. What are the key factors for a sustainable supply of CRM?

2. Should CRM extraction be allowed in protected areas, and under what conditions?

From the discussion over the first question the following recommendations emerged:

- Invest in the recovery and reuse of existing materials.
- Promote durability, repairability, and upgradeability of consumer products.
- Foster cultural and economic change to counter obsolescence and support long-term sustainability.
- Promote a culture of sustainable resource use through education, ethical marketing, and community engagement.
- Ensure regulated and traceable extraction within Europe, avoiding reliance on lower-standard imports.
- Introduce binding ethical regulations for European operations abroad.
- Link all extraction activities to long-term, needs-based planning.

From the discussion over the second question the following recommendations emerged:

- Extraction in protected areas may be considered only if:
 - The resource is present in significant and strategic quantities.
 - The area does not represent an irreplaceable ecosystem.
 - Multidisciplinary expertise and updated impact assessments must guide all decisions.

⁹ <https://www.kimberleyprocess.com/about/what-is-kp>

- When possible, promote dual-impact models that combine economic development with environmental stewardship.
- Evaluate extraction in protected areas on a case-by-case basis, starting with less sensitive sites and using clear, shared criteria.
- Allow extraction only with low-impact techniques, combined with mandatory restoration, territorial compensation, and landscape integration plans.

Figure 23 – Picture from the public dialogue in Baiso in Italy.

Figure 24 – Picture from the public dialogue in Baiso in Italy.

8.3.1 Public dialogues' key findings

Key statements were identified by each working group and later collectively validated during the plenary session.

Statements coming from the first group were:

1. Invest in the recovery and reuse of existing materials.
2. Promote products that are more durable, repairable, and upgradable.
3. Foster cultural and economic changes that counter obsolescence and support long-term sustainability.
4. Consider extraction in protected areas only if the resource is genuinely present in significant and strategic quantities.
5. Ensure that the area does not represent an irreplaceable ecosystem.
6. Base decisions on multidisciplinary expertise, impact assessments, and integrated approaches.
7. Recognize that in some cases, it is possible to design models with dual positive impacts, combining economic development with environmental protection.

Statements coming from the second group:

1. Promote a culture of sustainable resource use through education, information, and ethical marketing at all levels of society.
2. Do not abandon extraction in Europe, but ensure it is sustainable, regulated, and traceable.
3. Include binding ethical regulations for European companies operating abroad.
4. Link extraction activities to conscious planning of future needs.
5. Evaluate, on a case-by-case basis, the possibility of extraction in protected areas, starting with those that are less sensitive, and considering more delicate areas only as a second option, using clear and shared criteria.
6. Allow extraction only with low-impact techniques, ensuring mandatory environmental restoration, territorial compensation, and landscape integration plans.

A vote was not carried out, but all the statements were considered collectively validated by consensus.

Reflecting on these statements, the participants emphasised the need to view sustainability through a global lens, recognizing that seemingly green solutions like electric cars may have hidden environmental costs. They also warned against static views of ecosystems, proposing a reassessment of protected areas based on their current ecological value to better prioritize conservation efforts.

8.4 Key takeaways

Overall, these main takeaways can be identified from the results of the activities conducted in Baiso, Italy:

1. Toward a sustainable CRM supply
 - Shift from extraction to circular economy: strong emphasis on reducing dependency on new extraction through investment in recycling, reuse, and designing products for durability, reparability, and upgradeability.

- Cultural and economic change: citizens highlighted the need to foster a culture of sustainability through education, ethical marketing, and public awareness to counter planned obsolescence.
- Strategic and ethical planning:
 - Resource extraction should be linked to long-term, needs-based planning, not short-term profit.
 - Preference for local, traceable, and ethically regulated extraction within Europe to reduce reliance on imports from countries with lower environmental and labor standards.
 - Citizens supported binding ethical rules for EU companies operating abroad.

2. Extraction in Protected Areas

- Case-by-Case evaluation: extraction may be considered only under strict conditions, such as:
 - The resource is of strategic importance.
 - The area is not an irreplaceable ecosystem.
 - Multidisciplinary expertise and impact assessments guide decisions.
- Low-Impact techniques and compensation: if allowed, extraction must use low-impact methods (e.g., underground mining) and be paired with mandatory restoration, territorial compensation, and landscape reintegration.
- Innovative and dual-use models: some citizens suggested exploring dual-purpose projects, combining extraction with territorial regeneration (e.g., transforming quarries into green spaces).
- Flexibility in protected area definitions: participants called for a reassessment of protected areas based on current ecological value, cautioning against rigid classifications.

3. Cross-cutting themes and values

- Mistrust toward extractive industries: past environmental damage and lack of community involvement have caused deep mistrust. Citizens demand greater transparency, accountability, and participation in decision-making.
- Call for participatory governance: citizens stressed the need for open, inclusive, and continuous consultations, especially at the local level.
- Holistic and global view of sustainability: participants cautioned that “green” solutions (e.g., electric vehicles) can have hidden environmental costs if upstream supply chains are not ethical or sustainable.
- Alternative development models: citizens recommended investing in sustainable alternatives like eco-tourism, organic farming, and innovation, instead of relying solely on mining.
- Youth engagement and environmental education: there is a strong demand to educate and empower younger generations, making them active stakeholders in sustainability transitions.

9. Public engagement activities in Ireland: the community of Maynooth

9.1 Overview of the local context and stakeholders involved in the activities

Two citizen engagement activities were organised in Ireland. They both took place in Maynooth University in the County of Kildare which is part of the Mid-East Region. The region surrounds the Dublin Metropolitan area and therefore serves as a commuter zone for Dublin. It is characterised by agricultural land uses in Louth, Meath and Kildare. However, Wicklow County is predominantly mountainous with extensive environmental designation. With a population of around 17,000 residents, Maynooth has seen significant growth in recent years and residents include long-time locals, university students, and newcomers.

Overall, the focus group and the public dialogue brought together a total of 18 participants. The male participation was more prominent, with 12 men and 6 women taking part in the discussions.

The graph below shows the gender composition taking part in the activities.

Figure 25 – Gender of participants in activities in the Mid-East region in Ireland.

When it comes to the kind of stakeholders, the following graph illustrates the different profiles of participants with the largest group consisting of local entrepreneurs, with approximately 5 participants, most of whom were farming representatives. The second most prominent group included students accounting for around 4 participants.

Figure 26 – Types of stakeholders in activities in the Mid-East region in Ireland.

9.2 Implementation of the focus group and key findings

The focus group in Maynooth was held on the 10th of March 2025. The focus group was held to explore and understand the diverse perspectives of local citizens on the extraction of critical raw materials (CRMs) in environmentally protected areas.

The implementation of the focus group followed the methodology detailed in chapter 2.

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 29](#).

A total of 8 participants took part in the event, with a balanced age range and a slight majority of men, 5 men and 3 women. The group was diverse and included two farming representatives and two citizens, as well as one environmental activist, a student, an academic, and a public authority representative.

9.2.1. Focus group key findings

Three main themes of discussion were highlighted during the focus group, each focusing on different aspects of the critical raw materials (CRMs) debate:

- 1. Familiarity with the concept of CRMs:** Participants demonstrated a solid understanding of CRMs and their significance in today's world. Many associated the term with recent geopolitical events, such as the war in Ukraine, and their impact on energy and fertilizer supply chains. The discussion highlighted widespread awareness of the strategic risks posed by the global concentration of CRM supply, particularly in China, and how disruptions (like the Suez Canal blockage) expose Europe's vulnerability. The idea of "*criticality*" was explored from both economic and societal perspectives. Participants emphasised that not all scarce materials are critical, only those essential to societal functioning and survival, such as those used in medical devices. The conversation extended to

consumption trends and economic growth as driving forces behind increasing CRM demand. Recycling emerged as a hopeful alternative to mining, with many promoting circular economy strategies. However, doubts were raised about the economic and technical feasibility of extracting CRMs from existing products. Planned obsolescence was criticized as a key factor fueling CRM demand, with participants pointing to products like smartphones that are designed to fail rather than be repaired. There was concern over the lack of public discourse and policy regarding CRM preservation. Participants also questioned why resource conservation efforts rarely include raw materials, noting a societal tendency toward overconsumption. The need to shift focus from endless use toward strategic resource management was strongly felt. Finally, the group stressed the political implications of CRM dependency, warning against monopolies that “*hold us to ransom*”. The dominance of China in this field was perceived as amplifying scarcity and heightening Europe’s strategic insecurity.

- 2. Mining in environmentally protected areas:** Participants expressed a high level of awareness regarding the environmental consequences of mining, unanimously recognizing it as an inherently destructive process. They highlighted its harmful effects on biodiversity, ecosystems, and landscapes, citing the use of chemicals, habitat destruction, and toxic waste production as major concerns. One participant noted, “*Mining is always contaminating... it eats up a lot of earth, destroys habitats and produces toxic waste*”. Others warned of the long-term implications for biodiversity and environmental degradation. The impact on wildlife, particularly protected species such as badgers, was a recurring theme. Farmers voiced frustration over the double standards between strict protections they must follow and the perceived leniency towards mining companies. Additionally, participants stressed the threat mining poses to areas of natural beauty and tourism, such as the Wicklow Way, emphasizing that short-term industrial activities could irreversibly damage long-term ecological and economic assets. Despite these concerns, **some participants acknowledged that mining CRMs might be justified in protected areas, if a compelling, well-evidenced societal need is demonstrated**. The discussion pointed to a willingness to consider trade-offs under certain conditions, especially if linked to national security or supply chain resilience. However, calls were made for transparency regarding where and how extracted minerals would be used, with one participant stressing the need for “*a clear supply chain*” and proven public benefit before any decisions are made. The socio-economic impact on local communities, particularly farmers, was another significant point of discussion. Participants warned that while mining may generate temporary employment, it can simultaneously undermine existing livelihoods, especially in agriculture. Concerns were raised about the sustainability of such economic models once mining operations cease. Nonetheless, others acknowledged the potential short- to medium-term benefits, including job creation and infrastructure upgrades. A specific example cited was the Tara Mines project, which led to improvements in the railway infrastructure, with long-term benefits anticipated for regional connectivity.
- 3. Politics, policies and public perspectives:** Participants noted low public awareness of mining, with concerns typically arising only when projects are proposed locally. Negative perceptions, often driven by fear rather than facts, were seen as a major barrier, particularly during the planning process. Opposition was common, with people instinctively resisting mining in their area. Despite this, many acknowledged that mining, especially for Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), is unavoidable: “*If not here, then somewhere else*”. EU targets were identified as key drivers, cascading from European to local levels, likely leading to increased enforcement over time. However, significant concerns were raised about the quality and integrity of public consultation processes. These were frequently described as “*shallow*”, “*tokenistic*”, or as formalities undertaken after decisions had already been made. A sense of disempowerment among communities was noted, with one participant stating, “*It is clear where the European Union wants to go with this. We are just being softened*”. Participants advocated for decentralized decision-making, where local authorities play a stronger role in determining mining locations. The power imbalance between well-resourced mining companies and local communities was also highlighted, alongside examples of poor industry conduct, such as exploration without landowner consent. Stronger public engagement, transparency, and early communication were

considered essential to building trust and enabling more democratic, community-led decision-making in mining policy.

Therefore, the main arguments that emerged from the core discussions of the focus group can be summarized as follows:

- Participants strongly criticized current consultation processes as shallow, tokenistic, and often symbolic, with decisions perceived to be made in advance. This led to feelings of disempowerment and mistrust among communities.
- Mining is not widely understood by the public until it poses a direct local threat. Immediate reactions are therefore often based on fear and health concerns rather than informed understanding.
- Despite opposition, many participants recognized that mining, particularly for Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), is necessary and will occur either locally or elsewhere to meet EU targets.
- Some participants acknowledged that mining CRMs might be justified in protected areas, if a compelling, well-evidenced societal need is demonstrated.
- Ireland's centralized decision-making system was seen as a barrier to meaningful local engagement. Participants advocated for stronger roles for local and regional authorities in deciding where mining takes place.
- Mining companies' financial and legal resources were perceived to overshadow the voices of local residents, reinforcing mistrust and marginalization.
- There was a strong emphasis on the importance of clear, early, and honest engagement with local communities to implement trust and informed participation in decision-making processes.

9.3 Implementation of the public dialogues and key findings

The public dialogue took place on the 30th of April 2025 between 11:00am to 1:00pm in Maynooth University. The event brought together 10 participants from diverse sectors, with a notable predominance of men - 7 men and 3 women - and a good mix of age groups. The most represented groups were farming representatives and students, each with 3 participants. This was followed by representatives from public authorities and planning bodies, as well as one academic and one citizen not representing any stakeholder. The implementation of the public dialogue followed the methodology detailed in chapter 3.

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 30](#).

The participants were divided into two groups, each consisting of five individuals. Efforts were made to ensure that each group included representatives from the relevant stakeholder groups, as well as a mix of both men and women and of age groups. They deliberated on three key questions:

1. What should the European Union prioritize to ensure a sustainable supply of CRMs?
2. What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of CRMs? Do you think any changes are needed? If so, which ones?
3. Should the extraction of CRMs be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?

Figure 27 – Picture from the public dialogue in Maynooth, Ireland.

9.3.1 Public dialogues' key findings

The main discussion points emerged from the four groups were the followings:

- Participants acknowledged the importance of developing an independent and secure supply of CRMs by diversifying sourcing countries, reducing reliance on dominant players like China, and promoting the reduction, reuse, and recycling of existing materials.
- They also emphasised the need to enhance public understanding and acceptance of mining through investment in education and transparent communication, addressing misconceptions, and ensuring that communities are fairly compensated and actively involved in decision-making processes.
- All groups highlighted the importance of strengthening geopolitical relationships and streamlining planning procedures to enable timely project implementation, while respecting community rights to voice concerns and participate in discussions.
- The groups also stressed the value of fostering strong partnerships across public, private, and community sectors, encouraging collaboration, resource sharing, and goal alignment, including leveraging technologies such as AI to improve exploration efficiency.
- There was an agreement on adopting a context-specific and regulated approach to mining in protected areas, permitting it only under strict conditions, such as operations by state-run companies accompanied by clear restoration plans and transparent oversight.
- There was also a recognition in the need to promote technological innovation and increase public awareness of successful, environmentally responsible mining practices to shift public perception and build trust in the industry's capacity to operate sustainably, even in sensitive regions.

The dialogue concluded with the deliberation phase focused on the following six statements that summarize the main outcomes of the discussions:

1. **Developing an independent and secure supply via diversification, reduction and reuse should be an EU priority**
2. **Knowledge and education are critical in facilitating public acceptance of mining projects**
3. **Streamlining the planning process, stable geopolitical relationships and substitution of materials are important for a sustainable supply**
4. **Providing for joined up thinking and partnership creating in projects with public, private and local communities is essential**
5. **Mining in protected areas should not be permitted except under strict conditions such as a state company mining and a clear implementable restoration**
6. **More efforts should be made to give successful examples of mining in protected areas**

Several key statements received strong support throughout the discussions, reflecting shared priorities and some points of divergence.

All nine participants agreed (5 strongly agree, 4 agree) that knowledge and education are critical for public acceptance of mining projects, demonstrating unanimous recognition of the importance of public awareness in mining success.

Most participants (8 agree or strongly agree, 1 neutral) supported the idea that developing an independent and secure supply through diversification, reduction, and reuse should be an EU priority, indicating broad consensus on building resilient and sustainable supply chains.

A majority (7 agree or strongly agree, 2 neutral) endorsed that streamlining the planning process, maintaining stable geopolitical relationships, and substituting materials are important for sustainable supply, though some hesitation was noted.

Opinions were split on mining in protected areas under strict conditions: only 3 participants agreed or strongly agreed, 2 were neutral, and 3 disagreed, highlighting a divisive issue that calls for enhanced environmental safeguards and further discussion.

Additionally, 4 participants remained neutral on increasing efforts to publicize successful mining in protected areas, suggesting uncertainty or low priority on this topic.

The findings reveal a strong consensus around the importance of education, supply chain independence, and efficient planning as key priorities. However, opinions were divided on ethically sensitive matters such as mining within environmentally protected zones, indicating a need for careful consideration of environmental impacts and stakeholder concerns.

9.4 Key takeaways

Overall, these main takeaways can be identified from the results of the activities conducted in Ireland:

1. **Public understanding, trust, and participation**
 - Widespread distrust in consultation processes: participants strongly criticized current public consultations as tokenistic, superficial, and occurring after decisions are already made, leading to community disempowerment.
 - Low public awareness and fear-based reactions: mining is poorly understood until it affects local communities, often triggering fear-based opposition rather than informed debate. This highlights the urgent need for public education and transparent communication.
 - Call for genuine community involvement: citizens demand early, honest, and continuous engagement, with local and regional authorities given greater decision-making power to balance influence between mining companies and communities.
2. **Toward a secure and sustainable CRMs supply**
 - Support for EU supply chain independence: there was strong consensus on the importance of diversifying supply, reducing dependency on dominant countries (especially China), and prioritizing reuse, recycling, and circular economy approaches.

- cautious optimism for technological innovation: while recycling and circularity were embraced as solutions, concerns remained about economic and technical feasibility. Planned obsolescence was heavily criticized as a driver of unsustainable demand.
- Need for strategic planning and substitution: participants endorsed linking CRM extraction to long-term needs-based planning, with material substitution and stable geopolitical relationships identified as essential to resilience.

3. Mining in protected areas: a divisive issue

- Major environmental concerns and ethical tensions: mining is viewed as inherently destructive, especially to biodiversity, landscapes, and local livelihoods. Participants were particularly wary of its impact on protected areas, tourism, and farming.
- Conditional support in exceptional cases: some participants accepted that mining in protected areas may be permissible only under strict, evidence-based conditions, such as a demonstrated societal need, state-led operations, and comprehensive restoration plans.
- Transparency and clear supply chains: participants stressed the importance of knowing where and how minerals would be used, calling for clear, traceable supply chains and guaranteed public benefit.

4. Governance, power imbalances, and equity

- Uneven power dynamics: mining companies are perceived as overpowering local voices due to greater legal and financial resources, exacerbating mistrust.
- Centralized governance as a barrier: in countries like Ireland, centralized decision-making was seen as limiting local influence. Participants advocated for decentralized, locally accountable governance in mining decisions.
- Equitable economic development: while short-term benefits like job creation were acknowledged, participants questioned the long-term sustainability of mining-based economies, advocating instead for alternative economic sectors (e.g., sustainable tourism, agriculture).

5. Education and public perception

- Education as a pillar for social acceptance: there was unanimous agreement on the role of knowledge and education in building public acceptance of mining, especially for CRMs. Clear communication can shift perceptions from fear to informed dialogue.
- Need for positive examples: participants recommended showcasing successful, environmentally responsible mining operations to improve public trust and demonstrate that sustainable mining is possible—even in sensitive areas.

10 Public engagement activities in France: the community of Lens

10.1 Overview of the local context and stakeholders involved in the activities

One citizen activity was organised in France. The focus group took place in the heart of the Nord-Pas-de-Calais mining basin at the Lens Trade Union House -Maison syndicale de Lens- with the support of the Lens-Liévin Urban Community and members of ALDA. This venue holds deep symbolic significance, representing the many struggles faced by the mining community and providing a fitting backdrop to explore the complex and sometimes conflicting issues under discussion. The Lens-Liévin area, the largest coal basin in France (spanning 120 km by 12 km), is also the second largest coal deposit in Northwest Europe after Germany’s Ruhr region. Home to over 1.2 million people, the region’s identity has been profoundly shaped by more than 250 years of mining history.

Overall, the focus group included 11 participants and 2 facilitators, ACOM France President and a representative of ALDA’s Secretariat. The male participation was more prominent with a female representation of 27.3% - 8 men and 3 women took part in the discussions.

The graph below shows the gender composition taking part in the activities.

Figure 28 – Gender of participants in activities in Lens.

ACOM France called upon public and private stakeholders from the extractive industries and the local socio-economic world as well as local elected officials.

The following graph illustrates the different profiles of participants with the largest groups consisting of 5 public authority representatives with 3 elected officials from the Lens-Liévin Urban Community, alongside 2 representatives of public bodies linked to extractive activities. The second largest groups then consisted of

local companies/enterprises with 3 “private” representatives of the extractive industry and 3 representatives of the Civil Society.

Figure 29 – Types of stakeholders involved in activities in Lens.

10.2 Implementation of the focus group and key findings

The focus group in Lens was held on Thursday, the 15th of May 2025, from 10 a.m. to 12:15 p.m., in a meeting room at the Maison Syndicale in Lens.

The main focus of the activity was to gather opinions and proposals from participants in order to inform political and regulatory guidelines related to the extraction of these resources, while preserving ecosystems and the well-being of populations.

Compared with the other events which took place in the other communities the focus group in Lens gathered people that were already very much acknowledged about the topic of CRMs. For this reason the methodology was adjusted and the questions posed to the group adapted. In particular, 3 thematic questions linked to extraction were posed:

- The first thematic focused on the issues related to the extraction of CRMs on the European territory: "What do you think would happen if Europe stopped producing its own CRMs over the next 20 years? Conversely, what would happen if Europe continued or intensified the production of these materials?"
- The second thematic addressed the necessary extraction conditions for acceptable and responsible exploitation: "In your opinion, what conditions would be necessary for mining activity in a protected area to be considered acceptable? And what should be, according to you, the requirements regarding the protection of workers' rights, the interests of communities, and public health?"
- The third thematic dealt with democracy issues related to the extraction of raw materials: "Do you think citizens are sufficiently involved in the decision-making process concerning the exploration or exploitation of CRMs mines?"

The overall report of the event is available in [Annex 31](#)

Figure 30 – Picture from the event in Lens.

Figure 31 – Picture from the event in Lens.

10.2.1 Focus group key findings

For each of the above listed themes, participants expressed different opinions that can be summarized as follows:

1. Concept of critical raw materials (CRM)

Participants engaged in a rich discussion about the concept of critical raw materials (CRMs) and their importance for Europe's future. They recognized the essential role of extracting both critical and non-critical materials within Europe, emphasizing the need to balance resource use with environmental respect. As one of the participants noted, *"It is absolutely essential that all possible materials, critical or not, that we can use in Europe, can be extracted and used, naturally with respect for the environment"*. The group acknowledged the historical challenges of mining communities while highlighting opportunities for post-extraction land use, such as recreational projects on slag heaps that "structure the landscape" and create new ecosystems.

Concerns were raised about Europe's growing dependence on foreign sources for CRMs, linking this to issues of sovereignty and loss of local expertise. One speaker warned, *"When there are no more mineral resources*

extracted in a country, you become dependent on foreign countries, you lose your know-how". The debate also touched on the geopolitical dimension of raw materials, with participants noting the strategic risks posed by supply concentration and the need for Europe to maintain production capacity to avoid dependency.

The discussion also addressed societal attitudes toward mining, recognizing deep-rooted cultural prejudices. As one representative explained, *"There is an imaginary, there is even, somewhere, a collective unconscious behind the idea of the mine, of extraction."* The role of research and exploration was highlighted as fundamental, with the reminder that *"if you don't look, you don't find,"* underscoring the tension between the desire for carbon-free energy and the environmental impacts of extraction.

2. Mining in protected environmental areas

The discussion focused on the conditions necessary for mining activities in protected areas to be acceptable, emphasizing the need to address past mining legacies before any revival. The group also acknowledged that France's current regulatory framework is demanding, but benchmarking against other countries could improve practices.

Transparency and public communication emerged as central themes. As one energy producer noted, *"Let's make the activity acceptable. Let's communicate, be transparent, and educate so that people understand their interest"*. However, the challenge of overcoming public opposition was recognized, with the reminder that *"It's easier to bark than to take up one's staff and go out and convince"*.

Concerns were raised about the quality of democratic debate, described by a cultural representative as suffering from *"Trumpification"*, making nuanced discussion difficult. Several speakers highlighted the need to include diverse voices beyond technical experts, with one local official calling for *"more naive souls in the debate"* to balance lobbying influences.

The complexity of mining topics was noted as a barrier to public understanding, with calls to shift the conversation toward sustainable resource management rather than questioning the need for resources themselves. The ecological transition and resource sobriety were also discussed, stressing that while some strategic materials are essential, others may be dispensable.

State involvement was emphasised as crucial for regulating mining activities and protecting future generations, with one official stating, *"There is no other way for the State to be, at a minimum, a shareholder in the mines and their exploitation"*. The importance of protecting domestic industries from unfair competition was also raised, advocating for European frameworks to prevent the import of poorly regulated materials.

Finally, the role of citizens in mining acceptability was seen as vital but currently underdeveloped. One foundation representative stated that *"We always intervene 'ex post' and the citizen is seen as a constraint,"* urging early, co-constructed engagement. Trust-building between the state, industry, and citizens was identified as key, though the tension between democratic processes and economic timelines was acknowledged: *"When we debate, we inevitably slow down projects. And if we slow down projects, other countries move much faster than us"*.

3. Public policy and perspectives

In this final part, participants explored whether citizens are sufficiently involved in decision-making for CRM exploration and exploitation, sparking debate over differing perspectives on needs. The discussion therefore stated the pervasive lack of citizen knowledge on technical subjects. Mistrust in both the state and private companies was identified as a major challenge. As one local official put it, *"Can you imagine how citizens can trust a private company that has the right to exploit the preservation of the general interest and the interest of our children?"*

The participants also noted that a lack of planning and debate exacerbates the issue, creating a situation where *"everyone is running after a certain number of things in a very limited timeframe"*. Consultation methods were criticized for highlighting negative externalities and fostering a climate of distrust and rejection. One participant argued, *"We've already put citizens in a state of distrust, fear, and dread, because we're presenting them with a big machine that's going to change their living conditions."*

To address these issues, participants advocated for early citizen involvement, especially in exploration phases, though the large surface areas involved add complexity. The need to build trust and create compelling narratives was emphasised, with one representative noting that elected officials often feel that "*no matter what we say, our words won't be taken into account.*" The challenge lies in overcoming deep-seated fears and fostering genuine participation.

The 5 main arguments that emerged from the core discussions of the focus group are then summarized as follows:

6. Sustainable resource management is a strategic issue requiring eco-friendly practices, state responsibility for post-mining, and fair benefit sharing.
7. Public and private actors must commit to sustainable transitions, innovation, and ethical consumption, ensuring intergenerational justice.
8. Public mistrust due to past impacts and poor knowledge calls for early citizen engagement through education and mediation.
9. Transparency, citizen education, and informed consent are key to building trust and legitimizing mining projects.
10. Strengthening scientific culture and communication from an early age is essential to foster responsibility and acknowledge mining regions' heritage.

11 Conclusions

The present document outlines the methodologies used under Task 5.3, *“Engagement and Dialogue for Knowledge Co-Creation”*, to engage citizens from six different communities and co-create knowledge. The design of the methodologies and the identification of the participating communities spanned approximately two years. The current version of the methodologies, presented in Chapters 2 and 3 of this document, is the result of a long and collaborative process involving various partners in WP5 (ALDA, GENERATOR, and LPRC), the project coordinator (INTRAW), and continuous adjustments based on early implementation results.

In total, 12 citizen engagement activities were conducted—6 focus groups and 6 public dialogues—reaching 173 participants. The activities were generally successful across all communities, although some faced challenges in participant recruitment. This was particularly evident in the case of the public dialogue in Portugal, which led to the organization of a second session held in a school setting, as well as in Ireland and in Italy, where, despite extensive dissemination efforts, the events attracted respectively 10 and 11 participants.

Overall, the methodologies proved effective in informing citizens about the project and its themes, collecting their opinions, and generating recommendations to support Task 6.2, *“Policy recommendations for permitting, model social contract and ESG to achieve a social-environmental-economic equilibrium.”*

According to reports submitted by local partners and facilitators, participants expressed satisfaction with the organization of the activities. Evaluation questionnaires were distributed to participants in two public dialogue sessions—in Italy and Ireland. The results indicated a high level of satisfaction, particularly regarding the information received during the sessions.

In the Italian public dialogue held in the village of Baiso, the role-play scenario developed in Deliverable 3.3 was tested. Based on post-event questionnaires and the final report prepared by Futour facilitators, participants were highly engaged and contributed actively with their opinions and ideas. The experience suggests that this role-play method could be replicated in other communities.

No significant resistance emerged during the activities, with the exception of the focus group in Portugal. There, some participants expressed notable scepticism toward mining projects, driven by concerns about their long-term benefits and potential negative impacts on local systems.

Regarding the outcomes of the activities, while national and community-specific differences were observed, several common themes emerged across all locations. Participants consistently expressed deep concern for environmental sustainability, strong public mistrust toward mining actors, and a broad demand for education, transparency, and meaningful public involvement. Citizens across countries favoured circular economy models over extraction and were willing to accept mining only under strict, ethical, and transparent governance frameworks.

A particularly strategic perspective emerged during the focus group in Lens, France, where participants—many of whom had a high level of expertise—emphasized the importance of long-term sustainable resource management, innovation, and ethical consumption. They also stressed the need for strong commitments from both public and private actors.

The deliberative discussions held during the public dialogues revealed consistent viewpoints regarding the future governance of critical raw materials. Citizens called for ethical, transparent, and ecologically responsible approaches; policies supporting circular economies and sustainable lifestyles; a firm prioritization of environmental protection; and broad support for education, innovation, and inclusive public engagement.

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10 Annex 1 – Stakeholder selection table

	Name of the stakeholder	Gender (Female, male, non-binary, not disclosed)	Proposed by (stakeholder from the community/participant)	Type of stakeholder (representative of public body / private sector / Environmental Advocates / Civil Society (NGOs, Associations / Vulnerable Groups / Media / Academia)	More about his/her role in the community, institution, organisation,...	Contact information	Other relevant information
1							
2							
3							
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12							
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11 Annex 2 – Invitation letter to the focus group

Subject: Invitation to the Focus group of the CIRAN Project

On behalf of the CIRAN project's consortium, I am contacting you to kindly invite you to the focus group discussion which will help to assess the opinion of the population about a critical issue for the global energy and climate transition, and help to understand the social dimensions of the transitions that need to happen in the EU at the Climate, Energy, Industrial, Economic and Social levels. The opinion of the European citizens is critical for these transitions to happen accordingly to the peoples' will and to assure that the outcomes of the transition will be publicly accountable.

To better understand the social dimensions of energy and climate transition in Europe, the project team wishes to hear opinions of people residing in environmentally protected areas without any relevant mineral resources. We are inviting you based on the recommendation of _____ from the Municipality of _____. Your opinions, insights and feedback are highly valued, and we believe your input will be instrumental in helping us achieve our goals, so we hope you will consider our invitation and you will agree to participate.

CIRAN Project in a nutshell

CIRAN is a Research & Development project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2030 program and intends to produce knowledge to support the decision-making process in the so-called "European green deal".

For that purpose, within the CIRAN project, we want to assess the opinion of the population about a critical issue for the global energy and climate transition: reducing the dependency on non-EU countries, particularly regarding obtaining CRMs, which is a fundamental pillar for Europe to defend its Democracies and the European way-of-life.

CIRAN will, therefore, conduct its research in five different regions in Europe (Portugal, France, Slovakia, Italy and Spain). In each region we intend to carry out two specific initiatives: a focus group and a public meeting that will take place from October 2023 to June 2025.

The goal of these initiatives is to understand the social dimensions of the transitions that need to happen in the EU at the Climate, Energy, Industrial, Economic and Social levels. The opinion of the European citizens is critical for these transitions to happen accordingly to the peoples' will and to assure that the outcomes of the transition will be publicly accountable.

Focus group details

Date: [Date]

Time: [Start Time] to [End Time]

Location: [Physical address or virtual platform link]

Duration: The session is expected to last approximately [duration, e.g., 2 hours].

Purpose and Agenda:

The focus group's goal is to gather insights and opinions on critical raw minerals (CRMs) and their extraction. Participants will discuss import dependency, the balance between environmental protection and socio-economic resilience, personal experiences and concerns, environmental and community impacts, permitting processes, nature conservation, and preferred communication methods for involving participants in CRM-related decisions.

We are interested in your thoughts, opinions, and experiences related to this subject. During the session, you will have the opportunity to discuss, provide feedback, and share your insights with our team. Your input will remain anonymous and will be used exclusively for CIRAN project purposes.

Confirmation and Further Information

To confirm your participation or if you have any questions, please reply to this email or contact [Contact Name] at [Contact Email] or [Contact Phone Number]. Please let us know your availability for the session.

For any further questions or concerns, please contact _____ for the organisers.

Your perspective is extremely valuable to us, and we genuinely appreciate your consideration of this invitation. We look forward to having you as part of our focus group and working together to make a difference.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Cordially,

The CIRAN Consortium

REMINDER LETTER

Subject: Reminder: CIRAN Project Focus Group - Date Approaching

Dear [Participant's Name],

We hope this message finds you well. As you confirmed your participation in the CIRAN Project's upcoming focus group, we want to provide you with a friendly reminder and some important details:

Event Details:

Date: [Date]

Time: [Start Time] to [End Time]

Location: [Physical address or virtual platform link]

Duration: Approximately [duration, e.g., 2 hours]

Purpose and Agenda:

The focus group aims to collect valuable insights and opinions on critical raw minerals (CRMs), import dependency, environmental protection, socio-economic resilience, and more. Your thoughts and experiences are crucial to our research, and your input will remain anonymous, used solely for the CIRAN project's purposes.

If you have any further questions or concerns, please don't hesitate to reach out to us by replying to this email or contacting [Contact Name] at [Contact Email] or [Contact Phone Number].

We appreciate your willingness to be part of this vital discussion. Your input will significantly contribute to the project's success in understanding the social dimensions of energy and climate transition in Europe.

We look forward to your participation and to engaging in this meaningful dialogue.

Best regards,

The CIRAN Consortium

12 Annex 3 – Participant information sheet focus group

CIRAN – Participant Information Sheet

You have been invited to participate in a focus group for a research project called CIRAN, funded by the European Commission. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what participation will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this activity. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. You can withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without it affecting your status.

Information below summarise the main aspects of the activity you are going to participate in. If you have any concerns or complains, or if you don't find this information clear or sufficient, please do not hesitate to ask the facilitator of the Focus Group.

About the CIRAN Project

CIRAN is an EU-funded project to develop, test and validate processes to arrive at systemic policy-making, balancing environmental protection and societal needs for accessing critical raw materials (CRMs). For more information about CIRAN, please consult the project website at <https://ciranproject.eu/>.

About Focus Group in [name of the community]

[date, time, location]

Aim of the activity: The goal of this focus group is to understand different perspectives of local citizens on minerals extraction in environmentally protected areas; and to understand the social dimensions of the transitions that need to happen in the EU at the Climate, Energy, Industrial, Economic and Social levels. The opinion of the European citizens is critical for these transitions to happen accordingly to the peoples' will and to assure that the outcomes of the transition will be publicly accountable.

Activity description: During the meeting that will last 2 hours, participants will be invited to discuss Europe's dependence on CRM imports, the balance between environmental protection and socio-economic resilience, personal experiences and concerns, environmental and community impacts, licensing processes, nature conservation and preferred communication methods to involve participants in decisions related to this type of projects. Data collected from this focus group will serve as a basis for preparation of a public meeting, a second activity that will follow up in a couple of months, where the set of topics covered during the aforementioned Focus Group will be discussed and evaluated by a broader group of local citizens in a Public Discussion. Following that, the data collected from both Focus Group and Public Discussion will be compared to those collected in other regions involved in the research [(in France, Slovakia, the Czech Republic and Italy)] and a final report will be created based on the comparison. All opinions that will be expressed during events will be treated anonymously, as this is a research initiative.

About data handling and confidentiality

All the personal information that we collect during the course of the activity will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified in any ensuing reports or publication. The recordings and notes taken during this activity will be used only for analysis and for illustration in reports and presentations. No other use will be made of them without your written permission, and no one outside the project will be allowed access to the original recordings and notes.

CIRAN has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe coordination and support actions programme under grant agreement No 101091483.

13 Annex 4 – Consent form focus group

CIRAN – Consent form Focus Group

Focus group in [name of the community]

[Place and date]

- | | YES | NO |
|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 1. I have read the Information Sheet for this activity and have had details of the research explained to me. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 2. My questions about CIRAN's activities have been answered to my satisfaction and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 3. I understand that I am free to withdraw from this activity at any time without giving a reason for my withdrawal or to decline to answer any particular question without any consequences to my future treatment by the researchers. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 4. I wish to participate in this CIRAN activity under the conditions set out in the Information Sheet. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 5. I agree to provide information to the researchers under the conditions of confidentiality set out in the Information Sheet. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Name of Participant: _____

Contact details (email, phone): _____

Signature: _____

Place and date: _____

Researcher's name: _____

Researcher's contact details (email; phone): _____

Researcher's signature: _____

Please keep your copy of the consent form and the information sheet together.

CIRAN has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe coordination and support actions programme under grant agreement No 101091483.

14 Annex 5 – Facilitator checklist

Before the event, the facilitator should have:

- Read the document “CIRAN Methodology of Focus Groups”, ensuring that they understand the process and the project, and can provide an explanation in case they were asked to by the respondent.
- Read and understood the consent form for participants so that they can explain the concept of anonymous and protected data collection to respondents should they require any clarification before they give their consent.

Key materials for facilitators: What should each facilitator have by the opening of the event or start of the activity? (Variations may occur among project partners)

- A name badge that allows others to identify you as a facilitator for focus group (similar branding for all CIRAN personnel on site);
- Printed versions of Facilitator's guidance of CIRAN Focus Group tailored to specific community (see paragraph 2.7 of the present guide);
- Printed Consent form for each participant;
- Printed version of Note-Taking template that will be used by the assistant facilitator to capture key points, themes, and quotes;
- List of CRMs (available in Annex 7); pictures of daily necessities that contain CRMs (available in Annex 8); rare earths elements explanation of relationships and “criticality” (available in Annex 9). All these materials are also embedded in the presentation available [here](#);
- Data projector, screen and computer;
- Downloaded film on CRMs available [here](#);
- Room setting (chairs in a circle for all participants, facilitator and assistant facilitator);
- Recording equipment to capture the discussion;
- Name Badges for participants with a number for identification and space for their first name (which they will write on their own);
- Roll-up banner with CIRAN logo (available [here](#));
- Refreshments;
- Additional materials: pads and pencils for each participant, flip chart paper, and markers for the facilitator.

15 Annex 6 – Note-taking template

Focus Group Notes

Date: _____

Location: _____

Facilitator: _____

Assistant facilitator: _____

N. of participants: _____

Contextual notes about the group of participants:

Instructions for the note-taking:

Contextual notes about the group of participants: Note descriptions and impressions about the group that might be important for the analysis. For example, How many of them were men/women? What was the age range? Did people enter the focus group late or leave early?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments: Note key points of the whole discussion on the above listed question.

Notable Quotes: Note statements of participants in their own words

Observations/Contextual notes: Note impressions or insights that describe the "feel" of the focus group or that seemed to affect the conversation. For example, non-verbal cues, including body language, physical excitement, eye contact, or other clues that indicate participants' levels of agreement, support, or interest. These notes will help other people understand aspects of the focus group that are not in the verbatim notes. Indicate in the notes if people show non-verbal agreement or dissent through nodding/head shaking/other body language.

Topic 1: Critical raw materials

Q1: How familiar are you with the concept of critical raw materials (CRMs)? Have you ever heard about them? What do you consider to be CRMs?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments	
---	--

Notable Quotes	
Observations/Contextual notes	

Topic 1: Critical raw materials

Q2: What are your thoughts on potential outcomes if Europe did refrain from producing its own Critical raw materials in the next 20 years? Conversely, what if Europe initiates production instead?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments	
Notable Quotes	
Observations/Contextual notes	

--	--

Topic 1: Critical raw materials

Q3: What are your reflections on the dilemma between the need for environmental protection and the need to ensure socio-economic resilience?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments	
Notable Quotes	
Observations/Contextual notes	

Topic 2: Mining in environmentally protected areas

Q4: What do you know about the relationship between mining and communities nearby?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments	
---	--

Notable Quotes	
Observations/Contextual notes	

Topic 3: Politics, policies and public perspective

Q5: Would you be willing to accept a mining activity in a protected area in your region if it meant that it would help with the security of supply?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments	
Notable Quotes	
Observations/Contextual notes	

--	--

Topic 3: Politics, policies and public perspective

Q6: Do you think public opinion accurately reflects challenges and positives aspects of mining of critical raw materials?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments	
Notable Quotes	
Observations/Contextual notes	

Topic 3: Politics, policies and public perspective

Q7: Are you aware of any European, national, and local policies relevant to critical raw materials?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments	
Notable Quotes	

Observations/Contextual notes	

Topic 3: Politics, policies and public perspective

Q8: Do you feel that people are included enough in decision making when it comes to deciding about exploration or mining of Critical raw materials?

Brief Summary of Key Points and Comments	
Notable Quotes	
Observations/Contextual notes	

Further notes:

16 Annex 7 – List of Critical Raw Materials

Bauxite	Coking Coal	Lithium	Phosphorus
Antimony	Feldspar	Light rare earth elements	Scandium
Arsenic	Fluorspar	Magnesium	Silicon metal
Baryte	Gallium	Manganese	Strontium
Beryllium	Germanium	Natural Graphite	Tantalum
Bismuth	Hafnium	Niobium	Titanium metal
Boron/Borate	Helium	Platinum group metals	Tungsten
Cobalt	Heavy rare earth elements	Phosphate Rock	Vanadium
		Copper	Nickel

In bold are Strategic raw materials

Source: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials_en

17 Annex 8 – Pictures of objects of everyday use that contain critical raw materials

Bateries

Music (elektronics)

Medical devices

Nuclear reactors

Satelites and spacecrafts

Laundry detergent

Blue pigment for decorations

Cookware coating

Cancer treatment

Screen equipment

Sport equipment

Solar panels

Fertilizers

Turbines

Aluminum alloys

Dental fillings and bridges

18 Annex 9 – Explanation of relationships and criticality

Rare earths elements Explanation of relationships and "criticality"

The rare metal elements are an example of critical raw materials where the "criticality" of these materials can be well demonstrated and explained. It is a raw material that is key to many modern industries in Europe and around the world and is often irreplaceable in them. At the same time, it is currently mostly produced in China, so Europe is heavily dependent on their imports. Due to the fact that this raw material is in high demand, if new deposits are not found and mining is started elsewhere, there is a risk that it will be in short supply in the near future, which will subsequently have an impact on the use and development of the technologies for which it is used.

Presenting this "one example for all" can help participants better understand why they are participating in a focus group discussion.

Use:

- Currently quite significant – they are necessary for many new and innovative technologies.
- Electrical and electronic components for smartphones, digital cameras, computer components, semiconductors, etc.
- Technology of renewable energy sources
- Military equipment
- Glass production
- Metallurgy
- Lasers
- Magnetic materials

Current country of origin:

- 95% China, 1.7% USA, 1.3% Russia, 1.2% Australia
- China is currently the largest supplier.
- The dependence of the market for this strategic raw material on Chinese production leads to the search for new deposits, such as Greenland, Australia or the seabed near the Japanese island of Minami Torishima.

Increased demand and growing fears that the world may soon face a shortage of these rare metal elements:

- Within a few years, worldwide demand for rare earth elements is expected to exceed supply by tens of tons per year (currently 135,650 tons are produced annually).

- The demand for them will increase due to the EU's dependence on these elements, as well as the fact that rare earth elements cannot be replaced by other elements and also because they have a low recycling rate.
- Concerns that unless significant new resources are developed, the world may soon face shortages of these rare metal elements.

19 Annex 10 Invitation email – public dialogue

Invitation email to CIRAN public dialogue session “Building a Sustainable Europe: The Role of Critical Raw Materials”

Dear sir/madam

Following the Focus Group meeting held, the CIRAN European project team will organise on, at the, a public discussion session on the same subject in which we would like to invite you.

We intend, in this public discussion session, to open the participation to all people interested and willing to share their opinions on the challenge that Europe faces, in the current global context, for Critical Raw Material supply and their domestic extraction versus the importance of preserving environmentally protected areas. For us your opinion is extremely important.

The public session will be divided into three parts:

Part 1 - Presentation of the CIRAN project, introducing what Critical Raw Materials are and why they are critical for Europe and its future challenges.

Part 2 – Opening the discussion on the following main issues:

- European Union priorities to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials
- Factors that could contribute to a sustainable supply of critical raw materials and changes needed
- Extraction of critical raw materials in protected areas

Part 3 – Deliberation, summary and conclusions.

This public session is one of the stages of CIRAN (<https://ciranproject.eu/>).

As a project financed by the European Union, CIRAN is one of the initiatives aimed at helping to meet the objectives of the so-called “[European Green Deal](#)” and in support of the recently published “[Critical Raw Materials Act](#)”. It aims to better understand the opinion of the people regarding the need to bring back to Europe the mining of its own mineral resources and thus reduce the current dependency on a few countries outside Europe.

The European Union considers as ‘critical’ a range of raw materials that are important for maintaining our socio-economic well-being, including our societal model of democracy, and for combating climate change.

With large areas of Europe being designated as (environmental, cultural heritage, water resources, etc.) protected areas, it is likely that such critical minerals are found beneath such areas. We are, therefore, facing the dilemma of having to secure Europe’s socio-economic future, and the same time the need to protect such areas.

While there are technical solutions to safely mine such mineral resources, it is also important to hear the opinion of people living in or near such protected areas. The opinion of the European citizens is essential for a future to be built in accordance with the will of the people and to ensure that publicly responsible and accountable decisions are taken.

For this public consultation, we ensure that, in accordance with CIRAN's ethical principles, personal information will only be collected for management and research purposes and that opinions expressed during this meeting will be kept strictly anonymous. None of the participants will be linked to any statement made in the notes taken and recordings made during this meeting or any reports or publications resulting from it. No other use will be made of the information collected without the written permission of those present and no one outside the project will have access to the original recordings and/or notes.

Public Dialogue Details

Date:

Time:

Location:

Your participation is very important to our project and we count on you.

Please, feel free to share this invitation with others.

We are available to clarify any questions you consider relevant.

Thank you very much.

For the CIRAN Consortium

20 Annex 11 Example of social media post

This is a suggested text for a social media post that could be used for CIRAN or municipal social media. Enrich it with nice emoticons!

Take part in the public dialogue “Building a Sustainable Europe: The Role of Critical Raw Materials” that the CIRAN European project team is organising on xxx, from xxx, at xxxx.

We want to find out what people think about the challenge Europe faces in the current global context in terms of Critical Raw Materials supply and their extraction while preserving protected nature areas.

This public session is one of the stages of CIRAN (<https://ciranproject.eu/>), a European project that is studying people’s opinions on the challenge to bring back to Europe the exploitation of its mineral resources and thus reduce the current dependence on countries outside the EU.

The opinion of European citizens is crucial if the future is to be built according to the will of the people and to ensure that publicly accountable decisions are made.

Get involved. Register here [add link]

21 Annex 12 Invitation poster

Here is an example of the invitation poster that can be printed and posted on public spaces:

Here is the link to the English template of the Invitation poster:

<https://www.canva.com/design/DAGEi34Mazg/-7RrQg3tbbKcGENi9MaYaQ/edit>

It is an editable canvas link, so it can be copied and translated into different languages.

22 Annex 13 Registration form – public dialogue

Registration form to the public discussion in [name of the town]

Name of the Event: CIRAN - Building a Sustainable Europe: The Role of Critical Raw Materials

Description: Here you can register your participation at the public session that the CIRAN European project team is organising on xxxxxx, at xxxxxxxxxxxxxx.

We want to find out what people think about the importance of preserving protected areas while facing the challenge of the current global context in terms of Critical Raw Materials supply and their mining in Europe. The opinion of Europe's citizens is crucial, if the future is to be built according to the will of the people and to ensure that publicly accountable decisions are made.

This public session is one of the stages of CIRAN (<https://ciranproject.eu/>), a European project, that is studying people's opinions on the need to bring back to Europe the exploitation of its mineral resources to thus reduce the current dependence on countries outside the EU.

At this [link](#), you will find a document with more information about the public session, its topics, structure etc.

Questions:

- Surname, name
- Gender (male, female, non-binary, prefer not to say)
- Affiliation of stakeholder represented (public body / private sector / Environmental Advocates / Civil Society (NGOs, Associations / Vulnerable Groups) / Media / Academia & research / other / none of the above I am a normal citizen)
- Email address
- Did you participate in the previous focus group? (yes/no)
- Do you have any previous knowledge on the topic of critical raw materials? (yes/no)
- Do you have any special needs?
 - open answer
- I agree to be sent more detailed information about this public discussion. (Your consent here is necessary if you want to attend the discussion).
 - Yes
 - No
- Would you like to receive updates about future events or initiatives related to the CIRAN project?
 - Yes
 - No

23 Annex 14 Participant information sheet public dialogue

You have been invited to participate in a public dialogue for a research project called CIRAN, funded by the European Commission. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what participation will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this activity. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a signature list. You can withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without it affecting your status.

Information below summarise the main aspects of the activity you are going to participate in. If you have any concerns or complains, or if you don't find this information clear or sufficient, please do not hesitate to ask the facilitator of the Public Dialogue.

About the CIRAN Project

CIRAN is an EU-funded project to develop, test and validate processes to arrive at systemic policy-making, balancing environmental protection and societal needs for accessing critical raw materials (CRMs). For more information about CIRAN, please consult the project website at <https://ciranproject.eu/>.

About Public Dialogue in [name of the community]

[date, time, location]

Aim of the activity: The goal of this activity is to raise awareness on the topic of critical raw materials in environmentally protected areas as well as provide an in-depth insight into citizens' views, concerns and aspirations on minerals extraction in environmentally protected areas, which will be translated into a list of key statements that will flow into the project's policy briefs.

Activity description: During the event that will last 2 hours, participants will attend an informative session on mining of critical raw materials within the EU which will explore what makes these materials "critical" and the existing narratives and future perspectives related to mining in environmentally protected areas; also insights of the focus group will be shared and commented/validated. The core activity will be represented by a group work in which stakeholders will discuss about the future of critical raw materials reflecting on priorities in order to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials as well as on changes needed. Also the conditions under which critical raw materials could be extracted in protected areas will be explored. The group work will end up with the identification of a list of key statements for each group, on which in plenary participants will try to get to a consensus within a dedicated voting session. All opinions that will be expressed during events will be treated anonymously, as this is a research initiative. The results of this activity will flow into a project deliverable.

About data handling and confidentiality

All the personal information that we collect during the course of the activity will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified in any ensuing reports or publication. The recordings and notes taken during this activity will be used only for analysis and for illustration in reports and presentations. No other use will be made of them without your written permission, and no one outside the project will be allowed access to the original recordings and notes.

CIRAN has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe coordination and support actions programme under grant agreement No 101091483.

24 Annex 15 Signature list

PUBLIC DIALOGUE “BUILDING A SUSTAINABLE EUROPE: THE ROLE OF CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS”

Place:

Date:

You are participating in a public dialogue activity of a research project called CIRAN, funded by the European Commission.

By signing this list, you agree to participate in this activity. Participation in this activity is voluntary and you can withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

Any personal information that we collect in the course of the activity will be kept strictly confidential. The recordings and notes taken during this activity will be used only for analysis, will be anonymised, and be used for illustration in reports and presentations only. No other use will be made of the information without your written permission, and no one outside the project will be allowed access to original recordings and notes.

Name and surname	Signature	Email address	If you wish to receive news about further activities of the CIRAN project, check this box.	I consent to audio recording being made during the event	I consent to pictures being taken during the event
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No

				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No
				Yes / No	Yes / No

CIRAN has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe coordination and support actions programme under grant agreement No 101091483.

25 Annex 16 Guidelines of public dialogue activity for facilitators

Introduction (10 minutes)

- *Arrival of participants*

[While welcoming participants, prepare a slide with logo of the CIRAN project on the screen. You can also hand out cards of CIRAN with QR code and contact information.]

- *Welcoming session with introduction of the teams (facilitator(s) and note taker(s))*
- *Agenda of the activity*

Show the agenda (in the Introductory presentation) of the event and explain that the purpose of Public dialogue is to raise awareness on minerals extraction in environmentally protected areas on one hand and to collect recommendations and opinions from, local citizens regarding possible future scenarios of development in this regard. And thus to engage key stakeholders – citizens from local communities into future policy making on this topic.

The event starts with a presentation of the CIRAN project and the issues it tackles in order to be able to frame the topic and allow a more knowledge-base discussion. During the second part of the event, there will be a discussion in groups, during which participants will be able to share opinions, ideas and recommendations on the topics at stake. At the end, there will be a plenary session wrapping up the main outcomes and recommendations resulting from the group discussions, trying to get to a consensus to a set of statements, that will represent the main outcome of the day and will flow into policy recommendations that the project will elaborate as a project main output.

- *Mentimeter poll*
- Launch the poll and comment the results
- *Reassure participants that CIRAN is a research project*

Explain them that CIRAN is a research project and that there isn't any new mining project in the community and close by natural park, since locations selected for CIRAN activities in general are locations closed to protected areas without any active extraction of mineral resources. This is in order to gather unbiased opinions.

- *Recording and attendance*

Being a research project it is important that participants sign the attendance list, agreeing with recording. Recording are only needed for analysis purposes they will not be shared anywhere. Also all data will be treated anonymously.

In case participants do not feel comfortable in being recorded, then note takers can listen to their comments away from the recording.

- *Checking for questions*
- Before we start with our first informative part of the event, check if anyone has any questions or concerns about the format of our event.

Introductory part (20 minutes)

- **Objectives of Informative phase:**
 - To provide evidence-based information about the topics related to the project to the participants.
 - To allow participants to think critically about the information they are hearing.
 - To give participants the opportunity to question or challenge speaker(s).
- Show the 2-minute long video that briefly introduces the topics of the project. The video is in English, but there are automatic translations in other languages
- Full presentation

Discussion/deliberation activity in groups

- **Objectives of Deliberation phase:**
 - To stimulate discussions among participants on the topics/questions proposed.
 - To confirm and comment the results of the focus group (questions posed can be integrated with the results of the focus group if considered relevant by the facilitator).

[The methodology of the debate will differ based on the number of people registered to attend the discussion. Consult specific section of the methodology to select the appropriate method.]

- **Explanation of rules for the debate**

Now, you will have the chance to discuss the topics and scenarios that have been presented to you. We would like to hear how you feel about these topics and what you recommend, considering all the information that you have heard today and considering your own personal experience.

- The group discussion will last 60 minutes.
 - Everybody is welcome to share his/her/their comments, ideas or recommendations.
 - It is important to leave space for the discussion to each participant, therefore it is suggested that each person takes the floor for maximum 2-3 minutes for each topic/question *[Moderator's responsibility is to remind them if they are speaking too long.]*
 - A second round can be foreseen if time allows.
 - In any case, there is also the possibility to share further comments by email later on.
 - The aim of the discussion is to collect comments and recommendations from participants.
 - The note taker will take note and lead the group in the identification of 3-5 statements to propose for the vote in the plenary session.
- **Establishing ground rules**

- There are no right or wrong answers; all opinions and recommendations are highly valued.
 - Everyone has the right to speak, and only one person speaks at a time.
 - Avoid side conversations with neighbours.
 - Each participant will have an opportunity to share views; no one person should dominate the discussion.
 - It is important to listen respectfully when others share their views.
 - Conversations will be recorded for analysis purposes and prepare the report of the discussion and it will be anonymised with respect to who said what (the GDPR applies).
- **Participants split in groups 6-8 people each**
- **Debate/discussion (60 minutes)**

Guiding questions shown also in slides (try to answer all questions dedicating 10-15 each). The take notes take notes on what is being discussed, noting also specific quotes.

 1. What should be the European Union's approach to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?
 4. Does anything need to change within the EU to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?
 5. Should we allow the possible extraction of critical raw materials also in protected areas? If so, under what conditions? If not, what are the main reasons?
 6. How do you see the future of the critical raw materials currently being extracted?
- Identification of 3-5 statements on which the whole group agrees that will be posed during the plenary

[Simultaneously, as the participants speak, the facilitator writes down the comments/recommendations of participants, ideally summarised in a short sentence or a few words. He is inserting everything into a hidden PowerPoint presentation which is uploaded on Google drive (or similar platform) and shared with other colleagues on site who are supporting the facilitator in taking notes. They will also include the statements on which participants agree to be eventually fine-tuned by the facilitator/note takers before the plenary session for voting].
- **Short break**

10 minute break for fine-tuning groups statements for final voting. During the break the statements will be fine-tuned by the facilitator and note takers.

Plenary session/voting phase and closure (20 minutes)

- *Objective of Decision finding phase:*
 - *To provide consensual and negotiated recommendations/statements to be embedded into CIRAN policy recommendations.*
- Welcome back after the break.
- As last step of the meeting, statements coming from the different groups will be shared with all participants and voted.
- The facilitator can either show each statement in a slide and ask people to vote by raising their hands if they strongly agree/agree/are neutral/disagree/strongly disagree. As an alternative and to make things easier and faster the statements could be included in a google form which can be shared with participants through a QR code. Based on the results from the voting, the most relevant statements will be identified.

Conclusion

- ***Thanking participants***
- *Show project's contacts and email address for contacting in case they would like to add anything*
- *Follow up*

Explain that to those that left the email address a summary of the statements/recommendations resulting from the activity will be shared as well as upcoming news and results from the project as a whole.
- *Next Steps*

Explain that the team will carefully analyse the information gathered during this discussion and compare them with results obtained from similar discussion in other European countries and create a final report.
- *Final questions from participants (if any)*
- *Final Thanks*

26 Annex 17 Mentimeter questions

Which group do you belong to?

- citizen
- representative of the municipality
- representative of a private local business
- representative of an NGO
- media
- academia
- researcher
- other

What is your gender identity?

- woman
- man
- non-binary
- I prefer not to say

Have you previously participated in any discussion or other activity related to the topic of Critical Raw Materials?

- yes
- no
- I am not sure

Do you have any interest in the topics of today's meeting?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

Do you have any knowledge in the topics of today's meeting?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

27 Annex 18 Scenarios of the role-play

Scenario 1: EUtopia (Globalisation, Innovation-driven)

In this scenario, the world is highly interconnected and global cooperation is strong. Technological innovations resulting from new research areas lead to new material demands, impacting the existing raw materials landscape. The **EU benefits from robust global supply chains**, allowing it to cope with the changing demand profiles for the key raw materials needed. International agreements and globally-harmonised institutional frameworks ensure more sustainable business practices in the extractive industries and for other stakeholders, including producers and importers of CRMs.

Governmental action in CRM market regulation is strong, fostering sustainable practices and resource security. National, regional, and local regulations are built based on international consensus. The role of organisations such as the UN and the EU is highly influential in global governance and policymaking, and these institutions are highly trusted by citizens, as there is also a general trust in local and national politics. This is highly correlated to the fact that Civil Society Organisations are active and strong, and operate through supra-national networks, collectively pushing for their shared demands on high environmental standards and sustainable mining practices.

Another element explaining why citizens' trust in government and political institutions does not deteriorate is due to moves towards more transparent and inclusive policy-making processes. CRMs hold a high priority on the political agenda, given their strategic importance for technological and economic development. The EU's trade policy is proactive, securing global supply chains and fostering international cooperation for shared knowledge, technology, and resources.

- This scenario is characterised by high innovation and a strong focus on energy transition technologies, such as renewable energy systems, electrified vehicles and industrial processes, and advanced digital infrastructure.
- There is strong global cooperation, with extensive trade agreements and a generally stable flow of CRMs from geographically diverse sets of producers in most cases.
- Due to the emphasis on environmental sustainability, coupled with a stable geopolitical landscape and trade flows of raw materials, mining in protected areas is of limited interest: focus is on innovation in recycling, circular economy practices, and global imports instead.
- Supply chains of CRMs such as lithium, cobalt, nickel, rare earth elements (REEs), copper, and graphite are under focus — as these are essential for green technologies such as batteries, wind turbines, and solar panels.

Scenario 2: Insular Innovation (De-globalisation, Innovation-driven)

Despite a trend towards de-globalisation and increased protectionism, technological innovation continues to advance rapidly. Technology is developed in-house, highly protected against other countries/blocks. The EU focuses on self-sufficiency, adapting to new materials demands driven by technological progress. However, the lack of global cooperation leads to fragmented markets and higher costs. Supply chain resilience is challenged, but the EU manages to innovate domestically to meet its critical raw material needs, allied with exploration and mining in new areas.

Governments are active in CRM market regulation, seeking self-sufficiency and support for local industries. Civil society organisations are active, advocating for local solutions and sustainability. Citizens' trust in government and political institutions is moderate, influenced by protectionist policies and local focus. CRMs hold a high priority on the political agenda due to the need for self-sufficiency and technological progress. The EU's trade policy tilts towards more protectionism, supporting local industries and reducing dependency on external sources. International cooperation is limited, focused on strategic partners and regional alliances.

- Despite de-globalisation, innovation within the EU continues to drive the development of green technologies, with a focus on self-sufficiency.
- The EU adopts a more insular approach, forming trade blocks with a limited number of trusted partners and emphasising local production.
- Due to the need for self-reliance and domestic sourcing, the EU may face pressure to exploit protected areas, though with advanced, more sustainable mining techniques.
- Through a combination of domestic mining, recycling, and limited trade agreements, the EU manages to secure its resources, though at potentially higher costs.
- Lithium, cobalt, rare earth elements (REEs), and possibly domestic-focused CRMs such as copper and aluminium would gain more attention.

Scenario 3: Steady State (Globalisation, Technology stagnation)

In this scenario, characterised by high globalisation and low technological innovation, the demand for raw materials currently considered 'critical' (CRMs) remains steady with relatively small changes over the next decade. Key materials such as copper, aluminium, and silicon, essential for established technologies including solar panels, wind turbines, and electrical infrastructure, will continue in their demand trajectories.

Global trade relationships play a crucial role in maintaining continued supply chains, with international cooperation ensuring a stable flow of CRMs from trusted global partners. Policy focus in this scenario is on maintaining and upgrading existing infrastructure, with incremental improvements in CRM usage and recycling.

These policies work together to uphold sustainability and stability in supply chains, though they do not drive significant innovation or shifts in CRM demand.

- Technological innovation slows down, resulting in a reduced pace of new green technologies. The focus shifts to maintaining existing infrastructure development and industry adaptation.
- Global trade continues, with the EU relying on stable international relations and existing supply chains to meet its needs.
- With less pressure for resource extraction due to the slowdown in technological advancement, mining in protected areas is largely not needed.
- Stable global trade allows the EU to continue securing the CRMs it needs, although at a stable but non-expanding rate.
- Aluminium, copper, and other traditional metals used in more mature applications would still be in the spotlight.

Scenario 4: Barren Fortress (De-globalisation, Technology stagnation)

In this scenario, both globalisation and technological innovation are limited. The EU faces significant challenges in securing critical raw materials due to increased protectionism. Extraction in protected areas becomes more contentious as traditional methods lead to higher environmental impacts. The focus shifts to local solutions and circular economy practices, but progress is slow, and demand pressures remain high.

Governments are active in CRM market regulation, supporting local production and self-sufficiency. Civil society organisations advocate for sustainability and local solutions. Citizens' trust in government and political institutions is moderate, influenced by protectionist policies and local focus. CRMs hold a high priority on the political agenda to ensure local self-sufficiency and resource security. The EU's trade policy aims at reducing dependency on external sources. International cooperation is limited, focused on regional and strategic partnerships.

- With both de-globalisation and technological stagnation, there is minimal development of new green technologies, and existing technologies are maintained without significant advancement.
- The world becomes more fragmented, with the EU relying on limited, possibly unstable trade relationships and is struggling with self-sufficiency.
- The EU, facing resource scarcity, might be forced to mine in protected areas, compromising environmental standards to secure basic materials, also facing societal opposition.
- Due to limited trade and insufficient domestic supply, the EU faces significant challenges in securing necessary CRMs, leading to potential resource shortages.
- Basic metals such as iron, aluminium, and possibly some copper, with reduced need for CRMs such as lithium and cobalt due to stagnation in technology-driven industries.

28 Annex 19 Character cards of the role-play

"What if...?"
Character Card

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

Tourism Operator

Background:
Owner of a small locally owned eco-tourism business that brings visitors to the protected area, with georoutes and sport activities to consciously explore the site.

Role:
Advocate for eco-tourism, with a high respect for nature over economic profit.

Viewpoint:
Opposes extraction, as it could harm the area's natural beauty and biodiversity, which is the foundation of their business. Advocates for sustainable tourism to generate income (without unnecessary capital accumulation) without harming the environment.

Personality Traits:

-
Optimistic
-
Community-Focused
-
Entrepreneurial

"What if...?"
Character Card

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

Local/regional Government Official, Office for the Environment and Sustainable Agenda

Background:
The town's third advisor to the mayor, responsible for making or influencing the final decision based on the environmental perspective.

Role:
Mediator and decision-maker, with a master's in environmental sciences from a prestigious foreign university. Part of a network of European municipalities advocating for sustainability.

Viewpoint:
Sees both sides. Wants to balance economic growth with protecting the natural heritage of the area, much more leaning towards the latter given their position in the local/regional government. Interested in a sustainable solution that benefits the community in the long term.

Personality Traits:

-
Diplomatic
-
Pragmatic
-
Good Communicator

**“What if...?”
Character Card**

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

Environmental Scientist

Background:

A leading environmental scientist specializing in ecosystems and biodiversity.

Role:

Advocate for environmental preservation in the local/regional branch of a European/international NGO.

Personality Traits:

Logical

Detail-oriented

Passionate about conservation

Viewpoint:

Opposes extraction in or near the protected area, citing the potential damage to local wildlife and ecosystems. Believes the area is too valuable to sacrifice for short-term economic gain.

**“What if...?”
Character Card**

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

Local Farmer

Background:

A local farmer whose land borders the protected area.

Role:

Concerned local landowner.

Personality Traits:

Practical

Community-Focused

Independent

Viewpoint:

Undecided but leaning against mineral extraction. Worried about the potential disruption to the land, water sources, and the local climate, but also sees economic potential if done responsibly, although would need to see how this affects the land they're working with and their current economic activity - which is, nevertheless, decreasing and generating less income than ever.

**“What if...?”
Character Card**

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

**Local/regional Government Official,
Office for Markets, Economy, and
Technological Growth**

Background:

The town's second advisor to the mayor, responsible for making or influencing the final decision based on the economic and technological perspective.

Role:

Profit driven, tech geek, convinced decision-maker, member of a network of international municipalities advocating for technological progress, AI, and smart cities and tech hubs.

Viewpoint:

Driven by technological development. Observes what is happening in other countries, mainly outside of Europe, and wants the same for the municipality/region. Prioritises economic growth over the natural protection of the area, arguing that this will not bring economic benefits to the population and the local businesses in the long-term. Yet, technology labs and innovation hubs will.

Personality Traits:

Proactive

Intellectual

Convincing
Communicator

**“What if...?”
Character Card**

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

Mining Company CEO

Background:

CEO of a mining company looking to expand operations.

Role:

Advocate for
resource extraction.

Personality Traits:

Confident

Results-Driven

Persuasive

Viewpoint:

Supports extraction, arguing that it will boost the economy, create jobs, and provide critical resources for the community. Believes modern technology can minimize environmental impact.

**“What if...?”
Character Card**

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

**Multinational Electronic Store
Worker**

Background:

Works in the local store of a multinational electronic brand, whose products mainly depend on resource extraction and global supply chains.

Role:

Worker in the resource extraction industry.

Personality Traits:

Practical

Flexible and Empathic

Pragmatic

Viewpoint:

Supports extraction in general, as it provides the resources currently needed for the technologies and products that have become “basic” for our daily lives, which people from all ages and groups come to buy at the store they work at, searching for the cheapest offer. Defends that extraction provides job opportunities, however, thinks that most products are currently produced outside of Europe, and we should be concerned about the long-term effects on the environment and the local/regional economy.

**“What if...?”
Character Card**

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

**Local Community
Association Leader**

Background:

Leader of the local community association who believes in the societal spiritual and ancestral connection to the land.

Role:

Advocate for the importance of spiritual and cultural heritage connected to nature.

Personality Traits:

Wise

Connected to nature

Cultural traditions

Calm and Patient

Viewpoint:

Opposes current extraction methods and philosophy (for profit). Believes the land is sacred and must be preserved for future generations. To them, nature and humans are at the same level and, hence, destructive extractive techniques are exploiting nature and disrespectful to society. Defends ancestral knowledge and practices prior to “green-washing” and technologically driven techniques.

29 Annex 20 “What-if” questions

“What if...?”
Scenario 1- EUtopia

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

What if international cooperation eliminates the need for domestic mining?

Decision:
Can international cooperation eliminate the need for domestic mining?

This case study will explore the implications of a world where strong global partnerships and circular economy practices make domestic mining in protected areas unnecessary.

This may be brought to any of the communities, regardless of their connection with environmentally protected areas and environmental views, given that the scenario would not require mining there.

Nevertheless, participants will have to consider the potential benefits and challenges of this paradigm, including whether it is realistic enough, and acknowledging consequent factors, such as the continued dependency on international supply chains, and the environmental impact in other external producing countries.

They may also compare their current local economic development with the potential prospects for growth or negative impacts brought by this scenario.

“What if...?”
Scenario 3- Steady state

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

What if we maintained the Status Quo for the next 10+ years?

Decision:
Can the Status Quo be maintained for the next +10 years in our community / region?

Under this scenario, communities will examine the potential outcomes for their region (and, consequently, for Europe) of continued reliance on existing and somehow insecure CRM supply chains.

Participants will be invited to consider whether limited technological innovation is a realistic framework for the future of their community.

Discussions will address the risks of stagnation versus the benefits of predictable stability, with minimal pressure for new mining initiatives.

“What if...?”
Scenario 2 – Insular innovation

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

What if domestic mining became the only option for resource security?

Decision:

Can domestic mining become the only option for resource security in our community/region, or in Europe?

This case study addresses a future where protectionist policies necessitate mining in environmentally protected areas.

Community members will debate the trade-offs between resource independence and environmental preservation, focusing on the societal and ecological impacts of domestic resource extraction.

Local communities' responses to this case study may vary based on factors such as, but not limited to, their perspectives on the importance of environmental protection versus market development and economic growth, the technological and innovation potential of the region (which implies more use of CRMs), and the social and historical dynamics in relation to mining and other employment opportunities connected to the industry.

“What if...?”
Scenario 4 – Barren fortress

CIRAN

Funded by
the European Union

What if resource scarcity necessitated mining in protected areas despite fragmented governance?

Decision:

Can we allow mining in protected areas in our community / region justified by resource scarcity?

This case study explores a challenging future where protectionism, resource scarcity, and weak governance facilitate mining activities into protected areas with inadequate mitigation measures. Participants will evaluate how these pressures might affect environmental standards, community resilience, and regional autonomy.

They will carefully consider whether this is a realistic scenario for them based on the level of environmental protection and occurrences of environmentally protected areas in their region, including surrounding areas.

They will contrast these aspects against their perspectives on present and future needs of CRMs and mining/extraction activities in their area.

30 Annex 21 Focus group report - Idanha-a-Nova (Portugal)

FOCUS GROUP REPORT Idanha-a-Nova – Portugal

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This focus group report is based on findings from the focus group held on the 21st of November 2023 conducted in Idanha-a-Nova for the CIRAN project aimed to understand local perspectives on mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas and to prepare for a larger public meeting to be held in a later date.

Participants generally lacked awareness and understanding of critical raw materials (CRMs). There was a notable concern for environmental protection, overshadowing potential economic benefits of mineral extraction. Scepticism towards mining projects was prevalent, driven by doubts about their long-term benefits and impacts on local ecosystems.

The general scepticism was coupled with a desire for more transparent and inclusive decision-making processes. Key concerns include enhancing public awareness of CRMs, and the need for transparent, inclusive decision-making and better communication strategies to inform and engage the public on issues related to CRMs and environmental sustainability.

These findings were probably influenced by the fact that a significant number of participants had a direct or indirect connection to environmental professions or activities, which indicates that future focus group should find better strategies to ensure a more diverse participant selection and a better communication.

INTRODUCTION

The focus group, held in Idanha-a-Nova on the 21st of November 2023, was conducted in the context of CIRAN, an EU-funded project to develop, test and validate processes to arrive at systemic policy-

making, balancing environmental protection and societal needs for accessing critical raw materials (CRMs).

There were 2 main objectives for the focus group:

The first objective was to get insights about the different opinions and perspectives of Idanha-a-Nova's citizens regarding mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas, in particular Critical Raw Materials.

The second objective was to mobilize the findings to better help prepare a larger public meeting that is going to be held in Idanha-a-Nova in a few months. The key findings and collected insights from the focus group will constitute the basis for the preparation of the discussion that will be held on that meeting.

After both focus group and public meeting insights are collected and analysed, they will be compared to those collected in other regions involved in the broader research: France, Slovakia, Czechia and Italy.

Since this is the first focus group, special attention was given to identify limitations and recommendations, with the objective of giving subsequent focus groups in other countries useful information to better collect and analyse data.

In this report, the recommendations are highlighted throughout the document and summarized in the Recommendations and Limitations Summary section of this report.

LOCAL CONTEXT

The Focus Group was held in the Idanha-a-Nova village, a Portuguese village in the district of Castelo Branco, part of the province of Beira Baixa, with around 2,100 inhabitants. It is the seat of the Municipality of the same name (Idanha-a- Nova). The municipality is bordered to the north by the municipality of Penamacor, to the east and south by Spain, to the west by Castelo Branco and to the northwest by Fundão. The municipality of Idanha-a-Nova is as close to Lisbon as it is to Porto or Madrid.

Idanha-a-Nova was created in 1219 to distinguish it from the old Idanha (hereinafter Idanha-a-Velha), 18 kilometres away. It is a land of flavours, history, and culture, Idanha is rich in natural heritage, creativity, and innovation.

The population of the municipality in 2011 was 9,716 in an area of 1416.34 km², making it one of the largest and least densely populated municipalities in Portugal as well as the first Portuguese municipality by population ageing. The municipality is subdivided into 13 parishes.

The economy of the municipality of Idanha-a-Nova revolves around agriculture, animal husbandry, forestry, tourism, local government, and agribusiness. The municipality has excelled in sustainable farming, crop seeds, cheesemaking and horticulture, as well as a centre of olive and almond production and processing.

In the municipality, the historic village of Monsanto is a world tourist reference due to the ingenious way in which the houses are built taking advantage of the granite rocks (it was one of the footage locations of the last season episodes' of Game of Thrones).

The Montes-Ilha de Monsanto are part of the UNESCO Naturtejo Geopark, whose birthplace is the Ichneological Park of Penha Garcia, which preserves countless traces of what life was like here 480 million years ago, when these quartzite ridges were an immense sea where trilobites reigned, in an impressive world of aquatic biodiversity.

The biodiversity of the Tagus International Natural Park, which is part of UNESCO's Portuguese Network of Biosphere Reserves, currently constitutes a sanctuary where it is common to see eagles, vultures or griffon vultures.

The UNESCO stamp is also inscribed on the lands of Idanha due to the fact that it is a Creative City of Music, an artistic expression that accompanies people's daily lives and which, with the Adufe as its greatest symbol, functions as a pillar of economic and social development.

METHODOLOGY

This section explains the approach used to collect the insights from the Focus Group Participants.

Design of the Focus Group

The organization of the focus group in Idanha-a-Nova began with a formal contact with the mayor - most important representative of the territorial authority - to explain the project, the purpose of the initiative and to ask for support in identifying the participants from the region to invite.

After several interactions with the mayor and his office, CIRAN's representative was given a list of suggested participants from the region whose profile was suitable for attending the focus group. The mayor's office also offered to provide a room in the Municipal Library.

Once the date and time for the focus group was agreed with the mayor, an invitation was drawn up and sent by email which, in addition to details about the meeting, gave a brief description of the project and the purpose of the meeting. You can find a copy of this email in appendix.

After sending the email/invitation, each person was contacted by telephone by CIRAN's representative to confirm their attendance.

We found out afterwards that the invitation reached more people than those on the list provided by the City Council, which allowed the meeting to be attended by people with more diverse profiles.

Of all the people reached, 8 people showed up for focus group.

Location and Timing

The Focus Group was held in the Idanha-a-Nova village, a Portuguese village in the district of Castelo Branco, part of the province of Beira Baixa, which is the seat of the Municipality of the same name.

The meeting was held from around 14h30 until 16h30 in an interior room of the Municipal Library of Idanha-a-Nova. The room was about 40 square meters, resembling a classroom, modified by having 8 chairs in a circle, all facing the two people with the role of facilitators: one as the main facilitator (Rodrigo Castro) and the other serving the purpose of assistant facilitator and note taker (Luís Rosendo).

The room was well lit from the sunlight coming from a large window and the audio conditions were good which did not set any difficulties in the overall communications.

Data analysis

To begin the data analysis process, the two facilitators debriefed after the focus group to discuss session content, what was learned, what was surprising, and to process any emotions evoked throughout. Next, both facilitators conducted a preliminary analysis to get a general understanding of the data and reflect on its meaning.

To support a more detailed analysis, the audio of the meeting was fully recorded by a device placed near the participants and then automatically transcribed to a document which was analysed and corrected based on the recollection of both facilitators. This data was further complemented by some notes that were taken during the focus group by the assistant facilitator.

For each of the different phases of the focus group – Introduction, Core Discussion and Conclusion – the conversations were analysed, and the key findings were collected

PARTICIPANTS PROFILE

In order to better profile the participants without breaching any confidentiality requirements, below there is a list with relevant keyword and relevant notes:

Person 1 – female; showed up uninvited; defined herself as an environmental advocate.

Person 2 – female; defined herself as a “planet caregiver”; had already participated in demonstrations against mining activities.

Person 3 – female; she is a local entrepreneur in the area of Cultural Tourism.

Person 4 – female; University Teacher; has a small business with organic certification.

Person 5 – female; History teacher in a local school.

Person 6 – male; works at a non-profit association dedicated to innovation in sustainable food production.

Person 7 – female; works at an Environmental Non-Governmental Organization.

Person 8 – male; geologist; works at a local geopark.

The majority of the participants had direct connections to matters of sustainability and environmental protection through their personal and professional activities. More than a third of participants admitted to being environmental advocates, 1 of them at a professional level.

KEY FINDINGS

There were relevant findings across all of the phases of the focus group discussion. The key findings are the following:

PHASE 1 - INTRODUCTION

The first phase of the focus group lasted about 30 minutes. It served the purpose of welcoming the participants, introducing the team, explaining the purpose and format of the focus group and technical aspects about the research and data collection.

Furthermore, a brief context of CIRAN was given and some time was spent assuring that there were no active or planned projects for the extraction of mineral resources in Idanha-a-Nova.

To the assurance given, the facilitators were faced with lot of apparent scepticism demonstrated by most of the participants non-verbal stances (shaking of heads, grinning, roll of the eyes). Additionally, 3 participants expressed their doubts and mistrust openly as demonstrated by the following quote:

“It may be true that there is no plan for now, but we will never know what will happen in the future.”

After further explanation and assurances that there are no mineral assets to explore in Idanha-a-Nova, there was no apparent change in the mood of the group as expressed by the following quote:

“We never know what new type of minerals they will find useful, even if they are not useful now.”

Afterwards, a moment was given for the participants to review and sign the consent forms. In this instance one of the participants stated that she was not comfortable answering the second question of the form “My questions about CIRAN’s activities have been answered to my satisfaction and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point”, stating that she didn’t want to say YES at that time not knowing if further questions she may have, in course of the meeting, would be answered satisfactorily. She added:

“I’m not feeling comfortable answering this question at this time because I don’t know how the rest of the meeting will go.”

Most of the group expressed agreement with this concern so the facilitators decided to postpone the answer to that specific question in the consent form until the end of the focus group.

Finally, the main facilitator asked the group to individually introduce themselves briefly by sharing the first name, and if comfortable, adding some information about why each one agreed to join the focus group. All the participants were open and straightforward about sharing personal information. All of them chose to present themselves using first and family name and insisting to put both names in the card in front of them. In regard to the motivation for attending the meeting the answers fell in the following categories:

- 3 participants openly stated that they were there to have an active role against any mining project that may be planned for Idanha-a-Nova, as demonstrated by the quote:

“I’m here to be informed and give my contribution against any mining initiative for Idanha-a-Nova.”

- 5 participants stated that their main motivation was mainly to be aware and informed, but 3 of them directly expressed that they were against mining activities, as clearly exemplified by the following quote:

“I also do not want mining here [...], but I also want to be informed to maybe allow me to have a different opinion.”

PHASE 2 – CORE DISCUSSION

The second phase of the focus group lasted about 90 minutes and was composed of several questions organised by 3 main topics.

Topic 1 – Concept of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs)

Q1 – How familiar are you with the concept of CRMs?

When asked to demonstrate, by show of hands, if anyone on the group was familiar with the concept of CRM, none of the participants raised their hands. This indicates that there was a low familiarity about the concept among the group. It is important to note that one group member is a geologist, and even him was not comfortable raising his hand.

This meant that any further questions within this topic regarding CRMs, namely their geographical origins and importance, would have less value for data collection unless a detailed explanation was given. Faced with this situation the assistant facilitator gave a generic explanation about CRMs but didn’t have enough details or technical knowledge to clarify the concept fully and convincingly. At that point the facilitators understood that the participants needed real examples and even asked for a list of the minerals. One of the participants tried to search for a list on her cell phone, stating:

“It would have been useful that you had the exact list of minerals. Without that it’s difficult to understand exactly what we are talking about.”

After the explanation was given, 3 of the participants, were particularly focused on contesting the word “Critical” in Critical Raw Materials. They were contesting who considered those minerals “critical”, and to what or whom they may be critical to. Using one of the participants own words:

“They are not certainly critical for the Environment. Once coal was considered a critical mineral but since then it is being discontinued due to its impacts.”

There was no push-back from any other group members about this criticism.

Asked about the origins of CRMs and about the fact that they may be imported generally from a single country, most of the group stood silent. After a while, one of the group participants answered “China” and everybody acknowledged and agreed with the answer. Having settled on China as a focus point of the discussion, the country was strongly associated to two concepts that several participants referred to, and that are important to note: (1) rare earth elements and (2) unsustainable mining. To illustrate this connection, two different participants stated the following:

“I can only remember rare earth minerals, and most of them are in China.” “Mining in China is deplorable, with child labour. It’s not sustainable at all!”

The group seemed to agree with these concepts.

When asked where Europe could find these minerals if China refused to export them, the only answer given by one of the participants was “South America”, but he was not able to give any additional or relevant details.

Q2 – Do you think Europe could avoid using these minerals? What do we need these materials for?

When questioned about the need for using CRMs, the group agreed as a whole that there should be alternatives to the importing or mining of the minerals. In that matter the group split into two separate factions regarding the operationalization of the alternatives.

Three of the participants, focused their discussion mainly on the idea that the economic system needs to start a degrowth process to avoid further need for mining, and that everyone needs to start changing their behaviour in terms of consumption, as stated by some of the following remarks:

“Maybe we will have to rethink our economy, and this does not need to be growth, growth, growth, until we meet a breaking point. We are already at a breaking point.”

“There is the need to find alternatives, of different models for our economic system, to allow us to not need these minerals at all.”

“In truth, the economic system needs to be debated because we are all dependent on it.”

“I would rather live without a cell phone. There is no other option than to change our life or our behaviour.”

The remaining five participants highlighted alternatives within the current economic model, trying to make growth compatible with environmental concerns namely by: investing in technology, reusing and recycling, to avoid further needs in terms of CRMs. The following statements highlight the beforementioned points of view:

“There has to be economic growth, but it doesn’t need to be that way (unsustainable)”

“We can try and develop technology that allows me to use solar energy to power my cell phone without the use of minerals.”

“We need to have the will to invest in technological solutions and also recycling.”

“In Spain they are developing batteries made with waste products like cigarette butts.”

Q3 – What is your reflection on the dilemma between the need for environmental protection and the need to ensure socio-economic resilience?

Pertaining to the discussion on the dilemma between the need for environmental protection and the need to ensure socio-economic resilience, the discussion returned to the same arguments described above. The first group sees environmental protection as paramount as the other group proposes that it is possible to keep a balance between both, as a participant summed up by saying:

“Both (environmental protection and socio-economic resilience) are part of the same package. I don’t see any of them as the bad guy, you understand? We can have sustainable economic growth.”

Topic 2 – Mining in Environmental Protected Areas

Q4 – What do you know about the relationship between mining and the communities nearby?

When the group was asked to share experiences and give examples about mining activities, there were no answers. This indicated that, although the group had strong opinions regarding mining activities, there were no top of mind examples.

Following up with a question regarding the negative impacts of mining vs the positive impacts on the local communities, the group, once again, was divided between the two factions described earlier: the same 3 participants refused to see any upsides or positive impacts of mining activities, as the remaining 5 participants had a more integrative vision.

The main arguments of the first group were that mining operations are usually owned by private corporations that do not care about the impacts on the environment or the communities. One of these 3 participants, that lives in Sesimbra – where a quarry is located in a protected mountain range - said this:

“The quarries are all privately held, [...], I am from Sesimbra and the quarry there doesn’t bring any positive impacts. I can only see mountain disappearing and can’t see any benefits for me or my family”.

And added:

“If the mountain is gone, the tourism is gone. I’m an architect and I would gladly work without stone if that meant the closing of the quarry.”

This particular argument was contested by one of the participants from the second group who replied:

“It didn’t benefit you because your family didn’t work there. Jobs were created. There are positive social economic impacts.”

The second group, although trying to find positive impacts ended up agreeing that more often than not, the negative aspects outweigh the positive. This quote is an example of this:

“We have to look at the past, and the repercussions of mining have been more negative than positive.”

It is important to state that this discussion between the two groups was centred around one or two real examples, that only came up mid conversation.

Topic 3 – Politics, policies and public perspectives

Q5 – Do you think public opinion accurately reflects challenges and positive aspects of mining of CRMs?

Confronted by the issue regarding the public opinion about CRMs, the group mainly stated that most public opinion is on the side of environmental protection and against mineral extraction. One of the participants stated:

“The public in general is on the side of environmental protection.”

Everyone in the group agreed with this statement.

There were no further comments about how the public opinion accurately reflects the challenges or positive aspects of mining. The interpretation of the facilitators is that this question might be too abstract or difficult to answer since it contains two different interdependent questions on itself: first the group has to think about what the public opinion is, and then try to think more specifically of its implications in terms of challenges and impacts.

Q6 – Are you aware of any European, national or local policies relevant to CRMs?

No one in the group knew any policies at any level. No relevant comments followed up the question.

Q7 – Do you think European, national and local policies take sufficiently under account the needs of communities?

Since the group demonstrated that it does not know any policies, the follow up question regarding specificities of those policies only did not allow us to collect

informed opinions, only guess work. This diminishes the relevance of the insights collected.

The group had strong opinions regarding how communities should be involved in the process of deciding about exploration or mining of CRMs. Two people expressed, in a very articulated way, their points of view and their approach. Involving a local community should be done by several steps: start by accessing the degree of knowledge of the locals (usually low), then educating them on the relevant information about the topics at stake, and finally explaining the project in order to evaluate their opinion. This approach is illustrated by these quotes:

“The basic step is to understand the degree of knowledge the local population has, that in my opinion is near zero. I have a master’s in geology and even for me some topics are hard to understand. The people must be informed and only then the project has to be explained.”

“If you are going to listen to the locals when they don’t have enough information, that’s pointless.”

On another note, the same participants also referred to the fact that it is not enough to hear people, but it is essential to build mechanisms by which their opinions have real impact and implications in the final decisions. The following quotes express this sentiment:

“They should listen to the local population but that is not enough. The people’s opinion has to be somehow a binding opinion, or else it does not serve any purpose.”

“There is no use in pretending that the people are being listened to, when afterwards things are done anyway, even against their will.”

“The legislation should force companies to listen to local communities.”

Finally, a general sense of mistrust was felt in the group regarding the involvement of public agencies and private companies in the evaluation of environmentally sensitive projects like mining. One of the participants said it clearly:

“Environmental impact assessments are being thrown in the gutter, because the governmental agencies are not independent and are being paid by companies.”

PHASE 3 - CONCLUSION

The third phase of the focus group lasted about 15 minutes. The facilitators thanked the participants and explained the next steps, also asking if there were any final questions. No relevant findings were collected at this stage.

Finally, when asked what the most important point or key message from the discussions was, the participants did not have anything new to add, taking this moments to emphasise what was already said along the discussion and adding personal comments not relevant for the insight collection.

Additional notes about de discussion

Throughout the focus group, the discussion was generally calm and collaborative. There were no noticeable friction points between participants or any hostility towards the facilitators.

Two of the participants were notoriously quieter than the others, siding generally with the majorities' point of view and often refusing to add any more points to the discussion when the main facilitator asked them to.

There were two participants, sometimes three, with very strong views regarding environmental protection, expressed sometimes in a very forceful way. These participants presented themselves early on as environmental activists. The way that their opinions were voiced may have prevented the other participants from giving their opinions more freely. This might happen because of social desirability, as no one wants to be perceived as a person that does not care for the environment.

APPENDIX – Invitation Email

Dear Madam, Sir

On November 20th, at 2.30 pm, at the municipal library or at the cultural forum, in Idanha-a-Nova, a Focus Group meeting will take place, for which we would like to have your presence.

This Focus Group is one of the stages of the European project CIRAN, whose acronym results from Critical Raw materials extraction in environmentally protected areas (HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-03, Streamlining cross- sectoral policy framework throughout the extractive life-cycle in environmentally protected areas - CSA).

The objective of this Focus Group is to gather insights and opinions on Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) and their extraction. Therefore, during the meeting, participants will be invited to discuss Europe's dependence on CRM imports, the balance between environmental protection and socio-economic resilience, personal experiences and concerns, environmental and community impacts, licensing processes, nature conservation and preferred communication methods to involve participants in decisions related to this type of projects.

As a project financed by the European Union, CIRAN is part of the objectives set out in the so-called “European green deal” and the recent “Raw Materials Act” and aims to assess the opinion of the population regarding the need to bring back to Europe the exploration of its mineral resources and thus reduce the current dependence on non-EU countries, particularly with regard to obtaining critical raw materials, which is a pillar element for Europe to defend its democracies and the European social model.

Although CIRAN is oriented towards mineral resources, the project team considered as a structuring criterion, studying the opinion of people living in protected areas without mineral resources, so that we could obtain unbiased opinions, without the specter of possible mining projects in the region.

Therefore, and as one of the regions identified for this study was the Tagus International Natural Park (along with 4 other regions in France, Slovakia, the Czech Republic and Italy), we intend to carry out two initiatives in Idanha-a- Nova:

- Carrying out a Focus Group with key people from the region and, later,
- A public meeting, where the set of topics covered during the aforementioned Focus Group will be discussed and evaluated (opinions will be treated anonymously, as this is research work).

The opinion of European citizens is essential for these transitions to happen according to the will of the people and to ensure that the results of the transition will be publicly accountable.

Focus Group Details:

Date: November 20, 2023

Time: from 2:30 pm to 4:30 pm

Location: Municipal library or Cultural Forum, in Idanha-a-Nova

Your participation is very important (please confirm in response to this email).

We therefore count on your presence and are available to clarify any questions you consider relevant.

Thank you very much. Compliments,

The CIRAN Consortium

31 Annex 22 Public dialogue report - Idanha-a-Nova (Portugal)

PUBLIC DISCUSSION REPORT ***Idanha-a-Nova - Portugal***

Updated with key findings from the second public session, conducted on November 2024, at the
Management School of Idanha

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The public dialogue held in Idanha-a-Nova on May 14, 2024, followed a previous focus group in November 2023, providing further insights into the opinions of Idanha-a-Nova's citizens regarding mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas.

The event preparation involved coordination with the city council, invitations to interested individuals, announcements on social media, and local flyer distribution. Despite these efforts, only eight participants attended. The discussion was held in a well-equipped auditorium in Idanha-a-Nova, facilitated by Rodrigo Castro and Luís Rosendo, with Abigail Vistas as the note taker. The session was recorded, transcribed, and analysed, with key findings extracted from different phases of the discussion.

Of the eight participants, five were citizens and one represented an NGO. Gender distribution included three women and four men. Six participants expressed prior interest in the topics, though only two had previous involvement in CRM-related activities. This diverse group showed strong interest but limited prior engagement in the subject matter.

The discussion and voting phases revealed significant insights. Participants emphasised the importance of technological innovations and alternative energy sources, expressing confidence in the potential of scientific research to reduce reliance on CRMs. Some advocated for a shift in societal values and lifestyles to minimize the need for CRMs, emphasizing recycling and reduced consumption. There was a strong consensus on the need to prioritize environmental protection, with a fatalistic view of the current trajectory without significant changes. Participants exhibited deep distrust towards European politicians and corporate lobbies, questioning the transparency and motivations behind CRM-related policies. Additionally, there was unanimous opposition to mining in protected areas, highlighting the contradiction of allowing industrial activities in regions designated for conservation.

The voting phase, using a Likert scale, further illustrated the participants' views. There were mixed perceptions on finding technological alternatives to CRMs, but strong agreement on the benefits of environmentally friendly models like the circular economy. There was general resistance to the notion that reducing CRMs would harm the economy and significant distrust in the classification of CRMs influenced by economic lobbies. Many participants refused to respond to questions perceived as leading or manipulative, reflecting a deep-seated mistrust.

Based on the findings, several recommendations were made:

Enhanced information dissemination is crucial, providing balanced and credible data on mining practices, economic impacts, and policy transparency to address knowledge gaps and misconceptions. Ensuring diverse group compositions in discussions can balance the influence of environmental activists. Effective engagement strategies, such as hosting multiple sessions in low-density areas and offering financial compensation, can boost attendance and engagement.

On the 13th November 2024, a second public discussion was held at Idanha's School of Management, involving 40 students and teachers. Unlike previous sessions, this event did not feature representatives from environmental NGOs, creating a different dynamic. Participants expressed a pragmatic perspective, particularly when deliberating on potential CRM mining projects in an environmentally protected area. The consensus emerged that mining was conditionally acceptable only if it served a "greater good" rather than increasing consumption. This nuanced stance highlights the need for purposeful framing of CRM extraction discussions.

INTRODUCTION

The two public dialogues held in Idanha-a-Nova on the 14th of May 2024 and on the 13th November 2024, were conducted in the context of CIRAN, an EU-funded project to develop, test and validate processes to arrive at systemic policymaking, balancing environmental protection and societal needs for accessing critical raw materials (CRMs).

The two public dialogues were the follow-up to the focus group held in November 2023, aimed at getting insights about the opinions and perspectives of Idanha-a-Nova's citizens regarding mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas, in particular CRMs. This past focus group allowed not only to collect useful insights but also to lay down several recommendations for future focus groups in different countries (France, Slovakia, Czechia and Italy). The recommendations were also considered for the subsequent public discussion that is the object of this report.

In order to address one of the main recommendations from the focus group, the public dialogues were structured to include an informative phase aiming to provide clear evidence-based information about the topics related to the project to the participants. This allowed the participants to better understand the underlying concepts of the discussion, to critically evaluate the information and to feel more at ease to question and challenge speakers and other participants.

In this report, similarly to the previous focus group report, special attention was given to the identification of the key takeaways and respective recommendations in order to help inform the preparation of similar discussions in other countries.

METHODOLOGY

This section explains the approach used to collect the insights from the public discussion's participants.

Preparation of the Public Discussions

To prepare for the first public session, CIRAN's representative began by requesting a meeting with the city council to define and finalize the date and location for the public discussion. After this initial meeting, there

was an exchange of emails with the city council in order to formalize the agreed-upon details. This email communication ensured that the date, time and location of the public discussion were clearly established and confirmed.

Next, the CIRAN's representative focused on reaching out to individuals who had previously shown interest in similar events by sending email invitations to contacts who had earlier received invitations to the previous focus group.

To further divulge the event, it was announced on the city council's official Facebook page. This platform provided a direct channel to reach residents and interested parties within the community, ensuring that the information was widely accessible. In addition to this, the event was promoted on a variety of regional Facebook pages, broadening the approach to increase the event's visibility and attract a wider audience from neighbouring areas.

Finally, several hours before the public discussion, printed flyers were handed out to the local population in the vicinity of the event and a small explanation was given in order to try to persuade the people to participate. More than one flyer was given to each person to allow further sharing among the population. Approximately 30 flyers were delivered on the day of the event.

As a result of all these efforts, 8 people showed up for the public discussion.

For the second public session, the CIRAN's representative managed directly with the Schools Director Cabinet, first by inviting the school to participate in this initiative, identifying the courses and classes that matched best with CIRAN's topics, and, then, defining a date for the event. With this set, the CIRAN's representative shared the invite with the cabinet for them to send to the students.

Location and Timing

The Public Discussions were held in the same village as the previous focus group. Idanha-a-Nova is a Portuguese village in the district of Castelo Branco, part of the province of Beira Baixa, with around 2,100 inhabitants. It is the seat of the Municipality of the same name, the fourth largest municipality in Portugal with an area of 1,416.34 km², but with only 8,340 inhabitants, subdivided into 13 parishes. The municipality is bordered to the north by the municipality of Penamacor, to the east and south by Spain, to the west by Castelo Branco and to the northwest by Fundão.

The first meeting was held between 18h00 and 20h00 in the auditorium of the Cultural Forum of Idanha (Fórum Cultural de Idanha-a-Nova). After recent transformations, the old three-press olive mill now holds a comfortable and well-equipped auditorium with a capacity for 200 people, alongside two permanent exhibitions: one dedicated to Sacred Art and another to Pastoral Art, which was a perfect environment for a public discussion.

The participants were seated near the front of the auditorium facing the two people with the role of facilitators: one as the main facilitator (Rodrigo Castro) and the other serving the purpose of assistant facilitator (Luís Rosendo). Additionally, there was a note taker (Abigail Vistas). The facilitators and note taker

used the projection screen and the stage to speak to the participants, but also got nearer to the participants, off the stage, when needed.

The room was well lit from artificial lights and the audio conditions were very good which did not set any difficulties in the overall communications. It is important to note that it was one of the hottest days in Portugal that far in the year, but the inside temperature was adequate.

The second public discussion instead, happened at the School's auditorium, started at 3 pm and lasted for about 2 hours. The session was secured by the main facilitator (Rodrigo Castro), with the assistance of Generator's Luís Rosendo.

Pictures of the first session, on May, 2024:

Pictures of the second session, on November, 2024:

Data analysis

After the conclusion of the public discussions, both facilitators and the note taker, debriefed about the participants' involvement and content of the discussion. This debrief also considered the individual profiles of the participants and how it shaped the discussion and the data collected.

To ensure that all of the significant data was collected, the audio of the meetings was fully recorded by a device placed near participants and then automatically transcribed to a document which was analysed and corrected based on the recollection of both facilitators and note taker.

The data from the recording was then complemented by the notes that were taken by the note taker during all of the stages of the discussion.

For each of the different phases of the public discussions – Introduction, Informative phase, Deliberation phase, Voting phase and Conclusion – the conversations were analysed and the key findings were collected.

PARTICIPANTS PROFILE

In order to better profile the participants without breaching any confidentiality requirements, a short questionnaire was delivered to the participants at the end of the session. Seven out of the eight participants filled the questionnaire, as requested, and the information gathered was as follows:

Affiliation:

Options: Citizen; Representative of the Municipality; Representative of a local company; Representative of an NGO; Journalist; Affiliated with a University;

Results: Out of 7 participants, 5 were citizens and 1 was a representative of an NGO, 1 did not specified

Gender:

Options: Male; Female; Other; Rather not answer

Results: Out of 7 participants there were 3 female and 4 male

Interest in the topics of the discussion (previous to the discussion)

Options: Yes; No; Not sure

Results: Out of 7 participants, 6 already had interest for the topics, while 1 participant did not

Participation in previous public discussions or activities related to CRMs

Options: Yes; No; Not sure

Results: Out of 7 participants 2 had previous discussions/activities related to CRMs, while 5 participants did not

These results show that the group of participants was diverse, with varying affiliations. The majority, 5 out of 7 participants, identified as citizens, while 1 participant was a representative of an NGO. In terms of gender distribution, 3 self-identified as female and 4 as male. Prior to the discussion, there was a strong interest in the topics of the discussion, with 6 out of 7 participants expressing that interest. Despite the interest, only 2 participants had previous involvement in public discussions or activities related to Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), while 5 participants had not engaged in such activities before.

In summary the group was diverse, largely with a previous interest in the topics of the discussion but with limited involvement in prior activities/discussions regarding those same topics.

In the second public session, the participants were a homogen group from the school, with three teachers and the rest students (40 students) from different classes. Since the participation was not subject to any prior registration, as in the first session, and due to the mentioned homogeneity of the group, we didn't profile them.

KEY FINDINGS

The approach to the public discussions was structured based on a multi-phase approach: the process began with the introduction phase, where participants were welcomed, and the purpose of the discussion was explained. The facilitators ensured transparency by informing attendees that there are no active or planned mining projects in their communities. Participants were also asked to confirm their attendance and consent to recording, ensuring that all contributions were captured accurately for later analysis.

Following the introduction, there was an informative phase, where evidence-based information was presented to the participants to help them think critically about the topics. This phase began with a short video introducing the importance of CRMs in everyday technology and their critical role in the EU's green transition. Following the video, a detailed presentation covered various topics, including the definition and usage of CRMs, their economic importance, and the challenges associated with their supply and demand. The presentation explored potential future scenarios and strategic options for the EU with the goal to equip participants with a comprehensive understanding of the complex issues surrounding CRM extraction, especially in protected areas, enabling them to engage in informed and meaningful discussions.

The deliberation phase then allowed participants to discuss their views and recommendations in a semi-structured debate, based on the different scenarios presented in the presentation. Based on the ongoing comments and recommendations, a set of 10 questions were designed in real time in order to clarify the issues and points of view that emerged.

After a short break, the questions and methodology (Likert Scale) were presented to the participants and the voting phase began for all of the 10 questions.

In the conclusion, participants were thanked, and the next steps were outlined. An email ciran@intraw.eu was made available to ensure that additional comments or recommendations that might have emerged in the following hours/days could be sent to CIRAN ensuring a comprehensive collection of data.

In the context of these different phases, there were relevant findings, mainly in the deliberation phase and voting phase. The key findings are the following:

DELIBERATION PHASE

In the deliberation phase, the participants were invited to freely discuss their views and recommendations considering the different scenarios shown at the end of the presentation.

Five main topics/issues emerged during the first public discussion with relevant findings. These topics and respective findings are detailed below:

1. Technology and innovation are the alternatives

Early in the discussion, the majority of participants expressed a strong belief in the need for technological and innovation-based alternatives to reduce dependence on mining and critical raw materials. This perspective was evident throughout the session as participants emphasised the importance of exploring diverse energy sources and advanced materials.

One participant highlighted the potential of hydrogen energy as a viable alternative, asking:

“Why not invest in other types of energies, for example hydrogen, to avoid environmental impacts?”

This sentiment was echoed by others who pointed out the ongoing transition in material science, with one remarking:

“We are already transitioning from lithium to other types of materials.”

This comment underscored the group's awareness of the evolving landscape of energy storage technologies.

The discussion further expanded to include other innovative energy solutions, as stated by one of the participants:

“There are other materials that can store energy!”

The conversation also touched on global practices, with a participant noting:

“In China, they invest in wind energy and nuclear.”

This comparison prompted a broader debate on the merits and challenges of different energy strategies worldwide.

Underlying the entire discussion was a strong belief in the power of scientific research and innovation. As one participant succinctly put it:

“We need to trust science to find another way to capture energy.”

This statement captured the group's stance on the importance of exploring scientific methods to develop sustainable and efficient energy solutions.

Overall, the discussion was characterized by an agreement on the necessity of diversifying energy sources and reducing reliance on traditional mining practices, emphasising the role of technology and innovation as the main alternatives.

2. Changing society and the way we live is the alternative

The discussion then focused on another type of alternative, based on the need to change our lifestyle and way of life to reduce the need for mining and the reliance on critical raw materials. This point of view was mainly led by 2 of the participants that identified themselves as environmental activists. It was not clear, at this stage, if the participants predominantly believed that a fundamental shift in societal values and behaviours is desirable or essential to achieving a sustainable future.

One of the central points was the reevaluation of what constitutes quality of life. The first participants suggested:

“We have to think about what quality of life really means.”

This idea revolved around the need to change our lifestyle and way of life as an alternative to mining and the reliance on critical raw materials. The 2 participants strongly believed that a fundamental shift in societal values and behaviours is essential to achieving a sustainable future.

This argument was further elaborated by the other participant who said:

“Everyone thinks that quality of life is having a lot of stuff.”

And, then added:

“The Europeans’ idea of quality of life is shifting quickly!”

This was intended to highlight a growing trend towards minimalism and sustainability in certain regions of Europe. The conversation then turned towards practical steps individuals and communities could take to reduce their environmental impact.

Recycling emerged as a crucial element in this new way of life, has one participant emphasised:

“Recycling materials is also very important!”

Additionally to the necessity of reusing resources to minimize waste, the discussion also touched on the broader implications of current consumption patterns, especially concerning technological waste. One of the participants asked:

“And what are we going to do with batteries when they are used? What about the carbon footprint of that?”

This was meant to bring attention to the long-term environmental consequences of modern conveniences.

The 2 participants leading the discussion, were presenting a societal view that rejects materialism, as stated by:

“We have to rethink materialism!”

It was not clear if this desire for a cultural shift in order to reduce dependence on mining and critical raw materials was consensual, but it was presented in a loud and forceful manner.

3. The environment should be the most important thing to consider

As the discussion progressed, it became obvious that the previous discussion points were anchored on the idea of the paramount importance of the Environment, above any other issues. The discussion, in that regard, was dominated by the 2 passionate participants stated earlier that presented a fatalistic view of the future. These two voices significantly influenced the majority of the group, leading to a consensus on the urgent need for transformative changes to protect the planet.

One of the leading participants set the tone by stressing the necessity of a global perspective, urging the group to consider the broader implications of their actions on the entire planet, not just a certain region:

“We have to think globally. We have to think about the planet and not only about Europe!”

This global outlook resonated with the participants. Building on this, the second leading participant expressed a critical view of the current trajectory. “We need some sort of transformation.

The path we are in will not take us anywhere!”

This was meant to highlight the urgency of adopting a new direction to avoid catastrophic outcomes. This sentiment was echoed by another participant who stated:

“It makes no sense to invest in a strategy that is obviously leading uu nowhere.”

The group collectively acknowledged the inadequacy of current strategies and the pressing need for a paradigm shift.

The conversation then turned to the specific issue of mining, with significant scepticism about its sustainability, as one of the participants expressed:

“The mining industry has not evolved sufficiently in order to give me confidence to go forward with these types of projects. They are dooming our environment.”

This critique of the mining industry's environmental impact seemed to be supported by the majority of the group, reflecting a concern for the planet's future.

Throughout the discussion, the fatalistic outlook of the two leading participants shaped the group's perspective. They emphasised that without significant and immediate changes, the future looks bleak. The majority of the group was influenced by this viewpoint.

4. There is a lot of distrust regarding the European actors/politicians

In the discussion, at some point, it became very clear that there was a deep-seated distrust towards European actors and politicians, particularly concerning mining operations and critical raw materials. The participants collectively expressed scepticism about the motivations and actions of those in power, highlighting the need for greater transparency and independence from corporate interests.

One participant kicked off the discussion by questioning the reliance on certain energy sources and materials: “Why doesn’t Europe invest in other energies and materials not to be dependent on lobbies?”

Concerns were voiced regarding the influence of powerful interest groups on energy policies. This set the stage for a broader conversation about the perceived manipulation of public opinion, as another participant remarked:

“We are being led to a certain type of thinking... like there are no alternatives!”

This expressed that the narrative around energy and materials often seems constrained by a lack of visible options. This sentiment was echoed by another member of the group who stated:

“We are being pushed to the reasoning that there are no alternatives.”

In fact, participants felt that public discourse was being steered in a way that limits their perception of viable alternatives.

The discussion then took a turn towards the impact of digital control on public opinion and policymaking. A participant said:

“We are being controlled digitally!”

This highlighted concerns about the ways digital platforms and technologies might be used to influence and monitor citizens. This distrust extended to the legislative process as well, as stated by another participant:

“Laws are changing every time. People make the laws based on their own interests. Corporate interests obviously!”

This represented a belief that legislation is frequently swayed by corporate agendas rather than the public good.

A consensus emerged around the idea that Europe should strive for greater independence from corporate and lobbyist influence, as concluded by a participant:

“If Europe wants to be in the vanguard, we should not be dependent on lobbies and corporations.”

This part of the discussion revealed a pervasive distrust towards European politicians and actors involved in mining and critical raw materials. The participants emphasised the need for investment in alternative energies and materials, greater transparency in law-making, and independence from corporate and lobbyist influences to ensure that public interests are prioritized.

5. Mining in protected areas is unacceptable

Finally, amidst the several discussion points, it became clear that there was a unanimous consensus that mining in protected areas is entirely unacceptable. Participants expressed strong opposition to any form of mining activities in regions designated for protection, underscoring the importance of preserving these areas for environmental and ecological reasons.

One participant set the tone by stating emphatically:

“Mining in protected areas is completely unacceptable!”

This declaration resonated deeply with the group, establishing a clear and firm stance on the issue.

Building on this sentiment, another participant questioned the very premise of allowing such activities in protected regions:

“If they are called PROTECTED areas, what’s the deal? If they are protected, there should not be any mining there. It’s obvious!”

The discussion further differentiated between existing mining operations and new proposals, particularly in protected zones. One participant clarified his position:

“One thing is the mining that already exists in certain regions. Another completely different is new mining, especially in protected areas. That should not happen. Never.”

This distinction underscored the group's belief that while existing mining operations might be a complex issue, initiating new projects in protected areas is categorically unacceptable.

Throughout the discussion, participants consistently reiterated the need to honour the protected status of these areas. They emphasised that protected regions are designated as such for crucial reasons, including the preservation of biodiversity, natural habitats, and ecological balance. Allowing mining in these areas, they argued, would undermine these essential conservation efforts.

In summary, there seemed to be a unanimous agreement that mining in protected areas is unacceptable under any circumstances. Participants strongly advocated for the preservation of these regions, emphasizing the contradiction and ecological risks associated with allowing industrial activities in protected zones. Their collective stance highlighted a firm commitment to environmental protection and the integrity of designated conservation areas.

VOTING PHASE

During the discussion, the main facilitator took note of the main issues that arose from the participants interventions and designed 10 questions in order to assess the importance and the accession of those issues amongst all participants.

In order to conduct a vote, the main facilitator presented participants with 10 questions, using a Likert scale ranging from "1 - Strongly Disagree" to "5 - Strongly Agree.". The use of this type of scale is a reliable and effective tool for measuring attitudes, opinions, and perceptions, which were the main focus of this public discussion. Using this scale allowed participants to express varying degrees of agreement or disagreement, providing a nuanced view of their positions on complex issues. Furthermore, it was a way to quantify subjective data, making it easier to analyse and interpret the results as a whole. This scale also helps capture more subtle differences in opinion (rather than a simple yes/no answer) and helps minimize social desirability bias where respondents might feel pressured to choose more socially acceptable answers.

The results and dataset containing the responses for the eight participants can be found in appendix to this report. The results are explained in detail as follows:

The first question asked if it is credible to find alternatives through technologies to replace critical raw materials. Responses varied, with one participant strongly disagreeing, one disagreeing, three remaining neutral, and three strongly agreeing. This indicates a mixed perception regarding the feasibility of replacing CRMs with alternatives using technology in the short term.

The second question explored whether the circular economy and a paradigm shift in economic structures could significantly reduce the use of CRMs. All participants agreed, with three agreeing and five strongly agreeing, showing a strong consensus that such shifts could positively impact raw material usage.

For the third question, participants were asked if reducing the use of critical raw materials would have a negative impact on the economy. Here, four participants strongly disagreed, three disagreed, and one remained neutral. This suggests a general resistance regarding the link between the reduction of the use of CRMs and the slowing economic growth.

In the fourth question, participants considered whether most critical raw materials are deemed critical due to the pressure of lobbies and economic groups. Responses showed that one participant disagreed, one was neutral, three agreed, and three strongly agreed, indicating a general distrust regarding the classification and importance of CRMs attributed to the pressure of lobbies.

The fifth question addressed participants' willingness to reduce their economic income to support the reduction of critical raw materials. After one outspoken participant protested against the question, all remaining participants refused to respond, indicating that the mistrust about the question easily spread to everyone. The outspoken participant stated that the question was "rigged" in order to get a certain type of response. The exact words were:

"This is a dangerous question. We know exactly where you are going with it, so I'm not answering!"

The mistrust carried over to the next question regarding the difference of stance between mining in general and mining in protected areas. All participants again refused to respond. More than one participant expressed mistrust and reluctance saying:

"This is a trick question! It's not as simple as that. I won't answer that type of questions"

"I'm not comfortable answering that because it will sound that I am supporting mining in general, which I refuse to do!"

The seventh question inquired if it is possible to find a balance between responsible mining and environmental protection. Four participants strongly disagreed, and four disagreed, demonstrating a prevalent scepticism about achieving such a balance.

For the eighth question, which stated that mining almost always involves highly destructive activities to the environment, three participants remained neutral, three strongly agreed, and one refused to respond. This indicates a recognition among some participants of the environmental destructiveness of mining in general, while others are either neutral or unwilling to commit to an opinion.

In the ninth question, participants were asked if they would prefer importing CRMs or exploring them in Europe, if no alternatives were available. Although one participant remained neutral, the other seven exhibited the same mistrust and reluctance to answer a question. In this case, they refused to consider the

hypothetical, as they interpreted the question again as “rigged” in order to get a certain response. Participants told us:

“I won’t accept the premise of the question. There are alternatives and I refuse to answer a question that negates that.”

“Again, a trick question! I understand exactly what you are trying to do. But I will not fall into that trap!”

The final question explored support for underground mining if it could be done without significant environmental impacts. Six participants strongly disagreed, and two remained neutral, suggesting a predominant doubt or disbelief in the feasibility of environmentally benign underground mining.

In summary, the questions confirmed what transpired in the discussion phase regarding an overall reluctance to endorse mining, even with potential environmental safeguards. There is a complex and often mistrustful stance among participants towards CRMs and mining in general, and also towards the questions asked. While there is consensus on the potential benefits of a circular economy and technological alternatives, participants exhibit significant scepticism regarding the reduction of CRMs impacting economic growth and the possibility of environmentally responsible mining. Some responses revealed distrust towards the motives behind the questions, with participants sometimes interpreting them as leading or “rigged” to elicit specific answers.

Part of the prevailing sense of scepticism and distrust among participants regarding the discourse on CRMs was encouraged by one or two individual participants that have identified themselves as environmental activists, one of them being part of an environmental NGO. This led to defensive or non-cooperative responses in some cases as participants were wary of questions perceived as manipulative or oversimplified.

Insights from the November 2024 Public Session

The second session in Idanha-a-Nova brought a fresh perspective due to its distinct participants profiles. The absence of environmental NGOs allowed attendees to voice their personal and independent viewpoints.

Notable themes and conclusions from this session include:

- **Conditional Acceptance of Mining in Protected Areas:** Participants emphasised that any mining project in Idanha, a protected region, must align with a significant societal purpose. When faced with the question of approving a CRM mine, attendees unanimously opposed projects aimed at meeting excess consumption but cautiously supported those justified by collective benefits, such as renewable energy or critical infrastructure.
- **Pragmatism Over Idealism:** While earlier sessions highlighted fatalistic and activist-driven opposition to mining, this group displayed a more pragmatic approach. They sought a balanced perspective, recognizing the tension between ecological conservation and societal needs.
- **Reinforcing Regional Identity:** Participants strongly identified with their region's status as a protected area and viewed it as both a privilege and a responsibility. Discussions reflected a commitment to stewardship while remaining open to meaningful, transformative projects.

CONCLUSION

The final phase of the discussion lasted about 10 minutes served to thank the participants, explain the final steps, asking if there were any more comments or questions and giving an email that could be used to send further comments at a later date.

There were no relevant final comments, and no emails were received after the event so there were no more relevant findings collected.

The November session underscored a pragmatic shift in public sentiment regarding CRM extraction in protected areas. This change is significant for policymakers, indicating that clear communication of a project's purpose could determine its acceptability. Engaging younger audiences and academics also proved effective, offering a template for future discussions aimed at blending innovation, ecological integrity, and societal advancement.

Additional notes about de discussion

Throughout the discussion, the debate was generally calm and collaborative. There were no noticeable friction points between participants or any hostility towards the facilitators.

As stated earlier, there were 2 participants with very strong views regarding environmental protection issues and deep mistrust regarding policy makers and lobbies. These views were often expressed in a forceful way leading to a notable influence on the other participants and may have skewed the discussion at certain moments.

This fact is an exact repetition of what took place in the focus group and should be subject to a careful analysis in the context of further data collecting events.

KEY TAKEAWAYS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the key findings in both the deliberation and voting phases of the two public discussions, it's possible to sum up **3 main takeaways** of the public discussion:

1. Lack of knowledge and misinformation: The discussion highlighted a significant gap in understanding about mining in general and specially CRMs, with many participants displaying poor knowledge and misconceptions. Even with the initial video and presentation, there was a lack of clarity because of the complexity of the issue. In particular, there was significant confusion regarding the differentiation between various types of mining practices and materials.

2. Distrust in mining and related entities: There was a pervasive distrust towards mining activities, extending to the operations, policy makers, corporations, and lobbies in Portugal and the EU. This scepticism is rooted in concerns over the motivations and practices of these entities. Furthermore, this distrust also extended to the public discussion context, with participants raising doubts about the motivation of CIRAN, its constituent organizations, and even the public discussion process – not answering some of the questions in the voting phase is a good example of this distrust.

3. Susceptibility to activist influence: People are highly influenced by activists, who are very active, persuasive, and often advocate for environmental concerns above everything else. This influence is amplified by the aforementioned public's limited understanding of CRMs and distrust of mining-related entities. Activists' arguments, which often contrast corporate greed with environmental protection (“greed vs green”), find a receptive audience due to these preexisting attitudes and gaps in knowledge.

Based in these takeaways, there are **several recommendations** for future focus groups and public discussions regarding the topics of mining and CRMs:

1 – Introducing additional information about mining and CRMs

Although the initial video and presentation were useful to increase the knowledge of the participants, some gaps in the information/data could be addressed more specifically and in a balanced way:

- a) To help nuance the view that “all mining is bad” some examples of good mining practices could be presented in tandem with bad practices. This could help limit some of the preconceptions and prejudices that exist amongst the population;
- b) More credible data should be introduced about the impact of reducing the use of CRMs, mainly economic data like unemployment, economic growth and other concrete impacts;
- c) Information about transparency and policy good practices could also be presented to counteract the preconceptions about corporate and lobby influence on policy making regarding mining and CRMs.

2 – Balancing the extremes – environmental activists vs pragmatists

We have found, in both the focus group and the public discussions, that there is a very strong presence and influence of environmental activists in these events, with significant influence on the overall participant's opinions.

Measures could be taken to limit this influence, in particular:

- a) Ensuring that there is a diverse group composition for data collecting events, especially regarding individuals with strong opinions on both sides of the environmental protection and pragmatic economic protection. The presence of environmental activists could be balanced by the presence of individuals with strong pragmatic views and concerns regarding the impacts of environmental driven decision-making on the economy;
- b) Conducting individual interviews after the group sessions in order to get people's opinions unadulterated by the influence of peer pressure. This data should be then confronted with the results of the group discussions to assess if there is a significant gap in people's opinions depending on the format.

In addition, the Idanha School of Management session demonstrated the value of engaging broader audiences, such as students and educators, to capture diverse viewpoints. This group balanced idealistic concerns with practical considerations, suggesting that discussions free from overt activism might yield more actionable insights. Future events could consider selectively engaging such neutral yet informed stakeholders to complement the input from more polarized groups.

3 – Ensuring effective group events for data collection

To ensure effective public discussions or focus groups on topics like mining and critical raw materials (CRMs), which are both complex and of niche interest, it is crucial to carefully consider several aspects in order not to have poorly attended sessions and limited data collection:

- a) Choosing towns with low population density and ineffective reach of the municipalities drastically reduces the possibility of having a strong turn out on public sessions and focus groups. If there are no alternatives, hosting multiple sessions in the same region to capture more diverse perspectives could be implemented;
- b) In order to boost attendance and engagement in the public sessions and focus groups, some form of financial compensation could be offered to participants. This compensation should be fair and transparent and follow best practices. This approach could make participation more appealing and attract a more diverse group of attendees.

processes to arrive at systemic policymaking, balancing environmental protection and societal needs for accessing critical raw materials (CRMs).

The two public dialogues were the follow-up to the focus group held in November 2023, aimed at getting insights about the opinions and perspectives of Idanha-a-Nova's citizens regarding mineral extraction in environmentally protected areas, in particular CRMs. This past focus group allowed not only to collect useful insights but also to lay down several recommendations for future focus groups in different countries (France,

Slovakia, Czechia and Italy). The recommendations were also considered for the subsequent public discussion that is the object of this report.

In order to address one of the main recommendations from the focus group, the public dialogues were structured to include an informative phase aiming to provide clear evidence-based information about the topics related to the project to the participants. This allowed the participants to better understand the underlying concepts of the discussion, to critically evaluate the information and to feel more at ease to question and challenge speakers and other participants.

In this report, similarly to the previous focus group report, special attention was given to the identification of the key takeaways and respective recommendations in order to help inform the preparation of similar discussions in other countries.

CIRAN

FOCUS GROUP REPORT
Rimavská Sobota – Slovakia

Author: Centrum komunitného organizovania

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the results of a focus group discussion conducted in Rimavská Sobota, Slovakia, on December 11, 2024. The focus group was part of the CIRAN project, which examines sustainable extraction of critical raw materials in protected areas.

The discussion explored public attitudes toward resource extraction, balancing environmental protection with socio-economic needs, and the role of government policies. A key finding was the strong concern about misinformation in Slovakia, as well as distrust toward government decision-making related to environmental policies. Participants emphasised the need for public debates on sustainability and the importance of valuing natural ecosystems. The discussion was both exploratory and solution-oriented, generating recommendations for policy and public engagement.

INTRODUCTION

The focus group representing Slovakia took place on 11th December 2024 in Rimavská Sobota. The main reasons for choosing this town were its socio-economic context and ongoing discussions about environmental policies, particularly concerning resource extraction and waste storage. Rimavská Sobota is one of the economically most disadvantaged regions in Slovakia, with high unemployment and limited industrial development, making it a relevant location for exploring public attitudes toward critical raw materials and sustainable resource management.

The focus group was organised by Centrum komunitného organizovania (CKO) in collaboration with Rimavská kaviareň (RK), CKO as a well-established non-governmental organizations active in community engagement, public participation, and environmental advocacy in the city of Banská Bystrica (having active community called Green Banská Bystrica) and RK as a nonformal but very active community player in the region. These organizations have played a crucial role in fostering discussions on sustainability, social justice, and governance in central Slovakia, making them ideal partners for the CIRAN project.

Rimavská Sobota has historically been a center of industrial activity, particularly in mining and agriculture, and discussions about the region's economic future remain highly relevant. In recent years, proposals related to potential radioactive waste storage and the broader discourse on environmental regulations have heightened public concern about the local impact of resource extraction.

The focus group was conducted within the framework of Work Package 5 of the CIRAN project – *The Path Towards Sustainable Sourcing of Critical Raw Materials in the EU: An Integrated Approach to Extraction in Protected Areas*. WP5 focuses on "Inclusion and Knowledge Co-Creation" through discussions with citizen groups in selected European municipalities. The session aimed to engage local residents in deliberations about governance models, public participation, and strategies for balancing environmental protection with economic resilience.

The key objective of this focus group was to understand the perspectives of local citizens on the extraction of critical raw materials and to assess their views on mining activities, environmental policies, and socio-economic challenges in their region.

LOCAL CONTEXT

Regional Overview

Rimavská Sobota is a district town located in the Banskobystrický region of southern Slovakia. It lies in the Rimava River valley, within the larger Gemer-Malohont historical region. The area has a long history of industrial and agricultural activity, with mining, metalworking, and forestry playing key roles in its economic development. However, in recent decades, the region has faced economic decline, high unemployment rates, and depopulation, making it one of the most economically disadvantaged areas in Slovakia.

The town and its surrounding region have become the subject of environmental and economic debates, particularly concerning resource extraction and waste management. Discussions on the potential storage of radioactive waste, as well as broader issues related to mining governance and environmental protection, have made Rimavská Sobota a relevant location for public engagement on sustainability and critical raw materials.

Rimavská Sobota serves as an important administrative and economic hub for the surrounding rural communities. While it does not include protected landscape areas, the region has significant agricultural land and forested areas, which are vital for biodiversity and local livelihoods. Governance and regional development initiatives have been a focus of local organizations, such as Centrum komunitného organizovania and Rimavská kaviareň, which actively participate in public discussions on sustainability and environmental policies.

Given its socio-economic challenges and its role in ongoing national and EU-level debates on sustainable resource management, Rimavská Sobota was chosen as the Slovak case study location for the CIRAN project. The town provides a crucial perspective on the intersection of environmental protection, economic resilience, and citizen participation in decision-making processes.

The area has high unemployment, limited industrial development, and lower educational attainment compared to national averages. The region has faced historical economic challenges and continues to struggle with depopulation.

A key concern in the region is political and social polarization. The current government has been criticized for its anti-environmental policies, further fueling distrust among citizens regarding environmental decision-making.

Conservation and Culture

The Rimavská Sobota region has been shaped by human activity for centuries, particularly through agriculture, forestry, and mining. While industrialization brought economic development, it also left environmental challenges that remain relevant today. Despite these transformations, the region has preserved significant natural and cultural heritage, making it an important site for discussions on sustainable development. The landscape consists of a mix of cultivated fields, pastures, and forested areas, which provide habitats for diverse flora and fauna. Although the region does not have large-scale protected landscape areas, it contains important ecological sites, including river ecosystems and agricultural lands that play a key role in local biodiversity conservation.

These areas are essential for preserving biodiversity and offer insights into the region's ecological significance.

One notable protected area is the **Kurinecká dubina** Nature Reserve, established in 1952 and covering approximately 5.96 hectares. Situated within the cadastral territory of Rimavská Sobota, this reserve is managed by the Cerová vrchovina Protected Landscape Area administration.

Another significant site is the **Fenek** Protected Area, declared in 1993 and encompassing about 9.68 hectares. Located in the cadastral area of Petrovce, it also falls under the management of the Cerová vrchovina administration.

Additionally, the **Svetlianska cerina** Nature Reserve, established in 1976, spans approximately 15.3 hectares in the cadastral territory of Hrachovo. This reserve contributes to the conservation of the region's unique flora and fauna.

These protected areas, among others in the district, play a crucial role in maintaining the ecological balance and natural beauty of Rimavská Sobota. They serve as vital refuges for various species and offer opportunities for scientific research and environmental education.

Cultural traditions remain strong in Rimavská Sobota and the surrounding areas. The region has a rich folk heritage, with traditional crafts, music, and dance still practiced in many local communities. Festivals

celebrating historical customs are held throughout the year, reflecting the deep connection between the people and their land. Historically, Rimavská Sobota was an important cultural and trade center in the Gemer-Malohont region, and its historical architecture and urban layout still carry traces of its diverse past.

While large-scale tourism is not a major factor in the region's economy, there is growing interest in sustainable and community-based tourism. Efforts to promote ecotourism and cultural tourism focus on showcasing local history, gastronomy, and rural traditions. This approach aligns with broader European initiatives aimed at fostering tourism that respects local ecosystems and communities. However, the challenge remains in balancing economic development with environmental sustainability, a key topic of discussion in the CIRAN project.

Geological Specifics

The Rimavská Sobota district is geologically diverse, forming part of the Western Carpathian geological system. The region consists mainly of sedimentary rock formations, including limestone, sandstone, and claystone, with volcanic activity having played a significant role in shaping its geological character. The presence of neovolcanic formations is particularly notable in the nearby **Cerová vrchovina** (Cerová Highlands), which contains remnants of basaltic volcanic activity from the Neogene period. These volcanic formations contribute to the area's unique geomorphological features, including volcanic plateaus, lava fields, and extinct volcanic cones.

The region has a long history of quarrying and mineral extraction, with several former quarries now serving as important geological and environmental landmarks. Many of these sites provide insights into the geological evolution of the area and offer opportunities for scientific research and education. Notable examples include:

- **Hajnáčka Natural Monument** – A volcanic formation with visible evidence of solidified lava, pyroclastic material, and basaltic rock structures. The site is part of the Cerová vrchovina Protected Landscape Area and serves as a significant geological landmark.
- **Gemerská Poloma Quarry** – Known for its deposits of magnesite, one of Slovakia's key mineral resources. The site has been crucial for industrial mineral extraction, contributing to the region's economic history.

- **Kurinecká Dubina** – Although primarily a forest reserve, it contains sedimentary deposits that provide evidence of the area's prehistoric environments.

Additionally, mineral springs are present in the region, with local groundwater sources containing carbonated and mineral-rich waters, similar to other parts of Slovakia known for their healing springs. The geological conditions in Rimavská Sobota have influenced land use, settlement patterns, and the availability of natural resources, making them an important factor in discussions about environmental conservation and sustainable resource management.

Stone waterfall Šomoška

Socio-economic Disadvantages

Rimavská Sobota and its surrounding region are among the least economically developed areas in Slovakia. Located in the Banskobystrický region, the district has long struggled with high unemployment rates, low wages, and limited economic opportunities. The region's industrial decline, coupled with a lack of investment in infrastructure and services, has led to economic stagnation and a gradual decrease in population. Many residents, particularly younger generations, leave the area in search of better educational and employment opportunities, contributing to rural depopulation and an aging population.

The district's economy has historically been based on agriculture, small-scale manufacturing, and mining. However, with the closure of many industrial facilities and the reduction of mining activities, local employment opportunities have become scarce. Agriculture remains an important sector, but it is not sufficient to support widespread economic growth. Organic farming and local food production offer potential for sustainable economic development, yet these sectors face challenges related to market access and financial support.

Public infrastructure in Rimavská Sobota lags behind other regions in Slovakia. Limited transportation options make commuting to larger cities difficult, restricting access to better-paying jobs. Additionally, the region has fewer public amenities, such as parks, sports facilities, and cultural centers, which impacts the overall quality of life. Healthcare and social services are also inadequate, with some rural communities lacking sufficient medical facilities and eldercare services.

A significant issue for regional development is the tension between economic expansion and environmental conservation. While there is pressure to develop new housing and industrial zones, these initiatives must be balanced with nature protection policies. Illegal logging, land use conflicts, and unregulated hunting also present challenges to sustainable management.

Despite these socio-economic difficulties, Rimavská Sobota has cultural and community strengths. The region has a rich tradition of folk culture, music, and crafts, which contribute to its cultural identity. Local organizations and initiatives aim to promote sustainable tourism and eco-friendly economic activities, such as beekeeping, forestry, and handicrafts. These initiatives, along with efforts to improve education and infrastructure, could help revitalize the region while maintaining its environmental and cultural heritage.

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Focus Group

The focus group in Rimavská Sobota was organised in accordance with the CIRAN Methodology for Focus Groups to ensure a structured discussion with diverse perspectives. The goal was to gather 6-12 participants to assess local knowledge, attitudes, and concerns regarding critical raw materials and environmental sustainability. The focus group aimed to explore different public viewpoints, ensuring representation from various sectors of society, including activists, business owners, and concerned citizens.

To identify participants, we conducted a network analysis to map out key stakeholders, local leaders, and engaged community members in Rimavská Sobota and its vicinity. We prioritized geographical proximity and diversity to reflect the local context. An initial list of 10 potential participants was compiled, including individuals from different backgrounds such as law, local governance, business, and civil society organizations.

In the first stage, our local contact – Rimavská kaviareň, a nonformal active community was approached and invitations were sent out approximately one month before the scheduled meeting. The invitation letter outlined the purpose of the focus group, its relevance to local and EU policies, and logistical details regarding time and location. Out of the 10 invited participants, firstly 8 confirmed their participation, while others either did not respond or sent apologies.

The initial attempt to organise the focus group in Rimavská Sobota had to be postponed due to unforeseen health-related circumstances affecting key participants. To ensure a safe and productive discussion, the meeting was rescheduled to a later date, allowing all invited participants to fully engage in the conversation.

After rescheduling, a follow-up reminder was done by phone one week before the meeting to ensure attendance. Focus group was successfully conducted with a total of 10 participants plus one participant joined additionally, representing a balanced mix of local business owners, activists, and concerned citizens. The discussion provided valuable insights into the region's socio-economic challenges, environmental concerns, and public perceptions regarding mining and resource extraction in Slovakia.

The focus group was facilitated by an experienced moderator who has extensive knowledge of civic society and community engagement in the Rimavská Sobota region. With a deep understanding of local socio-economic challenges and environmental issues, the facilitator guided the discussion effectively, ensuring that all participants had the opportunity to express their perspectives. Their familiarity with local activism, public policy, and grassroots organizing helped create a comfortable and open atmosphere, allowing for a productive exchange of ideas and viewpoints.

- **Participant Selection:** Participants were invited based on a network analysis of stakeholders, targeting a diverse group. While the original intent was to include a range of perspectives, the final group consisted primarily of activists and concerned citizens.

- **Number of Participants:** 10 participants
 - Backgrounds: Activists, concerned citizens, local business owners, one lawyer
 - Gender: 7 men, 3 women (including one married couple)
 - Age: Adults and seniors
- **Structure of Discussion:**
 - Pre-planned questions guided the discussion
 - Presentation on critical raw materials and their global context
 - Open discussion and debate among participants
- **Data Collection and Analysis:** The session was recorded, and transcripts were analysed using thematic categorization

Location and Timing

The focus group took place on **11th December 2024** in **Rimavská Sobota** at the **community center CITADELA**, a relatively new local venue of independent culture, used for civic discussions, cultural events, and public meetings. The location was chosen for its accessibility and its role as a hub for local activism and community engagement. The venue provided a comfortable and neutral setting for an open discussion on critical raw materials and sustainability.

The meeting was held in a main room equipped with the necessary facilities, including a projector and screen for presentations. The organisers ensured a welcoming environment by providing a **coffee with refreshments**, including snacks, cakes, and drinks, to facilitate informal discussions and networking among participants.

PARTICIPANTS' PROFILE

The focus group in Rimavská Sobota successfully brought together a diverse group of participants, representing various segments of the local community, including activists, business owners, and concerned citizens. Many of the participants were engaged in multiple roles within the community, actively involved in civic initiatives, advocacy, or local businesses. Their experience with participatory methods varied, but most had some prior engagement with community discussions, public consultations, or activism.

All participants were adults, with a mix of educational backgrounds, though several had higher education degrees, particularly in fields related to law, business, or sciences. The group consisted of **seven men and three women**, with two of the participants being part of a married couple. While the majority lived and worked in or near Rimavská Sobota, their perspectives reflected a broad range of experiences, from local entrepreneurship to civic engagement.

Given the relatively small civic society in the region, some participants knew each other from previous collaborations or public meetings. While this familiarity could not be entirely avoided, it helped facilitate a dynamic and open discussion, as participants were comfortable engaging in debate and sharing their perspectives on critical raw materials and sustainability challenges in the region.

Participant	Gender	Background	Notes
P1	M	Concerned citizen	
P2	F	Business owner and activist	Concerned about economic development and environment
P3	M	Business owner	Involved in environmental issues

P4	M	Concerned citizen	No specific activism background
P5	F	Lawyer	Very aware of environmental issues
P6	M	Activist	Community active
P7	M	Senior citizen	Interested in sustainability discussions
P8	F	Senior citizen	Regular person, politically active
P9	M	Concerned citizen	Engaged in community initiatives
P10	M	Activist	Engaged in community initiatives

Data analysis

The focus group discussion in Rimavská Sobota was recorded (audio) to ensure accuracy in data collection, and a designated recorder took detailed notes using a structured note-taking template. Notes were taken manually and transcribed to the document.

Once the transcription was completed, we translated the text into English for further analysis. The translated text was then systematically reviewed, with key statements highlighted according to main topics and key questions outlined in the research framework.

The final categorization of statements was conducted based on thematic analysis, grouping responses under the pre-defined topics. Additionally, information from the recorder's notes was incorporated to supplement the findings.

PHASE 1 – INTRODUCTION

Phase 1 lasted approximately 20 minutes. Group started with watching introductory video about critical raw materials, provided by CIRAN. After, each participant introduced themselves by sharing their occupation, background, and motivation for attending the focus group. Most participants expressed a strong interest in gaining new insights into environmental issues and sustainability, attending the discussion out of curiosity and a desire to contribute to local decision-making. The facilitator noted that many participants were already active in public life, engaged in community initiatives, local activism, and various associations focused on environmental, social, and cultural topics. Their experience with public participation and grassroots organizing enriched the discussion, providing a well-informed perspective on the challenges facing the region.

Following personal introductions, the facilitator provided a general overview of the CIRAN project, explaining its objectives, the structure of the focus group, and the three key discussion topics. Participants were introduced to the focus group rules, and each signed an Agreement of Participation after confirming their understanding of the discussion framework.

KEY FINDINGS

The discussion highlighted several recurring themes and concerns:

1. Public Debate on Consumption and Sustainability

- The EU demonstrated that disconnecting from gas and oil was easier than expected.
- There is an ongoing debate on whether high consumption levels are truly necessary.
- Reducing consumption could force China to reduce mining, following the principle: "If I don't have it, I don't need it."

- Recycling requires a significant amount of energy and clean water.
- Regulations should be implemented to control waste imports and increase accountability.

2. Resource Extraction and Its Consequences

- "These raw materials are tools of war."
- Many feared that lobbying efforts could sway public opinion and enable corruption in government decisions.
- India and China are unlikely to reduce their resource consumption.
- Society is structured on continuous economic growth, creating long-term unsustainable debt.

3. Mining in Protected Areas

- Participants debated if mining could be allowed based on what is being extracted.
- A mining company should be required to pay for land revitalization upfront.
- The issue of corruption and lack of enforcement in Slovakia remains a major concern.
- "If it's not in my backyard, I don't care" reflects the attitude of the majority.

4. Public and Political Attitudes

- Regions like Gemer historically developed due to mining; future mining should be paired with research and education.
- Slovaks are poorly informed about critical raw materials.
- The public will likely oppose domestic mining but support foreign mining.
- "Why do you have two lamps on if you care about the planet?" was used to highlight contradictions in consumer behavior.
- Political populism and misinformation strongly shape public opinion in Slovakia.

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PUBLIC DIALOGUE REPORT
Rimavská Sobota – Slovakia

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The public dialogue held in Rimavská Sobota on 9 April 2025, organised by Centrum komunitného organizovania and Rimavská kaviareň, brought together 15 participants representing various sectors to discuss the sustainable management of critical raw materials. Following an introductory session comprising a presentation and a short video, participants engaged in structured group deliberations on four key questions concerning the European Union's strategic approach, necessary internal changes, mining in protected areas, and the future of critical raw materials. The dialogue concluded with an exploratory vote on eight statements summarizing the main outcomes of the discussions.

The findings revealed broad consensus on the need to prioritize environmental protection, modernize mining technologies, promote recycling and circular economy principles, and enforce ethical standards in sourcing. Participants emphasised the importance of reducing consumption, strengthening public awareness, and ensuring that mining activities are governed through professional, impartial mechanisms. While some participants conditionally accepted mining in protected areas under strict conditions, others opposed it due to past negative experiences and low institutional trust. Overall, the dialogue underscored strong public support for sustainability, innovation, and transparent governance in the critical raw materials sector.

INTRODUCTION

The public dialogue took place on 9 April 2025 in Rimavská Sobota, located in the Banská Bystrica region of southern Slovakia. The event was organised in line with the CIRAN project's goals to gather local perspectives on the extraction of critical raw materials and their sustainable governance.

A total of 15 participants attended the session, representing a diverse group of engaged citizens and professionals, including civil society, academia, research, business, media, and local government. Participants were both women and men, with an almost even gender distribution (7 women and 8 men).

The majority identified as interested in the topic of critical raw materials and had at least some knowledge or personal motivation to participate. While only 5 participants had prior experience with discussions or activities related to critical raw materials, most showed a high level of interest in the subject and actively contributed to the discussion.

The objective of the meeting was to introduce the CIRAN project and its focus through a short introductory presentation, followed by an in-depth dialogue. Participants worked in 2 small groups to reflect on and respond to four core questions concerning the sustainable supply and extraction of CRMs. Their discussions aimed to bring forward local insights, formulate key messages, and identify shared principles and concerns regarding future EU policy directions.

The diversity of perspectives ensured a rich and multi-dimensional discussion, combining scientific, civic, economic, and local viewpoints. This composition allowed for a nuanced dialogue on the challenges and opportunities connected to the sustainable sourcing of critical raw materials in the EU.

The town was selected as the location for this dialogue due to its significant socio-economic challenges and ongoing public concerns related to environmental governance, particularly around the extraction of natural resources and proposals for waste management. Rimavská Sobota is situated in one of the most economically disadvantaged regions of Slovakia, characterized by high unemployment rates, youth outmigration, and limited investment in innovation or sustainable industry. These factors made it a highly relevant site for exploring citizens' attitudes toward the sustainable sourcing of critical raw materials (CRMs).

The event was co-organised by two Slovak civil society actors: Centrum komunitného organizovania (CKO) and Rimavská kaviareň (RK) in Cultural centre CITADELA. CKO, a well-established NGO based in Banská Bystrica, has a strong record in community organizing, participatory democracy, and environmental education, including leading the Green Banská Bystrica initiative. Rimavská kaviareň, while operating as an informal local platform, plays a key civic role in the region, regularly initiating public events and community debates. Together, these organizations brought together diverse voices from the region to reflect on one of the most pressing environmental and political topics of our time.

Rimavská Sobota also holds historical significance as a former centre of mining and agricultural production. While many of these industries have declined, recent public debates – such as those concerning the potential siting of a radioactive waste facility – have revitalized questions about environmental risk, political trust, and

the future use of local land and resources. These discussions have become even more critical considering broader European Union strategies around CRM independence and supply chain resilience.

LOCAL CONTEXT

Regional Overview

Rimavská Sobota is a district town located in the Banskobystrický region of southern Slovakia. It lies in the Rimava River valley, within the larger Gemer-Malohont historical region. The area has a long history of industrial and agricultural activity, with mining, metalworking, and forestry playing key roles in its economic development. However, in recent decades, the region has faced economic decline, high unemployment rates, and depopulation, making it one of the most economically disadvantaged areas in Slovakia.

The town and its surrounding region have become the subject of environmental and economic debates, particularly concerning resource extraction and waste management. Discussions on the potential storage of radioactive waste, as well as broader issues related to mining governance and environmental protection, have made Rimavská Sobota a relevant location for public engagement on sustainability and critical raw materials.

Rimavská Sobota serves as an important administrative and economic hub for the surrounding rural communities. While it does not include protected landscape areas, the region has significant agricultural land and forested areas, which are vital for biodiversity and local livelihoods. Governance and regional development initiatives have been a focus of local organizations, such as Centrum komunitného organizovania and Rimavská kaviareň, which actively participate in public discussions on sustainability and environmental policies.

Given its socio-economic challenges and its role in ongoing national and EU-level debates on sustainable resource management, Rimavská Sobota was chosen as the Slovak case study location for the CIRAN project. The town provides a crucial perspective on the intersection of environmental protection, economic resilience, and citizen participation in decision-making processes.

The area has high unemployment, limited industrial development, and lower educational attainment compared to national averages. The region has faced historical economic challenges and continues to struggle with depopulation.

A key concern in the region is political and social polarization. The current government has been criticized for its anti-environmental policies, further fuelling distrust among citizens regarding environmental decision-making.

Administrative and Demographic Snapshot

The Rimavská Sobota district, located in the Banskobystrický region of southern Slovakia, is home to approximately 80,000 inhabitants. The administrative centre is the town of Rimavská Sobota, with other nearby towns and municipalities including Hnúšťa, Tisovec, Revúca, and Tornaľa. The district is characterized by a diverse population, including a significant Hungarian minority and one of the highest concentrations of Roma communities in Slovakia. This demographic diversity presents both opportunities and challenges for regional development, social inclusion, and policy implementation. Economic and social disparities remain visible across the district, influencing local governance, public service delivery, and citizen participation in democratic processes.

Transport and Infrastructure Overview

Rimavská Sobota lies along the important east-west road corridor Route I/16, which connects the region to major cities such as Zvolen and Košice. The town is also located on the Zvolen–Košice railway line, providing regional train connections; however, public transportation options within the district remain limited, especially in rural and mountainous areas. Many smaller municipalities face challenges related to transport accessibility, which hinders commuting, access to education, healthcare, and participation in civic life. Digital infrastructure in the region has improved in recent years, with increasing broadband internet availability. Nevertheless, disparities persist, particularly in remote villages, where limited digital access can restrict residents' engagement with public policies and online participation opportunities.

Conservation and Culture

The Rimavská Sobota region has been shaped by human activity for centuries, particularly through agriculture, forestry, and mining. While industrialization brought economic development, it also left environmental challenges that remain relevant today. Despite these transformations, the region has preserved significant natural and cultural heritage, making it an important site for discussions on sustainable development. The landscape consists of a mix of cultivated fields, pastures, and forested areas, which provide habitats for diverse flora and fauna. Although the region does not have large-scale protected landscape areas, it contains important ecological sites, including river ecosystems and agricultural lands that play a key role in local biodiversity conservation.

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Protected area Cerová vrchovina

Cultural traditions remain strong in Rimavská Sobota and the surrounding areas. The region has a rich folk heritage, with traditional crafts, music, and dance still practiced in many local communities. Festivals celebrating historical customs are held throughout the year, reflecting the deep connection between the people and their land. Historically, Rimavská Sobota was an important cultural and trade centre in the Gemer-Malohont region, and its historical architecture and urban layout still carry traces of its diverse past.

While large-scale tourism is not a major factor in the region's economy, there is growing interest in sustainable and community-based tourism. Efforts to promote ecotourism and cultural tourism focus on showcasing local history, gastronomy, and rural traditions. This approach aligns with broader European initiatives aimed at fostering tourism that respects local ecosystems and communities. However, the challenge remains in balancing economic development with environmental sustainability, a key topic of discussion in the CIRAN project.

Geological Specifics

The Rimavská Sobota district is geologically diverse, forming part of the Western Carpathian geological system. The region consists mainly of sedimentary rock formations, including limestone, sandstone, and claystone, with volcanic activity having played a significant role in shaping its geological character. The presence of neo volcanic formations is particularly notable in the nearby **Cerová vrchovina** (Cerová Highlands), which contains remnants of basaltic volcanic activity from the Neogene period. These volcanic formations contribute to the area's unique geomorphological features, including volcanic plateaus, lava fields, and extinct volcanic cones.

The region has a long history of quarrying and mineral extraction, with several former quarries now serving as important geological and environmental landmarks. Many of these sites provide insights into the geological evolution of the area and offer opportunities for scientific research and education. Notable examples include:

- **Hajnáčka Natural Monument** – A volcanic formation with visible evidence of solidified lava, pyroclastic material, and basaltic rock structures. The site is part of the Cerová vrchovina Protected Landscape Area and serves as a significant geological landmark.
- **Gemerská Poloma Quarry** – Known for its deposits of magnesite, one of Slovakia's key mineral resources. The site has been crucial for industrial mineral extraction, contributing to the region's economic history.
- **Kurinecká Dubina** – Although primarily a forest reserve, it contains sedimentary deposits that provide evidence of the area's prehistoric environments.

Additionally, mineral springs are present in the region, with local groundwater sources containing carbonated and mineral-rich waters, similar to other parts of Slovakia known for their healing springs. The geological conditions in Rimavská Sobota have influenced land use, settlement patterns, and the availability of natural resources, making them an important factor in discussions about environmental conservation and sustainable resource management.

Socio-economic Disadvantages

Rimavská Sobota and its surrounding region are among the least economically developed areas in Slovakia. Located in the Banskobystrický region, the district has long struggled with high unemployment rates, low wages, and limited economic opportunities. The region's industrial decline, coupled with a lack of investment in infrastructure and services, has led to economic stagnation and a gradual decrease in population. Many residents, particularly younger generations, leave the area in search of better educational and employment opportunities, contributing to rural depopulation and an aging population.

The district's economy has historically been based on agriculture, small-scale manufacturing, and mining. However, with the closure of many industrial facilities and the reduction of mining activities, local employment opportunities have become scarce. Agriculture remains an important sector, but it is not sufficient to support widespread economic growth. Organic farming and local food production offer potential for sustainable economic development, yet these sectors face challenges related to market access and financial support.

Public infrastructure in Rimavská Sobota lags behind other regions in Slovakia. Limited transportation options make commuting to larger cities difficult, restricting access to better-paying jobs. Additionally, the region has fewer public amenities, such as parks, sports facilities, and cultural centres, which impacts the overall quality

of life. Healthcare and social services are also inadequate, with some rural communities lacking sufficient medical facilities and eldercare services.

A significant issue for regional development is the tension between economic expansion and environmental conservation. While there is pressure to develop new housing and industrial zones, these initiatives must be balanced with nature protection policies. Illegal logging, land use conflicts, and unregulated hunting also present challenges to sustainable management.

Despite these socio-economic difficulties, Rimavská Sobota has cultural and community strengths. The region has a rich tradition of folk culture, music, and crafts, which contribute to its cultural identity. Local organizations and initiatives aim to promote sustainable tourism and eco-friendly economic activities, such as beekeeping, forestry, and handicrafts. These initiatives, along with efforts to improve education and infrastructure, could help revitalize the region while maintaining its environmental and cultural heritage.

Stone waterfall Šomoška

Stakeholder Roles

A variety of stakeholders play key roles in environmental and resource management in the Rimavská Sobota region. Local government bodies, particularly the municipal office of Rimavská Sobota and surrounding villages, are responsible for land use planning, waste management, and regional development initiatives that affect both the environment and public infrastructure. Forestry management is overseen primarily by LESY SR, the state-owned forestry enterprise, which manages extensive forested areas in the region and is responsible for both timber production and conservation practices.

Environmental oversight and enforcement are carried out by the Slovak Environmental Inspectorate and relevant departments within the Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic. However, confidence in regulatory institutions remains low due to previous lapses in enforcement and transparency, especially in sensitive cases such as the environmental degradation in nearby Nižná Slaná and Predajná.

Crucially, the administration of the **Cerová vrchovina Protected Landscape Area (CHKO Cerová vrchovina)**, part of the State Nature Conservancy of the Slovak Republic, plays an essential role in the protection of biodiversity and ecosystem services in the southern part of the Banskobystrický region, including parts of the Rimavská Sobota district. This institution manages nature reserves such as Kurinecká dubina, Fenek, and Svetlianska cerina, and coordinates activities related to biodiversity conservation, environmental education, and sustainable tourism.

Logo of Administration of protected area - CHKO Cerová vrchovina

Local educational institutions, including secondary schools with environmental, technical, or agricultural specializations, also contribute to awareness-raising and civic education. Their students often participate in environmental projects, clean-up activities, and workshops. NGOs such as Centrum komunitného organizovania and grassroots platforms like Rimavská kaviareň have been instrumental in fostering community dialogue, organizing public events, and facilitating citizen engagement on issues of sustainability, transparency, and democratic governance.

Environmental Challenges or Successes

While the Rimavská Sobota region itself does not currently face large-scale environmental disasters, nearby areas such as Nižná Slaná and Predajná offer cautionary examples of the consequences of poorly regulated mining and environmental mismanagement. In Nižná Slaná, a long-abandoned iron ore mine began leaking highly acidic water into the Slaná River in early 2022, causing severe ecological damage and prompting public outrage and grassroots mobilization. The incident highlighted systemic failures in environmental monitoring and the absence of preventive measures by the Slovak state. Similarly, in Predajná, the aftermath of historical mining operations has left significant ecological scars and unfulfilled promises of land revitalization, contributing to public distrust in environmental governance.

Nižná Slaná river pollution, Source: Pravda

Despite these challenges, the Rimavská Sobota district also offers positive examples of community-led environmental engagement. Local NGOs and civic groups have organised clean-up campaigns, educational workshops on biodiversity protection, and awareness drives around sustainable land use. The region's forests, meadows, and river valleys provide crucial ecosystem services—including carbon sequestration, water retention, and habitat provision—which support both human well-being and ecological stability. Protected areas such as the Kurinecká Dubina and Svetlianska Cerina nature reserves help preserve this biodiversity, offering models for balancing environmental protection with regional development goals.

METHODOLOGY

Organisers

The public dialogue in Rimavská Sobota was organised by the Centre for Community Organizing (Centrum komunitného organizovania, CKO) in collaboration with Rimavská kaviareň (RK), as part of the CIRAN project's Work Package 5: "Inclusion and Knowledge Co-Creation." Both organizations are known for their long-standing engagement in environmental education, civic participation, and public debate, particularly in central and southern Slovakia. CKO has coordinated numerous community engagement initiatives and public campaigns on issues such as sustainable development and social justice, while RK serves as a vital grassroots platform for discussion, civic activation, and informal community building in the Rimavská Sobota region.

Preparation of the Public Dialogue

Participants were selected through a combination of open calls through popular social media event and direct invitations, focusing on ensuring a balanced representation of sectors and perspectives. The organizing team

sought individuals from NGOs, academia, public administration, research, business, and civic communities. Particular attention was paid to include individuals from marginalized communities and underrepresented groups, in order to ensure an inclusive and diverse discussion. That unfortunately was not successful.

A total of 15 participants attended the dialogue, held on 9 April 2025 in Rimavská Sobota. The event included both experienced stakeholders and first-time participants in such dialogue formats. Most participants expressed strong interest in the topic of critical raw materials and had some level of prior knowledge or engagement with environmental or sustainability-related issues.

The session was moderated by external experienced facilitator. The dialogue was conducted in accordance with the CIRAN methodology for public engagement, ensuring a structured, inclusive, and transparent deliberative process.

Location and Timing

The event took place at the Cultural centre CITADELA in Rimavská Sobota, a venue equipped with necessary technical support for presentations and group work. The setting was chosen to be accessible and familiar to local residents and allowed for both formal discussion and informal exchange.

The meeting was held in a main room equipped with the necessary facilities, including a projector and screen for presentation. The organisers ensured a welcoming environment by providing a **coffee with refreshments**, including snacks and drinks, to facilitate informal discussions and networking among participants.

Structure of Discussion

- Introduction of the CIRAN project, welcoming of participants, and explanation of the event's structure
- Informative session with a presentation about critical raw materials
- Deliberative session – participants divided into two smaller groups, each working through a set of questions with a facilitator
- Break and preparation of summary messages
- Presentation of group outcomes and exploratory voting on proposed statements
- Wrap-up, feedback collection, and acknowledgments

Data Collection and Analysis

Discussions were documented by appointed group members using flipcharts and observation notes. Participants' statements were later thematically analysed in relation to the four discussion questions. The organizing team compiled a structured summary of findings, highlighting key messages and areas of consensus or divergence.

Each discussion group produced specific "postulates" (draft statements) reflecting their conclusions. These were then presented to all participants for exploratory voting to indicate the level of support or concern. The

outcomes were synthesized into this report to contribute to the overall CIRAN knowledge base on public engagement in critical raw material governance.

PARTICIPANTS PROFILE

In total, **15 participants** took part in the public dialogue held on **9 April 2025** in Rimavská Sobota. The group was balanced in terms of gender and diverse in terms of background and professional affiliation. Participants included representatives from civil society organizations, academia, public administration, the business sector, and the general public.

Gender Distribution

The group consisted of **8 women and 7 men**, representing a near-equal gender distribution.

Group Representation

Participants came from various sectors:

- Civil society/NGOs: 2
- Academia and research: 4
- Public administration: 1
- Business: 2
- General public/residents: 4
- Media: 1
- Local government: 1

This diversity ensured a broad spectrum of views and experiences were represented during the discussion.

Table 1: General Profile of the Participants

ID	Sex	Affiliation / Notes
P1	f	NGO, environmental advocacy
P2	m	General public
P3	m	General public
P4	m	General public
P5	f	General public
P6	m	Research, natural sciences, environmentalist
P7	m	Research, environmentalist
P8	m	Business sector
P9	f	Research and academia
P10	m	Academic expert

ID	Sex	Affiliation / Notes
	x	
P1 1	f	NGO, community development
P1 2	f	Business sector
P1 3	f	Local government
P1 4	m	Media
P1 5	m	Academia

* P = participant, f = female, m = male; NGO – non-governmental organisation

KEY FINDINGS

PHASE 1 – INTRODUCTION

The public dialogue began with an introductory session led by representatives from Centrum komunitného organizovania (CKO) and Rimavská kaviareň (RK). The organisers welcomed the participants and introduced the goals and structure of the CIRAN project. A short explanatory video on critical raw materials (CRMs) was screened to familiarize the participants with the topic. The presentation clarified what CRMs are, their role in strategic industries, and the geopolitical and environmental challenges surrounding their extraction.

The facilitators explained the aims of the public dialogue and its connection to Work Package 5 of the CIRAN project. Participants were provided with background information on CRMs, their supply chains, and potential impacts of extraction, especially in sensitive and protected areas. This phase set the context for the deliberation that followed.

Group of participants

PHASE 2 – DELIBERATION PHASE

During the second phase of the event, participants were divided into two facilitated discussion groups, each comprising a diverse mix of individuals based on their background, gender, and institutional affiliation to ensure heterogeneity. The deliberation lasted approximately 50 minutes. Each group addressed four key questions formulated to explore the sustainable governance of critical raw materials from a European perspective. The questions focused on the EU's strategic priorities regarding sustainable supply, necessary changes to ensure future resilience, the possibility of permitting extraction in protected areas, and the envisioned future of critical raw materials. Discussions were guided using printed visual aids, and participants were encouraged to formulate concrete proposals ("postulates") to be considered for broader public debate or policymaking. The dialogue was conducted in Slovak and simultaneously recorded in writing by appointed group members. Outputs from both groups were analysed and synthesized in the concluding session.

The four questions were:

1. What should the European Union prioritize to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?

(E.g., location and method of extraction, cooperation with countries outside the EU, internal competition, strategic autonomy.)

2. What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of critical raw materials? Do you think any changes are needed?

(E.g., quality of life, environmental standards, economic resilience, consumer behaviour, technological development.)

3. Should the extraction of critical raw materials be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?

(E.g., criteria for protecting natural values, types of extraction technology, irreversible environmental impacts.)

4. What do you envision for the future of critical raw materials that are currently being extracted?

(E.g., changes in demand, technological alternatives, geopolitical context, circular economy approaches.)

Group 1

Question 1 – What should the European Union prioritize to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?

Participants emphasised the need to avoid extraction in places where irreversible environmental damage could occur, including risks to human health and biodiversity. They advocated for site-specific evaluations, suggesting that even if a CRM is considered essential, its extraction should be weighed against the social and ecological value of the land. They called for compromise solutions such as opting for underground mining despite higher costs.

Statement for exploratory vote: The EU should prioritize mining sites where there is no risk of irreversible damage to the environment or public health, or apply more sensitive extraction methods, even if more costly.

Question 2 – What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of CRMs? Do you think any changes are needed?

Participants supported increasing the reuse of materials and ensuring that extraction and monitoring strategies are driven by expert, non-political processes. They called for stricter regulation of production standards, a reduction in demand through public education, and a strong focus on circular economy principles.

Statement for exploratory vote: Extraction and monitoring strategies should be expert-driven and impartial, with a focus on reducing consumption, increasing recycling, and raising public awareness. Extraction should be carried out by EU-based or national entities.

Question 3 – Should the extraction of CRMs be allowed in protected areas?

The group strongly opposed mining in protected areas unless it was the only possible source. Even in such cases, extraction should only occur under significantly stricter conditions and with minimal environmental and health impact.

Statement for exploratory vote: NO – unless it is the only viable source, extraction in protected areas should be banned. If unavoidable, stricter environmental and health conditions must be applied.

Question 4 – What do you envision for the future of CRMs?

Participants advocated for the modernization of mining methods, greater investment in innovation, and a review of both existing sources and technologies used. They also suggested reassessing political decisions related to electromobility.

Statement for exploratory vote: Modernize extraction technologies and methods, apply stricter and impartial regulation, and invest in reviewing past extraction sites and practices.

Group 2

Question 1 – What should the European Union prioritize to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?

Participants emphasised geopolitical aspects such as the EU's strategic position toward supplier countries and the necessity for ethical conduct by European companies.

Statement for exploratory vote: Introduce a code of ethics for companies extracting or importing CRMs. Promote fair trade in supplier countries and consider the ecological burden on those regions.

Question 2 – What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of CRMs? Do you think any changes are needed?

Participants supported the “spaceship economy” model – minimizing waste and preserving CRMs for essential use. They stressed the need for investments in alternative materials, increased product longevity, and better regulation.

Statement for exploratory vote: Support a sustainability-focused “spaceship economy” by reducing CRM waste and ensuring long-term access to essential materials.

Question 3 – Should the extraction of CRMs be allowed in protected areas?

Views were mixed. Some supported conditional extraction based on environmental impact assessments (EIA), while others expressed mistrust toward institutions, citing poor experiences from cases such as Nižná Slaná and Predajná.

Statement for exploratory vote: No extraction in protected areas – past incidents (e.g., Nižná Slaná, Predajná) have shown failures in institutional oversight and environmental protection.

Question 4 – What do you envision for the future of CRMs?

Ideas included long-term planning based on consumption projections, renewed interest in space mining, and improved public education, particularly using international case studies like Ghana.

Statement for exploratory vote: Encourage innovation in finding alternative materials and solutions to reduce dependency on currently extracted CRMs.

Group of participants

PHASE 3 – DECISION MAKING PHASE

Throughout the deliberation phase, facilitator and appointed group members carefully recorded participants' insights, concerns, and suggested solutions. After both groups concluded their discussions, they formulated a series of proposed statements (postulates)—representing the shared priorities and positions voiced during the session. These statements were then presented to all participants for an exploratory vote. The aim of this voting process was not to reach consensus but to better understand the level of support for various ideas and to highlight key directions for future policy and public engagement in the field of critical raw materials.

STATEMENTS FOR EXPLORATORY VOTE

- 1. The EU should prioritize mining sites where there is no risk of irreversible environmental and health damage, or choose more sensitive mining methods, even at higher cost.**

_for: 15; against: 0; abstentions: 0

2. **Strategies and monitoring mechanisms for mining should be carried out professionally and impartially, with emphasis on reducing consumption, increasing recycling, and raising consumer awareness. Implementation within the EU should be conducted by EU-based or domestic entities.**

_for: 14; against: 1; abstentions: 0

3. **Mining in protected areas should not be allowed, unless it is the only source, in which case stricter conditions must apply to minimize environmental and health impacts.**

_for: 9; against: 5; abstentions: 1

4. **Technologies and mining methods should be modernized, mining strictly regulated and monitored, and investment made in innovation while reassessing past mining practices.**

_for: 15; against: 0; abstentions: 0

5. **An ethical code should apply to companies mining or importing critical raw materials, and the EU should support fair trade in supplier countries, ensuring compliance with environmental and social limits.**

_for: 15; against: 0; abstentions: 0

6. **A “spaceship economy” approach should be adopted—minimizing waste of critical raw materials so they remain available for essential needs, while supporting the search for alternatives.**

_for: 15; against: 0; abstentions: 0

7. **Extraction should not take place in protected areas due to past negative experiences (e.g., Nižná Slaná, Predajná) and lack of trust in Slovak institutions.**

_for: 13; against: 1; abstentions: 1

8.

9. **The future lies in innovation, such as space programs and research into alternative materials, along with public awareness campaigns.**

_for: 15; against: 0; abstentions: 0

CONCLUSIONS

The public dialogue in Rimavská Sobota revealed that while the majority of participants initially thought they had limited knowledge about the topic of critical raw materials (CRMs), they demonstrated creative thinking, complex understanding of various sides of this topic, strong curiosity and openness to learning during the informative phase. The introductory presentation and video successfully stimulated interest, which was reflected in the active and thoughtful engagement throughout the deliberation phase. Participants quickly moved beyond general questions and began critically evaluating the environmental, social, and economic implications of CRM extraction in both a local and European context. This was reflected in the depth and clarity of the proposed statements and the exploratory voting in the final phase.

Both discussion groups emphasised that any extraction of critical raw materials (CRMs) must be approached with caution, respect for environmental values, and attention to long-term societal impacts. The protection of human and environmental health was a priority. Participants stressed the importance of avoiding irreversible environmental damage and called for individual, case-by-case evaluation of extraction sites—particularly in or near protected areas.

One group supported a postulate stating that the European Union should prioritize extraction only in areas where no irreversible harm is likely and should opt for more sensitive forms of extraction even if they are

more expensive. The same group argued that extraction strategies and controls must be handled professionally and impartially, aiming to reduce consumption and improve consumer awareness while increasing recycling and reuse. They also explicitly rejected extraction in protected areas unless it is the only possible source and strict environmental and health conditions are met.

The second group addressed the geopolitical and ethical dimensions of CRM supply. They proposed that companies extracting or importing CRMs should follow an ethical code and adhere to fair trade standards, especially in third countries. They supported the concept of a “spaceship economy” in which critical materials are conserved, and waste is minimized. The group also rejected mining in protected areas due to negative experiences in nearby localities (e.g., Nižná Slaná and Predajná), citing a lack of trust in Slovak institutions. Instead, they advocated for investment in alternatives, technological innovation, and greater public education.

In the final phase, participants voted on eight postulates that had emerged from the two group discussions. There was unanimous agreement on several key areas, including prioritizing environmentally safe mining, the modernization of mining technologies, the need for ethical sourcing and fair trade, and long-term investments in innovation and public awareness. These results highlight a shared commitment to sustainable, responsible, and forward-looking approaches to raw material extraction. However, more divided views emerged on mining in protected areas. While one postulate calling for conditional mining only in extreme necessity passed with moderate support, another calling for a categorical ban due to institutional mistrust and prior negative experiences was approved with slightly lower consensus. These nuanced outcomes reflect the community’s environmental sensitivity, ethical awareness, and demand for accountability, as well as a healthy diversity of views on how best to manage competing public interests.

34 Annex 25 Focus group report - Veselí nad Moravou (Czech Republic)

CIRAN

FOCUS GROUP REPORT

Veselí nad Moravou – Czech Republic

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report consists of several main parts.

Introduction: contains a brief description of the aim of the focus group discussion, the position of the local participating subject, the Education and Information Centre Bílé Karpaty (VIS BK), and the reason for choosing the location of Veselí nad Moravou.

Local context: briefly introduces the regional context of the case study, the White Carpathians (Bílé Karpaty) Protected Landscape Area, natural and cultural heritage, geological peculiarities, socio-economic characteristics and the state of natural resource extraction in the study region.

Methodology: this section explains the approach used to gather insights from focus group participants and the process of data collection, analysis and findings.

Participant profile: explains how we achieved diversity in stakeholder representation within a focus group and includes a table showing anonymised key characteristics of participants.

Key Findings: this section is the most important part of the report and provides generalised findings, including supporting quotes from participants.

The appendix includes the invitation email, adapted to the regional context.

INTRODUCTION

The focus group representing the Czech Republic took place on 20th June 2024 in Veselí nad Moravou. The main reasons for choosing the town of Veselí nad Moravou were the following: it is one of the points of entrance to the White Carpathians (Bílé Karpaty) Protected Landscape Area (PLA) and UNESCO Biosphere Reserve and it is the headquarters of the Czech partner that helped organise the focus group meeting – the non-governmental organisation Education and Information Centre Bílé Karpaty (VIS BK). Also, the regional office of the White Carpathians PLA Administration is located here. In 2024, the White Carpathians House of Nature was opened in Veselí nad Moravou. It serves as a modern visitor centre for the White Carpathians Protected Landscape Area and the adjacent Morava River valley.

VIS BK is a strong regional partner. The organisation was founded by three institutions (municipal, state and non-governmental): the Municipality of Veselí nad Moravou, the Agency for Nature Conservation and Landscape Protection of the Czech Republic (ANCLPCR) and the Czech Union for Nature Conservation (CUNC). The aim of VIS BK is to focus on providing environmental education, consultancy, and tourist information, organising field trips and raising public awareness about nature protection, natural and cultural heritage of the White Carpathians PLA and in South-East Moravia. The target groups include schools, general public, local and foreign experts. The organisation also provides various services to ensure sustainable regional development and cooperates with various stakeholders in the region, including microregions, LAGs, municipalities, mayors, NGOs. Through these activities it has a good overview of the region. VIS BK has been involved in many regional, national and international projects, such as Interreg CentralParks (2019-2022), LIFE – Conservation of selected Natura 2000 insect species in the transboundary area of the Western Carpathian Mts. (2018-2022), LIFE Apollo 2020 (2021-2025), Erasmus+ (2023-2024).

The aim of the focus group is to implement activities within Work Package 5 of the project CIRAN - The path towards sustainable sourcing of critical raw materials in the EU: An integrated approach to extraction in protected areas. WP5 focuses on "Inclusion and knowledge co-creation" in one of the five case study areas across Europe. Activities will focus on designing, testing and validating governance models by involving citizen groups from five different EU municipalities in co-creation processes (through focus groups and public consultations) aimed at defining/improving standards for mining activities in protected areas. The questions prepared for the focus groups aim to elicit responses that will enable to achieve the following objective: to understand the different perspectives of local citizens on mineral extraction in protected areas. VIS BK is a strong regional partner. The organisation was founded by three institutions (municipal, state and non-governmental): the Municipality of Veselí nad Moravou, the Agency for Nature Conservation and Landscape Protection of the Czech Republic (ANCLPCR) and the Czech Union for Nature Conservation (CUNC). The aim of VIS BK is to focus on providing environmental education, consultancy, and tourist information, organising field trips and raising public awareness about nature protection, natural and cultural heritage of the White Carpathians PLA and in South-East Moravia. The target groups include schools, general public, local and foreign experts. The organisation also provides various services to ensure sustainable regional development and cooperates with various stakeholders in the region, including microregions, LAGs, municipalities, mayors, NGOs. Through these activities it has a good overview of the region. VIS BK has been involved in many regional, national and international projects, such as Interreg CentralParks (2019-2022), LIFE – Conservation of selected Natura 2000 insect species in the transboundary area of the Western Carpathian Mts. (2018-2022), LIFE Apollo 2020 (2021-2025), Erasmus+ (2023-2024).

LOCAL CONTEXT

General information:

The White Carpathians PLA covers small south-western edge of the Carpathian mountain range. The PLA was established in 1980 in former Czechoslovakia and until 1991 there was a common management of both the Czech and Slovak parts. After the split of Czechoslovakia into two independent states, the Czech Republic and Slovakia, the PLA was also divided into two PLAs on the Czech and Slovak sides. Despite this formal split, bilateral cooperation is still alive, especially in the field of regional development, tourism and nature conservation management, and many joint bilateral cultural and tourist events take place on the border. At present, the Czech part is 70 km long, has a northeast-southwest orientation, an altitude of 175-970 m (the highest peak being Velká Javořina), an area of 715 km² and covers mainly the Zlín administrative region and part of the South Moravia region. It is managed by the White Carpathians PLA Administration, a regional branch of the Agency for Nature Conservation and Landscape Protection of the Czech Republic. Due to its length and size, it includes several administrative units (offices) – the main headquarters is located in Luhačovice (central part), outposts in Veselí nad Moravou (southern part) and Zlín (western part), and a contact point in Brumov (northern part).

Figure 1: PLA White Carpathians

Source: Agency for Nature Conservation and Landscape Protection of the Czech Republic

Conservation and culture

The whole of the PLA (especially its southern part) has been cultivated by man for hundreds of years by the local inhabitants, we can say that "the landscape has been co-created by man and nature for thousands of years" (The White Carpathian House of Nature, 2024). Despite or because of this fact, exceptionally important natural treasures have been preserved here. Most of the area can be considered as a balanced and mosaic landscape structure, unique are mainly orchid meadows, orchards, flowering groves, well preserved structure of traditional rural settlements and overall landscape character, which can be seen mainly in aerial photographs. Only a few parts are currently untouched by man, such as the ancient beech forest on the highest parts of Velká Javořina. For these natural and landscape qualities, Bílé Karpaty was declared a UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserve (1996). The most valuable areas, with the highest priority protection within the PLA, are designated as National Nature Reserves (NNR), there are 5 of them, 4 of these consist mainly of orchid meadows and only scattered trees or orchards (NNR Čertoryje, NNR Porážky, NNR Zahrady pod Hájem, NNR Jazevčí) and only one of is a forest with plateau meadow (NNR Velká Javořina).

The region is very much characterised by folk traditions and old customs that are still alive, the local people dress up in colourful costumes on festive occasions. There is a great variety of these from an ethnographic point of view. The most important ethnographic areas are mainly Slovácko (southern part) and Valašsko (northern part). Due to the strong nature protection, the rather remote peripheral location, the region has remained protected from large-scale destructive tourism development compared to other PLAs in the Czech Republic (except for a few extreme examples of highly intensive tourist infrastructure concentration from the communist era), and thus the region represents a challenge for the development of rather sustainable and sensitive tourism, focusing on families, small groups and tourists who prefer deep understanding of the region instead of fast and immediate entertainment.

Geological specifics:

The territory of the White Carpathians Protected Landscape Area is part of the Carpathian system, which is a regional-geological unit much younger than the Bohemian Massif, consolidated by Variscan folding 380 - 300 million years ago during the Tertiary. Most of the territory belongs to the western part of the Carpathian flysch zone, and the central part is unique for the occurrence of neovolcanites, especially in the vicinity of Bojkovice, Bánov, Komňa, Nezdenice and Starý Hrozenkov. The area is rich in basalt, andesite and mineral springs (Luhačovice Spa).

There are many former quarries, which in the past were used mainly for the extraction of building stone or for small rural industries such as glassworks, brickworks or ironworks. They were linked to further processing facilities, such as crushers, and some were equipped with a narrow-gauge railway to the crusher and a cableway to the village. Now many of them have the status of natural monuments (NM). The existence of the quarries is connected with the development of the construction industry at the beginning of the 20th century and the increased demand for construction aggregates, for example during the construction of the road to Trenčín during the Second World War. After that, mining declined steadily and was mostly stopped in the 1960s (some of them remained in operation until the 1980s), leaving many smaller quarries to develop naturally. They contain various rocks and minerals such as amphibole, porcelanite, olivine, and limonite. These abandoned quarries provide important geological information about the geological heritage of the PLA and are useful for environmental education and research. Examples of the most important quarries:

- NM Skalka (Starý Hrozenkov), typical of basalt formations;

- NM Rasová and a number of smaller quarries where sandstone, claystone and andesite were quarried. Currently a lake with scattered vegetation;
- Bučník quarry (Komňa) is still an active mining area and one of the richest mineralogical sites (51 mineral species have been described here, e.g. galena, pyrite, sphalerite, wulfenite, cinnabarite). The main peculiarity of this quarry is the presence of porcelanite, a thermally altered rock (originally clay). Due to its vein-like structure it is often used as a raw material for jewellery;
- Natřix quarry (Bzová) – is still active mining area, deposit of sandstone;
- Bánov quarry (Bánov) – extraction of andezite, in the past illegal dumping, currently revitalised and preserved;
- Javorník quarry (Javorník) – clay mining, used for local brickworks;
- Vápenky, Vápenice near Bystřice pod Lopeník, and Slovak side of PLA - extraction of limestone for glassworks and ironworks;
- NM Střečkův kopen (Blatnice) – small-scale mining of claystone, sandstone. Currently important geological site – uncovered geological structure of the Carpathians;
- U Kyselky and V Háji (Nezdenice) - andezit, currently covered by forest and small lake.

In some areas, calcium carbonate is leached out in the form of calcareous putty or veins filling cracks. They are washed out by water and then precipitated from cold aqueous solutions with a higher $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$ content to form foams.

Mineral springs are mainly found in the vicinity of Luhačovice, where there are outpourings of carbonated waters, which are characterised as carbonic, bicarbonate-chloride, sodic, iodine, cold, hypotonic with additions of bromine, iron, lithium, barium and metaboric acid. Another group of mineral waters are the sulphur waters, which mainly contain hydrogen sulphide.

Note: most of the information in this subsection has been derived and adapted from ANCLPCR (2024) and Velká nad Veličkou IC (2024).

Socio-economic disadvantages

The region in which our focus group meeting took place falls mainly within the Horňácko ethnographic region, which administratively falls mostly under the municipality with extended competence of Veselí nad Moravou. The main municipalities of this region are Velká nad Veličkou, Javorník, Nová Lhota, Blatnička, Blatnice pod sv. Antonínkem, Malá Vrbka, Hrubá Vrbka, Suchov, Kuželov.

Figure 2: LAG Ostrožsko and Horňácko

Source: LAG Ostrožsko and Hornácko

What is an advantage for nature conservation and sustainable tourism is a disadvantage for the economy. The region belongs to the less developed areas, typical for small rural municipalities, with higher unemployment in the national context – almost 5% (Bujáková et al., 2021), higher necessity to commute to work outside the region, and it also suffers from difficult transport accessibility (also due to the previous separation of the Czech and Slovak states) to schools and workplaces, fewer public amenities (parks, sport zones, playgrounds for children), social services, health care and other necessary public infrastructure (social housing, residential social facilities).

It is a challenge for the younger generation, which has a higher demand for quality of life and different perspectives for socio-economic development, but also for the elderly, who suffer from difficult access to health and social services. Several communities do not have schools and children have to commute, or kindergartens do not have sufficient capacity. For the elderly, there is a lack of capacity in local social services or residential facilities. Recently, the number of inhabitants has decreased by 1.7% (Bujáková et al., 2021). It is a challenge for the municipalities and the state administration of the PLA to protect nature on the one hand and ensure adequate socio-economic development on the other hand. In the past, several key industries present in the region, such as the defence industry, were closed or limited, and the current development of other industries is also limited. On the other hand, the region is favourable for organic farming, local handicrafts, food processing and wineries. It is also characterised by a rich social life and a wide range of sports, cultural, music, dance, hunting, bee-keeping, gardening and mushroom growing clubs.

One of the most important employers in the region is the tyre factory Kordárna and the distillery Žufánek in Velká nad Veličkou, the textile manufacture LG Lipov in Lipov, wineries in Blatnice and Blatnička, etc. The main discrepancies between regional development and nature conservation lie in the pressure for new housing, the development of tourist facilities, the interests of some interest groups such as hunters and the search for a balance in forest management, including lobbying.

Figure 3,4: Hornácko region, Bučník quarry

Education and Information Centre Bílé Karpaty

Source:

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Focus Group

We sought to organise this focus group in accordance with the recommendations of the CIRAN Methodology for Focus Groups, to ensure high relevance, with a group of 6-12 people, to assess the general knowledge and interests of local citizens, and to explore different public opinions and viewpoints. We carried out a network analysis to identify key stakeholders, local leaders and interested people in the community and invited them to participate in the dialogue. We first looked at the conditions for selecting participants (local context, groups, diversity and geographical proximity), suggested potential participants and consulted them within the organisation and with the facilitator. We created a table with potential participants. In the first stage we made a list of 16 potential participants. To ensure geographical proximity we focused on the geographical diameter of about 30 kilometres from Veselí nad Moravou.

In the second stage we sent an invitation letter to all 16 potential participants about one month before the meeting, explaining the reason for the invitation, the place and time of the focus group meeting. We received a positive response from 8 potential participants. The remaining 8 potential participants did not respond or sent an apology (media, civil society, vulnerable group, general public, 2x policy maker, academia, NGO). Approximately one week before the meeting, we sent a reminder to the participants. One participant (active student, environmental advocacy) sent an apology for not being able to attend. In the end we had a group of 7 confirmed participants.

Location and Timing

The focus group took place on 20th June 2024 in Veselí nad Moravou in "Panský dvůr", náměstí Míru No. 664. It is a public building, the location of the municipal gallery, the business incubator, the tourist information centre and the seat of several NGOs, including the Education and Information Centre Bílé Karpaty (VIS BK). VIS BK was designated as the organiser of the focus group meeting. The large building provides suitable facilities for organising various kinds of public meetings. The focus group was held in the conference room, which was equipped with a projector, screen and other necessary equipment. The organiser provided coffee break, drinks and appropriate refreshments – sandwiches and cakes.

PARTICIPANTS' PROFILE

In general, we succeed in selecting a highly diverse group of participants, representing different segments of the local and regional community and from different backgrounds. An interesting finding was that most of the participants fit into more than one target group. They are very active in their work, but also in public life, and are connected to professional and different interest networks. In terms of experience with participatory methods, most participants already had some personal experience with active citizenship.

All focus group participants were over 18 years old. Most of them had a university education (although these criteria were not specifically identified, but were recognisable from their professional background). There was a gender balance with a slight predominance of women: four participants were women and three were men.

Participants live and work nearby the municipality of Veselí nad Moravou, which is geographically close to the protected area, and in the municipalities within or nearby the PLA, such as Uherské Hradiště, Blatnička, Nová Lhota, Javorník and Velká nad Veličkou. One participant came from a geographically distant region (Brno), but she very quickly got to know the topic and the other participants. On the other hand, due to this geographical proximity, they know each other to a certain extent. Even though they did not work in the same organisation – they sometimes meet during joint work and other events. Therefore, we could not strictly enforce the condition that participants should not know each other, but at least we ensured that they have some limited prior relationships.

Table 1. General profile of the participants.

Participant	Gender	Group	Notes
F1*	F	Academia/Research Center Civic society	Employed in academic institution, focus on environmental geography, active in several NGOs
P2*	F	Academia/Research Center Environmental Advocates	Representing CZ in international organisation, environmental field. Interested in geodiversity, sustainable tourism, natural and cultural heritage.
P3	F	Civic society Policy-maker Vulnerable groups	Active local resident, employed in local municipality, engaged in NGO oriented on environmental education, culture and public beneficiary facility for children, elderly and general public.
P4	M	Policy-maker Environmental Advocate Civic society	Active local resident, focus on regional development, employed in local municipality and microregion, and member of international NGO on soil issues
P5	M	Private Sector Environmental Advocate Civic society	Private farmer, active in local projects dealing with regeneration of agricultural land, environmental advisor in NGO

P6	M	Civic society Media Environmental Advocate	Member of NGO dealing with nature protection and environmental education, cooperation with Czech Radio
P7	F	Civic society Vulnerable groups	Ethnographer, member of local NGO focus on local culture, traditional habits and memory, work with children and local residents
P8	F	Policy-maker Civic society	Employed in state administration and local municipality, territorial planning, active in local development
R9*	F	Civic Society	Director of local NGO, organiser of event, experienced with participatory process

*F – facilitator, P-participant, R-recorder

Data analysis

First, we recorded the focus group meeting and the designated recorder took notes according to a template of how to take notes. We transferred the recording partly through AI instruments and partly manually to ensure better transcription (AI reported higher occurrence of "not understand" and we needed to check it in a transcript. Unfortunately, some parts remained incomprehensible due to technical limitations of the recording, but are not so important for the overall analysis).

After the transcription, we translated the whole text with the help of DeepL translator. Then we checked the whole rough text, and highlighted by various colour key statements according to 3 topics and 8 key questions, to eliminate unimportant or redundant phrases. Then we classified key statements into the three main topics and 8 key questions given by the template. We also utilised information from the recorder's notes as additional material for analysis. The entire manuscript was checked by DeepL Write.

PHASE 1 – INTRODUCTION

This phase lasted about 20 minutes. During the first part, each participant introduced themselves to the others, stated their occupation, background and the reason why they came to the meeting. Mostly they were interested in new information and knowledge about the environment and they did it out of curiosity. The facilitator appreciated that most of the participants were already very active in public life, involved in many associations and had very rich experience in public participation, local community development and organising cultural, environmental and other events for the benefit of the public. Almost half of the participants also had some international relations and connections in the field they were engaged in.

After the personal introductions, the facilitator continued with the general introduction of the CIRAN project, explained the format of the focus group, three key issues and rules of focus group. Participants read and signed the Agreement. After participants confirmed that they understood and accepted everything, the focus group moved on to phase 2.

PHASE 2 – CORE DISCUSSION

This core phase lasted approximately 80 minutes.

At the beginning, facilitator introduced the topic of raw materials – examples of raw materials, products, key sectors and deposits. The facilitator used a short PowerPoint presentation and at the end of the introduction the organiser played a video. Besides, the facilitator gave a short description of the situation in the Czech Republic, thanks to the already running research project “Rock environment and raw materials” and available publications (Starý, 2022).

On the one hand, the participants were attentive, but on the other hand, several stronger personalities repeatedly redirected the discussion to other topics that were less relevant and helpful for the goals of the discussion. The facilitator had to bring them back to the core of the discussion throughout the meeting. In general, the facilitator kept discussion with participants over the three main topics, but sometimes participants found new connections beyond the prescribed topics and the facilitator let them to follow the direction of the discussion over new issues, ideas and thoughts. At one stage, one participant expressed some mistrust about this project and its incentives, and the representative of the CIRAN project (Pavla Bednarikova) was asked by the facilitator to explain more about the background of the project. To sum up, the discussion showed the need to better explain and communicate what critical raw materials are, why they are important, and their impacts on society and the environment.

Topic 1 – Concept of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs)

Q1 – How familiar are you with the concept of CRMs?

In general, participants admitted that they were not very familiar with raw materials and tended to stick to topics closer to their educational or professional background. Despite this, they were interested in raw material issues, open to new information to broaden their general knowledge and tried to make a connection between what they already knew and new information.

After being stimulated by the facilitator, what they know about raw materials, products, countries of extraction, they tend to first connect raw materials with their background or personal experiences. For example, farmers associated it with soil – as a natural resource threatened by depletion due to irresponsible farming techniques; several participants mentioned personal experiences with threats to underground drinking water resources due to the plans for expansion of sandy gravel extraction nearby.

After a better clarification, they started to recall information about raw material, especially in connection with their personal needs (mobile phones, PC, tablets, etc.).

“Generally I guess elements that are put into cell phones and there's not a lot of them, cobalt, iridium, or batteries.”

Participants were surprised by the range of commodities (they mostly only mentioned lithium and cobalt) and by range of products or sectors where they are used. They were surprised by the wide scale of products

used in medicine, defence, space research. In general, they understood that the raw materials are quite important and quite rare.

"It's the kind of raw material that we desperately need."

Participants were also aware of some geo-political realities and the fact that most deposits are located in third countries and that Europe is dependent on imports. They also perceived environmental and social injustices in these countries. They estimated the location of deposits to be mainly in China, Australia, South America and African countries.

"And we're still relying actually on those third world countries to be there somewhere."

"Which we depend on at the moment, for example, as an import."

"It seems to me that we do not consider individually that there are other interests of other powers, that the European Union is small compared to China or America. Secondly, we do not even consider the fact that, for example, mining takes place in poor conditions, child labour, etc. But I think I'm going beyond that."

Some participants mentioned the negative circumstances of the short life span of current electronic devices and the unfair treatment with electronic waste, such as import to third countries, partial recycling and instead of proper disposal of the remaining waste, burning it in the open air. Many participants pointed out the necessity of slow consumption and reduction of demands in many aspects of human life.

"And then the other problem I see is that what we import from that world, we make here, those appliances don't last much longer. Like my first laptop lasted 6 years, no other laptop has lasted that long. Most of the time it's like two or three years and it just breaks down and is beyond repair."

Q2 – What are your thoughts on potential outcomes if Europe did refrain from producing its own Critical raw materials in the next 20 years? Conversely, what if Europe initiates production instead?

In general, the participants tended not to solve the issue of raw material extraction, but rather to return to the core of the problem – they questioned the real need for these materials and in which strategic sectors they are needed. Instead of discussing these complicated and abstract geopolitical circumstances (the orientation of Europe in the next 20 years), they preferred to discuss concrete issues, personal experiences in lifestyles and consumer society. They reiterated the need to slow down consumption, to be modest and to respect the environment. They were disgusted by the current orientation of the consumer society, the faster exchange of everyday products, etc.

"There's this tendency to always have something new. And it's about the electronics, the electronic novelties... Most of us don't do it here. But a lot of people go that way with the fast consumption. So slow down the consumption behavior."

After being reminded by the facilitator to return to the topic, the participants mentioned the need for good international relations with resource-rich countries, the need to get rid of a certain "colonial" perspective and the need for reciprocal and mutually beneficial relations.

In the case of a possible European initiative, they mostly agreed that exploration and research should be stepped up. However, most of them were not willing to accept the possibility of opening new quarries

anywhere (not only in protected areas), but suggested other alternatives and solutions: such as using products only when necessary, searching for alternatives and substitution, protection of (all) natural resources, ensuring longer life of products, and strong focus on circular economy, including recycling.

Most participants strongly favoured the possibility of reopening closed quarries (brownfields), arguing that the main reason for their closure was mostly economic and limited knowledge at the time. New, more effective and less costly mining methods could be developed using current knowledge and innovative technologies.

Although participants did not put much faith in policy, including EU strategy, they accept that there is an urgent need for strong state and EU states control in the area of raw materials, understood as strategic raw material, that is motivated by concerns about potential corporate abuse and loss of control over the flow of critical raw materials and by ensuring material self-sufficiency. In particular, they emphasised the need for negotiations between EU countries on specific locations for the reopening of new quarries – in order to be effective on a European scale.

Q3 – What are your reflections on the dilemma between the need for environmental protection and the need to ensure socio-economic resilience?

The discussion on this issue was very diverse and included even some quite radical statements, as several participants were sceptical about any reasonable solution to this dilemma, claiming that people cannot learn from their mistakes. Some participants suggested banning marketing, advertising and the general orientation of society towards unnecessary consumption.

“There is just one Earth. It's not that Europe is separate from the rest of the world. And the only solution, I think, is maybe some kind of complete blackout. I really think so. Until people learn not to be greedy.”

“So let's ban advertising, let's ban the unnecessary production of absolutely every single thing that I, when I go to the store, I don't even understand who's buying it and why. A million things that don't even need to be produced.”

Others recommended strict control over the extraction of raw materials and the need to ask whether it is really needed and in what quantity. The less extraction, for necessary purposes only, the better.

“We should first of all say whether we really need the element that is there. And, for example, in terms of health, the health sector needs a lot of materials - so there I will say ok, the health sector needs it.”

Topic 2 – Mining in Environmental Protected Areas

Q4 – What do you know about the relationship between mining and communities nearby?

Participants recollected various examples of mining in communities nearby or even in the whole of the Czech Republic. They also remember the situation in the then communist regime and the unscrupulous attitude of communist government towards communities and environment.

Participants recalled again the “water” issue in nearby municipality Ostrožská Nová Ves and Uherský Ostroh where extension of sand gravel is planned and strong community protest have been taking place recently.

Local inhabitants and municipalities worried about the deteriorating quality and decreasing amount of underground drinking water in wider area and gained some political support. They also remember the existence of small-scale deposits of oil and gas in nearby areas.

One participant appreciated that they are quite “lucky” that in the White Carpathians PLA no important deposits of raw material have been found. They only knew about former quarries of various kind of rock for the need of the construction sector. Currently, most of these quarries are closed and have been left to evolve naturally. One participant appreciated a different approach from the past, when protection focused on artificial, costly recultivations.

“So to respect the conditions of nature conservation, nowadays it's being thought of differently, not that it's to be returned to the original state... now it's being left like that, and different water bodies evolve naturally...”

Q5 – Would you be willing to accept a mining activity in a protected area in your region if it meant that it would help with the security of supply?

Again, participants tend to connect mining activity mainly with natural sources they were familiar with.

For example, “soil” issue in agriculture was mentioned by one participant, especially from the point of view that there is no need to extract phosphorus, because soil is full of this and there is only need to apply agronomical measures how to utilise it by plants. Attention was given not only to the protection of soil, but even to its improvement (regenerative agriculture).

“Does it make sense to mine phosphorus? No, because there is an excess of phosphorus in the Czech soil. During communism, too much phosphorus was added to the soil, it was imported from communist friendly countries (for example Morocco). Phosphorus has the property that you put, for example, 100 kg per hectare, but the plant needs 1 kg of it and the other 900 kg stays there. And there are technologies where you can release that phosphorus with the right plant choice. Phosphorus is needed for agricultural crops.”

Again, participant expressed the need to apply preventive approach. Instead of allowing new quarries, they focus on prevention, even though they know how much raw materials are needed in many strategic and critical sectors.

“If there is an opportunity to mine phosphorus in the country, I will say that we don't need phosphorus because instead of destroying the Carpathians to mine phosphorus, we can do it through measures of getting it out of the agricultural land where it is stored. And this is how we can ask about the other elements – do we need cobalt? There are possible deposits here, the health sector will leave a certain percentage (10%), but here we are again, the circular economy is needed.”

Finally, participants stressed that more feasible is to reopen already used and destroyed localities, compared to opening new deposits.

One participant mentioned initial negotiations among a private mining firm, state administration of the White Carpathians PLA and representatives of affected municipality regarding re-opening of a new quarry. This case is worth observing because it could serve as an interesting case study about negotiation between the mining

industry and local community about specifying, accepting or denying potential conditions of extraction in future.

“...then across the hill an opening new part of Bučnik quarry is being considered. Only a few meetings have already taken place... we will see if it will be opened. It is currently being discussed what should be observed if the mine is reopened. For example, if there's a forest, cutting it down and leaving bushes is absolutely perfect for some species, for example, for some butterfly species. Then if you have those steep walls, then there's also some rare plants, succulents...”

Topic 3 – Politics, policies and public perspectives

Q6 – Do you think public opinion accurately reflects challenges and positive aspects of mining of critical raw materials?

Participants were not able to answer this question adequately, but were aware of the potential environmental impacts of mining. Some participant recognised difference of environmental burden among different raw materials.

“That is the stone mining, with the raw materials it is a whole different thing. Okay, half the mountain will disappear, but actually the environment won't be destroyed that much. A lot of other minerals have the disadvantage that you mine the whole mountain, then you process it in a complicated way and you have 1 kg of the resulting raw material, but a huge amount of heap, actually waste, which cannot be put back into the landscape.”

Q7 – Are you aware of any European, national, and local policies relevant to critical raw materials?

Participants did not know much about strategic materials relevant to critical raw materials, but they remembered other strategic materials like the Green Deal, CAP etc. They pointed out the low comprehension among ordinary people, too much bureaucracy, and that ordinary people do not understand the European strategic plans well. They pointed out that although these strategic plans have good intentions, without good understanding and acceptance of the need, they can be misused or abused.

“It seems to me that there is a bubble in the EC that cannot explain these things at all, as the colleague said. Look at how the Green Deal turned out, well that's hell ...”

“For example in the field of agriculture something is approved, there are decrees and implementing regulations, and it's very difficult, people don't understand it ... and in the end it turns against the intention and those farmers are suddenly against the Green Deal and the European Union...”

Q8 – Do you feel that people are included enough in decision making when it comes to deciding about exploration or mining of Critical raw materials?

Participants generally agreed that local people and stakeholders have the best knowledge of the situation in their region and have the right to comment and participate in the decision-making process on resource extraction plans.

Local people are also interested in the impact on the local economy, the environment and future regional development. They consider it important that local interests are taken into account.

“Setting the conditions of operation, quarries are usually on the edge of the municipality, usually the municipality has to set some limits, for example it has to set the traffic carrying capacity etc...”

Participants stressed the need for proper discussion with local community representatives about the conditions of extraction, the inclusion of externalities, compensation and protection of the local community. They stress the need for some kind of control mechanism over the extraction and the best option is to create a consortium/association in which local stakeholders are members and can influence the process of negotiation and decision making.

“For example, in Dambořice, when they started extracting oil there, they probably had some agreements on the basis that the village suddenly blossomed materially – infrastructure, sidewalks, investments in culture, and so on, so it's a kind of compensation, it's logical and this is how it should be, of course, because on the one hand the people lose something, but for the money, if they get any, something should be built there, at least in the medium term, that would be beneficial for the local community.”

They also emphasised that it is important who represents the local community to ensure that the community works well.

“I think it's essential that the local communities themselves work well, that they have mayors who can think about these things not just locally, but globally, just balancing the two more broadly and looking at it from different perspectives. It's important that the people in those communities take an interest in those things, in what's happening in their areas, long term and continuously, and that they don't get brainwashed by advertising, but it's terribly difficult to change that...”

PHASE 3 – CONCLUSION

The facilitator appreciated that the participants were open-minded and during the meeting they came to some surprising conclusions, tended to think backwards all the time, went back to the basics, pushed for it and came up with new things that were not really in the propositions/pattern.

One participant mentioned statement of compatriot:

“What's in the earth let it be in the earth, God put it there.”

The participants mostly expressed that the meeting was very fruitful and they had the opportunity to hear new information, but it rather supported their rather pessimistic approach and worries about the future development of society.

KEY FINDINGS

- **Participants were not very familiar** with the raw materials and tend to stick to topics that are closer to their educational or professional background.
- Despite the first point, the **participants were interested in the issues of raw materials**, open to new information to broaden their general knowledge and sought to make connections between what they already knew and new information.
- In general, **participants maintained a very critical attitude towards the current state of the environment, society** and social processes (including public participation, self-governance, elections and legal systems, national and European authorities), and worried about the future, and this influenced their approach to the discussion. Participants pointed out **social and environmental injustice** in current geo-political and economic system.
- **Most participants gave priority to the principle of prevention and caution** before taking any action that could potentially harm or negatively affect the local community and the environment.
- Participants were sensitive to environmental and societal issues, suggesting the important role of **environmental education, raising public awareness and voluntary modesty and humility**.
- Most of the participants **were not willing to accept the possibility of opening new quarries in any location** (not only in protected areas), instead they **suggested other alternatives and solutions**: such as using products only when necessary, search for alternatives, substitution of raw materials, conservation of (all) natural sources, slow consumption, ensuring longer lifespan of products, and strong focus on circular economy, including recycling.
- Participants **were not prepared to accept that it is necessary to open up new mining areas**, even though they know how much raw materials are needed in many strategic and critical sectors (i.e. medicine, research, IT, defence).
- **Most participants rather accepted the possibility of reopening already closed quarries** (brownfields) arguing that the main reason for their closure was mostly economic and at that time limited knowledge. New, more effective and less costly mining methods could be developed using current knowledge.
- **Only a minority of participants accepted the possibility of opening new mining areas, and then only under very strict conditions**: they preferred at least **strong state or better EU control**, proper **discussion with representatives of the local community** about the conditions of mining, inclusion of **externalities, compensations** and **protection of the local community**.
- The use of strong state and EU control was motivated by **concerns about potential corporate abuse and loss of control over the flow of critical raw materials**, and ensuring **raw material self-sufficiency**.
- On local level, there is a need for some **kind of control mechanism** over the extraction and the best option is to create a **consortium/association** in which **local stakeholders** are members and can **influence the process of negotiation and decision making**
- Discussion showed the **need to better explain and communicate** what critical raw materials are, why they are important, and their impacts on society and the environment.

THE KEY HIGHLIGHTS FROM THE WHOLE DISCUSSION

- **PRIORITY SHOULD BE GIVEN TO ANY ALTERNATIVE TO OPENING NEW QUARRIES**
- **THE RE-OPENING OF ALREADY CLOSED QUARRIES IS STRONGLY RECOMMENDED**

- IN CASE OF RE-OPENING OF QUARRIES, STRONG STATE AND LOCAL COMMUNITY CONTROL IS NEEDED
- ELIMINATION OF THE ROLE OF BUSINESS IN CASE OF STRATEGIC RAW MATERIALS TO PREVENT MISUSE AND LOSS OF CONTROL OVER THE PROCESS
- STRATEGIC MATERIAL SHOULD BE UNDERSTANDABLE TO ORDINARY PEOPLE
- NEED TO BETTER EXPLAIN AND COMMUNICATE THE ISSUE

Additional notes about the discussion

Discussion showed the need to better explain and communicate what critical raw materials are, why they are important, and their impacts on society and the environment.

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APPENDIX – Invitation Email (Czech language)

Předmět: Pozvánka na fokusní skupinu projektu CIRAN

Jménem konsorcia projektu CIRAN se na vás obracím s pozvánkou k účasti na diskusi ve fokusní skupině. Ta se bude věnovat tématům ochrany přírody a také globální energetické, průmyslové, hospodářské a společenské transformaci. Diskuse nám pomůže zjistit více o tom, jaké názory na dané témata mají místní obyvatelé a jak se k nim staví společnost. Názor evropských občanů je zásadní pro to, aby budoucí změny politik v tomto ohledu byly v souladu s očekáváním a potřebami veřejnosti, proto je těmito diskusemi chceme zahrnout do debaty. V rámci připravovaných konzultací s veřejností budou uspořádány diskuse v několika evropských zemích, kde vždy budou na názory dotázáni místní obyvatelé, kteří žijí v blízkosti nějakého chráněné přírodní oblasti, kde ale v současné době neprobíhá těžba kritických surovin.

Právě vás zveme (na základě doporučení VIS Bílé Karpaty / reprezentujete Veřejnou správu - místní skupinu, jejíž názor je pro tuto debatu důležitý / neboť se o dané téma zajímáte a věříme, že byste k němu měl co sdílet). Vaše názory jsou pro diskusi velmi důležité, proto věříme, že naše pozvání zvážíte a budete s účastí souhlasit. Vašich názorů,

O projektu CIRAN

CIRAN je výzkumný projekt financovaný Evropskou unií v rámci programu *Horizont Evropa*, a jeho cílem je shromáždit poznatky, které budou sloužit jako podklad pro tvorbu politik v rámci takzvané evropské „Green deal“.

Za tímto účelem v rámci projektu CIRAN mimo jiné zjišťujeme názory evropských občanů na otázku, která je důležitá pro globální energetickou a klimatickou transformaci, a sice snížení závislosti na zemích mimo Evropskou unii, zejména pokud jde o získávání surovin pro tuto transformaci nezbytných, protože to je klíčové pro zachování evropské demokracie a aktuálního životní úrovně místních obyvatel.

CIRAN proto bude tento výzkum provádět v pěti evropských zemích (Portugalsko, Francie, Slovensko, Itálie a Česká republika). V každé zemi se do června 2025 uskuteční dvě události – fokusní skupina a veřejná diskuse.

Podrobnosti o fokusní skupině

Datum: 20. 6. 2024

Čas: 16.00 až 18.00

Umístění: Panský dvůr 664, přednáškový sál, 698 01 Veselí nad Moravou

Účel a program:

Cílem fokusní skupiny je nashromáždit názory účastníků na téma kritických nerostných surovin (Critical raw materials) a jejich získávání. Účastníci budou diskutovat o rovnováze mezi ochranou životního prostředí a socioekonomickou odolností, o závislosti na dovozu suroviny nebo jejich lokálním získávání, o osobních zkušenostech a obavách, dopadech na životní prostředí a komunitu, rozhodovacích procesech i o zapojování občanů do těchto rozhodovacích procesů. Zajímají nás vaše názory a zkušenosti týkající se těchto témat, vše bude moci sdílet s naším organizačním týmem, ve kterém budou zástupci Vzdělávacího a informačního střediska Bílé Karpaty, o.p.s.

Vzhledem k tomu, že se jedná o výzkumnou aktivitu, bude z diskuse ve fokusní skupině pořizován audiozáznam. Nicméně všechny informace získané od účastníků v diskusi zůstanou anonymní a budou použity výhradně pro účely projektu CIRAN.

Potvrzení účasti

Prosíme, potvrďte svůj zájem o účast v diskusi odpovědí na tento email.

V případě jakýchkoli dalších dotazů se obraťte na organizátory na Marie Petrů, na e-mail petru@bilekarpaty.cz nebo kontaktní telefonní číslo 736682614.

Váš názor je pro nás nesmírně cenný, proto předem děkujeme za zvážení účasti.

Děkujeme vám za váš čas a pozornost.

S pozdravem,

Marie Petrů, DiS.

Vzdělávací a informační středisko Bílé Karpaty, o.p.s.

sídlo: nám. Bartolomějské 47

doručovací adresa: Panský dvůr 664

698 01 Veselí nad Moravou

PUBLIC DIALOGUE REPORT

Buchlovice – Czech Republic

Vladimír Šácha

Education and information center Bílé Karpaty

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is divided into the following sections:

Introduction briefly describes the objectives of the public dialogue and the heterogeneity of the participants.

Local context presents the White Carpathian Protected Landscape Area in its various aspects as an area that could be affected by the extraction of critical raw materials.

Methodology describes the selection of participants of the public discussion. Furthermore, details of the location and how the results were evaluated are provided.

Participant profile shows anonymised key characteristics of the public discussion participants in graphical and tabular form.

Key findings: This section presents general findings, including direct quotes from each discussion group. In addition, the results of the voting on the statements that emerged from the discussions are presented.

INTRODUCTION

The public discussion took place on 14 November 2024 in Hotel Buchlov as part of the 2024 Carpathian Convention Stakeholders Meeting. It was attended by 40 people from different sectors (representatives of ministries, regional and local administrations, protected areas administrations, NGOs, students of ecological studies - secondary school and university levels - , foresters and others) and different regions of the Czech Republic related to the White Carpathians and affected by the topics of the CIRAN project.

The aim was to introduce the CIRAN project and its focus to the participants through introductory presentations. The subsequent objective was to obtain feedback and opinions from the participants of the discussions on the topic of critical resource extraction.

LOCAL CONTEXT

Where

Bílé Karpaty (The White Carpathians) are located in the eastern part of the Czech Republic, on the border with Slovakia. It is part of two administrative regions (the Zlín Region and the Jihomoravský/South Moravia Region).

Biologically and environmentally it is an extremely valuable area. In 1980 Bílé Karpaty were designated a Protected Landscape Area (PLA) and in 1996 a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. The protected area covers 715 km². The main object of protection here are species-rich meadows with abundance of orchids. In the area of Velké Javořina (the highest peak of the Bílé Karpaty - 970 m above sea level) and around the Vlárský průsmyk (the Vlára River Pass) there are extensive natural forests.

Figure 1: Location of the Bílé Karpaty PLA within the Czech Republic

Figure 2: The Bílé Karpaty PLA

Approximately 80 thousand inhabitants live in the municipalities whose cadastre extends into the Bílé Karpaty Protected Landscape Area. In the affected part of the territory of the Zlín Region it is about 62

thousand inhabitants and in the part of the territory of the South Moravia Region about 18 thousand inhabitants.

In the vicinity of the PLA there are larger towns - Zlín (the regional town), Otrokovice, Uherské Hradiště, Uherský Brod, Veselí nad Moravou, and Hodonín, which provide additional employment opportunities and services to the inhabitants of the Bílé Karpaty.

The largest town within the territory of the Bílé Karpaty Protected Landscape Area is Slavičín, with 6,200 inhabitants. Other towns of comparable size are Valašské Klobouky, Bojkovice, Brumov-Bylnice, Luhačovice, and Strážnice. Industrial production is also concentrated here (e.g. the arms industry in Bojkovice, the shoe industry in Slavičín, the construction industry in Strážnice, the automotive industry in Velká nad Veličkou), together with service centres and job opportunities. Most of the settlements are medium and small villages and the landscape is predominantly agricultural.

In the vicinity of the Bílé Karpaty Protected Landscape Area, the D55 motorway is under construction, specifically the section between Otrokovice and Moravský Písek. There are 4 border crossings on the border with Slovakia - Javorník, Strání, Starý Hrozenkov, and Vlárský průsmyk. There are also several railway lines in the territory of the PLA - line No. 343 runs from Strážnice through Veselí nad Moravou to Javorník, and Velká nad Veličkou, line No. 341 runs from Uherské Hradiště to Luhačovice, Bylnice, and Vlárský průsmyk, line No. 283 runs from Bylnice through Valašské Klobouky to Horní Lideč.

Figure 3: Characteristic landscape of the southern part of the Bílé Karpaty (Čertoryje Nature Reserve)

Geology of the White Carpathians

The bedrock of the Bílé Karpaty consists of flysch. It is an alternation of mainly sandstone and clay layers. In the Mesozoic era, sand and clay were deposited in the form of massive sinkholes at the bottom of what was then the sea. In the Tertiary period, during the folding of the Alps, these layers were lifted to form the present mountain ranges.

The flysch layers give rise to numerous landslips and landslides, which affect hydrological conditions, vegetation and land use.

In the Tertiary period, the central part of the Bílé Karpaty (around Bojkovice, Bánov, Komňa and Starý Hrozenkov) experienced volcanic activity and the formation of andesite and basalt deposits. These rocks were mined in the past and, in the case of the Bučník and Bzová quarries, are still being mined. These quarries are also associated with the occurrence of the minerals galena, pyrite, sphalerite, wulfenite, and cinnabarite. The volcanic activity is also connected with the occurrence of mineral springs, especially in the vicinity of Luhačovice (the largest spa in the Moravia part of the Czech Republic).

Figure 4: Bučník quarry

There are a number of small inactive quarries in the PLA which were used in the past for the extraction of building stone - sandstone. There are also remnants of peat mining, which was used for the production of fired clay bricks. At present there is active mining only near Komňa (Bučník, Bzová - andesite).

Glass sand is also found locally. There used to be glassworks in Sidonia in Vlárský průsmyk (the Vlára Pass) and in Hutě in Moravské Kopanice near Žitková. At present there is a working glassworks in the village of Strání-Květná. Glass has been produced here since 1794, making it one of the oldest glassworks in the Czech Republic.

To a lesser extent, raw materials for the production of lime were processed in the PLA, as evidenced by some of the names of the villages - Vápenice (near Starý Hrozenkov in Moravské Kopanice) and Vápenky (near Nová Lhota in Hornácko).

There are also oil and gas deposits in the immediate vicinity of the PLA (Hluk and its surroundings), but they are not currently being exploited. The nearest active extraction of these raw materials is located in the vicinity of Kyjov and Hodonín, already outside the boundaries of the PLA (15-20 km away).

Figure 5: Geology of the Bílé Karpaty PLA. 1 – Luhačovice mineral springs, 2 – Nezdenice mineral spring, 3 – Bučník quarry, 4 – Bzová quarry, 5 – oil and gas deposit, 6 – Strání-Květná glassworks.

METHODOLOGY

The event was organised by the Bílé Karpaty Education and Information Centre, o.p.s. (hereinafter referred by the Czech name VIS BK), a non-profit organisation that has long been involved in the interpretation of the natural, historical and cultural heritage of Bílé Karpaty. It runs environmental programmes in schools, conducts guided field trips, participates in the preparation of conceptual documents for the development of sustainable tourism in the region, and also implements projects focused on practical nature conservation.

Preparation of the Public Discussion

Participants of the 2024 Carpathian Convention Stakeholders Meeting were invited to the public discussion. All participants had a professional relationship or were interested in the Bílé Karpaty PLA and knew at least part of the area in detail. The discussion group was also very heterogeneous in terms of profession and age - there were representatives of state administration, regional government funded organisations, NGOs, local farmers, students. The total number of participants was 40 (36 direct discussion participants and 4 facilitators). The facilitators were Pavla Hládková (CIRAN project), Eliška Rolfová (Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic) and Marie Petrů and Vladimír Šácha (VIS BK).

Location and Timing

The public discussion took place on 14 November 2024 at 6:30 p.m. at Hotel Buchlov (Polesí 297, Buchlovice, Czech Republic) conference hall with the necessary equipment (beamer, laptop...).

6:30 – 6:45 pm: Introduction (welcoming of participants, introduction of the presenters and facilitators, project presentation including its goals, description and justification of different parts of the public discussion)

6:45 – 7:15 pm: Informative session (showing of a video about critical raw materials, presentation of the background information on the topic and short discussion on the information given).

7:15 – 8:00 pm: Discussion (division of the participants into 4 groups, discussion of the presented questions and written and recording of the conversations)

8:00 – 8:15 pm: Break for the participants, preparation of the minutes by the facilitators and formulation of the main messages.

8:15 – 8:25 pm: Decision-making session (presentation of the formulated statements and exploratory vote)

8:25 – 8:30 pm: Acknowledgements and closing

Data analysis

In each discussion group (see below: Phase 2 - Deliberation Phase), the facilitator noted the findings of the participants on a paper flipchart. The sound recordings were only taken as a backup, in case a point recorded on the flipchart needed to be clarified. The group of four facilitators then evaluated the findings and presented the results to all participants during the final group discussion.

PARTICIPANTS PROFILE

In terms of gender representation, it was a very balanced group, see the attached chart.

Figure 6: Gender distribution of the participants

In terms of the representation of different groups of participants, representatives of the state administration (45%) and NGOs (35%) were the most represented.

Figure 7: Groups of participants

Table 1. General profile of the participants

person*	sex*	Notes*
F1	f	NGO, environmental geography
F2	f	director of a NGO, information and education in the field of natural and cultural heritage
F3	f	state administration, department of international conventions
F4	m	NGO, information and education in the field of natural and cultural heritage
P1	m	state administration, regional office of the PLA administration
P2	m	director of a NGO, nature protection
P3	m	state administration, regional office of the PLA administration
P4	m	student of ecology, secondary school level
P5	f	NGO, wildlife conservation
P6	f	NGO, information and education in the field of natural and cultural heritage
P7	f	state administration, nature conservation officer
P8	m	state administration, nature and landscape conservation officer
P9	m	state administration, director of a regional office of the PLA administration
P10	m	state administration, department of environmental and organic agriculture
P11	f	state administration, department of environmental and organic agriculture
P12	f	public institution, cultural heritage
P13	f	public institution, cultural heritage

person*	sex*	Notes*
P14	m	NGO, lecturer of environmental education
P15	m	state administration, forest management
P16	f	student of ecology, secondary school level
P17	m	NGO, information and education in the field of natural and cultural heritage
P18	m	state administration, regional office of the PLA administration
P19	m	private organic farmer
P20	f	state administration, international protected areas coordinator
P21	f	state administration, forest management
P22	f	NGO, nature and landscape protection
P23	m	public institution, forest ecology
P24	f	NGO, natural and cultural heritage
P25	f	NGO, natural and cultural heritage
P26	f	student of ecology, secondary school level
P27	m	Student of ecology, university level
P28	f	state administration, nature and landscape conservation officer
P29	m	NGO, nature and landscape protection
P30	m	public institution, researcher
P31	m	state administration, department of nature conservation
P32	m	NGO, nature and landscape protection
P33	m	student of ecology, secondary school level
P34	f	state administration, department of the environment
P35	f	NGO, interpretation of local heritage
P36	m	state administration, international treaties coordinator

* P = participant, F = facilitator; f = female, m = male; NGO – non-governmental organisation

KEY FINDINGS

PHASE 1 - INFORMATIVE PHASE

At the beginning, Pavla Hládková (CIRAN project) together with Marie Petrů (VIS BK) presented the CIRAN project and the main issues it deals with. The participants then watched a short film about critical raw materials.

The film was followed by a presentation in which M. Petrů and P. Hládková defined critical raw materials, recalled the ways of their use, talked about the short and long term perspective of their extraction and also

presented the geographical aspect of their distribution, extraction, processing and consumption (local, European, global).

The second part of the presentation focused on the aspects related to the extraction of critical raw materials, in particular the possible overlap of extraction areas with protected natural areas and the possible negative consequences resulting from this. A map of Europe showing protected areas in close proximity to critical raw materials was also presented.

Figure 8: Informative phase

PHASE 2 – DELIBERATION PHASE

During the facilitator-led discussion session, participants were divided into four groups and discussed the following 4 questions for about 45 minutes. The division into groups was not random, but followed specific rules to ensure that each group was as heterogeneous as possible (type of institution of the participants, age, gender).

- 1. What should be the European Union's approach to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?**
(control of supply – international cooperation with countries outside Europe – competition within the EU – where to allow extraction)
- 2. Does anything need to change within the EU to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?**
(quality of life – stability – economic and technological development – geopolitical independence – environmental standards)

3. Should we allow the possible extraction of critical raw materials also in protected areas? If so, under what conditions? If not, what are the main reasons? (What are the criteria for protecting natural values – what are acceptable extraction technologies – what is "absolutely not permissible").

4. How do you see the future of the critical raw materials currently being extracted? (relevance – need – volume – importance – crisis developments – new discoveries – replacements...)

Group No. 1 (facilitator: Pavla Hládková)

Question No. 1

The panellists agreed that there is a need to value the raw materials extracted within the EU and try to use them as much as possible to minimise the need for resources from other countries. However, there is also a need to ensure political security for resources extracted within the EU. Extraction should always be multi-sourced so that there is no dependence on any single source. In the event of scarcity, there could be a shortage of raw materials and therefore a reduction in production activity.

"Each case must be considered on its own merits."

A real price should be paid for the raw materials extracted. Even for raw materials that are not found in the EU, or are found in insufficient quantities and therefore have to be sourced from abroad, the moral aspect should be taken into account and efforts should be made to limit supplies from politically unsuitable countries (China, Russia...).

Question No. 2

The EU should try to regulate consumption, for example by reducing the pressure of advertising that forces consumers to consume more. The reparability of products and the associated reduction in disposable products is also important, but the panellists agreed that this would be unpopular, as it would make products more expensive and consumers would be unwilling to pay more, and overall it would mean a reduction in living standards.

"Either way, we're going to have to give something up."

The EU should also actively invest more money in science and technological development, which can solve many problems in the more distant future.

Question No. 3

On the question of whether critical raw materials should be allowed to be mined in protected areas, the group agreed that the environmental impact on a specific site needs to be assessed. The scale of the impact

will then be important. At this point, it is imperative that conservation authorities are involved in any mining permit. However, mining should definitely not take place where there is a risk of total destruction of the area. Such mining could also mean the displacement of the local population.

In general, people have a negative perception of mining, and locals who would be affected by mining will always cry foul.

On the other hand, although it may seem devastating, it can create new opportunities for nature by creating new habitats. Quarries, for example, are often islands of biodiversity.

Question No. 4

When asked about the future of critical raw materials, participants again agreed that we need to value the resources we have and try to recycle them as consistently as possible.

"Despite all this, every resource will eventually run out".

Critical resources change over time, but we will probably always need at least some of them. An alternative might be off-Earth mining on other bodies in the solar system. In any case, as long as we need critical resources, we should accept reality and not shy away from mining.

Group No. 2 (facilitator: Eliška Rolfová)

Question No. 1

On the first question, the group agreed on the need for sufficient data and, based on this, impact studies for different scenarios. The most important and immediate in this case is diversification, which consists of recycling, reducing consumption and substitution with other raw materials. It is not so important whether extraction takes place in EU countries or outside. The problems associated with extraction will always have a negative impact at the point of extraction. But if extraction takes place directly in the EU, it is at least possible to ensure stricter rules and to eliminate the effects of extraction.

The following view was also expressed without the support of the whole group:

"Recycling will never cover consumption, so further extraction is necessary. But the technology is improving."

Question No. 2

The group agreed that action to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials requires a change in mindset that can reduce over-consumption. Pressure should be put on producers to produce more sustainably and to make products that are more durable and repairable. At the same time, science and research should be encouraged. They can support technological development and the subsequent transfer of innovations into practice. It is important to build strategic partnerships abroad in places where raw materials can be extracted. Neo-colonialism should be avoided.

"We should not export the negative effects of our high consumption outside the EU".

Question No. 3

As in the first group, participants in the second group agreed that raw material extraction in protected areas needs to be assessed on a case-by-case basis and not generalised. There may be situations where there is a critical need for the raw material and there are no other options for extraction. Also, the issue of protection in a particular area may not be as fundamental. The question of balancing public interests is important. In any case, negative impacts should be eliminated as far as possible and damages should be compensated. Decisions on mining in protected areas should always take into account the views of experts in different fields.

"Although the protection of the territory is based on the public interest, other public interests may prevail."

"Too much conservation legislation means limited space for economic activity".

Question No. 4

The Group is optimistic about technological developments. This will make it possible to look for alternatives that will allow us to get rid of our dependence on raw materials, which is critical at the moment. Then there would be no need to extract them in an unsustainable way.

Group No. 3 (facilitator: Marie Petrů)

Question No. 1

On the question of the EU's approach to securing the supply of critical raw materials, the third group asked how much raw material we actually need and what we can extract from it on EU territory. Only if there is no possibility of extraction in the EU will critical raw materials have to be imported.

The group reflected on the five options for an EU approach outlined in the opening presentation and thought that all of them need to be considered, but more emphasis needs to be placed on moving towards a circular economy, on more efficient use of resources, and on drastic change in the values and consumption patterns of European society (in particular a reduction in consumerism). As in the previous two groups, the panellists agreed on the need to promote research and to look for alternatives.

Question No. 2

If changes are to be made within the EU to ensure sustainable supply, the group agreed that research must be reinvigorated and alternatives sought. At the same time, systematic awareness and education should be provided. Maximum efforts should be made for joint action between EU countries. Where extraction is carried out by global companies and producers, states must insist on their responsibility.

Question No. 3

The group agreed that every effort should be made to preserve protected areas.

"What we cannot replace, we should not be destroyed."

Hazardous chemical extraction should be avoided in mining, and mining should not take place where water resources are at risk.

Question No. 4

Discussants were optimistic about the future of critical raw materials and expressed confidence that people will understand what they do not need. In any case, the search for substitutes for current critical raw materials and new technologies is necessary.

Group No. 4 (facilitator: Vladimír Šácha)

Question No. 1

On the first question, the panellists agreed that we need to reduce our consumption, but noted that this requires education, as new technologies do not necessarily lead to this. Different options should also be considered to address mining. One is mining in the EU, so that we have at least some infrastructure in the EU. The second is recycling, which can reduce the extraction of critical raw materials, and the last option is extraction outside EU countries.

When we look for alternatives for critical raw materials, we should think about the consequences. Alternatives are not always better.

Question No. 2

The EU should always take a fair trade approach to securing supplies of critical raw materials. At the same time, the panellists would not oppose the seizure of critical raw material resources, as China does, for example, but maximum consideration should be given to good access at the point of extraction, with respect for nature, landscape, and local communities. Economic practices should be harmonised across the EU.

Question No. 3

On the issue of mining critical resources in protected areas, the group first asked itself under what circumstances it would allow mining in these areas and under what circumstances it would not.

It would be possible to allow mining in protected areas, but always under strict conditions, such as conservation technologies, provision of compensation, etc. On the other hand, the reason why mining should not take place in protected areas is, in principle, for conservation reasons. Therefore, mining companies should try to look for resources elsewhere.

In any case, the public interest needs to be assessed and the role of the state strengthened.

Question No. 4

The future of today's critical raw materials depends, among other things, on the size of the human population. However, this is not a good solution to the problems of extraction. It must be emphasised that we do not know the future consumption of critical raw materials, which depends on many factors. That is why we need to put a lot of emphasis on recycling.

Figure 9: Deliberation phase

PHASE 3 - DECISION MAKING PHASE

During the discussion, the facilitators recorded the thoughts, ideas, and suggestions expressed. The notes of all 4 facilitators were then compared, particularly in terms of similarity and interconnectedness of responses. Based on this processing, 12 statements were formulated that represented the main messages of the discussion. All participants then voted on whether they agreed or disagreed with these statements.

It is always necessary to compare results of mining and describe its impact.
for: 34; against: 0; abstentions: 1

It doesn't matter whether the extraction of critical raw materials takes place in the EU or outside the EU.
for: 17, against: 5, abstentions: 9

There needs to be support for research and science and search for alternatives.
for: 35, against: 0, abstentions: 0

Diversification of production of critical raw materials (EU, non-EU) and recycling is necessary.
for: 33, against: 0, abstentions: 2

It is necessary to educate society to change consumer behaviour.

for: 33, against: 1, abstentions: 1

It is necessary to insist on the responsibility of global corporations, producers, and politicians.

for: 32, against: 0, abstentions: 3

It is important to build strategic partnerships while maintaining moral standards.

for: 31, against: 3, abstentions: 1

If possible, mining in protected areas should be avoided.

for: 28, against: 2, abstentions: 5

Environmental damage should be compensated (but mining can also create new habitats).

for: 27, Against: 0, abstentions: 8

Advanced (environmentally friendly) technologies should be used in mining.

for: 13, against: 11, abstentions: 11

Mining should be avoided if it means endangering water resources.

for: 34, against: 0, abstentions: 1

Abstraction needs can change over time.

for: 33, against: 0, abstention: 2

Figure 10: Decision making phase

CONCLUSIONS

- Most of the participants did not have much information about critical raw materials extraction before the meeting, but during the informative phase they showed great interest in this issue. This was then reflected in the public discussion groups, where they had very stimulating ideas and comments.
- In all the discussions it was clear that the participants understood both the need for mining of critical minerals, and that mining has negative impact on nature, landscape, and local people.
- There was a clear focus on several aspects of critical resource extraction:
 1. the careful methods used in extraction
 2. mining ideally in EU countries
 3. multi-source extraction
 4. a fair price for the raw materials extracted
- All the public groups came to the conclusion that:
 - a) we probably cannot do without critical raw materials and b) the following should be ensured for sustainable extraction without adverse effects on nature, landscape, and local communities:
 1. support for science and research
 2. awareness raising and dissemination of information
 3. search for alternatives
 4. recycling
 5. better quality repairable products with longer lifetimes.
- In the case of mining in protected areas, the participants were also in agreement. They would allow mining in such valuable areas, but always under strict conditions, using environmentally friendly technologies and respecting the values of the area. Each case would have to be assessed individually.
- In the last phase, when voting on the statements arising from the discussions, the participants were almost unanimous, with a few exceptions.

36 Annex 27 Focus group report - Baiso (Italy)

FOCUS GROUP REPORT

Baiso – Italy

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarizes findings from a focus group discussion held on 26th July 2024 in Baiso, aimed at exploring local perspectives on critical raw materials (CRMs) and their environmental and socio-economic impacts.

The report consists of several main parts:

Local Context: Baiso, with its rich natural and cultural heritage, has a history of mining, particularly in clay and ceramics, which has brought both economic benefits and environmental challenges.

Methodology: The focus group used qualitative methods, engaging participants through open-ended questions to gather insights about CRMs, environmental concerns, and local development. Discussions were recorded and analysed thematically.

Participant Profile: The group included diverse stakeholders such as local administrator and residents, environmental advocates, and industry representatives, ensuring varied perspectives on the issues discussed.

Key Findings: This section is the report's core, presenting summarized findings along with relevant quotes from participants. Participants emphasised the need to protect biodiversity and ecosystems, prioritizing environmental preservation over security of supply. While they acknowledged the economic potential of critical raw materials (CRMs), they stressed the importance of long-term sustainability over short-term gains. Additionally, there was a strong call for increased community engagement in decision-making processes related to resource extraction, underscoring the necessity for transparency and public participation.

INTRODUCTION

The focus group in the Municipality of Baiso took place on 26th July 2024. This meeting was organised as part of the CIRAN project, an EU-funded initiative focused on developing, testing, and validating inclusive approaches to systemic policy-making that balance the need for critical raw materials (CRMs) with environmental protection in sensitive areas. Baiso was chosen due to its location in the Apennines, a region known for its rich natural heritage and proximity to several environmentally protected zones.

Two main objectives were defined for the focus group in Baiso. Firstly, the focus was to gather a range of perspectives from local citizens and stakeholders regarding CRM extraction in protected areas. Secondly, the findings from this session will help shape an upcoming public meeting that will be held in Baiso, aimed at expanding discussions and fostering broader community engagement. The insights gathered in Baiso will inform the agenda and discussion points for this larger meeting, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of public opinion on mining activities in protected areas.

The data from this focus group will later be compared with those collected from other case study areas involved in the CIRAN project (Portugal, Czechia, Slovakia and France). By integrating the findings from Baiso with the wider European context, the project aims to develop governance models that effectively incorporate public perspectives into decision-making processes for sustainable mining practices in protected areas.

The results of the Baiso focus group are outlined in the following chapters, with an emphasis on key findings and strategic recommendations for future action.

LOCAL CONTEXT

The focus group was organised in Baiso, a small municipality located in the province of Reggio Emilia, in the Emilia-Romagna region of northern Italy. Positioned on the hills of the Reggio Apennines, Baiso lies between the provinces of Modena and Reggio Emilia, offering panoramic views of both the Po Valley and the Apennine mountain range. The municipality is known for its scenic landscapes, rich history, and strong connection to its natural environment.

Baiso's history is rooted in the Middle Ages, closely linked to the rule of Countess Matilde di Canossa, a significant figure in the region's medieval politics. The town's strategic location played a role in the power struggles between the Papacy and the Holy Roman Empire, leaving a legacy visible today through landmarks like the Castello di Baiso.

Inhabitants and Population

Baiso has a population of approximately 3,200 inhabitants. The local community is characterized by a rural lifestyle, with a close connection to agriculture and small-scale industries. Like many rural Italian towns, Baiso has faced challenges related to population decline, particularly among younger generations who tend to move to larger cities for education and employment opportunities. Despite these challenges, the town remains an active and cohesive community, with a strong sense of local identity and pride in its cultural heritage.

Economy

The economy of Baiso is predominantly based on agriculture and small-scale local businesses. Farming, particularly the cultivation of wine grapes, olives, and chestnuts, plays a central role in the town's economy. The region is also known for the production of Parmigiano Reggiano cheese, which contributes to both local economic activity and the town's culinary reputation. Other agricultural products include grains, fruits, and vegetables.

In recent years, rural tourism has become an increasingly important economic sector. Visitors are drawn to Baiso for its natural beauty, historical significance, and tranquil environment. This has led to the development of agritourism, with local farms offering hospitality and cultural experiences to visitors.

Natural Parks and Protected Areas

Baiso is located near several significant natural protected areas. These include:

MAB UNESCO site, focal point of the Euro-Mediterranean climatic frontier. This characteristic has determined, together with the geological heritage and other factors, the establishment of a complex ecological and cultural mosaic, which in turn is the basis for the evolution of the landscape.

Rupe di Campotrera Natural Reserve, situated 15-20 km west of Baiso near Canossa. This reserve protects a unique geological formation and serves as a significant natural habitat for local flora and fauna.

Parco Regionale dei Sassi di Roccamalatina, about 20 km to the north, known for its striking sandstone formations and rich biodiversity. It is a popular destination for hikers and nature enthusiasts.

Parco Nazionale dell'Appennino Tosco-Emiliano, a national park located approximately 35-40 km south of Baiso, which protects the biodiversity and landscapes of the Apennine mountain range. The park is a designated UNESCO Biosphere Reserve, highlighting its ecological importance.

These natural areas, along with the local hilly terrain, play a crucial role in preserving biodiversity and offering opportunities for sustainable tourism and outdoor activities. They also form part of the broader Collina Reggiana – Terre di Matilde, a region renowned for both its historical significance and natural beauty.

In this setting, the local community of Baiso has a deep connection to its surrounding environment, where both conservation and sustainable development are key priorities. The focus group held in Baiso reflects these values, as it seeks to balance the protection of natural resources with the need for economic development, particularly in the context of critical raw material extraction in environmentally protected areas.

METHODOLOGY

This section explains the approach used to collect the insights from the Focus Group Participants.

Design of the Focus Group

The focus group in Baiso was organised through collaboration with the local municipality and with a local organization - environmental education and sustainability centre (CEAS). Initial contact was made with the organization and the mayor to discuss the project's objectives and seek assistance in identifying potential participants. A list of suitable candidates was compiled, ensuring diverse representation from the community. Invitations were sent via email, followed by phone calls to confirm attendance. Ultimately, nine participants attended the focus group.

Location and Timing

The focus group took place on 26 July 2024 in the CEAS office in Baiso . The room was set up with chairs arranged around a table a circle to foster open discussion. The meeting ran from 10:00 to 12:00, facilitated by the main facilitator, who was supported by a note-taker. Introductory words were said by the present mayor of the municipality and two representatives of the CIRAN project, Anna Chiara and Christian Marasmi.

Data analysis

After the focus group, the facilitator and organisers of the focus group held a debriefing session to reflect on the discussions and key takeaways. The meeting was audio-recorded for accuracy, and an analysis of the discussion was conducted based on the recording and notes taken during the discussion. The conversations were categorized into phases—Introduction, Core Discussion, and Conclusion—allowing for a structured analysis of the key findings and insights gathered during the focus group.

PARTICIPANTS PROFILE

The group consisted of 9 participants, with a good representation of men and women of different ages. Approximately 50% of the participants were under 40 years of age. 3 women and 6 men. One participant arrived late, but quickly caught up and participated in the discussion.

Description of participants:

- Participant 1: Mayor, involved in local political and administrative affairs.
- Participant 2: Councillor for Public Works, Urban Decoration, Urban Planning, Environment and Land Protection, responsible for urban and environmental resource management.
- Participant 3: Collaborative councillor for youth policy and culture, involved in youth policy and culture.
- Participant 4: Representative of an environmental education and sustainability centre, involved in environmental education and awareness-raising projects.
- Participant 5: Representative of an environmental education and sustainability centre, involved in environmental education and awareness-raising projects, expert of community involvement.
- Participant 6: Representative of an environmental education and sustainability centre, involved in environmental education and awareness-raising projects, expert in circular economy
- Participant 7: Citizen and geologist, expert in raw materials and natural resources.
- Participant 8: Citizen and university professor, lecturer in the engineering department, with a background in sustainable technologies.
- Participant 9: Citizen and member of an association

KEY FINDINGS

PHASE 1 – CORE DISCUSSION

This part reports the results of focus group divided in the three main topics

Q1: How familiar are you with the concept of critical raw materials? Have you ever heard of it? What do you think are critical raw materials?

Topic 1 – Concept of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs)

Summary of key points and comments

Participants' responses demonstrate a widespread understanding of the importance of critical raw materials, albeit with varying levels of detail. There is consensus on the ubiquity of these resources in everyday life and the need to raise awareness among the non-technical public. Europe's dependence on external sources, particularly China, is seen as a significant concern. The importance of these resources for modern technology and future economic development is recognised, emphasising the need for sustainable policies to secure their supply.

P1 "I am aware that critical raw materials are fundamental to our economy and technology. For example, our area has historically been involved in clay extraction for the ceramic industry. This experience has shown us the importance of natural resources for local economic development. However, we must strike a balance between the exploitation of these resources and the protection of our environment".

P2: "I believe that all of us, without realising it, use products containing critical raw materials on a daily basis."

P3 "Critical raw materials are crucial for many modern technologies, from electronic devices to renewable energy."

P4: 'I have heard about critical raw materials, and I think it is crucial to raise awareness of this issue among the non-technical public."

P5: "The fact that we have them in our hands constantly and we don't realise it is very important. We don't realise how much we exploit them and how much we need them. At the level of citizens and communities it is our role to make people realise how dependent we are on them and how much we exploit them, especially we have to make people who are not in the industry realise this."

Observations/Contextual notes

Participants showed a widespread understanding of the importance of critical raw materials. Most of them mentioned the daily use of these resources in electronic devices and the strategic importance for Europe. Furthermore, all participants showed great interest in the topic.

Q2: What do you think of the potential results if Europe refrained from producing its critical raw materials in the next 20 years? What if Europe started a production effort instead?

The participants' responses reflect a clear awareness of the risks associated with Europe's dependence on external sources for critical raw materials. If Europe does not start producing these resources internally, it may find itself in a position of geopolitical and economic vulnerability. However, domestic production also brings significant challenges, including environmental and social impacts. Participants agree on the need to invest in research and development of sustainable technologies for the extraction and processing of critical raw materials in order to ensure greater autonomy and security for Europe.

P3: "It is crucial that Europe invests in research and development of sustainable technologies for the extraction of critical raw materials. If we do not, we risk losing our economic and technological independence. The domestic production of these resources could also stimulate innovation and the creation of new jobs. However, we have to be very careful how we manage these processes to minimise negative impacts on the environment and local communities."

P5: 'Diversification of supply sources is crucial to avoid situations of crisis. If Europe does not start producing its own critical raw materials, we risk being totally dependent on third countries. This could lead to serious consequences in the event of supply disruptions. On the other hand, producing these resources internally would mean investing in new technologies and research, while ensuring greater economic and technological security.'

P1: "Recycling of these materials however is not a very easy process, it costs a lot of money also in terms of pollution: the impact of recycling could actually be negative: water used, effluents, chemicals, etc."

P6: "I think it is important to consider the geopolitical context. If Europe does not start producing its own critical raw materials, it could find itself at a disadvantage compared to other economic powers. China, for example, has invested enormously in technology and infrastructure for the extraction and processing of rare earths. If we do not do the same, we risk losing our competitiveness. On the other hand, starting to produce these resources in house would require significant investment, but could lead to greater autonomy and security."

P7: 'Politically and economically, it is essential that Europe becomes more autonomous in the production of critical raw materials. If we continue to depend on China, we could find ourselves in a very precarious situation. Domestic production would not only improve our economic security, but also create jobs and stimulate technological innovation. However, we must also consider the environmental and social impacts of these mining activities.'

P8: 'In Europe there should be a less disposable economy model, there should be the concept of repair, before recycling and especially before production from scratch. The EU should give more subsidies for start-ups that invest in repair and modularity.'

P9: 'We are a big world on a small planet. In this issue I feel more European than usual, because we have been outsourcing the production of these materials for years and we are now paying back the consequences of this. Recycling we don't have the technology needed and above all demand is growing, so there would be no need for those already extracted. Respect for environmental and social standards is very important.'

The discussion revealed a strong concern about foreign dependence and a consensus on the need to develop sustainable domestic production. Europe's dependence on China for critical raw materials and the associated

risks were highlighted. They discussed the benefits of domestic production, such as autonomy and economic security, but also recognised the environmental and social challenges.

Q3: What are your thoughts on the dilemma between the need to protect the environment and the need to ensure socio-economic resilience?

Summary of key points and comments

Participants' responses highlight the need to strike a balance between environmental protection and socio-economic resilience. Although mining activities can bring significant economic benefits, it is essential to adopt sustainable practices and advanced technologies to minimise environmental impacts. Research and development, together with policies that promote a circular economy and the involvement of local communities, are key to achieving this balance. Environmental protection and economic development should not be seen as mutually exclusive goals, but as interconnected components of a sustainable development strategy.

P4: 'The dilemma between environmental protection and socioeconomic resilience is complex, but not insurmountable. We can take an integrated approach that considers both aspects. For example, more advanced extraction technologies can reduce environmental impacts and improve efficiency. In addition, research and development can lead to new solutions to exploit natural resources in a sustainable way. We also need to promote environmental awareness and education so that everyone understands the importance of protecting our planet as we develop our economy.'

P1: 'Environmental protection must be a priority, but we must also consider the socio-economic needs of our communities. Mining can bring jobs and economic development, but it must be balanced with the conservation of ecosystems. For example, we can develop training programmes for local communities so that they can benefit from economic opportunities without compromising the environment. Furthermore, it is important to continuously monitor the environmental impacts of mining activities and take corrective measures when necessary.'

P2: 'Protecting the environment and ensuring socio-economic resilience are not mutually exclusive goals. We can develop policies that promote a circular economy, reducing dependence on new extractions and increasing recycling and reuse of resources. For example, promoting the repair and maintenance of electronic equipment can reduce the demand for new raw materials. Furthermore, it is essential to involve local communities in decision-making processes, ensuring that they have a say in activities that directly affect them.'

P5: 'Research and development are essential to find sustainable solutions. Europe has missed opportunities in the past, as in the case of solar panels, but we can recover by investing in new technologies. We must ensure that mining activities are conducted in a way that minimises negative impacts on the environment. For example, the recovery and recycling of critical raw materials can reduce the need for new extraction. However, we must be aware that even these operations are never neutral and can have significant environmental impacts.'

P6: 'The choice is always tragic; the tragedy arises when you must choose between two extremes, and the political solution is the middle one between two extremes. In our area, the historical management of these two extremes has been to exploit the quarries by exploiting the environment in the name of socioeconomics. What is left now is a great economic wealth at the level of ceramics, but also the enormous holes of the disused quarries, some of which have been restored but many have not, and now there are many settlements. So as far as the area is concerned, there is a historical awareness of what it was, the great wealth it brought, it had a payback time of 20-30 years, an economic boom that has ceased now that better performing economic materials have been found from all over the world and so ceramics here have lost their wealth. The ceramics market here survives only because of Italian labour and creativity; it does not survive because of raw materials.'

Observations/Contextual notes

Participants showed a clear understanding of the challenges of balancing economic and environmental needs, with strong support for sustainable solutions.

Topic 2 – Mining in Environmental Protected Areas

Q4: What do you know about the relationship between the mines and neighbouring communities?

Summary of key points and comments

Participants' responses reveal a consensus on the need to balance the economic benefits of mining with environmental protection and the well-being of local communities. Mining can bring economic development and jobs, but it can also cause significant environmental damage. It is crucial that local communities are informed and involved in decision-making processes. Mining activities must be planned and managed in a sustainable manner, with appropriate measures to minimise negative impacts and ensure the rehabilitation of areas after mine closure.

P1: 'Mining activities in our area, such as clay quarrying, have had a significant impact on local communities. During the period of activity, there was an economic boom that brought considerable benefits. However, these activities have also left deep environmental scars. Mining can bring economic prosperity and jobs, but we must also consider the long-term negative effects, such as the destruction of the landscape and the possible contamination of water resources. It is important that local communities are involved in decision-making processes to ensure that economic benefits are not obtained at the expense of the environment.'

P6: 'Mining can create many economic opportunities for neighbouring communities, such as new jobs and infrastructure development. However, these benefits must be balanced against potential negative impacts on the environment and quality of life. Communities must be informed and involved in decision-making processes. For example, the clay quarries in our territory have led to economic expansion, but now we must deal with the holes left by mining. This teaches us that we have to plan for the long term, considering both economic and environmental aspects.'

P7: 'Mining affects neighbouring communities in many ways. They can bring economic prosperity, but also environmental damage. It is important that mining activities are conducted in a sustainable way, with a focus on environmental protection. Local communities must be involved in the decision-making process and have a say. For example, it is crucial to monitor environmental impacts and take corrective measures when necessary. In addition, communities should be informed about the benefits and risks of mining activities.'

P1: 'Baiso is an area now in a waning phase, in the past it experienced an impressive boom, there were productive activities that came on the block. The quarries are de facto holes that have destroyed the territory. So, there must now be a far-sightedness on these issues that was lacking in the past.'

P6: 'Ecosystems are critical raw materials according to her. They have to be preserved per se, we realised with covid how important green areas are. So maybe the right way is in the middle, but you really have to take ecosystems into consideration, even if they have no economic power: forests, for example, do not bring economic value but they have a very important psychological value: and if we dig on one side then the policy has to make sure that on the other side we have irrefutable protection of the land'.

Observations/Contextual notes

The discussion highlighted the complexity of the relationship between mining and local communities, with a strong call for community involvement. Participants recognised that mining could bring economic development and jobs but can also cause significant environmental damage. They emphasised the importance of involving local communities in decision-making processes.

Topic 3 – Politics, policies and public perspectives

Q5: Would you be willing to accept mining in a protected area in your region if it meant contributing to security of supply?

Brief summary of key points and comments

Participants' responses indicate a clear awareness of the complexity and ethical implications of accepting extractive activities in protected areas. Although security of supply is recognised as an important objective, participants are unanimous in emphasising that this cannot be achieved at the expense of destroying natural heritage and biodiversity. Any decision on this should be based on solid guarantees of environmental sustainability, involvement of local communities, and rigorous environmental management and restoration plans. Transparency and public participation are seen as crucial in balancing economic needs with environmental protection.

P1: "Accepting mining in a protected area is a very sensitive issue. On the one hand, security of supply is crucial for our economy and our geopolitical independence. On the other, we have to consider the environmental impact of such activities. If we were able to ensure that extraction takes place in a sustainable manner and with minimal impact on the environment, I could be in favour. However, it is essential that there are strict controls and restoration plans to ensure that the protected area is preserved as much as possible."

P2: "It is a very difficult decision. Protected areas are vital for nature conservation and for our well-being. Accepting mining activities in these areas must be a last resort, only if there are no viable alternatives and if

there are solid guarantees of environmental sustainability. Security of supply is important, but we must be very careful about sacrificing protected areas. It is crucial to involve local communities and make sure that extraction takes place with as little impact as possible."

P3: 'Mining in protected areas should only be considered if necessary and if there are no better alternatives. Security of supply is important, but it cannot justify the destruction of valuable habitats. If highly sustainable extraction technologies and complete restoration of areas after extraction could be guaranteed, it could be considered a possibility. However, it is essential that there are clear and transparent plans to minimise the environmental impact and involve local communities."

P7: 'Protected areas are crucial for biodiversity and the quality of life of local communities. Accepting mining activities in these areas must be a well-considered decision, based on sound sustainability and environmental management plans. Security of supply is important, but it cannot be achieved at the expense of destroying protected areas. Strong involvement of local communities and the adoption of advanced technologies that ensure minimal impact on the environment is necessary."

P6: 'On the level of acceptance of mining in the home turf, the answer is obviously no. It has been seen in several situations, even just creating roads and giving us a clear picture of the level of acceptance of the distortion of one's own territory. Unfortunately, citizens no longer count for anything: multinationals and big industries create our needs and feed them, and therefore have more say on these things than we do. There is a lack of strategies and political ideas that can nurture research even in substitute areas: the real deficiency is the lack of political directions and choices that are geared towards sustainability and preserving the environment. There is also a lack of education in this regard. variable is that of prices: nobody tells industrialists not to do unethical things because they cost less, there is a lack of political will. There is also a cultural gap between countries, which corresponds to 50-60 years of development: 50-60 years ago, even here children went to the quarry to get stones, as they are doing now in many developing countries".

Observations/Contextual notes

Participants recognised that mining could bring economic development and jobs but can also cause significant environmental damage. They emphasised the importance of involving local communities in decision-making processes. The discussion highlighted the complexity of the relationship between mining and local communities, with a strong call for community involvement.

Q6: Do you think public opinion accurately reflects the challenges and positive aspects of extracting critical raw materials?

Summary of key points and comments

Participants' responses indicate that the public often does not have a complete and accurate view of the challenges and benefits associated with the extraction of critical raw materials. Communication and education on this topic are considered insufficient, leading to an unbalanced and generally negative

perception of mining. It is essential that institutions, companies and experts improve the transparency and clarity of information provided to the public, promoting a balanced understanding that considers both risks and benefits. Only with adequate and complete information can we hope to have an informed public debate and gain support for sustainable extraction policies.

P3: 'Public opinion often does not accurately reflect the complexities of extracting critical raw materials. People tend to see only the negative impacts and do not consider the benefits. It is crucial to improve communication and education on this issue so that the public can have a complete understanding of the issues involved. Only with proper information can we hope to gain public support for sustainable extraction policies.'

P7: 'I believe that the public is not adequately informed about the challenges and positive aspects of extracting critical raw materials. Discussions tend to focus on the risks and negative impacts, neglecting the economic and technological benefits. It is essential to improve communication and public education on these issues, so that people can have a balanced understanding and make informed choices. Only then can we hope to gain public support for sustainable extraction policies.'

P2: 'Many people are not aware of the complexities involved in extracting critical raw materials. They only see the environmental damage and do not consider the economic and technological benefits. It is essential to improve communication and education on this issue so that the public can understand both perspectives. Only with a complete and balanced view can we hope to have an informed and constructive public debate.'

P1: "The difficulty is to make people understand that CRMs are really needed. After that it will still be difficult to get approval, but without knowing why they are needed, in 99% of cases the public response will be negative."

P4. "The key word in this discourse on public opinion is awareness. Raise awareness that too low a price means non-economic hidden costs and raise awareness of over consumerism. What is the point of beating young people over the head with right ideas if the whole world, then gives them the opposite message. There must be a ruling class ready, but we must be ready to form the ruling class of tomorrow."

Observations/Contextual notes

Participants emphasised that the public often does not have a complete and accurate view of the challenges and benefits associated with the extraction of critical raw materials. They emphasised the need to improve communication and education on this issue.

Q7: Are you aware of European, national and local policies concerning critical raw materials?

Summary of key points and comments

Participants' responses indicate a general knowledge of European policies on critical raw materials, with a focus on the EU strategy to ensure sustainable and secure supply. However, a significant gap emerges in the awareness of national and local policies. Communication and transparency on these policies are considered insufficient, which limits the understanding and involvement of local communities in decision-making processes. It is essential to improve the dissemination of information about policies at all levels to ensure that people are informed, involved and able to actively participate in decisions that directly affect them.

P3: "I have a general knowledge of European policies on critical raw materials, but I must admit that I am not fully aware of the specific details of national and local policies. I know that the European Union has put in place strategies to reduce dependence on imports of critical raw materials by promoting recycling and sustainable use of these resources. However, I believe there is a need for more communication and transparency on these policies at all levels to ensure that local communities are also informed and involved."

P5: 'I know some of the European policies on critical raw materials, such as the European Union's raw materials strategy, which aims to ensure a sustainable and secure supply. However, information on national and local policies is less accessible. I believe there is an urgent need for more dissemination of information about these policies so that people can better understand what is being done and how they can get involved.'

P1: 'I am aware of European policies that aim to reduce the EU's dependence on imports of critical raw materials through recycling and sustainable extraction. However, regarding national and local policies, information is often fragmented and not always easily accessible. It is crucial that there is more communication and that policies are more transparent so that everyone can understand the initiatives and how they can affect local communities.'

Observations/Contextual notes

Participants had a general knowledge of European policies on critical raw materials but highlighted a significant gap in awareness of national and local policies. They emphasised the need for improved communication and transparency on these policies. The discussion highlighted the need for better dissemination of information and greater transparency at national and local level.

Q8: Do you think people are sufficiently involved in the decision-making process when it comes to deciding on the exploration or extraction of critical raw materials?

Brief summary of key points and comments

Participants' responses indicate a clear consensus that people are not sufficiently involved in decision-making processes related to the exploration and extraction of critical raw materials. Decisions are often made without adequate involvement of local communities, leading to a lack of trust and potential conflicts. It is essential to develop participatory mechanisms that allow people to be active participants in the decision-making process. Transparency and inclusiveness are crucial to ensure that decisions are balanced, sustainable and acceptable to all stakeholders. Only through active and meaningful involvement of local communities can we hope to gain public support for the sustainable exploration and extraction of critical raw materials.

P1: 'People are not sufficiently involved in decision-making processes. Decisions concerning the extraction of critical raw materials have a significant impact on local communities, but these communities are often not consulted adequately. It is important that there is a more transparent and inclusive participatory process that allows people to voice their opinions and influence decisions that affect their future and their environment.'

P4: "Often, decisions are made by experts and politicians without real dialogue with local communities. It is essential that there is greater transparency and that people have the opportunity to actively participate in decisions. This would not only improve the quality of decisions, but also increase the trust and support of local communities."

P5: "Usually, local communities are kept in the dark until decisions have already been made. This creates a sense of exclusion and frustration. It is important to develop participatory processes that involve people from the very beginning. Decisions regarding the extraction of critical raw materials must be transparent and inclusive, ensuring that all voices are heard and considered."

P2: "Many times, decisions are made without meaningful consultation with local communities. This leads to a lack of trust and conflicts between companies and communities. It is necessary to develop participation mechanisms that allow people to be active participants in the decision-making process. Only in this way can we ensure that decisions are sustainable and acceptable to all stakeholders."

P7: "Young people are not involved enough. There is a lack of battle against disinformation, decision-making processes are driven by very large and powerful structures that influence democracy. Information must be of quality."

P3: "One must learn to recognise which sources are reliable. There is a lack of desire to investigate, but there are also those who profit from trying to give wrong information. We must learn to use technology better, which young people sometimes know how to use better, they are more aware of what they have in their hands. Are we then sure that everyone should be able to decide, perhaps without knowing anything?"

Observations/Contextual notes

Participants indicated that people are not sufficiently involved in decision-making processes related to the exploration and extraction of critical raw materials. They emphasised the need to develop participatory mechanisms that enable people to be active participants in the decision-making process.

PHASE 3 - CONCLUSION

The focus group in Baiso provided a diverse range of perspectives on the extraction of critical raw materials (CRMs) and its impact on the local community. Participants demonstrated a strong understanding of the importance of these materials while also expressing concerns about Europe's dependence on external sources, particularly China. However, discussions revealed a significant level of skepticism regarding the feasibility of new mining activities in the region, mainly due to past experiences with extractive industries and their long-term negative consequences.

One of the most prominent issues raised was the **need for environmental compensation strategies**. Participants stressed that any future extractive activity must be accompanied by tangible measures to **preserve ecosystems and biodiversity**, including the creation of protected areas to counterbalance land loss. Moreover, the long-term environmental damage caused by previous mining activities, such as landscape degradation and water contamination, has led to a **general mistrust** of this industry.

From an economic perspective, while mining previously contributed to local development, the community now feels the **lack of economic diversification**. Participants emphasised the need to support other sectors such as **sustainable tourism, organic agriculture, and technological innovation** instead of relying solely on

resource extraction. There was a strong interest in alternative economic strategies that promote growth without compromising environmental sustainability.

Another key issue discussed was the **role of youth and environmental education**. While younger generations are more environmentally aware, they lack opportunities to influence decision-making processes. Additionally, participants pointed out that current environmental education efforts remain insufficient and are not properly integrated with economic and development policies.

Finally, a recurring concern was the **lack of transparency and limited public participation in decision-making**. Participants noted that in the past, decisions regarding extractive activities were made without meaningful community consultation, resulting in **distrust and opposition**. To ensure truly sustainable mining policies in the future, it is crucial to establish **open and accessible consultation processes** that actively involve local stakeholders and address their concerns throughout the planning and implementation phases.

Additional notes about de discussion

The focus group discussions reflect the ongoing dilemma between securing CRM supply and protecting both the environment and the local community's quality of life. The residents of Baiso are willing to engage in these discussions, but they demand **greater transparency, real environmental compensation, economic diversification, and a more active role for youth in decision-making**. These factors should be carefully considered in the design of future governance models for sustainable mining in protected areas.

PUBLIC DIALOGUE REPORT

Baiso (RE), Italy

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the outcomes of the public dialogue event held in **Baiso (RE), Italy, on March 29, 2025**, within the framework of the **CIRAN** project – *Crisis and Risks in the Anthropocene*, co-funded by the European Union. The event focused on the critical topic of **Critical Raw Materials (CRM)** and explored how to reconcile **environmental protection with economic, social, and technological development** through responsible extraction practices.

The event was structured in three phases:

- An **introductory session** presenting the CIRAN project and the challenges related to CRM.
- A **group activity using the role-playing methodology** “What if...?”, based on two future-oriented scenarios (*Innovazione Insulare* and *Stato Stazionario*).
- A **plenary discussion**, during which participants stepped out of their roles to formulate **shared reflections and policy recommendations**.

Each group discussed two core questions:

1. What are the key factors for a sustainable supply of CRM? Should CRM extraction be allowed in protected areas, and under what conditions?

The key findings include:

- A **shared awareness of the strategic importance** of CRM.
- A strong focus on **sustainability through recycling, repairability, and product durability**.
- The need for **greater public awareness and cultural change** to reduce overconsumption and counteract marketing-driven demand.
- A nuanced view on protected areas, advocating for **case-by-case evaluation, low-impact technologies, mandatory environmental restoration, and territorial compensations**.
- A call for **European strategic autonomy**, including ethical extraction both within and beyond EU borders, governed by **clear and enforceable standards**.

The dialogue served as a meaningful platform for community engagement, multi-perspective debate, and contribution to CIRAN’s goal of informing **resilient, inclusive, and evidence-based policy** on CRM in Europe.

INTRODUCTION

On 29th March 2025, a public dialogue was held in Baiso at the Centro Funzionale, located on Toschi Street, 53. The event was co-organised by ALDA, with session facilitation by Futour. The Emilia Romagna Region, as a CIRAN project partner, contributed the initial informative segment, together with Generator, also a CIRAN partner.

As Baiso was chosen due to its location in the Apennines, a region known for its rich natural heritage and proximity to several environmentally protected zones. 11 participants were present, although 15 registered to the event.

The data from this public dialogue will later be compared with those collected from other case study areas involved in the CIRAN project (Portugal, Czechia, Slovakia, Ireland and France). By integrating the findings from Baiso with the wider European context, the project aims to develop governance models that effectively incorporate public perspectives into decision-making processes for sustainable mining practices in protected areas.

The results of the Baiso public dialogue are outlined in the following chapters, with an emphasis on key findings and strategic recommendations for future action.

LOCAL CONTEXT

The public dialogue was organised in Baiso, a small municipality located in the province of Reggio Emilia, in the Emilia-Romagna region of northern Italy. Positioned on the hills of the Reggio Apennines, Baiso lies between the provinces of Modena and Reggio Emilia, offering panoramic views of both the Po Valley and the Apennine Mountain range. The municipality is known for its scenic landscapes, rich history, and strong connection to its natural environment.

Baiso's history is rooted in the Middle Ages, closely linked to the rule of Countess Matilde di Canossa, a significant figure in the region's medieval politics. The town's strategic location played a role in the power struggles between the Papacy and the Holy Roman Empire, leaving a legacy visible today through landmarks like the Castello di Baiso.

Inhabitants and Population

Baiso has a population of approximately 3,200 inhabitants. The local community is characterized by a rural lifestyle, with a close connection to agriculture and small-scale industries. Like many rural Italian towns, Baiso has faced challenges related to population decline, particularly among younger generations who tend to move to larger cities for education and employment opportunities. Despite these challenges, the town remains an active and cohesive community, with a strong sense of local identity and pride in its cultural heritage.

Economy

The economy of Baiso is predominantly based on agriculture and small-scale local businesses. Farming, particularly the cultivation of wine grapes, olives, and chestnuts, plays a central role in the town's economy. The region is also known for the production of Parmigiano Reggiano cheese, which contributes to both local economic activity and the town's culinary reputation. Other agricultural products include grains, fruits, and vegetables.

In recent years, rural tourism has become an increasingly important economic sector. Visitors are drawn to Baiso for its natural beauty, historical significance, and tranquil environment. This has led to the development of agritourism, with local farms offering hospitality and cultural experiences to visitors.

Natural Parks and Protected Areas

Baiso is located near several significant natural protected areas. These include:

- MAB UNESCO site, focal point of the Euro-Mediterranean climatic frontier. This characteristic has determined, together with the geological heritage and other factors, the establishment of a complex ecological and cultural mosaic, which in turn is the basis for the evolution of the landscape.
- Rupe di Campotrera Natural Reserve, situated 15-20 km west of Baiso near Canossa. This reserve protects a unique geological formation and serves as a significant natural habitat for local flora and fauna.
- Parco Regionale dei Sassi di Roccamalatina, about 20 km to the north, known for its striking sandstone formations and rich biodiversity. It is a popular destination for hikers and nature enthusiasts.
- Parco Nazionale dell'Appennino Tosco-Emiliano, a national park located approximately 35-40 km south of Baiso, which protects the biodiversity and landscapes of the Apennine mountain range. The park is a designated UNESCO Biosphere Reserve, highlighting its ecological importance.

These natural areas, along with the local hilly terrain, play a crucial role in preserving biodiversity and offering opportunities for sustainable tourism and outdoor activities. They also form part of the broader Collina Reggiana – Terre di Matilde, a region renowned for both its historical significance and natural beauty.

In this setting, the local community of Baiso has a deep connection to its surrounding environment, where both conservation and sustainable development are key priorities. The public dialogue held in Baiso reflects these values, as it seeks to balance the protection of natural resources with the need for economic development, particularly in the context of critical raw material extraction in environmentally protected areas.

METHODOLOGY

This section explains the **methodology** used to conduct the public dialogue, highlighting any **adjustments** made from the methodology provided. The public dialogue in **Baiso** was designed following the **participatory methodology** proposed within the **CIRAN project framework**. The objective was to create a **safe, inclusive, and reflective space** in which citizens could explore the **complexities** surrounding the supply of **Critical Raw Materials (CRM)** and the potential **trade-offs** between **environmental protection** and **socio-economic development**.

The methodology was structured in **three main phases**:

1. **Introductory Session**

Participants were welcomed and introduced to the **goals of the CIRAN project**. A short presentation provided key **background information** on CRM, their relevance to **European policy**, and the **challenges** associated with their extraction. **Instructions** for the participatory activity were also shared at this stage.

2. **Scenario-Based Role-Playing (“What if...?”)**

Participants were divided into **2 small groups**, and each group was assigned a **future-oriented scenario** (“*Innovazione Insulare*” (Insular Innovation) or “*Stato Stazionario*” (Steady State)). Within each group, participants received a **fictional character card** representing a **stakeholder** with a specific point of view on the issue (e.g., a **local farmer, environmental activist, government official, mining company representative**, etc.). They were asked to **role-play** a discussion, interpreting their characters’ **interests and decisions** in response to a fictional proposal to **extract CRM in a protected area**. This method allowed participants to step into **different perspectives** and explore the **tensions and dilemmas** that arise in **real-world decision-making**.

3. **Collective Reflection (Out of Role)**

After the role-play, participants **stepped out of their characters** and shared their **personal views** on the two main questions posed:

- What are the **key factors** for a **sustainable supply** of CRM?
- Should CRM **extraction** be allowed in **protected areas**? If so, under what conditions?

The groups then worked collaboratively to **summarize their discussion** and present **key takeaways and recommendations** during the **final plenary session**.

Adaptations from the original methodology

While the activity largely followed the original methodology proposed in the CIRAN toolkit, some minor adjustments were made to better fit the local context and group dynamics:

- Facilitators encouraged participants to freely improvise within the logic of their character, allowing for more fluid and natural discussions.
- The plenary session was extended to allow space for shared synthesis and direct peer-to-peer feedback among groups.

Overall, the methodology proved effective in engaging participants with diverse backgrounds and levels of expertise, encouraging deep reflection, and producing meaningful, locally grounded insights and recommendations.

Preparation of the Public Discussion

The public dialogue held in Baiso brought together a small but diverse group of participants for a structured discussion on the future of Critical Raw Materials (CRM) in Europe. The goal was to involve citizens with different backgrounds and perspectives in a collaborative, forward-looking reflection.

Selection and Invitation Process

Participants were selected through a targeted invitation process, supported by local networks and project partners. The selection aimed to ensure:

- A mix of professional backgrounds and lived experiences (e.g., farming, tourism, retail, public service, environmental advocacy).
- Individuals with a personal or professional connection to the territory.
- A willingness to engage in constructive and imaginative dialogue.

Participation Overview

A total of 11 participants took part in the working groups:

- 5 participants engaged with the *Innovazione Insulare* (“Insular Innovation”) scenario.
- 6 participants explored the *Stato Stazionario* (“Steady State”) scenario.

Each group was guided by a trained facilitator from FUTOUR, applying a participatory methodology based on role play and structured reflection.

Additional attendees

The session was also attended and supported by:

- Marzia Cescon – ALDA
- Luis Rosendo – Generator, CIRAN Partner (Portugal)
- Christian Marasmi – CIRAN Partner, Emilia-Romagna Region (Italy)

Their presence ensured a smooth facilitation process and helped connect the local dialogue to the broader European policy and project context.

Location and Timing

Where exactly was the focus group held, which was the setting and the timing. Who conducted the event (facilitators/co-facilitators/note takers).

The public dialogue held in Baiso on the 29th of March 2025, followed a **structured participatory methodology** developed within the CIRAN project. The aim was to actively involve citizens in reflecting on the social, environmental and technological challenges linked to the sustainable supply of Critical Raw Materials (CRM), particularly in relation to extraction in protected areas.

Structure of the Event

The session was organised into three main parts:

1. **Welcome and Introduction** (35 minutes)
 - Participant reception and informal welcome
 - Quick round of personal introductions (name, background, motivation)
 - Overview of the CIRAN project and its mission
 - Presentation of the concept of CRM and their importance for Europe
 - Introduction to the two fictional future scenarios used in the workshop
2. **Group Work – Role-playing Exercise** (70 minutes)

Participants were divided into two groups and worked with one of the following future-oriented scenarios:

- *Innovazione Insulare* (“Insular Innovation”) scenario.
 - *Stato Stazionario* (“Steady State”) Stazionario
1. Each person adopted a **fictional stakeholder role** (e.g., environmentalist, tourism operator, farmer, miner), and reflected from that perspective on what actions they would take in the given scenario.

The group collectively discussed, recorded their inputs, and distilled **2–3 shared recommendations** per scenario.

2. **Plenary and Deliberation** (20 minutes).

Both groups shared their outcomes in plenary, reflected on the complexity of the issues raised, and agreed on common insights. The session concluded with a recap of the next steps and a light refreshment offered to all participants.

Workshop Tools and Instructions

The activity “**Cosa succedrebbe se...?**” (“What if...?”) used gamified role-play methods to help participants explore contrasting positions in a constructive and creative environment. Each group:

- Choose one of eight-character cards
- Discussed the proposed questions from their character’s perspective
- Used post its to collect individual reflections
- Synthesized common viewpoints and formulated shared responses

Participants then stepped out of their roles to address two central questions as themselves:

1. What factors contribute to a sustainable CRM supply, and what changes are needed?
 2. Should extraction be allowed in protected areas? Under what conditions?
- Facilitation and Coordination

The session was conducted and supported by the CIRAN partnership team, including:

- **Two professional facilitators from FUTOUR**, responsible for guiding the activities and ensuring inclusive participation

- **Marzia Cescon** – ALDA, CIRAN partner, supporting the process and documentation
- **Luis Rosendo** – Generator, CIRAN partner (Portugal)
- **Christian Marasmi** – Emilia-Romagna Region, CIRAN partner (Italy)

Facilitators ensured an inclusive and respectful environment, while documentation was managed through **audio recordings, visual notes, and participant input on post-its**, enabling accurate analysis and reporting.

Partecipa al Dialogo Pubblico su

Costruire un'Europa Sostenibile: il ruolo delle Materie Prime Critiche

sabato, 29 marzo 2025
10:00 - 12:15

presso il Centro polifunzionale,
Via Toschi 53, Baiso (RE)

Per registrarti contatta
Debora 349.373934
oppure usa il seguente link
<http://forms.gle/sdGT3V1fqXkm1h676>

CON FINESCO FINALE

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"Cosa succederebbe se...?" Scenario 1 - Eutopia

E se la cooperazione internazionale eliminasse la necessità dell'estrazione mineraria a livello domestico?

Decisione:
La cooperazione internazionale può eliminare la necessità di estrazione mineraria a livello domestico?

Questo caso studio esplora le implicazioni di un mondo in cui **solite partnership globali e pratiche di economia circolare rendono superflua l'estrazione mineraria domestica** nella crisi prodotta.

Questo scenario potrebbe essere applicato a qualsiasi comunità, indipendentemente dal loro legame con aree protette dal punto di vista ambientale o dalle loro posizioni ecologiche, poiché non richiederebbe attività minerarie in tali luoghi.

Tuttavia, i partecipanti devono valutare i potenziali benefici e le sfide di questo paradigma, tra cui la sua reale fattibilità, e considerare i fattori conseguenti, come la continua dipendenza dalle catene di approvvigionamento internazionali o l'impatto ambientale nei paesi produttori esteri.

Inoltre, potranno confrontare lo sviluppo economico locale attuale con le prospettive di crescita o gli eventuali effetti negativi derivanti da questo scenario.

"Cosa succederebbe se...?" Carte dei personaggi

S2: Innovazione Insulare

Aumento del protezionismo, delle barriere commerciali e della frammentazione dei mercati

S1: Eutopia

rapidi progressi tecnologici che determinano cambiamenti nel profilo della domanda dei materiali

S3: Stato Stazionario

Forte cooperazione globale, mercati e strutture di regolazione interconnessi

S4: Fortezza Arida

Lento progresso tecnologico, con domanda stabile di materie prime critiche esistenti

Sviluppo tecnologico

Sviluppo tecnologico

CIRAN Scenario 1: 2023, In Lopez, Lisa, Robert Campos, Verónica, Karriñi Horreo, Marzo (2024). *Scenario 1 policy document* available at www.cirana.eu

Data analysis

Description of how data analysis was conducted.

The analysis of the public dialogue held in Baiso (RE) on 29 March 2025 followed a qualitative and participatory approach, aligned with the overall methodology of the CIRAN project. The process focused on capturing the richness of the discussions, the diversity of viewpoints expressed, and the collective recommendations formulated by participants.

Data was collected through:

- **Direct observation** by the two professional facilitators from FUTOUR;
- **Detailed notes** taken during the group work and plenary sessions;
- **Post-it summaries** written by participants during the deliberative phase;
- **Audio recordings** used to verify and integrate the facilitators' notes;
- **Feedback** provided by participants via QR code at the end of the session.

The analysis was conducted in two main phases:

1. **Immediate synthesis** by facilitators and CIRAN partners during and after the event to identify key themes, tensions, and emerging positions.
2. **Thematic coding and clustering** of content by the reporting team, based on the questions posed during the deliberation (“What factors contribute to sustainable supply of critical raw materials?” and “Should extraction be allowed in protected areas?”), and structured around the two exploratory scenarios: “*Insular Innovation*” and “*Steady-State*”.

Special attention was given to:

- Contrasting perspectives generated by the role-play phase;
- Convergences and divergences in the open reflection phase;
- Specific, actionable recommendations raised in each group.

In addition, **participants' feedback** on the process and content of the session was analysed to support future refinement of the methodology and to feed into the cross-national comparison across other CIRAN events.

This dual-layer analysis – content-based and feedback-based – ensures that the voices of participants are faithfully represented and meaningfully contribute to the CIRAN project's policy outputs.

PARTICIPANTS PROFILE

A total of **11 participants** took part in the public dialogue, alongside the organisers, project partners, and facilitators. The table below provides an overview of the participants' profiles, including their gender. All participants were already acquainted with one another, and approximately half had **previously participated in the focus group held on July 26th, 2024**.

Kind of participant	Number	Gender
Representatives of the Municipality	4	3M 1F
Representatives of local association on environmental topics	2	1M 1F
Normal citizen	3	1M 2F
Representative of the academia (geologists)	2	2M

As visible most of the participants were male 7 out of 11, with a great representation of the municipality.

KEY FINDINGS

Here below the agenda of the workshop

Time and Activity
8:45 – 9:45 Arrival and briefing
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome coffee Preparation and coordination with facilitators and partners
10:00 – 10:35 Informative Session
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome and participant introductions Presentation of the CIRAN project What are Critical Raw Materials and why do they matter? Overview of the EU foresight scenarios
10:35 – 11:45 Group Activity: “What if...?”
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario-based role-playing Group discussion from character perspectives Reflection on two key questions Identification of shared recommendations
11:45 – 12:15 Plenary Session
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of group findings Collective reflection and discussion Voting on shared priorities
12:15 onwards Closing & Informal Networking
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Light refreshments offered to participants

The following section summarizes the main findings and reflections that emerged throughout the different phases of the public dialogue.

PHASE 1 - INTRODUCTORY PHASE

This section provides a description of the **activities** carried out during the **introductory phase** of the public dialogue, including its **duration** and a summary of participants' **main reactions**. Where relevant, **direct quotes** from participants are included to illustrate key points.

The introductory phase took place from **10:00 AM to approximately 10:45 AM**, lasting around **35 minutes**. Its purpose was to **welcome participants**, provide **context**, and create a **shared foundation** for the subsequent **group activity**.

The phase unfolded through the following steps:

- A **welcome and agenda presentation** by the facilitation team.
- A brief round of **participant introductions**, during which each person shared their **name**, **background**, and **motivation** for attending.
- A presentation of the **CIRAN project**, its **objectives**, and its connection to the broader **European framework on Critical Raw Materials (CRM)**.
- An informative segment explaining what **CRMs** are, their **importance** for the **EU's strategic autonomy**, and the **challenges** associated with their **extraction and supply**.
- An overview of the **"What if...?" role-play methodology** and the two future scenarios selected for group discussion: *Innovazione Insulare* and *Stato Stazionario*.

The presentation was supported by **visual slides** and complemented by **printed materials**—including **scenario descriptions** and **character cards**—distributed in advance to support participants' **understanding**.

Although no **structured feedback** was collected during this stage, participants appeared **engaged** and **curious**, particularly during the introduction of the scenarios. Several commented on the **speculative** and **creative** nature of the methodology and expressed interest in how the activity would unfold.

"It's nice to be part of something so forward-looking and creative."

"The scenario is not too far from what could really happen."

"I'm curious to see how people will think in character."

Overall, this phase successfully set the tone for an **open and inclusive dialogue**, equipping participants with both the **information** and the **mindset** needed to fully engage in the next stage of the activity.

PHASE 2 – ROLE PLAY AND DELIBERATION IN GROUPS

The second phase of the event focused on **role-play and small group deliberation**, lasting approximately **70 minutes**, from **10:35 to 11:45**. This activity constituted the **core of the participatory methodology** and enabled participants to explore complex issues through the lens of **fictional stakeholder roles**.

Participants were divided into **two groups**, each composed of **five to six people**, ensuring a manageable size that allowed for meaningful interaction. The composition of both groups was **balanced in terms of gender** and represented a **diversity of profiles**, including individuals from different backgrounds and perspectives relevant to the theme—such as environmental concerns, local governance, economic development, and social activism.

Each group was supported by a **facilitator** responsible for guiding the discussion, clarifying the role-play dynamics, and ensuring that every voice was heard. A **note-taker** was also present in each group to document key arguments, reactions, and emerging ideas.

Time was **well-managed**, and both groups succeeded in addressing the two **main guiding questions** within the allocated time. Participants remained engaged and focused throughout the session, actively stepping into their assigned roles and navigating the tensions between **economic interests, environmental priorities, and community values**.

Group Composition

Participants were divided into **two groups**:

- **Group 1** worked on the scenario *“Innovazione Insulare”* and included **5 participants**.
- **Group 2** worked on the scenario *“Stato Stazionario”* and included **6 participants**.

The groups were **balanced in terms of gender** and featured a **diversity of profiles**, including individuals with backgrounds or interests

Each participant selected or was assigned a **fictional stakeholder character**, which they embodied during the discussion. This allowed them to adopt viewpoints that might differ from their personal opinions, enhancing empathy and critical thinking.

Facilitation and Group Management

Each group was supported by a **professional facilitator from FUTOUR**, whose role was to:

- Introduce the scenario and clarify instructions
- Encourage balanced participation
- Monitor timing and guide the group through the discussion

In addition, **note-taking** was ensured through a combination of:

- Written **post-its** from participants
- **Observational notes** by facilitators
- **Audio recording** for post-event analysis

Facilitators ensured that **all voices were heard**, including those less accustomed to speaking in public. The group dynamics were respectful and constructive, with participants showing high levels of engagement and curiosity.

Discussion Content and Timing

The groups successfully addressed the core question proposed in the role-play simulation:

“What would your character think or decide about the proposed CRM extraction project in this scenario?”

Each group discussed:

- The interests and values of their fictional character
- The trade-offs between economic development and environmental protection
- The broader social and political implications of CRM extraction

Although the **second part of the group work** (the open deliberation and formulation of shared recommendations) was fully developed within each group, **only the first part (the role-play)** was presented during the plenary due to limited time.

Despite this, **time was well-managed** within the groups, and participants appreciated the structured yet flexible format, which allowed for deep and meaningful exchange.

“It was easier than expected to put myself in someone else’s shoes.”

“This role helped me understand the broader implications of extraction beyond the usual arguments.”

The group activity succeeded in **stimulating diverse viewpoints, critical reflection, and collective sense-making**, laying the foundation for the final insights presented in the closing session.

This section presents the outcomes of the role-play activity, which lasted approximately 25 to 30 minutes. Participants were divided into small groups and invited to engage with one of the two proposed future scenarios by embodying assigned characters. The activity aimed to stimulate critical thinking and collaborative exploration of speculative futures, responding to key “what if” questions. During the session:

- The selected scenarios included both ***Innovazione Insulare*** and ***Stato Stazionario***, with each group focusing on one of them.
- Participants assumed pre-assigned roles based on fictional characters previously introduced. Each group featured a diverse mix of characters, including **local authorities, young activists, business representatives, environmentalists, and researchers**, allowing for a plurality of viewpoints to emerge in the discussion.

The role-play generated a rich exchange of ideas, reflecting contrasting **discourses** and **positions** in response to the speculative challenges posed by each scenario. Participants engaged actively, adopting the perspective of their characters and articulating strategies, concerns, and visions shaped by those roles.

The following table summarizes the key elements of the role-play, including the scenario explored, characters involved, and the main arguments or narratives that emerged during the discussion

Group 1	Scenario: Island Innovation Main discourses / positions / quotes
Local electronic store worker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Supportive of local extraction if environmentally respectful. Highlights economic opportunities and infrastructure development. ● Calls for revising outdated protected area classifications. ● Evokes the 'old Baiso' as more active and vibrant.
Local government official – Office for Economy and Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Supportive, with a rational view of progress. ● Argues resource use is inevitable for tech development. ● Proposes innovations like recovering materials from incinerator residues. ● Stresses tech can reduce, not eliminate, impact.
Tourism operator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strongly opposed to extraction due to the impact on eco-tourism. ● Warns about deterring tourists and considers relocating. Acknowledges job creation, but sees it as insufficient to outweigh environmental damage.
Environmental expert	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Opposed, yet pragmatic. ● Differentiates types of protected areas and supports ecological value analysis. ● Open to integrated models that combine conservation with limited economic use. ● Criticizes extreme environmentalism.
Local farmer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Initially uncertain, then conditionally supportive. Seeks revitalization of struggling agriculture. ● Favors controlled extraction aligned with local activities. ● Urges smart agreements and shared management.

Group 2	Scenario: Steady State Main discourses / positions / quotes
Local Farmer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Concerned about land impact. Against opening new mines. ● Prefers improving existing sites over starting new ones. ● Suggests optimizing current technologies via sharing and co-working. ● Requests longer product life cycles to reduce CRM demand. ● Supports extraction only in pre-existing sites.
Environmental Activist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cautious, supports alternatives to extraction. ● Warns against overuse of Earth's resources. ● Favors recycling, waste reduction, and alternative tech. ● Emphasizes intergenerational responsibility.
Local Government Official	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pragmatic and realistic, case-by-case evaluation. ● Supports status quo with targeted evaluations. ● Cites salt batteries as alternatives to lithium. ● Opposes costly or low-yield extraction operations.
Tourism Operator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Against extraction, supports environmental protection. ● Believes a pristine environment benefits tourism. ● Advocates for outdoor activities and community health benefits.
Electronics Store Worker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Supports local extraction if environmentally compliant. ● Works in a multinational chain, acknowledges e-waste issue. ● Advocates for durable products and customer awareness. ● Favors European extraction under strict laws.
Mining Company Representative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In favor of extraction and territorial investment. ● Claims site is strategic for tech development. ● Promises jobs, infrastructure, and social benefits. ● Suggests sustainability funds and public access to natural sites.

Final Reflections Emerging from the Role-Play Activity

Although the role-play activity was carried out in two separate groups, many of the ideas, concerns, and proposals expressed during the exercise were reiterated during the plenary phase. The following synthesis

presents a set of shared conclusions that reflect a collective understanding across both scenarios (*Innovazione Insulare* and *Stato Stazionario*).

These reflections do not replace the detailed group-specific results presented in the previous tables, but rather offer a consolidated overview of the main points that resonated across the discussions.

Sustainable CRM Supply

- **Promote a cultural shift** towards responsible consumption through **education, awareness campaigns, and ethical marketing**. Emphasize **repairability, durability, and reuse** of products.
- **Invest in recycling and recovery systems** (e.g., RAEE, incinerator residues) to **reduce dependence on new extractions**.
- Support **European self-sufficiency** by encouraging **local, ethically regulated extraction**, rather than relying on imports from regions with **lower environmental and labor standards**.
- Establish **international ethical regulations** and **traceability mechanisms** for CRMs, inspired by models such as the **Kimberley Process** for diamonds.
- Align extraction activities with **actual needs**, connecting mining efforts to **long-term strategic planning** rather than **short-term market speculation**.

Extraction in Protected Areas

- Apply a **case-by-case assessment**, considering both the **ecological value** of the area and the **strategic importance** of the resource.
- **Clarify and differentiate** the concept of protected areas, recognizing that not all hold the same level of ecological significance.
- Permit extraction only when **low-impact techniques** (e.g., underground mining) are used, ensuring **environmental restoration** and **compensation to local communities**.
- Explore **dual-use models**, integrating mining with **territorial regeneration** (e.g., transforming former quarries into green public spaces).
- Guarantee **multidisciplinary expertise** in decision-making processes, involving **ecologists, geologists, urban planners, and local residents**.

In conclusion, participants emphasised the importance of **balanced, informed decision-making** that integrates **environmental protection** with **technological, social, and economic development**. Principles such as **co-design, transparency, and active local participation** were seen as essential to ensure the **legitimacy** and **sustainability** of any future interventions.

Post Role-Play Discussion and Group Reflections

After the role-play simulation, participants moved into an **open reflection phase**, stepping out of character to collaboratively address the **guiding questions**. The aim of this phase was to identify **shared concerns**, formulate **concrete recommendations**, and prepare **key messages** to be presented during the **plenary discussion**.

Below is a summary of the reflections and discussions that emerged in **Group 1** in response to the first guiding question:

Group 1 – Question 1

What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of critical raw materials? Do you think any changes are needed? If so, which ones?

The group explored the issue from multiple angles, combining **practical considerations** with **systemic critiques**. The following key discussion points emerged:

- **The myth of “zero-kilometre” sourcing**
- Participants challenged the widespread narrative that **local sourcing** of CRMs is always possible or desirable. They emphasised the **unequal geographical distribution** of many resources and noted that **local extraction is not always viable or sustainable**.

“Zero-kilometre sourcing is unfeasible.”

- **Recovery and recycling**

A strong emphasis was placed on the **need to recover and reuse existing materials**, rather than focusing exclusively on new extraction. Strategies discussed included:

- **Recycling of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE)**
- **Recovery from industrial by-products and incinerator residues** (e.g., titanium)
- **Revalorisation** of materials currently treated as **waste**

“Not everything we separate is actually recovered.”

- **Product durability and repairability**

The group stressed the need to move away from a **fast-consumption culture** and called for **products that last longer and can be repaired**. They advocated for:

- Stronger **policies against planned obsolescence**
- Legal protection of the **“right to repair”**

“A phone should last 15 years.”

- **Challenging toxic economic mechanisms**. Participants criticized the **economic system** for promoting **overconsumption** and making **reuse and repair economically unattractive**. They called for **political and industrial reforms** that would **incentivize sustainability** over profit.
- **Education and cultural change**. Achieving systemic transformation was seen as requiring deep **cultural shifts**, starting with **education**. Ideas included:
 - Organizing **swap events**
 - Promoting **vintage and reuse culture**
 - Encouraging **intergenerational awareness** about **consumption habits**

Summary of Shared Recommendations – Group 1

- Invest in the **recovery and reuse** of existing materials.
- Promote **durability, repairability, and upgradeability** of consumer products.
- Foster **cultural and economic change** to counter **obsolescence** and support **long-term sustainability**.

Group 1 – Question 2

Should the extraction of critical raw materials be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?

The group approached this complex question by emphasizing the importance of **context-sensitive evaluation**, grounded in **technical knowledge**, **ecological awareness**, and **balanced decision-making**. Rather than adopting rigid positions, participants advocated for **flexibility** based on real data and environmental relevance.

- **Case-by-case evaluation.** Participants agreed that extraction in protected areas should **not be ruled out categorically**, but rather assessed individually. Two guiding questions were considered essential:
 - Is the **resource genuinely present in strategic quantities**?
 - Does the area hold **significant ecological value**, or is it a **marginal or degraded zone**?
"Does the resource really exist? And is the area truly worth protecting?"
- **Multidisciplinary expertise.** To make informed decisions, a **technical, scientific, and cultural approach** was deemed necessary. Participants stressed the need to involve diverse stakeholders and professionals:
 - **Geologists, engineers, ecologists, and urban planners** should work collaboratively.
 - Decisions must be based on **updated data, impact assessments, and integrated methodologies**.
- **Balance and consideration.** The group emphasised that **technological advances** and a more **informed society** enable better impact mitigation compared to the past. Participants advocated for **pragmatic approaches** that move beyond ideological positions.
 - Today's extraction processes can be more **controlled and accountable**, provided they are well designed and regulated.
- **Dual-purpose value.** A particularly innovative idea that emerged was the concept of **dual-purpose land use**:
 - Extraction activities could be combined with **environmental protection or regeneration efforts**.
 - For example, a **quarry that also serves as a habitat** for a **protected species** or includes **community green spaces**.

Summary of Shared Recommendations – Group 1

- **Extraction in protected areas** may be considered only if:
 - The **resource is present in significant and strategic quantities**.
 - The area does **not represent an irreplaceable ecosystem**.
- **Multidisciplinary expertise** and **updated impact assessments** must guide all decisions.
- When possible, promote **dual-impact models** that combine **economic development** with **environmental stewardship**.

Group 2 – Question 1

What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of critical raw materials? Do you think any changes are needed? If so, which ones?

The group adopted a systemic view, identifying both **cultural and structural changes** needed to transition towards a more sustainable supply of critical raw materials (CRMs). Their reflections combined **ethical considerations, economic independence, and regulatory foresight**.

- **Culture of sustainability and consumption reduction**

A key message was the need to **educate and raise awareness** across all levels of society to foster a culture of **conscious resource use**.

- Reduce **consumerism** by promoting **shared use** of goods (e.g., car sharing), extending product lifespans, and minimizing waste.
- Critically address **marketing-driven consumption**, which fuels unnecessary purchases for reasons of **status** rather than real need.
- Reframe **ethical behavior** as desirable and aspirational, encouraging people to view sustainable choices as signs of **social prestige**.

- **Shorter supply chains and European independence**

The group emphasised the importance of **not abandoning extraction in Europe**, but instead ensuring it is done **sustainably and transparently**.

- **Shorten supply chains** to improve **traceability** and reduce dependency on **imports from regions with weaker standards**.
- Strengthen the **internal European technology market** to support local production aligned with **high environmental and labor standards**.

- **International ethical regulation and certification**

Participants called for Europe to take a leading role in setting **binding environmental and social standards**, especially for **European companies operating abroad**.

- Reference was made to existing frameworks like the **Kimberley Process** as models for **mandatory traceability and certification** in CRM supply chains.
- The creation of **internationally valid certifications** was considered essential to guarantee accountability.

- **Planning and forecasting of needs**

Finally, the group advocated for **supply plans based on actual needs**, not speculation.

- Extraction should be guided by **strategic long-term planning**, ensuring resource use responds to real demand and avoids wasteful overproduction.

Summary of Shared Recommendations – Group 2

- Promote a **culture of sustainable resource use** through education, ethical marketing, and community engagement.
- Ensure **regulated and traceable extraction within Europe**, avoiding reliance on lower-standard imports.
- Introduce **binding ethical regulations** for European operations abroad.
- Link all extraction activities to **long-term, needs-based planning**.

Group 2 – Question 2

Should the extraction of critical raw materials be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?

The group recognized the sensitivity of this topic and approached it through a **gradual and conditional logic**, emphasizing **precaution, transparency, and territorial justice**.

- **Priority to non-protected areas**

Participants agreed that **protected areas should not be the first option**.

- A **territorial hierarchy** should be established, evaluating the suitability of **less sensitive zones first**, to avoid unnecessary ecological risks.
- **Redefinition of the concept of “protected area”**
The group stressed the need to **clarify the meaning of “protected”**.
 - Some sites possess **high ecological uniqueness**, while others may be **protected for less critical reasons**.
 - **Not all protected areas are equal**, and **each case should be evaluated individually**.
- **Compatible extraction methods**
If extraction is considered, it should involve **low-impact techniques**, such as **underground mining**, with a strong focus on **landscape restoration**.
 - Participants cited **positive examples** of former quarries converted into **public parks or bike paths**, illustrating how **mining can coexist with regeneration**.
- **Obligation of restoration and compensation**
Any extraction project must guarantee:
 - **Environmental restoration**
 - **Social compensation** (e.g., infrastructure, services, or benefits for local communities)
- **Protection of all territories**
In a final, thought-provoking reflection, the group proposed a **broader view**:
 - **Every territory should be treated as worth protecting**, and all extraction should include the goal of **restoring land for public use** after operations end.

Summary of Shared Recommendations – Group 2

- Evaluate extraction in protected areas **on a case-by-case basis**, starting with less sensitive sites and using **clear, shared criteria**.
- Allow extraction only with **low-impact techniques**, combined with **mandatory restoration, territorial compensation, and landscape integration plans**.

The following section reports the key statements identified by each group during the discussion phase, highlighting the main points raised in response to the guiding questions.

Group	Statements
Group 1	<p>Question 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Invest in the recovery and reuse of existing materials. ● Promote products that are more durable, repairable, and upgradable. ● Foster cultural and economic changes that counter obsolescence and support long-term sustainability. <p>Question 2</p> <p>Extraction in protected areas can be considered only if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The resource is genuinely present in significant and strategic quantities. ● The area does not represent an irreplaceable ecosystem. Decisions are based on multidisciplinary expertise, impact assessments, and integrated approaches. <p>In some cases, it is possible to design models with dual positive impacts, combining economic development with environmental protection.</p>
Group 2	<p>Question 1</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote a culture of sustainable resource use through education, information, and ethical marketing at all levels of society. ● Do not abandon extraction in Europe, but make it sustainable, regulated, and traceable. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Include binding ethical regulations for European companies operating abroad. ○ Link extraction activities to conscious planning of future needs. <p>Question 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Evaluate on a case-by-case basis the possibility of extraction in protected areas, starting with those that are less sensitive and considering more delicate areas only as a second option, using clear and shared criteria. ● Allow extraction only with low-impact techniques, ensuring mandatory environmental restoration, territorial compensation, and landscape integration plans.
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PHASE 3 - PLENARY AND VOTING SESSION

The final phase of the public dialogue consisted of a **plenary session**, during which the two groups reconvened to **share their conclusions** and engage in a **collective voting process** to identify the most relevant proposals and statements emerged during the role-play and reflection phases.

Each group presented a summary of their main points, followed by a brief open exchange to clarify or complement the ideas. Participants were then invited to **vote individually on the different proposals**, selecting those they considered most important for the future of sustainable and ethically governed critical raw material (CRM) supply.

Statements shared by the group N°1

Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Invest in the recovery and reuse of existing materials.					
Promote products that are more durable, repairable, and upgradable.					
Foster cultural and economic changes that counter obsolescence and support long-term sustainability.					
Extraction in protected areas					

can be considered only if: The resource is genuinely present in significant and strategic quantities.					
The area does not represent an irreplaceable ecosystem.					
Decisions are based on multidisciplinary expertise, impact assessments, and integrated approaches.					
In some cases, it is possible to design models with dual positive impacts, combining economic development with environmental protection.					

Statements shared by the group N°2

Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Promote a culture of sustainable resource use through education, information, and ethical marketing at all levels of society.					
Do not abandon extraction in Europe, but make it sustainable, regulated, and traceable.					
Include binding ethical regulations for European companies operating abroad.					
Link extraction activities to conscious planning of future needs.					
Evaluate on a case-by-case basis the possibility of extraction in protected areas, starting with those that are less sensitive and considering more delicate areas					

only as a second option, using clear and shared criteria.					
Allow extraction only with low-impact techniques, ensuring mandatory environmental restoration, territorial compensation, and landscape integration plans.					

During the plenary session, the two groups presented their conclusions and jointly reviewed the main statements that had emerged during the previous discussion phase. Although a **formal voting process** was not carried out—neither manually nor via an online tool—**participants were explicitly asked whether they disagreed** with the shared conclusions proposed by each group.

As no one expressed objections or dissenting views, the statements were considered **collectively validated by consensus**.

This method, based on **open discussion and the absence of opposition**, was chosen to respect the **participatory nature of the event** and to avoid redundancy, since a **shared understanding** had already been reached during the deliberation phase.

As such, **no numerical voting results are available**, and **no additional tools were used** for the validation. The **consensus-based approach** proved effective in confirming the final outputs without the need for further formal procedures.

Final Reflections and Closure

The event concluded with a collective reflection that broadened the discussion beyond the local level. Participants raised important points about the complexity of sustainability, emphasizing that sustainable choices should not only be evaluated locally but also globally. One participant highlighted that replacing diesel cars with electric ones, while seemingly sustainable in local contexts, might create unintended environmental burdens elsewhere if not properly managed. Others reflected on the dynamic nature of ecosystems, cautioning against a static, "photographic" view of protected areas that fails to account for natural evolution and change over time.

A shared proposal emerged to reassess the current classification of protected areas. Participants recommended evaluating their present ecological value to determine whether the designation as "protected" is still justified, distinguishing between areas of high conservation priority and those that may have undergone natural or anthropogenic transformation.

Closure

At the end of the session, it was reiterated that the results of the discussions and group work would be included in a collective report of the CIRAN project. This report will contribute to broader European-level reflections and inform future EU policy recommendations. Participants were thanked for their active and thoughtful participation and were invited to a light buffet/aperitif, which provided an informal and convivial setting for continued exchange and community building.

Additional notes about de discussion

The atmosphere throughout the event was constructive and engaged. Participants approached the activities with curiosity, openness, and respect for diverse perspectives. The role-play exercise successfully encouraged empathy and critical thinking, while the deliberative phase fostered a shared sense of responsibility. Overall, the quality of participation was high, and the event generated thoughtful, grounded contributions that reflect the local community's values and insights.

At the end of the event, participants were invited to stay informed and engaged with the CIRAN project through several channels. They were encouraged to visit the official website www.ciranproject.eu for further updates, including the outcomes of the participatory process, future events, and policy recommendations that will be submitted to the European Commission.

In addition, they were invited to:

- Participate in the **CIRAN video contest** targeting European adolescents aged 12 to 19, open until **May 31st, 2025**, by submitting creative content related to the project's themes.
- Share feedback, comments, or further ideas by contacting the project team via:
 - **Email:** ciran@intraw.eu
 - **ALDA contact:** marzia@aldaintranet.org

The project team reminded participants that the final report, including findings from this local dialogue and other locations, will help inform EU-level reflections on resilience and sustainability in the context of critical raw materials.

They were also invited to scan the QR codes provided on flyers and visual materials to access further content and tools.

Annex 1– Follow up email

The ex-post questionnaire shared after the event was later sent also by email to participants. The results of the ex post questionnaire were extremely positive showing that all participants filling it (8 out of 11) were satisfied with how the public dialogue was carried out, what they learnt and how they contributed to the group work. The full report of the questionnaires is available in Annex 1.

In the follow up email the slide set used during the event was also shared as well as information on how to participate in the video contest.

Another email will be sent with the main results of the workshop coming from the present report.

Results of the ex-post questionnaire

Genere

8 responses

Tipo di stakeholder rappresentato

8 responses

Sei soddisfatto/a di come si è svolta questa attività?

8 responses

● Si
● No
● Parzialmente

Hai ricevuto le informazioni che ti aspettavi?

8 responses

● Si
● No
● Parzialmente

Ti sei sentito/a di poter contribuire efficacemente al lavoro di gruppo?

8 responses

● Si
● No
● Parzialmente

Pensi che qualcosa potrebbe essere migliorato? se si cosa?

Nel complimentarmi ancora per la bellezza e la rilevanza dell'iniziativa, mi sento di suggerire quanto già anticipato sabato: sarei molto curioso di vedere quali spunti escano portando un'attività così di pregio in contesti meno strutturati, come un locale pubblico. Penso possa essere frutto di molti spunti ancora ulteriori.

Va bene così

Vorresti condividere qualche pensiero/commento relativamente all'attività e al tema delle materie prime critiche?

Nel complimentarmi ancora per la bellezza e la rilevanza dell'iniziativa, mi sento di suggerire quanto già anticipato sabato: sarei molto curioso di vedere quali spunti escano portando un'attività così di pregio in contesti meno strutturati, come un locale pubblico. Penso possa essere frutto di molti spunti ancora ulteriori.

Estremamente interessante

Gia fatto durante il focus

38 Annex 29 Focus group report - Mid-East region (Ireland)

CIRAN

FOCUS GROUP REPORT

Mid-East Region

Ireland

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides a summary of the findings of a focus group discussion exploring the diverse perspectives of local citizens on the extraction of minerals in environmentally protected areas. The focus group was held in Maynooth University in Co. Kildare on March 10th, 2025.

The objective of the focus group was to understand different perspectives of local citizens on minerals extraction in environmentally protected areas; and to understand the social dimensions of the transitions that need to happen in the EU at the Climate, Energy, Industrial, Economic and Social levels. The discussion explored the following key issues:

1. Familiarity with Critical Raw Materials.
2. Mining in environmentally protected areas.
3. Politics, policies and public perspectives.

Overall participants were familiar with the concept of critical raw materials (CRMs). Europe's dependence on external suppliers, especially China, was seen as concerning. Participants voiced concerns about the potential harmful effects of mining on the environment, particularly its impact on wildlife and areas of natural beauty. For participants, the decision to consider mining in environmentally protected regions is dependent on the clear demonstration of societal need for the materials. Participants highlighted the importance of communication and transparency in policies at the EU, national, and local levels. They stressed the need for improvements in the public consultation process and greater decision-making power at the local level to enhance public engagement and boost participation in the decision-making process.

The key issues that were highlighted as most important by the participants included:

- Provide greater clarity on the use of minerals.
- Improve awareness on the impact of mining on farming and farming communities.
- The economic benefits of mining should be more equitably distributed within the community.
- Provide more transparency on the negative impacts of mining such as pollution, economic dependence on industry, impact on communities etc.
- Address the shortcomings in the planning system that hinder public involvement in decision making process.
- Facilitate increased public participation in decision making process.
- Increase accountability and transparency regarding the potential damage to the environment.

INTRODUCTION

This report presents a summary of the main findings of the CIRAN focus group which took place in Maynooth University in Ireland on March 10th, 2025. Participants included representatives from the local community as well as representatives from environmental groups, academia, farmers groups and policy makers. The goal of the focus group was to understand different perspectives of local citizens on minerals extraction in environmentally protected areas; and to understand the social dimensions of the transitions that need to happen in the EU at the Climate, Energy, Industrial, Economic and Social levels.

The focus group aimed to evaluate participants general awareness of the concept of critical raw materials, gather perspectives on mining in environmentally protected areas, and explore the influence of public opinion and the level of public participation in decision-making regarding the extraction of critical raw materials.

This analysis presents an insight into the different viewpoints of participants on protecting environmentally sensitive areas and promoting socio-economic resilience within the EU. Furthermore, it offers a deeper understanding of local citizens' knowledge and beliefs on this issue, emphasizing the crucial role of community awareness and public involvement in decision-making.

LOCAL CONTEXT

The Mid-East Region consists of the territory of the counties of Kildare, Louth, Meath and Wicklow (see Figure 1). The Mid-East spans 6,891 km², 9.8% of the total area of the state (roughly 7% of the Island) and, according to the 2022 census, had a population of 764,154, roughly 14.84% of the national population. The Eastern and Regional Assembly provides a planning framework for the wider region, and each county is administered by a County Council, which is the principal level of local government. The region surrounds the Dublin Metropolitan area and therefore serves as a commuter zone for Dublin. It is characterised by agricultural land uses in Louth, Meath and Kildare. However, Wicklow County is predominantly mountainous with extensive environmental designation. The Natura 2000 network is illustrated below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Location of Maynooth and the Natura 2000 network in Ireland (Source: myplan.ie)

Tara Mines located in Navan Co. Meath is the single mine operating in the Region. It is 50km from the town of Maynooth and is one of Europe's largest zinc and lead mines. There are potential deposits of lithium in the Wicklow Mountains at the southern end of the region. Maynooth is located in County Kildare, close to the Meath border and is therefore centrally positioned within the Region. Maynooth is known for its university, historical landmarks and proximity to both Dublin and the Irish countryside. Situated approximately 25 kilometres west of Dublin, Maynooth is well-connected by road and rail, with regular train services to Dublin.

Maynooth has a population of around 17,000 residents¹⁰, though this number increases considerably during the academic year due to the influx of students attending the university. The town has seen significant growth in recent years and residents include long-time locals, university students, and newcomers.

Maynooth has a rich history dating back to medieval times. The town is home to Maynooth Castle¹¹, originally built in the 12th century and residence of the Fitzgerald family. Over the centuries, it has played a significant role in Irish history. In the 18th century, Maynooth became a prominent centre for education with the establishment of the Royal College of St. Patrick¹² (now Maynooth University¹³), the first university in Ireland to offer higher education to Catholics. The town also became the site of various important political and religious events, making it a key location in Ireland's historical landscape.¹⁴

In addition to its educational significance, Maynooth is also known for Carton House¹⁵ a Georgian mansion and former home of the influential Fitzgerald family. Carton House, set within expansive parklands, has been a focal point in Irish aristocracy and is now a luxury hotel and conference centre.

The economy of the area is multifaceted, driven by a mix of education, services, retail, and tourism. Maynooth University is a major contributor to the local economy, not only through education but also by supporting research and innovation in fields such as science, engineering, and business. The town's proximity to Dublin also makes it a desirable place for commuters, with many residents working in the capital or in Intel¹⁶ in the nearby town of Leixlip. Located approximately 5 km from Maynooth, Intel has contributed significantly to local economic development. The company employs approximately 5,000 people at its facility, and many of these workers live in and around Maynooth, bringing in disposable income and increasing demand for local goods and services. Intel has played a crucial role in establishing Maynooth as a hub for high-tech professionals, with many residents either working directly or indirectly for Intel, as well as benefiting from the increased economic activity. Retail and hospitality are also significant sectors in Maynooth, with a wide range of shops, cafes, and restaurants serving the community.

The town of Maynooth and its hinterland have several notable natural parks and green spaces. The town is particularly renowned for its Greenway¹⁷, a walking and cycling path that connects Maynooth to nearby towns. The Royal Canal Greenway stretches for over 130 kilometres, providing a route between Dublin and

¹⁰

<https://kildarecoco.ie/AllServices/Community/KildareLCDC/LocalEconomicandCommunityPlan/Census2022Datasets/Demographics.pdf>

¹¹ <https://heritageireland.ie/places-to-visit/maynooth-castle/>

¹² <https://sppu.ie/about>

¹³ <https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/>

¹⁴ <https://maynoothtown.ie/our-town/maynooth-history/>

¹⁵ https://www.cartonhouse.com/uploads/documents/GeneralDocuments/Carton_House_History.pdf?srsId=AfmBOop3jePMwtJ-ih37eY3H4afmc3kZSSqEBdN1pfio3FSSChNAWb3d

¹⁶ https://download.intel.com/newsroom/2023/manufacturing/Intel_Ireland_Fact_Sheet.pdf

¹⁷ <https://www.waterwaysireland.org/our-waterways/royal-canal/royal-canal-greenway>

the River Shannon. Along this stretch, the path offers views of the waterway, surrounded by landscapes, farmland, and woodlands. In addition to the Greenway, Maynooth is home to estates like Carton House and nearby Castletown House¹⁸, one of Ireland's finest Georgian houses, surrounded by parkland and woodlands. The surrounding areas of Maynooth are also home to several environmentally protected areas aimed at conserving biodiversity and protecting Ireland's natural heritage. One such area is the Boyne Valley UNESCO World Heritage Site¹⁹, which lies not far from Maynooth and is home to numerous archaeological sites and natural landscapes. The nearby Rye Water Valley (Carton)²⁰ Pollardstown Fen nature reserve²¹ and Ballynafagh Lake²² are designated as Special Areas of Conservation (SACs)²³, providing habitats for a variety of local wildlife, including rare bird species and aquatic life. The Rye Water (or River Rye) is classified as 'at risk' under the Water Framework Directive. The river is a tributary of the River Liffey which traverses Dublin City and discharges into the Irish Sea in Dublin Bay.

Located approximately 40 kilometres from Maynooth, the Curragh²⁴ is an area of natural conservation, known for its extensive grasslands, wetlands, and diverse habitats. Covering around 5,000 acres, it is one of Ireland's most important ecological sites. The Curragh supports a rich variety of wildlife, including rare bird species like the curlew and the lapwing, and is a vital breeding ground for many other species. It is also home to traditional farming practices that have helped maintain its biodiversity. Recognized as a Special Area of Conservation (SAC), the Curragh plays a key role in preserving Ireland's natural heritage and is managed to protect its ecological balance while balancing human and agricultural activity.

METHODOLOGY

A focus group was held to explore and understand the diverse perspectives of local citizens on the extraction of critical raw materials (CRMs) in environmentally protected areas.

An initial list of potential participants was identified with reference to the criteria for stakeholder selection. Potential participants were contacted either by email or by phone to introduce the CIRAN project, explain

¹⁸ <https://castletown.ie>

¹⁹ <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/659/>

²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rye_Water_Valley/_Carton

²¹ <https://www.npws.ie/nature-reserves/kildare/pollardstown-fen-nature-reserve> and

²² <https://www.npws.ie/protected-sites/sac/001387>

²³ <https://www.npws.ie/protected-sites/sac>

²⁴ <https://www.kildareheritage.com/places-in-kildare/the-curragh>

the purpose of the focus group and invite them to participate. Additional participants were identified and recruited through word of mouth and snowball sampling techniques²⁵.

The focus group was held in Maynooth University on March 10th between 11.00am and 1.00pm. A total of eight participants attended. In addition, a facilitator, assistant facilitator and observer from the CRAIN project were in attendance. A discussion outline was used to structure and guide the discussion. The discussion focussed on a series of questions under three key topics:

1. Familiarity with Critical Raw Materials.
2. Mining in environmentally protected areas.
3. Politics, policies and public perspectives.

The session was recorded using a meeting recording app (Fellow²⁶). In addition, notes were taken during the discussion by the assistant facilitator. The recording was transcribed, and the notes were written up. A thematic analysis of the data analysis was then conducted. This involved reading through the transcript and identifying themes relevant to the key issues and assigning codes to themes. A software analysis program (MAXQDA) was used to assist the coding and analysis of the transcript. From this process an analysis of the discussion emerged under the key headings.

PARTICIPANT PROFILE

A diverse group of participants were invited to attend the focus group, including representatives from environmental organizations, academics, farming groups, policymakers, students and the local community. Efforts were made to ensure both men and women and a range of age groups were represented. Participants were selected on the basis of having a genuine interest in sharing their opinions and insights on the topic. This facilitated an engaging and informative discussion.

The following chart illustrates the represented stakeholder groups:

²⁵ <https://www.simplypsychology.org/snowball-sampling.html>

²⁶ <https://fellow.app>

Figure 1: Focus Group Participant Profile

KEY FINDINGS

Topic 1: Familiarity with CRMS

Overall participants were familiar with the concept of critical raw materials (CRMs). Participants associated the concept of CRMs with the war in Ukraine and its impact on the supply of energy and fertiliser.

There was also a strong awareness of the criticality of raw materials. Participants linked this criticality to the control of CRMs by individual countries, especially China. They highlighted the risk of supply chain disruptions, such as those seen in the Suez Canal incident. Furthermore, the discussion of criticality was extended to projections of economic growth and increasing levels of consumption.

The concept of criticality was also explored in terms of how the scarcity of products directly impacts society. One example highlighted was the shortage of medical devices. The availability of CRMs to ensure access to products that are important for survival was highlighted:

“Criticality is also related to what we use it for. There’s lots of scarcity in a variety of raw materials but there is a number that we are dependent on. So that is an element of criticality, not every raw material that is scarce is necessarily critical but if it leads to survival, it is”

Several respondents emphasised the role of recycling of CRMs as an alternative to mining. This discussion focussed on the circular economy and the possibility of recycling CRMs from minerals that have already been extracted. However, some raised concerns about economic viability of this approach, citing challenges of extracting very small quantities from existing products.

Planned obsolescence was also identified as a key driver in the demand for critical raw materials.

"I think phones are also made the break, like planned obsolescence. It's designed to break after a few years, so the blame isn't on the individual. It's all the actual means of production and they're not made that I can replace the bit that does break, they have to replace the whole thing."

Participants expressed concern over the lack of strategic thinking regarding the recycling and reusing of products that require CRMs. Reducing consumption was also identified as a crucial factor in lowering societal need for CRMs:

"So to reduce actual demand for it we can stop or reduce our need with these materials I mean we have to, we have to because there's not actually enough minerals in the ground to meet projected demand, even if it was all extracted"

There was also a discussion about increased awareness on the preservation of critical raw materials. Specifically, participants questioned the absence of public dialogue on the need to preserve materials:

"I find it odd that we talk about preservation, preservation of energy, preservation of a lot of things but we don't talk about preservation of these materials. So we have to ask why we don't? There's a bit of a suspicious answer in the sense there is encouragement to use, use, use."

The political implications of CRM scarcity were identified as an important consideration. Control of resources by monopolies who can "turn the tap on and off" and "hold us to ransom" was considered to be a key challenge for Europe

"We live in what was called a common market – and you have all these things about competition and so on and yet we're facing monopolies, huge monopolies."

In particular, the control of CRMs by countries such as China was seen to 'amplify' the issue of scarcity.

"Maybe there is an overall scarcity, but it's amplified by the fact that it's controlled and increasingly controlled in the future by one country. That's why we see the deal with the Ukraine. At the moment it's China and that is a huge political factor."

In conclusion, participants recognized the essential role of raw materials to society and emphasised the importance of reducing consumption by focusing on recycling and identifying alternatives to mining. Europe's dependence on external suppliers, especially China, was seen as a major concern.

Topic 2: Mining in Environmentally Protected Areas

Overall there was a high level of awareness of the potential impact of mining on the environment:

"Mining is always contaminating, you know, some mines more so than others. But it always is by its very nature, you know, it uses chemicals to extract ore from rock. It eats up a lot of earth, destroys habitats and produces toxic waste."

"In the future it will have a huge impact on biodiversity and environmental impact"

The impact of mining on wildlife, particularly badgers was highlighted:

"The badger is a protected species. You know as farmers we have to be notifying departments of sets and whether badgers are dead in the road....but when these companies see...there's two opinions there and its almost draconian effects."

It was noted that mining in areas of natural beauty and tourism would have a negative impact:

"So certain areas that might have much longer-term value like the Wicklow Way tourism. A short term enterprise would damage the longer term assets"

However some would consider the option of mining of CRMs in environmentally protected areas if a strong argument was made for it:

“But Critical Raw Materials is a different category. Are we willing to make more sacrifices to get them? To mine in the Wicklow Mountains in the Wicklow Way, forget about it, but if the argument is made that we have to have these for our security then we may have to consider it.”

For another participant, the decision was dependent on demonstrating the societal need for proposed mining of particular CRMs in environmentally protected areas:

“Talking about mining in environmentally protected areas, how can you ask people to decide that when we don't even know where the minerals are going? That means there is a clear supply chain where these minerals are going with an actual societal need”

The potential impact of mining on farmers was identified as an important consideration:

“Mostly you talk about communities – but a lot of communities are farmers, farm families and farm businesses”

Another participant noted the negative impact of mining on livelihoods and jobs in the local community:

“So there's jobs when the mine is there but that decimates other local livelihoods such as farming. And then when the mine closes and the mine goes, then those jobs are lost.”

However, the positive effects of mining on local communities were also noted:

“Mining can have a very positive effect on local communities as well. And maybe only in the shorter to medium term but not in the longer term... But it does create employment for a community where there was very little other employment.”

Improvements to infrastructure was also identified as a potential benefit of mining to local communities. In the case of Tara Mines upgrade to the railway was identified as a direct economic benefit:

“That railway from Drogheda to Navan would have been closed millennia ago. It has actually been kept open and upgraded for the massive trains. And the long term plan is to upgrade the railway again and to put railway cars on it to meet the Dublin Belfast Enterprise line. This is a long term goal. So that's the positive part of it.”

In conclusion, participants voiced concerns about the potential harmful effects of mining on the environment, particularly its impact on wildlife like badgers and areas of natural beauty, such as the Wicklow Way. The decision to consider mining in environmentally protected regions would depend on the clear demonstration of societal need for the materials. In addition, the positive effects of mining on communities, including job creation and infrastructure improvements, were also acknowledged.

Topic 3: Politics, policies and public perspectives

In general, participants referred to a lack of public awareness of mining:

“I don't think it features for most people until the risk of mining is in their locality”

Negative public perceptions of mining were identified as a key challenge:

“It's not even the impact, its fear....when they say everyone knows people get cancer because of such things so that's part of it.”

“People's immediate reaction is we don't want it here.”

This was particularly apparent in the planning process:

"I think it's very striking at the moment that in our planning process the message seems to be that there is a lot of 'aginners'. People who are against them. And they're holding up all kinds of vital things."

There was also an acknowledgement that mining is unavoidable and will continue despite public opposition:

"But the weird thing about this is that its either on your doorstep or it's not . It's not like if we have to mine it, we have to do it."

"If it's a real critical recourse, if it doesn't happen here, it will happen somewhere else."

Another respondent indicated that in the future mining would most likely occur everywhere, noting that it's not a question of "if" but 'if not here, then somewhere else':

"But we are not taking mining away from there....the plan is to mine here and to mine there, more here and more there"

European targets were considered to be a key driver in the future mining of CRMs in Ireland:

"What's going to happen with this in the sense that you have an EU target, then it's a national target and then it becomes a regional and a local target"

It was suggested that increased targets from Europe would inevitably result in enforcement:

"It's kind of inevitable then if they have this agreement already that eventually there will be more enforcement in the same way that we see in renewables."

The process of public consultation was considered problematic. One participant referred to consultation as 'shallow and tokenistic'. Another remarked that the decision had already been made and another participant stated:

"It is clear where the European Union wants to go with this. We are just being softened."

Ireland's centralised government was identified as a barrier to effective public engagement:

"We have a very centralised government and governance system in this country. If we could actually have a more decentralised government and governance system starting with regional assemblies' serious regional assemblies not just 10 people and local government groups that the decisions are taken, and the information is given and organised at a local and regional level rather than the central level. Creates more trust, people are informed at an earlier stage."

The planning system described as 'top down' was identified as a key deterrent in facilitating public engagement:

"When people say lack of consultation, what do they actually mean by that....is it just a kind of an anger or feeling like they're disempowered? But that all points to the kind of democratic structures rather than the industry."

It was argued that local authorities should have a greater role in deciding on the location of mining:

"The local should maybe not set the targets but they should decide where it goes. And at the moment that's not quite happening, and the targets are set nationally by Europe and then the national is still having a larger involvement with how it's actually implemented."

The power and influence of the mining companies was seen as disempowering to communities:

“Because companies come with massive resources there’s a real power dynamic there. So whenever the companies are at the table communities have much less of a voice.”

One participant referred to several alleged incidences of lithium exploration without permission from landowners in Wicklow and the negative impact this had on the local community:

“You should have a public meeting with the local people – give them an idea of what you are doing....you inform the public; you bring them with you.”

Effective public engagement and communication were considered as important prerequisites to the commencement of any mining related activity.

In summary, participants emphasised the need for communication and transparency regarding policies at the EU, national, and local levels. Improving the public consultation process and increasing decision-making capacity at local level were considered essential for fostering meaningful public engagement and encouraging greater increased public participation in decision making regarding the mining of CRMs.

Topic 4: Conclusion

The participants highlighted a range of critical concerns related to mining activities, emphasizing the need for greater transparency, accountability, and community involvement. Key issues included the call for clearer information on the environmental and social impacts of mining—particularly on farming communities and biodiversity. Participants stressed that the economic benefits of mining should be distributed more equitably and that the public should be better integrated into the planning and decision-making processes. Transparency around pollution, land ownership rights, and the long-term risks of mining was also seen as essential. In addition, there was a strong consensus on the importance of enabling communities to have a meaningful say, including the right to oppose mining projects, and ensuring that both the advantages and disadvantages of mining are fully understood by all stakeholders

The following issues were highlighted as most important by the participants:

- Provide greater clarity on the use of minerals.
- Improve awareness on the impact of mining on farming and farming communities.
- The economic benefits of mining should be more equitably distributed within the community.
- Provide more transparency on the negative impacts of mining such as pollution, economic dependence on industry, impact on communities etc.
- Address the shortcomings in the planning system that hinder public involvement in decision making process.
- Facilitate increased public participation in decision making process.
- Increase accountability and transparency regarding the potential damage to the environment.

In addition, the following key messages were identified by participants as important:

APPENDIX

Invitation Email

Dear Participant

We are part of CIRAN, which is an EU-funded project to develop, test and validate processes to arrive at systemic policy-making, balancing environmental protection and societal needs for accessing critical raw materials (CRMs). For more information about CIRAN, please consult the project website at <https://ciranproject.eu>.

We are seeking your, or a nominee's, participation in a focus group discussion for the CIRAN project. Please find attached participant's information sheet.

Purpose and Agenda:

The focus group aims to collect valuable insights and opinions on critical raw minerals (CRMs), import dependency, environmental protection, socio-economic resilience, and more. Your thoughts and experiences are crucial to our research, and your input will remain anonymous, used solely for the CIRAN project's purposes. It will be followed approximately 1 month later with a follow up meeting.

Details are

Date: **10th March 2025**

Time: **11 am to 1pm**

Location: **Kildare Room, 3rd Floor, Rhetoric House, Maynooth University South Campus, Co. Kildare**[No. 4 on attached Campus Map]. If arriving by car enter the South Campus, and take a left. After 50m drive through the gap in the wall. Pay and Display parking is on your left. Travel and parking expenses will be reimbursed.

Duration: **Approximately 2 hours**

Please confirm if you, or a nominee of the IFA, is available to participate. Please don't hesitate to reach out to us by replying to this email or contacting myself on 0874179969, or 01 6762594

We look forward to your participation and to engaging in this meaningful dialogue.

Kind regards

Jerry Barnes

On behalf of the CIRAN Consortium

39 Annex 30 Public dialogue report - Mid-East region (Ireland)

PUBLIC DIALOGUE REPORT

Mid-East Region, Ireland

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INTRODUCTION

This report presents a summary of the main findings of the CIRAN public dialogue which took place in Maynooth University in Ireland on April 30th, 2025.

Participants included representatives from the local community as well as representatives from academia, planning, mining and agriculture from the Mid East Region. The goal of the public dialogue was not only to raise awareness about the importance of critical raw materials but also to actively gather input from citizens and stakeholders.

This analysis presents an overview of the individual group discussions on each of the key questions as well as the six final statements that reflect the preferences and priorities as discussed and agreed by the participants.

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LOCAL CONTEXT

The Mid-East Region consists of the territory of the counties of Kildare, Louth, Meath and Wicklow (see Figure 1). The Mid-East spans 6,891 km², 9.8% of the total area of the state (roughly 7% of the Island) and, according to the 2022 census, had a population of 764,154, roughly 14.84% of the national population. The Eastern and Regional Assembly provides a planning framework for the wider region, and each county is administered by a County Council, which is the principal level of local government. The region surrounds the Dublin Metropolitan area and therefore serves as a commuter zone for Dublin. It is characterised by agricultural land uses in Louth, Meath and Kildare. However, Wicklow County is predominantly mountainous with extensive environmental designation. The Natura 2000 network is illustrated below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Location of Maynooth and the Natura 2000 network in Ireland (Source: myplan.ie)

Tara Mines located in Navan Co. Meath is the single mine operating in the Region. It is 50km from the town of Maynooth and is one of Europe's largest zinc and lead mines. There are potential deposits of lithium in the Wicklow Mountains at the southern end of the region. Maynooth is located in County Kildare, close to the Meath border and is therefore centrally positioned within the Region. Maynooth is known for its university, historical landmarks and proximity to both Dublin and the Irish countryside. Situated

approximately 25 kilometres west of Dublin, Maynooth is well-connected by road and rail, with regular train services to Dublin.

Maynooth has a population of around 17,000 residents²⁷, though this number increases considerably during the academic year due to the influx of students attending the university. The town has seen significant growth in recent years and residents include long-time locals, university students, and newcomers.

Maynooth has a rich history dating back to medieval times. The town is home to Maynooth Castle²⁸, originally built in the 12th century and residence of the Fitzgerald family. Over the centuries, it has played a significant role in Irish history. In the 18th century, Maynooth became a prominent centre for education with the establishment of the Royal College of St. Patrick²⁹ (now Maynooth University³⁰), the first university in Ireland to offer higher education to Catholics. The town also became the site of various important political and religious events, making it a key location in Ireland's historical landscape.³¹

In addition to its educational significance, Maynooth is also known for Carton House³² a Georgian mansion and former home of the influential Fitzgerald family. Carton House, set within expansive parklands, has been a focal point in Irish aristocracy and is now a luxury hotel and conference centre.

The economy of the area is multifaceted, driven by a mix of education, services, retail, and tourism. Maynooth University is a major contributor to the local economy, not only through education but also by supporting research and innovation in fields such as science, engineering, and business. The town's proximity to Dublin also makes it a desirable place for commuters, with many residents working in the capital or in Intel³³ in the nearby town of Leixlip. Located approximately 5 km from Maynooth, Intel has contributed significantly to local economic development. The company employs approximately 5,000 people at its facility, and many of these workers live in and around Maynooth, bringing in disposable income and increasing demand for local goods and services. Intel has played a crucial role in establishing Maynooth as a hub for high-tech professionals, with many residents either working directly or indirectly for Intel, as well as benefiting from the increased economic activity. Retail and hospitality are also significant sectors in Maynooth, with a wide range of shops, cafes, and restaurants serving the community.

²⁷

<https://kildarecoco.ie/AllServices/Community/KildareLCDC/LocalEconomicandCommunityPlan/Census2022Datasets/Demographics.pdf>

²⁸ <https://heritageireland.ie/places-to-visit/maynooth-castle/>

²⁹ <https://sppu.ie/about>

³⁰ <https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/>

³¹ <https://maynoothtown.ie/our-town/maynooth-history/>

³² https://www.cartonhouse.com/uploads/documents/GeneralDocuments/Carlton_House_History.pdf?srsId=AfmBOop3jePMwtJ-ih37eY3H4afmc3kZSSqEBdN1pfio3FSSChNAWb3d

³³ https://download.intel.com/newsroom/2023/manufacturing/Intel_Ireland_Fact_Sheet.pdf

The town of Maynooth and its hinterland have several notable natural parks and green spaces. The town is particularly renowned for its Greenway³⁴, a walking and cycling path that connects Maynooth to nearby towns. The Royal Canal Greenway stretches for over 130 kilometres, providing a route between Dublin and the River Shannon. Along this stretch, the path offers views of the waterway, surrounded by landscapes, farmland, and woodlands. In addition to the Greenway, Maynooth is home to estates like Carton House and nearby Castletown House³⁵, one of Ireland's finest Georgian houses, surrounded by parkland and woodlands. The surrounding areas of Maynooth are also home to several environmentally protected areas aimed at conserving biodiversity and protecting Ireland's natural heritage. One such area is the Boyne Valley UNESCO World Heritage Site³⁶, which lies not far from Maynooth and is home to numerous archaeological sites and natural landscapes. The nearby Rye Water Valley (Carton)³⁷ Pollardstown Fen nature reserve³⁸ and Ballynafagh Lake³⁹ are designated as Special Areas of Conservation (SACs)⁴⁰, providing habitats for a variety of local wildlife, including rare bird species and aquatic life. The Rye Water (or River Rye) is classified as 'at risk' under the Water Framework Directive. The river is a tributary of the River Liffey which traverses Dublin City and discharges into the Irish Sea in Dublin Bay.

Located approximately 40 kilometres from Maynooth, the Curragh⁴¹ is an area of natural conservation, known for its extensive grasslands, wetlands, and diverse habitats. Covering around 5,000 acres, it is one of Ireland's most important ecological sites. The Curragh supports a rich variety of wildlife, including rare bird species like the curlew and the lapwing, and is a vital breeding ground for many other species. It is also home to traditional farming practices that have helped maintain its biodiversity. Recognized as a Special Area of Conservation (SAC), the Curragh plays a key role in preserving Ireland's natural heritage and is managed to protect its ecological balance while balancing human and agricultural activity.

METHODOLOGY

The public discussion was held in Maynooth University on April 30th between 11.00am and 1.00pm. A total of ten participants attended. In addition, two facilitators and two observers from the CIRAN project were in attendance.

³⁴ <https://www.waterwaysireland.org/our-waterways/royal-canal/royal-canal-greenway>

³⁵ <https://castletown.ie>

³⁶ <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/659/>

³⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rye_Water_Valley/_Carton

³⁸ <https://www.npws.ie/nature-reserves/kildare/pollardstown-fen-nature-reserve> and

³⁹ <https://www.npws.ie/protected-sites/sac/001387>

⁴⁰ <https://www.npws.ie/protected-sites/sac>

⁴¹ <https://www.kildareheritage.com/places-in-kildare/the-curragh>

The agenda of the public dialogue was as follows:

Time	Activity
11.00.-11.30	Welcome and introduction Presentation on the CIRAN Project and Critical Raw Materials
11.30-12.30	Discussion and deliberation
12.30-12.40	Break
12.40-end	Plenary session, voting and conclusion

Participants were recruited through multiple methods. The event was promoted on social media platforms including LinkedIn and Facebook. Posters were displayed in the local community - at libraries, and on community boards at local venues and shops. All participants were required to complete a registration form that collected their name and contact details. To make registration more accessible, a QR code linking to the registration form was included on the posters.

Specific groups and individuals were invited to attend via email. All participants from the focus group which was held in March also received an invitation to the public meeting. Prospective attendees were encouraged to share the invitation with friends, family and colleagues. Efforts were made to ensure diverse representation at the event, including both men and women and individuals across a range of age groups. Despite multiple efforts to recruit participants to the event the overall response was relatively low. A total of 15 individuals initially indicated they would attend however several participants were unable to participate on the day resulting in an actual attendance of 10. Nonetheless, the small group size allowed for a meaningful and engaging discussion, with participants showing strong interest in the topic.

Figure 2 below illustrates the profile of participants who attended the public dialogue:

Figure 2: Profile of Participants

A total of three females and seven males attended with a good mix of age groups represented. The survey of participants indicated that seven participants had some prior knowledge on the topic of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) and three participants had no prior knowledge. All of the respondents stated that they were interested in the topic of the meeting and four of the ten respondents had previously participated in a discussion or other activity related to the topic of Critical Raw Materials.

The session was recorded using the Smart Noter meeting app, and additional notes were taken during the discussion. The audio recording was transcribed, and the notes were compiled. A thematic analysis was then carried out, involving a thorough review of the transcript to identify key themes and assign corresponding codes. This process led to an organised analysis of the discussion, structured under key thematic headings.

Introductory Session

The session commenced with a presentation introducing the CIRAN project, providing some background on CRMs explaining their importance and presenting various scenarios relevant to the European Union. The presentation included a discussion of the following:

- The supply of CRMs
- Findings from the CIRAN project to date
- Arguments for and against European supply of CRM's
- Key questions for consideration regarding the supply of critical raw materials mining in environmentally protected areas

Figure 3: Introductory Session

Deliberation Session

Participants were then divided into two groups, each consisting of five individuals. Efforts were made to ensure that each group included representatives from the relevant stakeholder groups, as well as a mix of both men and women and of age groups. Each group was asked to discuss the following three key questions:

6. What should the European Union prioritize to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?
7. What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of critical raw materials? Do you think any changes are needed? If so, which ones?
8. Should the extraction of critical raw materials be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?

The facilitator outlined the tasks of the group deliberation as:

- (1) To reflect on and discuss the questions as outlined
- (2) To develop a shared understanding of the key issues at stake
- (3) To agree on three statements and to present these to the full group for voting on following the deliberation process

Each group was assigned a facilitator and a note taker. Participants were given approximately 60 minutes to reflect on the questions, engage in discussion, deliberate, and agree on key statements. The presentation sparked strong interest, and participants engaged actively in the discussion. Those who had previously attended the focus groups appeared particularly well-informed. One participant shared that, as a result of her earlier involvement, she had developed a strong interest in Critical Raw Materials and had since engaged in numerous conversations with friends and family on the topic. Overall, participants expressed similar views and concerns regarding the discussion questions. After thoughtful discussion, consensus was reached on all three statements.

Following the deliberation session there was a brief coffee break and refreshments were served. During this time the facilitators prepared the statements for final voting.

Plenary Session

During the plenary session, participants voted online on each of the agreed group statements. Each statement was presented to the full group, and all participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with each statement using the Mentimeter app.

KEY FINDINGS

Deliberative Session – Analysis and Findings

The following section provides a thematic analysis of the three key questions discussed by each group, followed by the key statements that each group agreed on.

Question 1: What should the European Union prioritize to ensure a sustainable supply of critical raw materials?

Analysis of Group 1 Discussion

Participants in Group 1 noted that, in light of the current political climate, traditional international alliances are weakening. To secure a reliable supply of critical raw materials, they emphasised the importance of maintaining strategic independence and reducing exposure to geopolitical instability. This was seen as a key factor in securing long-term resource security. Increased diversification in the countries that supply raw materials was also considered important, as this would help mitigate risks associated with overreliance on any single country or region. As one participant noted:

“I think the first thing that we have to do is to try to separate the sources of materials not to have all the sources from one country like in the past with the gas from Russia.”

Participants also identified fostering relationships with alternative source countries—such as South Africa—as a potential strategy for the EU to consider. Such partnerships were seen as a way to diversify supply chains and reduce China’s dominant influence in key jurisdictions, thereby enhancing the EU’s autonomy in securing access to CRMs. One participant specifically emphasised the importance of reducing China’s influence in this sector:

“Reducing the control that China has over source countries which they have been establishing for the last thirty years while we were asleep”

Participants also highlighted the need to reduce dependence on CRMs as part of a broader solution to supply challenges. In particular they emphasised the importance of reducing, reusing, and recycling.

“So it’s prioritizing, reducing, reusing”

“Lithium batteries are a good example. Rather than sourcing new sources using and saving these batteries, many of them are going to waste.”

Participants discussed the challenges associated with these strategies, including the impact on economic growth and the need for technological innovation.

Following discussion and deliberation the participants in Group 1 came to a consensus on the following first statement:

“Developing an independent and secure supply via diversification, reduction and reuse should be an EU priority”

Analysis of Group 2 Discussion

Participants in Group 2 discussed how a key challenge for public acceptance of mining is the widespread perception that mining disproportionately benefits large corporations while offering limited advantages to local communities, thereby contributing to social and economic inequality and a power imbalance.

A widespread fear and general distrust of mining projects was seen as a barrier to the sustainable supply of critical raw materials. As one participant stated:

“There’s a fear that people are very principled against these type of projects”

This public distrust and perceived inequity, fuels resistance and opposition to mining.

Participants also highlighted the importance of consultation and engagement with the public to address fear and uncertainty regarding mining activities and questioned if improved education would help improve public attitudes towards mining. One participant questioned if education may promote increased understanding and acceptance of mining:

“Would there be greater operational understanding or even sympathy towards mining if there was a greater education on what is actually involved?”

Participants emphasised that proactive communication could help alleviate public opposition and foster greater awareness through education about what mining entails and its potential benefits. As noted by a participant:

“Education on what exploration involved, particularly in relation to people going to the land and what they are actually going to do”

Fair compensation to landowners was highlighted as a key issue. Participants highlighted the importance of public engagement to address potentially divisive conflicts around land use and compensation, helping to build stronger community support for projects.

Following discussion and deliberation the participants in Group 2 came to a consensus on the following first statement:

“Knowledge and education are critical in facilitating public acceptance of mining projects”

Question 2: What factors could contribute to a sustainable supply of critical raw materials? Do you think any changes are needed? If so, which ones?

Analysis of Group 1 Discussion

Participants in Group 1 emphasised the importance of safeguarding supply chains and stabilizing geopolitical relationships through proactive engagement and strategic trade agreements. As one participant noted:

“If you create stable geopolitical relations that is a factor in sustainable supply”

A key theme, the need to streamline the planning process, was seen as critical for improving engagement with communities, enabling clearer communication and reducing delays linked to public opposition or

regulatory complexity. The right of communities to oppose projects was acknowledged as valid and essential. One participant stated:

“Everybody has the right to say whatever they want. You know communities have the right to block, to prevent”

However, participants highlighted that early, meaningful communication can reduce opposition and promote collaboration. Nevertheless, the criticality of raw materials was also highlighted as an important consideration:

“I mean we are talking about something that’s critical here. If it’s critical, it’s essential”

Early and effective engagement and communication with the local community was considered to be important in facilitating increased acceptance:

Following discussion and deliberation the participants in Group 1 came to a consensus on the following second statement:

“Streamlining the planning process, stable geopolitical relationships, substitution of materials are important for a sustainable supply.”

Analysis of Group 2 Discussion

Participants in Group 2 discussed the importance of fostering stronger partnerships—whether at the state level or within specific sectors—as a means to accelerate the exploration process. These collaborations were seen as key to streamlining efforts, sharing resources, and enhancing overall impact. According to one participant involving the state would accelerate the exploration process:

“Becoming more of a partnership...state partner partnership or certain sector partnerships to help and that would certainly accelerate the exploration process”

Participants discussed the potential of using Artificial Intelligence to identify potential mining locations by analysing GSI survey data. They noted that public bodies could take a more active role in leveraging these technologies to support the sustainable supply of raw materials through more efficient and targeted exploration efforts.

Providing for joined-up thinking in the creation of partnerships across public, private, and community stakeholders was also considered essential. Participants stressed that aligning efforts and building partnership among public and private groups could enhance project outcomes, foster trust, and greatly facilitate the sustainable supply of critical raw materials.

Following discussion and deliberation the participants in Group 2 came to a consensus on the following second statement:

“Providing for joined up thinking and partnership creation in projects with public, private and local communities is essential”

Question 3: Should the extraction of critical raw materials be allowed in protected areas? If yes, under what conditions? If no, why not?

Analysis of Group 1 Discussion

Participants in Group 1 explored the trade-offs between preserving protected natural areas and accessing critical raw materials. There was recognition of the need to weigh the ecological and societal benefits of protected areas against the strategic importance of raw material extraction. Some participants highlighted the challenge of being "on one side or the other," stressing the need to evaluate which benefit—environmental or economic—is greater in each case. As one participant noted:

"I think it's how much benefit you are going to get from one or the other. So are you getting more benefit from a protected area? Are you getting more benefit from sort of balancing what you value or what do you need more?"

The relatively limited number of CRM sites compared to the abundance of protected areas was used to argue for a more flexible approach. Mining, if confined to a small fraction of protected zones, was seen by some as justifiable:

"When we think about consequences of the mining, how many locations of critical raw materials do we have for example here in Ireland? Because we probably have hundreds of protected areas. So for me, the answer is yes, because it only influences a very small proportion of all the protected areas. And if you say no to this question, it means you can't extract."

Participants questioned the current practice of treating all protected areas equally, proposing instead a "hierarchy of value" based on ecological importance and species rarity. Participants also discussed the likely scale of impact when considering the number of protected areas and the few locations of critical materials:

"Right now we're blanketing and putting each protected area on a similar level. The reality is that some included more rare or endangered species. Some are more general."

Overall, the discussion emphasised that decisions about mining in protected areas must be context-specific. A firm "no" was considered too rigid, with one participant suggesting that mining should be permitted under strict regulations and only in exceptional circumstances:

"It's too broad, too context dependent. Depends on what circumstances. Is there a war going on or not? Are we going to be overtaken? Do you need those raw materials to protect yourself? Then the question and the answer become completely different. So the resolute no I think is difficult. So yes, under strict regulations, strict conditions"

The role of the state emerged as a potential solution for building public trust. The development of stringent guidelines on protecting what already exists was highlighted by participants as important. Increased state involvement would allow greater accountability, visibility and sharing of the benefits and the outputs of mining. Participants felt that state involvement in mining operations could lead to greater transparency, accountability, and equitable distribution of benefits. For one participant, state involvement would provide greater benefits for the nation as a whole:

"To me (with) a state company the benefits of the extraction are more guaranteed to support the entire nation rather than a company"

This may also lead to increased public acceptance of mining as one participant noted:

"Is there greater acceptance if the state has more of a role in actually doing mining in some shape rather than the big nasty mining?"

This view was contrasted with concerns over foreign-operated projects—such as the Wicklow lithium exploration programme run by a Chinese company—which raised questions about national control, security of supply, and the offshoring of value-added processing.

Following discussion and deliberation the participants in Group 1 came to a consensus on the following third statement:

“Mining in protected areas should not be permitted except under strict conditions such as a state company mining and a clear implementable restoration”

Analysis of Group 2 Discussion

Participants in Group 2 expressed a general concern that mining can leave lasting negative effects on the environment if not properly managed. One participant referenced the Lithium mines in Chile:

“I think because everybody has seen pictures of lithium mines in Chile and....it’s a giant scar on the landscape”

The public perception of environmental damage were seen as a key driver of public scepticism and opposition toward mining activities.

The decision to allow mining in environmentally protected areas was seen by participants as largely dependent on the context and the process. As one participant noted:

“It depends...it depends on what you want to do and how you are going to do it”

The issue of mining in environmentally protected areas was viewed as highly context-dependent, with participants emphasising the importance of a transparent, well-managed decision-making process.

Participants also discussed how technological innovations in mining—such as cleaner extraction methods, improved waste management, and reduced land disruption—could significantly reduce environmental impacts. Such advancements were seen as potential enablers for more sustainable mining, even in environmentally protected areas. One participant provided the example of the Woodsmith Mine in England which is lying under a national park.

Importantly, participants noted that increasing public awareness of these technological improvements could help shift perceptions. By demonstrating a commitment to safer, cleaner, and more efficient practices, the mining industry could begin to rebuild public trust and reduce opposition.

Following discussion and deliberation the participants in Group 2 came to a consensus on the following third statement:

“More efforts should be made to give successful examples of mining in protected areas”

Plenary Session – Analysis and Findings

The following section provides an analysis of the voting on the six key statements as presented by both groups.

Agreed Statements from Group 1 and Group 2

- A. Developing an independent and secure supply via diversification, reduction and reuse should be an EU priority
- B. Knowledge and education are critical in facilitating public acceptance of mining projects

- C. Streamlining the planning process, stable geopolitical relationships and substitution of materials are important for a sustainable supply
- D. Providing for joined up thinking and partnership creating in projects with public, private and local communities is essential
- E. Mining in protected areas should not be permitted except under strict conditions such as a state company mining and a clear implementable restoration
- F. More efforts should be made to give successful examples of mining in protected areas

Table 1 below illustrates the extent to which participants agreed or disagreed with each of the six statements (A-F) as presented above.

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
A	3	5	1		
B	5	4			
C	5	2	2		
D	4	2	1		
E	2	1	2	3	
F	3	2	4		

Table 1: Level of agreement with statements A-F

The statements that received the highest levels of agreement were Statement B, Statement A, and Statement C

Statement B: The statement ‘**Knowledge and education are critical in facilitating public acceptance of mining projects**’ was strongly agreed with (5) or agreed with (4) by all nine participants. This statement achieved unanimous support, indicating a shared recognition that public understanding and awareness are essential for the successful implementation of mining projects.

Statement A: The statement ‘**Developing an independent and secure supply via diversification, reduction and reuse should be an EU priority**’ was strongly agreed with (3) or agreed with (5) by 8 out of 9 participants with one respondent indicating a neutral position on this statement. This statement reflects broad support for building supply chain resilience and sustainability through diversification and circular economy principles.

Statement C: The statement ‘**Streamlining the planning process, stable geopolitical relationships and substitution of materials are important for a sustainable supply**’ was strongly agreed with (5) or agreed with (2) by 7 out of 9 participants with two respondents indicating a neutral position on this statement. While strongly supported by a majority, the presence of two neutral responses suggests some hesitation or ambiguity regarding this statement.

It is interesting to note that Statement E; “**Mining in protected areas should not be permitted except under strict conditions such as a state company mining and a clear, implementable restoration plan**”, was not

agreed with by the majority of respondents. Whereas 3 respondents strongly agreed or agreed with the statement, 2 were neutral, and 3 disagreed. This suggests that the issue of mining in environmentally protected areas is divisive, underscoring the need for more stringent environmental safeguards.

Furthermore 4 respondents were neutral on the statement **‘More efforts should be made to give successful examples of mining in protected areas’** indicating some uncertainty on this issue. This may indicate low priority or limited consensus on the value of publicising mining operations in environmentally protected areas, even if deemed successful.

Conclusion

The findings reveal strong consensus around education, supply chain independence, and efficient planning as critical priorities. However, the group showed divided opinions on the more ethically sensitive issue of mining in environmentally protected areas.

Evaluation Survey

An email was sent to all participants thanking them for their participation and asking them to fill in an evaluation questionnaire and provide any additional comments or feedback they had on the public dialogue. Seven participants responded to the survey. All indicated that they were satisfied with the public dialogue and that they received the information they expected. In response to the question on what could be improved one respondent suggested more time be allocated to the discussion, another requested further refining the questions and another suggested more examples be provided on the types of statements that are required. Other comments that were provided include the following:

“It is a complex topic. The concept of the public good needs to be central to the discussion on how to balance environmental protection with the need to extract critical raw materials. Up front issues become more important, e.g. Do we need these materials? Can we recycle? Is there another location which does not cause environmental damage?”

“Everything went well. It was very informative, inclusive and collaborative”

“I am interested in this topic as a result of this discussion”

“Great to see a wide range of bodies represented”

“Everything was really well prepared and presented”

Overall participants responded positively to the event, describing it as informative and collaborative. They appreciated the informative insights and found the content well prepared and well-organised.

APPENDIX

Mentimeter Results

More efforts should be made to give successful examples of mining in protected areas

Providing for joined up thinking and partnership creation in projects with public, private and local communities is essential

Developing an independent and secure supply via diversification, reduction and reuse should be an EU priority

Streamlining the planning process, stable geopolitical relationships, substitution of materials are important for a sustainable supply.

Mining in protected areas should not be permitted except under strict conditions, such as A State Company mining and a clear implementable restoration

Knowledge and education are critical in facilitating public acceptance of mining projects

FOCUS GROUP REPORT

Lens – France

15 mai 2025

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RÉSUMÉ

Ce rapport est rédigé dans le cadre du projet « **Critical RAw materials extraction enviroNmentally protected areas** » (Extraction de matières premières critiques dans les zones protégées environnementales) : le projet **CIRAN** ⁴².

Financé par le programme-cadre de l'Union européenne pour la recherche et l'innovation (Horizon Europe), le projet CIRAN vise une conciliation des enjeux relatifs à la résilience socio-économique avec ceux de la protection des zones écologiquement sensibles.

Dans ce cadre, le projet CIRAN comprend 6 modules thématiques (Work Packages) :

WP1 - Coordination et gestion

WP2 - Capture et évaluation des bonnes pratiques

WP3 - Liens des vulnérabilités sociétales

WP4 - Évaluations de performance

WP5 - Inclusion et co-crédation de connaissances

WP6 - Vers une élaboration efficace des politiques

Ce document entre dans les travaux du module 5 « Inclusion et co-crédation de connaissances », qui traite notamment des enjeux de démocratie participative.

Aussi, ACOM France a organisé un groupe de discussion en France pour recueillir des avis et des propositions des citoyens afin d'alimenter les orientations politiques et réglementaires liées à l'extraction de ces ressources, tout en préservant les écosystèmes et le bien-être des populations.

Le choix s'est porté sur un ensemble de participants composé de professionnels des filières extractives, des acteurs de la vie locale ainsi que des élus locaux.

Réunissant 12 participants, ainsi que 2 animateur/modérateur, les débats ont permis une présentation de différents points de vue à partir 3 questions thématiques liées à l'extraction, ainsi que de mettre en lumière les enjeux « d'externalité négative » des ressources minières.

⁴² <https://ciranproject.eu/>

INTRODUCTION

Les enjeux miniers croissants

En 1989, un mémorandum de la Commission Européenne sur la politique minière européenne souligne que le secteur minier est en « *perte de vitesse irrémédiable et qu'il est condamné de jouer un rôle de plus en plus marginal dans l'approvisionnement global de la Communauté.* »⁴³

En 2018, le rapport de l'Organisation de Coopération et de Développement Economiques (OCDE)⁴⁴ prévoit le doublement de l'utilisation mondiale des matières premières d'ici 2060, compte tenu du maintien de la demande des pays dits « développés », de la croissance de l'Asie, (notamment la Chine, l'Inde et les pays du Moyen-Orient), ainsi que du continent Africain, dont le PIB va sextupler d'ici 2060.

Si les matériaux de construction (sables, graviers, calcaire, etc.) représentent la plus importante part de cet accroissement, les technologies de la transition écologique, énergétique et numérique, sont très consommatrices de matières premières, notamment de métaux et minerais stratégiques.

Dans son avis du 25 mars 2020, le Comité économique et social européen « *considère que l'extraction des matières premières nécessaires au déploiement des technologies vertes constitue une étape fondamentale (...) la principale préoccupation est de trouver un équilibre entre la promotion d'une exploitation minière durable en Europe et la garantie de l'acceptation par le public (...).* »⁴⁵

Alors que le plan européen sur les matières premières critiques⁴⁶, présenté en 2020 comprend une étude prospective dans les chaînes de valeur européenne ainsi que 10 mesures.

Lors du discours d'ouverture de la conférence sur la sécurité des matières premières en Europe, le vice-président Maroš ŠEFČOVIC rappelle que « *les matières premières critiques sont la pierre angulaire de toute économie décarbonée et numérisée* », ajoutant que « *c'est une tâche économiquement complexe, politiquement difficile et socialement sensible* », mais que l'Europe ne peut pas « *fuir la responsabilité de donner l'exemple et de commencer à développer des projets nationaux selon les normes de durabilité les plus élevées.* ».⁴⁷

⁴³ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/fr/P_89_24

⁴⁴ <https://www.oecd.org/publications/global-material-resources-outlook-to-2060-9789264307452-en.htm>

⁴⁵ <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/fr/our-work/opinions-information-reports/opinions/resilience-des-matieres-premieres-critiques-la-voie-suivre-pour-un-renforcement-de-la-securite-et-de-la-durabilite>

⁴⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/42881/attachments/1/translations/en/renditions/native>

⁴⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/SPEECH_22_5484

Pour répondre aux nombreux défis des chaînes d'approvisionnement, les mesures sur les matières premières critiques (Critical Raw Materials Act), présentées le 16 mars 2023 par la Commission Européenne, vise l'engagement de « *programmes nationaux d'exploration des ressources géologiques* » afin que l'extraction dans l'Union Européenne permette la production d'« *au moins 10 % de sa consommation annuelle* ».

Dans le même temps, les demandes de Permis Exclusif de Recherches de Mines (PERM), c'est-à-dire l'exploration, génèrent des oppositions (en Ariège, en Bretagne, etc.).

L'Association des Communes Minières de France

Créée en 1970, l'Association des Communes Minières de France (ACOM France)⁴⁸ est un acteur national reconnu sur l'ensemble des enjeux des bassins miniers.

Comprenant près de 300 communes adhérentes, 8 Etablissements Publics de Coopération Intercommunale (EPCI), 4 Conseils départementaux et une dizaine d'associations adhérentes, ACOM France est engagée dans la défense des droits de la corporation minière, la gestion des risques miniers et des problématiques de « l'après-mine », ainsi que dans l'accompagnement des collectivités locales sur les questions d'urbanisme et d'environnement minier, ainsi que sur les enjeux de redynamisation socio-économique et de valorisation du patrimoine culturel.

De plus, ACOM France est une force de propositions auprès du législateur et des territoires pour la création d'un modèle minier qui réponde aux conséquences anthropiques d'hier et de demain, ainsi qu'aux défis de la transition écologique, énergétique et numérique

ACOM France possède aussi un engagement au niveau international qui se traduit par des engagements au sein des instances européennes en sa qualité de membre fondateur de l'Association des Régions Minières d'Europe (EURACOM), ainsi que par la participation à des actions du programme de soutien aux politiques d'investissements publics et d'innovation des régions européennes (INTERREG Europe), comme par exemple le projet transfrontalier RISSC⁴⁹ sur les cavités souterraines entre la Région Hauts-de-France et la Wallonie.

Enfin, ACOM France développe des échanges avec différentes instances de pays ayant des exploitations minières. Cet engagement s'est notamment traduit par la création de l'Association des Communes Minières au Portugal en 2022 et au Congo en 2024. Ce travail se poursuit actuellement sur la mise en place d'une Association des Communes Minières au Cameroun, et des contacts sont en cours avec d'autres pays intéressés sur le continent africain (Maroc, Guinée et Gabon) et le Japon.

⁴⁸ <https://www.acomfrance.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.rissc-interreg.eu/>

Le groupe de discussion

L'Association Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale (ALDA) ⁵⁰ a contacté ACOM France pour collaborer au projet CIRAN sur le travail de participation citoyenne face aux enjeux environnementaux, économiques et sociétaux liés aux besoins de matières premières critiques, et notamment leur exploitation en Europe.

Alors que le territoire métropolitain français ne comprend plus qu'une mine en activité (la mine de sel de Varangéville en Meurthe-et-Moselle), le choix s'est porté sur une réunion au cœur du Bassin minier du Nord-Pas-de-Calais.

Organisé avec le soutien de la Communauté d'Agglomération de Lens-Liévin et de membres de l'ALDA, le groupe de discussion s'est déroulé le **jeudi 15 mai 2025**, de 10h à 12h15 au sein de la Maison syndicale de Lens.

Pour répondre aux objectifs de débat citoyen, ACOM France a sollicité des acteurs publics et privés des filières extractives et du monde socio-économiques local ainsi que des élus locaux.

CONTEXTE LOCAL

Un territoire majeur de l'épopée minière française

Le territoire de Lens-Liévin est au cœur du Bassin minier du Nord-Pas-de-Calais, le 2^{ème} plus grand gisement charbonnier d'Europe du Nord-ouest après celui de la Ruhr en Allemagne et le plus grand bassin houiller français (120km sur 12km).

Dans ce gisement souterrain, l'homme a creusé 110.000 km de galeries, jusqu'à plus de 1200 mètres, pour y extraire près de 2.5 milliards de tonnes de charbon et au moins autant de

« déchets ».

Regroupant plus de 1.2 millions d'habitants, le Bassin minier du Nord-Pas-de-Calais a été modelé par plus de 250 années d'exploitation minière, de la structuration urbaine à la transformation des paysages, du « melting-pot » des populations à un héritage culturel complexe.

C'est dans les entrailles de ce territoire qu'a eu lieu de la plus meurtrière catastrophe minière d'Europe, celle du 10 mars 1906 à Courrières et ses 1 099 victimes,

⁵⁰ <https://www.alda-europe.eu/fr/>

C'est à côté de Lens que l'on trouve les plus hauts terrils d'Europe (Terril 74 a & b de Loos en Gohelle, culminant à 186 mètres) ainsi que le plus long terril plat d'Europe (terrill de Pinchonvalles à Avion, avec 1.750 km de long).

Si 51 terrils sont classés à l'UNESCO (avec 312 autres sites remarquables)⁵¹, le Bassin minier du Nord-Pas-de-Calais compte 357 dépôts miniers issus de l'exploitation charbonnière, dont la moitié des dépôts nationaux de plus de 500.000m³.⁵²

Ces dépôts miniers constituent à la fois une identité paysagère, des secteurs de surveillance de risques, des sites d'activités et de tourisme ainsi que des écosystèmes protégés

Un lieu de réunion symbolique

Le groupe de discussion s'est déroulé à la Maison syndicale de Lens⁵³, qui fut le siège du syndicat des mineurs du Pas-de-Calais, puis de l'Union régionale des syndicats de mineurs CGT (Confédération Générale du Travail) après la seconde guerre mondiale.

Symbole des nombreuses luttes sociales portées par la corporation minière, ce lieu, qui accueille désormais le service Culture et Patrimoine de la Communauté d'agglomération de Lens-Liévin, apparaît propice à rappeler les enjeux divers et parfois contradictoires, du sujet mis en débat.

MÉTHODOLOGIE

Activités extractives : Mines et carrières

Le droit français distingue les substances dites de « mines » et celles dites « de carrières » pouvant être exploitées sur des gisements souterrains ou à ciel ouvert.

En effet, les substances de « mines » sont définies par une liste à l'article L.111.1 du Code minier et toute autre substance relève de la classe des « carrières » (article L311-1 du Code minier) dont l'exploration et l'exploitation est à la libre disposition du propriétaire du sol et relève du Code de l'environnement.

⁵¹ <https://bassinminier-patrimoinemondial.org/>

⁵² https://reporterre.net/IMG/pdf/n2013-042de_bis_inventaire_des_depots_miniers_issus_des_exploitations_charbonnieres.pdf

⁵³ <https://www.calameo.com/agglolenslievin/read/0069207813c01e25319a9>

Si le projet CIRAN est orienté sur les « ressources minières », il est décidé d'intégrer les « ressources de carrières » afin de permettre un débat sur l'ensemble des activités extractives, sachant que les matières de carrières peuvent aussi relever, ou pourront relever à l'avenir, des enjeux sur les ressources critiques.

Le choix des participants

Dans l'objectif de débats ouverts, le groupe de discussion comprend plusieurs « types » de participants :

- Des élus locaux
- Des professionnels des activités extractives (mines et carrières)
- Des établissements publics liés aux activités extractives : le Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières (BRGM) et l'Institut national de l'environnement industriel et des risques (INERIS)
- Des acteurs locaux de la « société civile »

Les invitations ont été lancées par courrier électronique (confère annexe) à différents profils correspondants :

- Plusieurs élus des Communautés d'Agglomérations du Bassin minier du Nord Pas-de-Calais, ainsi qu'à différents élus du Conseil régional Hauts-de-France et des Conseils départementaux du Nord et du Pas-de-Calais
- Aux parlementaires du Bassin minier du Nord-Pas-de-Calais
- Des acteurs locaux du monde économique et de la culture
- Des représentants des industries extractives locales et nationales
- Des universitaires

Si le processus s'est basé en majorité sur des acteurs locaux, il comprend aussi des invitations ciblées aux élus des communes de Varangéville (mine de sel en activité) et d'Echassières (projet de mine de lithium en cours).

Compte tenu d'un délai assez court entre l'invitation et l'évènement (15 jours), l'envoi d'invitation s'effectue sur un panel assez large.

Un axe d'amélioration peut être envisagé pour un prochain groupe de discussion, par un travail préparatoire plus en amont permettant une amélioration du nombre de potentiels participants. En revanche, cette méthode nécessitera l'élaboration d'un processus de sélection clair et argumenté pour obtenir un panel de participants représentatifs.

Le format du groupe de discussion

Le groupe de discussion s'est tenu le jeudi 15 mai 2025, de 10h à 12h15, dans une salle de réunion de la Maison syndicale de Lens.

Pour faciliter les échanges, l'ensemble des participants sont positionnés autour d'une grande table rectangulaire.

A une extrémité de la table se tient le Président d'ACOM France, Jean-Pierre KUCHEIDA, qui a tenu le rôle de modérateur.

A ses côtés, un représentant de l'ALDA, Adrien LICHA, présente les objectifs du projet CIRAN et apporte des éléments complémentaires lors de l'animation des débats.

Derrière eux, un écran projette sur le mur des informations et éléments nécessaires à ce groupe de discussion.

A la droite du modérateur, un autre écran permet à l'ensemble des participants de voir les deux participants présents par visioconférence.

A l'autre extrémité, en retrait de la table, quelques chaises sont disposées afin de permettre aux accompagnants, qui ne participent pas directement au débat, de suivre les échanges.

L'intégralité des échanges est enregistrée par vidéo et par un enregistreur vocal, permettant une retranscription complète qui est jointe en annexe.

Des notes ont été prises lors des échanges afin de faciliter le travail d'analyse et de transcription des idées forces pour l'élaboration de ce rapport.

Le débat s'effectue en 3 parties, à partir d'une question ouverte par thème.

- La première partie s'axe sur les enjeux liés à l'extraction des matières premières critiques sur le territoire européen : « Que se passerait-il selon vous si l'Europe cessait de produire ses propres matières premières critiques au cours des 20 prochaines années ? Inversement, que se passerait-il si l'Europe continuait ou intensifiait la production de ces dernières ? »
- La deuxième partie aborde les conditions d'extraction nécessaires pour une exploitation acceptable et responsable : « À votre avis, quelles seraient les conditions nécessaires pour qu'une activité minière dans une zone protégée soit considérée comme acceptable ? Et quelles devraient être, selon vous, les exigences en matière de protection des droits des travailleurs, des intérêts des communautés et de la santé publique ? »
- La troisième partie traite des questions de démocratie liées à l'extraction des matières premières : « Pensez-vous que les citoyens sont suffisamment impliqués dans le processus de décision concernant l'exploration ou l'exploitation des mines premières critiques ? »

PROFIL DES PARTICIPANTS

Le débat compte **11 participants**, dont 2 par visioconférence : 8 hommes et 3 femmes, soit une représentation féminine de 27.3%.

Le groupe de discussion présent autour de la table comprend aussi :

- le modérateur d'ACOM France (Jean-Pierre KUCHEIDA),
- le représentant de l'ALDA (Adrien LICHA) qui co-anime le débat
- la déléguée générale d'ACOM France (Audrey DEUDON)

De plus, membre du consortium du projet CIRAN, 2 représentants de l’ALEFF Group ⁵⁴ participent aussi au groupe de discussion.

Aussi, l’intégralité des personnes autour de la table se porte à **16 personnes** (11 hommes et 5 femmes).

Les participants peuvent se classer en **4 catégories** :

Elus locaux (3 élus de la Communauté d’Agglomération de Lens-Liévin)

4^{ème} adjoint au Maire de Courcelles-lès-Lens ⁵⁵, en charge de l’Environnement, du développement durable, de la transition écologique, des finances

2^{ème} adjointe au Maire de Liévin ⁵⁶, en charge de l’Environnement et de l’éco-transition

1^{er} adjoint au Maire de Vimy ⁵⁷, en charge de la Transition écologique

Représentants des organismes publics liés à aux activités extractives

Directeur de la Direction des Ressources minérales du Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières (BRGM) ⁵⁸

Chargé de Mission Délégué au développement de l’expertise mines et après-mines à l’international de l’Institut national de l’environnement industriel et des risques (INERIS) ⁵⁹

Représentants de l’industrie extractive

⁵⁴ <https://aleffgroup.com/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.courcelles-les-lens.fr/>

⁵⁶ <https://lievin.fr/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.ville-de-vimy.fr/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.brgm.fr/fr>

⁵⁹ <https://www.ineris.fr/fr>

Directeur de projet de La Française de l'Énergie (FDE est un producteur d'énergie) ⁶⁰

Responsable Environnement & Relations Institutionnelles de Breizh Ressources (entreprise d'exploration de ressources minières) ⁶¹

Secrétaire générale de Minéraux Industriels de France (organisation professionnelle du secteur extractif des carrières) ⁶²

Représentants de la « société civile »

Chargée de mission de Lianes Coopération, le Réseau Multi-Acteurs de Coopération Internationale de la Région Hauts-de-France ⁶³

Directeur du Centre historique minier de Lewarde (Etablissement Public de Coopération Culturelle) ⁶⁴

Le Président de la Fondation Territoriale des Lumières ⁶⁵ (soutien de projets pour lutter contre la précarité sur le bassin minier).

⁶⁰ <https://www.francaisedelenergie.fr/>

⁶¹ <https://www.breizh-ressources.bzh/>

⁶² <https://www.mi-france.fr/>

⁶³ <https://www.lianESCOOPERATION.org/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.chm-lewarde.com/fr/>

⁶⁵ <https://www.fondationterritorialedeslumieres.org/>

PRINCIPALES CONCLUSIONS

Les échanges identifient 2 idées fortes sur les enjeux majeurs liés aux activités extractives :

- ECORESPONSABILITE (risques sur l'environnement et la santé humaine, nuisances locales de l'exploitation, gestion des ressources et sobriété...)
- DEMOCRATIE (enjeux géopolitiques et de souveraineté liées à la maîtrise d'une ressource, place du citoyen dans le processus de décision d'un projet minier...)

Le débat montre des convergences de l'ensemble des participants sur :

- L'importance des matières premières dans nos modes de vie, tant sur le développement de nos sociétés que sur les besoins de la transition écologique
- La nécessité d'une meilleure information sur les enjeux techniques, économiques et géopolitiques liées aux ressources minières

En résumé, ces échanges pointent 5 thématiques majeures sur les enjeux liés à l'exploitation des ressources :

1. La gestion durable des ressources naturelles et l'exploitation minière

L'exploitation des ressources naturelles locales est unanimement perçue comme un enjeu stratégique de souveraineté et de défense des valeurs démocratiques.

Les intervenants soulignent la nécessité d'une gestion écoresponsable des activités extractives à travers le respect des normes environnementales et sociales, ainsi que par la sobriété, c'est-à-dire consommer moins et mieux.

De plus, face à des pratiques du passé souvent perçues comme destructrices et injustes, la question de la relance de l'activité minière passe aussi par la responsabilité de l'État, notamment sur les questions d'après-mine, ainsi que sur une meilleure répartition des bénéfices, notamment à travers la fiscalité et les garanties financières.

2. La responsabilité des acteurs publics et privés

Les intervenants évoquent la nécessité pour l'État, les collectivités, et les entreprises d'engager une transition vers des pratiques plus durables, intégrant la recherche, l'innovation technologique et la gestion responsable des passifs environnementaux.

Si le renforcement de la confiance passe par une gestion écoresponsable des projets de demain, la gestion des conséquences des exploitations du passé est aussi un facteur important.

D'autre part, la réflexion éthique sur la consommation et le progrès technologique questionne la place du citoyen, la justice intergénérationnelle et la nécessité de la sobriété.

3. La perception sociale et l'acceptabilité des projets

Les débats pointent la méfiance et la défiance de l'opinion publique envers les « externalités négatives » des activités extractives, alimentées par les conséquences des exploitations passées et des narratifs

historiques négatifs, ainsi que par une méconnaissance globale des sujets miniers et des chaînes de valeurs qui en découlent.

Face aux nuisances des exploitations et un manque de compréhension des enjeux, les intervenants insistent sur l'importance d'associer les citoyens en amont, par la médiation, l'éducation, afin de créer une confiance nécessaire à un consensus acceptable sur des activités souvent perçues comme nuisibles ou invasives.

4. La dimension démocratique et la participation citoyenne

Les échanges pointent le rôle crucial de la démocratie locale et de la participation citoyenne dans la gestion des ressources et des projets industriels.

Dans ce cadre, la transparence de l'information et la formation des citoyens sont des principes fondamentaux pour transformer la méfiance en confiance.

Le consentement éclairé permet de renforcer l'implication citoyenne dans les projets pour une co-construction qui améliore la légitimité et l'acceptabilité sociale des activités minières.

5. La culture, l'éducation et la communication

Face à ces enjeux complexes il faut renforcer l'éducation, la culture scientifique, et la communication auprès du grand public, dès le plus jeune âge, pour réduire la méfiance et favoriser une société plus informée et responsable.

De plus, les intervenants ont abordé la nécessité d'une réflexion sur la consommation, le progrès technologique et la nécessité de sobriété, en questionnant notamment la place du citoyen et la justice intergénérationnelle.

D'autre part, des intervenants évoquent une meilleure reconnaissance du rôle historique et social des régions minières, avec une volonté de valoriser leur patrimoine et leur contribution à la société, tout servant de socle pour éviter les erreurs commises.

ÉTAPE 1 - INTRODUCTION

En tant que modérateur, Jean-Pierre KUCHEIDA indique l'importance du projet CIRAN par l'importance d'effectuer un débat sur les enjeux de l'exploitation des richesses du sol et du sous-sol, notamment pour la préservation de l'indépendance et la sauvegarde des valeurs de la démocratie.

« Il n'y a aucune raison pour qu'on ne puisse pas exploiter sans respecter les conditions nouvelles de notre époque »

Jean Pierre KUCHEIDA rappelle aussi l'importance du secteur minier, notamment du charbon dans le développement de nos sociétés et de nos modes de vie, tant sur les progrès techniques que sur les avancées sociales obtenues de hautes luttes.

D'autre part, il souligne l'importance des questions minières dans le cadre de la transition énergétique.

Adrien LICHA a présenté l'historique et les missions de l'ALDA, ainsi que les objectifs du projet CIRAN : « *Il s'agit ici de toucher un enjeu de démocratie important dans un contexte géopolitique qui a remis vraiment en avant la nécessité de revoir les richesses européennes pour des questions de souveraineté, pour des questions d'indépendance, et de développement économique en général.* »

ÉTAPE 2 – DISCUSSION CENTRALE

Thème 1 - Concept de matières premières critiques (MPC)

QUESTION 1 : « Que se passerait-il selon vous si l'Europe cessait de produire ses propres matières premières critiques au cours des 20 prochaines années ? Inversement, que se passerait-il si l'Europe continuait ou intensifiait la production de ces dernières ? »

Après avoir présenté la question, Jean-Pierre KUCHEIDA apporte la position d'ACOM France sur cette question : « *Il faut absolument que toutes les matières possibles, critiques ou pas critiques, que nous pouvons utiliser en Europe, puissent être extraites et utilisées, naturellement dans le respect de l'environnement d'une façon générale.* »

Il évoque les contraintes de l'exploitation, notamment en termes de nuisances immédiates

« *A chaque fois qu'on exploite quelque chose, dans un premier temps, il y a quelques désagréments.* »

Mais il souligne l'importance de montrer les perspectives qui peuvent émerger après l'exploitation, en citant l'exemple des terrils qui structurent le paysage et permettent de mettre en place différents projets (activités pédestres, piste de ski, viticultures) ainsi que la création de nouveaux écosystèmes sur ces dépôts miniers.

Après être revenu sur les difficultés de la vie des mineurs lors de l'exploitation charbonnière dans la région, **la première intervenante**, une élue locale, exprime à la fois une compréhension des besoins de matières premières et un manque d'information sur les activités extractives.

« *J'aurais bien aimé qu'on me dise déjà, actuellement, où était l'extractivisme en Europe, parce que je pense qu'effectivement, nous aurons toujours besoin de plus en plus de matières, de minerais rares. (...) Et l'on voit bien à quel point il s'agit maintenant d'enjeux géopolitiques* » (T. CHIARELLO)

Si elle rappelle l'importance de l'exploitation de ces matières pour notre mode de vie, elle exprime aussi des doutes sur une fuite en avant de la société de consommation et des usages numériques notamment dans les jeunes générations.

La 2^{ème} intervenante, représentante des industries de matières de carrières, apporte une réflexion sur les matières premières, en termes d'enjeux de société.

« S'il y a une vraie réflexion sur les modes de consommation, la matière première ne peut pas toujours être responsable de tout. La matière première, on en a besoin, c'est un postulat. » (S. RIMEY)

Ensuite, elle aborde la question de l'indépendance et de la souveraineté issus des exploitations de ces matières en soulignant aussi les difficultés existantes en France.

« Quand il n'y a plus de ressources minérales extraites dans un pays, vous devenez dépendant de l'étranger, vous perdez votre savoir-faire ». (S. RIMEY)

Le 3^{ème} intervenant, représentant du BRGM, revient sur les notions de la demande et des usages exprimées par les deux premières intervenantes.

Indiquant que la notion de « matières critiques » est le résultat du fait qu'on ne les produit pas localement, il évoque les questions d'approvisionnement d'une matière sur les enjeux de souveraineté et d'écoresponsabilité.

« À partir du moment où vous la produisez, vous prenez des positions sur la chaîne de valeur avale (...). A partir du moment où on ne les produit pas sur notre territoire, on transfère l'impact de nos modes de vie ailleurs. » (P. D'HUGUES)

Enfin, il indique que si la question des usages relève véritablement du débat démocratique, ce débat ne répond pas aux enjeux de dépendance liés aux besoins de matières.

Le 4^{ème} intervenant, représentant d'un producteur d'énergie, revient sur l'importance de la recherche et de l'exploration.

« il y a quelque chose de fondamental, c'est que si on ne cherche pas, on ne trouve pas. Et on trouve quelquefois par hasard. » (Y. FOUANT)

Il souligne les contraintes et les contradictions de la transition écologique.

« On veut avoir des énergies décarbonées, mais on ne veut surtout pas les conséquences de cette extraction, on ne veut surtout pas les conséquences de cette industrie qui est nécessaire. » (Y. FOUANT)

Il prend l'exemple de l'importation de gaz de schiste américain pour répondre à nos besoins mais de l'interdiction d'exploiter nos réserves de gaz.

Le 5^{ème} intervenant, représentant d'une société d'exploration, souligne les préjugés négatifs sur la mine, notamment issus d'ancrages culturels dans l'inconscient collectif ainsi que des messages véhiculés dans la culture populaire.

« Il y a un imaginaire, il y a même, quelque part, un inconscient collectif derrière l'idée de la mine, de l'extraction. (...) Ces problèmes d'acceptation, ça vient de très loin, il y a un héritage énorme, et aujourd'hui, il y a des narratifs. » (G. MAMIAS)

Thème 2 - L'exploitation minière dans les zones environnementales protégées

QUESTION 2 : « À votre avis, quelles seraient les conditions nécessaires pour qu'une activité minière dans une zone protégée soit considérée comme acceptable ? Et quelles devraient être, selon vous, les exigences en matière de protection des droits des travailleurs, des intérêts des communautés et de la santé publique ? »

Le modérateur indique l'importance d'une gestion préalable des problèmes issus des exploitations passées et une révision de la fiscalité minière.

« Pour pouvoir relancer la mine, il faudrait, pour commencer, régler les problèmes de l'après-mine partout où ils peuvent encore se poser dans le pays. Et ça, ça n'est pas fait. » (J.P KUCHEIDA)

La 1^{ère} intervenante, représentante des industries de matières de carrières, rappelle qu'au-delà d'un passif négatif, le cadre réglementaire actuel en France est exigeant en termes d'exigences environnementales, avec notamment une prise en compte en amont des questions de financements des conséquences d'une exploitation.

« Faites un benchmark entre chaque Etat membre afin de voir comment chaque pays prend en compte déjà l'activité extractive. » (S.RIMEY)

Le 2^{ème} intervenant, représentant d'un producteur d'énergie, explique l'importance d'informer la population sur les enjeux de ces activités extractives.

« Qu'est-ce qu'il faut rendre nécessaire ? c'est justement l'acceptabilité. On n'arrivera pas à forcer les gens comme ça a pu être à l'époque. (...) Rendons l'activité acceptable. Communiquons, soyons transparents, éduquons pour que les gens comprennent leur intérêt. » (Y. FOUANT)

Il évoque aussi une prise de parole publique par les opposants et les détracteurs plus que par les défenseurs d'un projet ou les indécis, il indique que le travail d'information et de formation est un enjeu démocratique majeur.

« Je pense que l'État, ou même les industriels que nous sommes, devons prendre en considération cet aspect communication, cet aspect d'éducation parce qu'il y aura toujours quelqu'un qui lèvera la main pour dire non » (Y.FOUANT)

Le 3^{ème} intervenant, représentant d'un établissement public culturel, souligne que si la question des « valeurs » liées à la démocratie et à la souveraineté est importante, le climat social actuel n'est pas propice à des échanges sereins sur des enjeux miniers complexes et de longs termes.

« On sent bien qu'il y a une « trumpisation » du débat public qui fait que de toute façon avoir une position subtile sur des enjeux compliqués, ça reste difficile. (...) Les enjeux d'acceptabilité il faut voir qu'il faut le prendre sur le long terme. » (L. PIRALLA)

La 4^{ème} intervenante, élue locale, indique que ces enjeux relevant de la société dans son ensemble et de son avenir, le débat doit aussi passer par des questions philosophiques.

Elle souligne aussi que les discours de représentants des activités extractives apportent une technicité nécessaire aux échanges mais qu'ils relèvent aussi du lobbying.

« Quand on va analyser un sol, c'est parce qu'on a une petite idée derrière la tête, et je pense qu'il faudrait des âmes plus naïves (dans le débat) » (T. CHIARELLO)

Le 5^{ème} intervenante, représentante des industries de matières de carrières, estime que la méconnaissance du grand public sur la complexité liée à l'exploitation limite aussi la capacité citoyenne d'apporter des avis éclairés sans l'apport technique des experts.

« Si vous voulez une tasse française en céramique, c'est feldspath, kaolin, silice. Il y a un moment, le débat doit être sur la gestion durable des ressources, mais pas sur le besoin de la ressource » (S. RIMEY)

Le 6^{ème} intervenant, élu local, évoque les enjeux sobriété de la transition écologique, tant sur la question des usages que sur l'extraction elle-même.

« Il y a des matériaux stratégiques dont on a besoin pour faire certaines activités, peut-être même aussi en réduction des émissions d'effets de serre. Mais, il y en a d'autres où on peut se passer » (J. WOJCIESZAK)

Il insiste sur la mission de régulation de l'Etat dans les activités extractives.

« Il me semble qu'aujourd'hui, dans le modèle capitalistique où on est, pour que nos enfants et pour que leur intérêt soient préservés, il n'y a pas d'autre moyen que l'État soit, à minimum, actionnaire des mines et de leur exploitation. » (J. WOJCIESZAK)

Enfin, il évoque les exigences règlementaires et environnementales dans la concurrence.

« Au niveau européen, on met un cadre et une barrière aux frontières qui empêche les matériaux mal exploités d'entrer. Et on fait ce qu'il faut pour que, dans notre enceinte, ne plus les acheter ou moins les acheter progressivement. Et produire en interne ce dont on a réellement besoin. » (J. WOJCIESZAK)

Le 7^{ème} intervenant, représentant d'une fondation, indique que les questions d'acceptabilité passent par la place du citoyen dans le processus de réflexion éclairée.

« On ne fait aucun effort en matière d'éducation, de formation, d'information, de médiation sur tous ces sujets-là. On intervient toujours « ex-post » et le citoyen est vécu comme une contrainte au moment où il faut passer à un investissement industriel » (D. SOYER)

Il souligne la nécessité d'intégration du citoyen par un dialogue très en amont.

« Si l'on veut avancer sur les questions d'acceptabilité, il faut faire de l'investissement vis-à-vis du citoyen. C'est considérer qu'il fait partie de la chaîne de valeur. On doit investir pour le mettre dans le jeu mais de manière coconstruite. » (D. SOYER)

Le 8^{ème} intervenant, représentant de l'INERIS, indique que les conséquences négatives des modes d'exploitation du passé apportent aussi une expertise et une connaissance sur la gestion des risques miniers pour demain.

« Il faut considérer notre savoir et valoriser cette expérience pour l'avenir. Il ne faut pas avoir peur d'ouvrir des mines demain. » (R. HADADOU)

Le 9^{ème} intervenant, représentant du BRGM, revient sur les divergences de points de vue entre le citoyen et le professionnel du secteur concernant la protection de l'environnement et les intérêts socio-économiques.

« L'acceptation, ça va être sans doute une combinaison de médiation et d'éducation. Il faut restaurer la confiance avec l'État, il faut restaurer la confiance avec les industriels, il faut restaurer la confiance avec les citoyens. » (P. D'HUGUES).

Il évoque aussi la question des contraintes d'échelles temporelles entre le débat démocratique et l'activité économique.

« C'est notre démocratie. Quand on débat, forcément, on ralentit les projets. Et si on ralentit les projets, d'autres pays vont beaucoup plus vite que nous. » (P. D'HUGUES)

Thème 3 - Politique et perspectives publiques

QUESTION 3 : Pensez-vous que les citoyens sont suffisamment impliqués dans le processus de décision concernant l'exploration ou l'exploitation des mines premières critiques ?

Un débat s'engage entre **les 2 premiers intervenants**, le représentant d'un producteur d'énergie et un élu local, concernant la divergence de point de vue relative aux besoins.

Le premier questionne sur l'acceptabilité locale d'un projet minier en lien avec les besoins de la transition écologique.

« Est-ce que vous seriez prêt à accepter une extraction de ces minerais pour la construction de vos champs photovoltaïques sur votre propre commune ? » (Y. FOUANT)

Le second estime que la divergence profonde provient d'une définition différente de la sobriété entre les citoyens et les industriels.

« Il y a un problème de définition du besoin qui n'est pas la même entre vous et nous. (...) Vous voyez la sobriété comme une contrainte nécessaire à la société de consommation. Nous, on la voit comme la base de notre réflexion sur ce sur quoi le modèle énergétique doit reposer, doit répondre à notre juste besoin et notre besoin juste. » (J. WOJCIESZAK)

La 3^{ème} intervenante, une élue locale souligne que le manque global de connaissances des citoyens sur des sujets techniques limite la capacité d'avoir un avis éclairé immédiatement.

« Vous voyez à quel point mes collègues et moi nous sommes complètement incompetents sur l'hydrogène et à quel point on peut dire des âneries. (...) Donc, quand on parle de démocratie, imaginez comme il y a du boulot. Et quand on va demander aux gens de dire oui, de dire non, il y a quand même du boulot avant. »

Le 2^{ème} intervenant, un élu local, reprend la parole sur la difficulté engendrée par le manque de confiance citoyenne.

« Si l'Etat a du mal à être juste dans sa redistribution des choses, notamment entre les générations, imaginez-vous comment les citoyens peuvent faire confiance à une entreprise privée qui aurait le droit à l'exploitation sur la préservation de l'intérêt général et l'intérêt de nos enfants ? » (J. WOJCIESZAK)

Le 4^{ème} intervenant, le modérateur, rappelle les réglementations mises en place concernant les garanties financières, mais il aborde la question d'un manque de planification et de débat.

« Tout le monde est en train de courir après un certain nombre de choses dans une durée tout à fait restreinte (...). C'est une catastrophe parce qu'on ne prévoit absolument pas de quelle manière les choses pourraient être projetées à 5 ans, 10 ans ou 20 ans. » (JP. KUCHEIDA)

La 5^{ème} intervenante, représentant les industries de carrières, revient sur les enjeux de concertation face à une situation géographique imposée par le gisement. Elle souligne un climat de défiance notamment dû à une méconnaissance de sujets techniques et complexes.

Le 6^{ème} intervenant, représentant une fondation, estime que le propos précédent apporte une perception négative du citoyen. Il ajoute que les modes de consultations actuels font ressortir principalement les externalités négatives, ajoutant à une méfiance et un sentiment de refus.

« On a déjà mis les citoyens dans une démarche de méfiance, de crainte, de peur, parce qu'on leur présente un gros machin qui va venir modifier leurs conditions de vie. Si on travaille en amont, c'est différent, comme on le fait sur les opérations d'aménagement aujourd'hui. » (D. SOYER)

Le 7^{ème} intervenant, représentant d'une société d'exploration, approuve la nécessité d'implication le plus en amont possible, indiquant que la « méfiance de l'opinion » provient d'une méconnaissance alliée à une perception d'exclusion du débat et de la décision.

« Les élus que je rencontre, on va essayer de les impliquer, mais quelque part, il y a du désœuvrement. En gros, ils vous disent, OK, on nous donne la parole, mais peu importe ce qu'on va dire, on ne va pas tenir compte de notre parole. » (G. MAMIAS)

Alors que l'exploration du sous-sol comprend des superficies très importantes, ajoutant de la complexité puisque cela touche de nombreuses communes, il revient sur la notion culturelle du message porté par l'exploitation minière.

« On part de loin, et il y a énormément de peur en lien avec cette activité, (...) il va falloir qu'on construise des histoires, un narratif qui donne envie. » (G. MAMIAS)

ETAPE 3 - CONCLUSION

En conclusion, le modérateur demande l'avis sur les débats aux deux membres de l'ALEFF.

Le **premier intervenant** explique en premier lieu la satisfaction de la tenue d'un groupe de discussion en France.

Il indique que les échanges font ressortir les enjeux démocratiques, tant sur les notions de géopolitiques liées à l'approvisionnement que par la volonté citoyenne d'être acteur et décideur d'un projet local

« La conclusion la plus frappante, c'est de confirmer qu'il y a un lien vraiment très fort entre les principes démocratiques et les principes des projets miniers. » (Julian HILTON)

En se basant sur les différentes idées, parfois contradictoires, émises lors des échanges, il indique que les « externalités négatives » ressortent comme un vecteur de contestation mais aussi comme un élément central à prendre en compte.

« le défi selon vos interventions, c'est la convergence entre la santé humaine et l'efficacité » (Julian HILTON)

La **seconde intervenante** revient l'importance de la place de l'individu sur l'ensemble des enjeux miniers

« Que ce soit l'investisseur, que ce soit le chercheur, que ce soit l'individu qui veut apprendre ou celui qui dit « It's not in my back yard » (...) la matière critique, c'est l'individu : S'il est bien initié, s'il a bien appris, il sait quoi faire de ce qui est. Il y a le tangible, c'est la matière, et il y a l'intangible, c'est le savoir. » (M. MOUSSAID)

Elle développe l'importance du partage des connaissances auprès du plus grand nombre, tant pour lutter contre les préjugés issus des conséquences des exploitations passées que pour permettre aux citoyens d'avoir un avis éclairé pour décider.

Enfin, elle indique que l'intérêt de la prospection du sous-sol répond au besoin de connaissance des potentialités qui permet aussi d'avoir des réflexions sur le long terme.

Le dernier intervenant, le modérateur rappelle que l'exploitation minière depuis la révolution industrielle laisse beaucoup de préjugés négatifs dans l'inconscient collectif

« les bassins miniers étaient quelque part les « colonies » de ce pays, comme elles l'étaient, je pense, en Angleterre ou ailleurs. On les a exploitées et, une fois qu'elles étaient exploitées, on les a, quelque part, laissé tomber. » (JP. KUCHEIDA)

Il rappelle aussi le manque d'anticipation de l'État pour accompagner la fin de l'exploitation et la nécessité des acteurs locaux de lutter pour obtenir un accompagnement.

« Si nous n'étions pas intervenus inlassablement depuis les années 70 sur les questions de réindustrialisation, de reconversion, etc., rien ne se serait fait. » »

Pour conclure, il indique que l'ouverture des mines de demain ne peut se faire sans bien fermer les mines d'hier, c'est-à-dire d'assumer pleinement l'ensemble des conséquences et des risques miniers.

S'il ajoute que les exploitations de demain doivent déjà préparer l'après-mine en termes de projets économiques, il revient sur l'importance de l'individu.

« Parce que c'est l'individu et sa promotion qui doit être l'objet de toutes nos attentions pour que cette promotion permette à une région non seulement de survivre, mais de vivre, et de vivre pleinement, et peut-être de trouver un éclat encore meilleur dans l'avenir. » (JP. KUCHEIDA)

ANNEXES - Mails d'invitation

De : Contact

Envoyé : mercredi 30 avril 2025 16:25

Objet : Invitation Projet CIRAN

Bonjour à toutes et tous,

Dans le cadre de notre pôle Europe et International, L' [ALDA](#) (Association Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale) est entrée en contact avec nous pour explorer une collaboration potentielle avec ACOM France dans le cadre d'un projet de participation citoyenne lié aux enjeux environnementaux.

Fondée il y a 20 ans à l'initiative du Conseil de l'Europe, l'ALDA est une organisation basée sur l'adhésion, dédiée à la promotion de la participation citoyenne et de la bonne gouvernance au niveau local. Ils se concentrent sur le renforcement des liens et de la coopération entre les autorités locales et les organisations de la société civile. Avec plus de 60 projets actifs, ils interviennent à travers l'Europe et les régions voisines, y compris les Balkans occidentaux, la Méditerranée et le Partenariat oriental. L'ALDA coordonne également les travaux de 16 Agences de la Démocratie Locale.

Ils souhaitent nous proposer une collaboration dans le cadre du projet [CIRAN](#) (Horizon Europe), dont l'ALDA est un partenaire.

Le projet CIRAN vise à concilier deux objectifs sociétaux souvent contradictoires : protéger l'environnement tout en assurant le développement économique, social et technologique. Plus spécifiquement, il promeut le développement durable à travers une approche innovante d'approvisionnement en matières premières critiques dans des zones protégées. La mission du projet est de développer des politiques et des réglementations permettant l'extraction responsable de ces ressources, tout en préservant l'équilibre délicat des écosystèmes.

Une des activités principales du CIRAN est l'engagement citoyen. Ces activités visent à sensibiliser le public aux thèmes du projet et à recueillir les recommandations des citoyens, lesquelles contribueront aux propositions de politiques pour les décideurs.

Ils aimeraient donc organiser avec notre aide un groupe de discussion de **deux heures**, réunissant entre **8 et 30 participants** maximum issus des membres d'ACOM (municipalités, élus, techniciens, associations, universitaires, parlementaires, etc.),

Trois thèmes seront abordés :

Sujet 1-Matières Premières Critiques :

Sujet 2-Exploitation Minière dans les Zones Protégées :

Sujet 3-Politiques et Opinion Publique :

Voici quelques questions pour orienter les débats :

Q1 : Que se passerait-il, selon vous, si l'Europe cessait de produire ses propres matières premières critiques au cours des 20 prochaines années ? Inversement, que se passerait-il si l'Europe continuait ou intensifiait la production de ces dernières ?

Q2 : Qu'en pensez-vous du dilemme entre la nécessité de protéger l'environnement et celle d'assurer une résilience socio-économique ? Seriez-vous favorable à la réouverture de l'activité minière dans votre commune ? Oui? Non? Pourquoi?

Q3: À votre avis, quelles seraient les conditions nécessaires pour qu'une activité minière dans une zone protégée soit considérée comme acceptable?

Q4: Quelles devraient être, selon vous, les exigences en matière de protection de l'environnement, des droits des travailleurs, des intérêts des communautés et de la santé publique?

Q5: Pensez-vous que les citoyens sont suffisamment impliqués dans le processus de décision concernant l'exploration ou l'exploitation des matières premières critiques ?

Q6: Pensez-vous que les politiques, lois et réglementations actuelles, au niveau français et/ou européen concernant le secteur minier, en particulier l'exploitation minière dans les zones protégées, devraient être ajustées ou optimisées? Si oui, dans quel sens? Pour faciliter l'exploitation minière ou pour protéger la nature?

Je vous invite à participer à cet événement qui se déroulera le **15 mai prochain de 10h00 à 12h00 à Lens (Maison Syndicale – 32 rue Casimir Beugnet)** et à débattre sur les questions figurant ci-dessus.

Merci de me confirmer votre présence par retour de mail.

Bien à vous,

Mr Jean-Pierre KUCHEIDA

Président

ACOM France

3 rue Jules Bédart

62800 LIEVIN

De : Bertrand CARDON

Envoyé : mardi 6 mai 2025 10:54

À : ...

Objet : invitation

Monsieur,

Dans le cadre de notre pôle Europe et International, l'ALDA (Association Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale*) est entrée en contact avec nous dans le cadre d'un projet de participation citoyenne lié aux enjeux environnementaux, dont l'ALDA est un partenaire : le projet CIRAN (Horizon Europe).

Le projet CIRAN vise à concilier deux objectifs sociétaux souvent contradictoires : protéger l'environnement tout en assurant le développement économique, social et technologique. Plus spécifiquement, il promeut le développement durable à travers une approche innovante d'approvisionnement en matières premières critiques dans des zones protégées.

La mission du projet est de développer des politiques et des réglementations permettant l'extraction responsable de ces ressources, tout en préservant l'équilibre délicat des écosystèmes.

Une des activités principales du CIRAN est l'engagement citoyen. Ces activités visent à sensibiliser le public aux thèmes du projet et à recueillir les recommandations des citoyens, lesquelles contribueront aux propositions de politiques pour les décideurs.

Aussi, nous organisons un groupe de discussion le **15 mai 2025 à la maison syndicale de Lens** (Pas-de-Calais).

Cette rencontre réunissant entre 8 et 30 participants maximum (municipalités, élus, techniciens, associations, universitaires, parlementaires, etc.), durera 2 heures en France (en français), autours de 3 thèmes :

Sujet 1-Matières Premières Critiques

Sujet 2-Exploitation Minière dans les Zones Protégées

Sujet 3-Politiques et Opinion Publique

Nous savons que le timing est très restreint, mais seriez-vous disponible pour y participer ? ou quelqu'un de votre équipe ?

Bien à vous

Bertrand CARDON

Chargé de mission

Tél : 03.21.45.85.51

Port : 06.27.93.29.84

3, rue Jules Bédart
62800 LIEVIN

*Fondée il y a 20 ans à l'initiative du Conseil de l'Europe, l'ALDA est une organisation basée sur l'adhésion, dédiée à la promotion de la participation citoyenne et de la bonne gouvernance au niveau local. Ils se concentrent sur le renforcement des liens et de la coopération entre les autorités locales et les organisations de la société civile. Avec plus de 60 projets actifs, ils interviennent à travers l'Europe et les régions voisines, y compris les Balkans occidentaux, la Méditerranée et le Partenariat oriental. L'ALDA coordonne également les travaux de 16 Agences de la Démocratie Locale.

Le mail du 30 avril a été transmis à un ensemble large de personnes, décrit dans la méthodologie (élus locaux, acteurs locaux de la « société civile », professionnels des activités extractives, établissements publics liés aux activités extractives, universitaires)

Le second mail, du 6 mai 2025, a été transmis à 2 universitaires, ainsi que par un message privé sur les réseaux sociaux (LinkedIn) auprès de 2 représentants d'un pôle de compétitivité des filières industrielles du sous-sol.

PHOTOS DU GROUPE DE DISCUSSION

